

A Modal Type-Theory of Expected Cost in Higher-Order Probabilistic Programs (Technical appendix)

Vineet Rajani ³

¹University of Kent, United Kingdom

²MPI-SP, Germany and IMDEA Software Institute, Spain

³Max Planck Institute for Software Systems, Germany

Contents

1	Development without coeffacts	2
1.1	Syntax	2
1.2	Type system	4
1.3	Operational Semantics	10
1.4	Model	13
2	Development with coeffacts	74
2.1	Syntax	74
2.2	Type system	77
2.3	Operational Semantics	83
2.4	Model	86
3	Embedding ℓRPCF	157
3.1	Type translation	157
3.2	Term translation	157
3.3	Type preservation	162
4	Examples	193
4.1	Randomized Response	193
4.2	Randomized weighted majority	197
4.3	Multi-armed bandit	212
4.4	Stochastic gradient descent	223
5	Isomorphism	230

1 Development without coeffects

1.1 Syntax

Expressions	$e ::= v \mid x \mid S e \mid e_1 e_2 \mid e :: e \mid \text{let } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \mid \text{if } e \ e_1 \ e_2 \mid \langle\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle\rangle \mid \text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \mid \langle e, e \rangle \mid \text{fst}(e) \mid \text{snd}(e) \mid \text{inl}(e) \mid \text{inr}(e) \mid \text{case } e \text{ of } x.e; y.e \mid \text{let}! x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \mid \text{Split } e \mid \text{Swap } e \mid \text{toDist } e$
Values	$v ::= () \mid \text{tt} \mid \text{ff} \mid Z \mid r \mid \lambda x.e \mid \langle\langle v_1, v_2 \rangle\rangle \mid \langle v, v \rangle \mid \text{inl}(e) \mid \text{inr}(e) \mid !e \mid \text{nil} \mid v_1 :: v_2 \mid \text{return } e \mid \text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2 \mid \uparrow^I \mid \text{store } e \mid \text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2$
Static Distribution	$\mu ::= (C_s, M_s)$ <p>$C_s = \text{Finite set of indices over natural numbers}$ $M_s : C_s \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$</p>
Dynamic Distribution	$\nu ::= (V_d, M_d)$ <p>$V_d = \text{Finite set of values}$ $M_d : V_d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$</p>
Types	$\tau ::= \mathbf{1} \mid \mathbf{B}(I) \mid \mathbf{N}(I) \mid \mathbf{R}(I) \mid L_{i < I} \tau \mid \tau_1 \multimap \tau_2 \mid \tau_1 \times \tau_2 \mid \tau_1 \& \tau_2 \mid \tau_1 + \tau_2 \mid !\tau \mid \exists x:S.\tau \mid \forall x:S.\tau \mid \forall \alpha.\tau \mid \alpha \mid C\&\tau \mid C \Rightarrow \tau \mid [I]\tau \mid \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} I \tau$
Index term	$I, \kappa, p, n ::= i \mid B \mid N \mid R \mid I + I \mid \lambda_s i : S . I \mid I I \mid \text{if } I \ I \ I \mid I == I \mid \text{exp } I \mid \log I \mid \vec{I} \mid \ I_1 - I_2\ _n \mid \nabla I$
Sort	$S ::= \mathbb{B} \mid \mathbb{N} \mid \mathbb{R} \mid (S, S) \mid S \rightarrow S \mid \mathbb{D}_S \mid \mathbb{S}_S$
Constraints	$c ::= I = I \mid I < I \mid c \Rightarrow c \mid c \wedge c \mid (1 - I) \leq \text{exp } (-I)$
Lin. context for term variables	$\Gamma ::= . \mid \Gamma, x : \tau$
Unres. context for term variables	$\Omega ::= . \mid \Omega, x : \tau$
Unres. context for index variables	$\Theta ::= . \mid \Theta, i : S$
Unres. context for type variables	$\Psi ::= . \mid \Psi, \alpha : K$

Definition 1 (Sum of linear context).

$$\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \triangleq \begin{cases} \Gamma_2 & \Gamma_1 = . \\ (\Gamma'_1 \oplus \Gamma_2), x : \tau & \Gamma_1 = \Gamma'_1, x : \tau \wedge (x : -) \notin \Gamma_2 \\ \text{undefined} & \Gamma_1 = \Gamma'_1, x : \tau \wedge (x : -) \in \Gamma_2 \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.

$$(V_1, M_1) \otimes a.(V_2, M_2) \triangleq (V, M)$$

where

$$V \triangleq \{(v_1, v_2) \mid v_1 \in V_1, v_2 \in V_2[v_1/a]\} \triangleq \sum a \in V_1, V_2$$

$$M \triangleq \{(v_1, v_2) \mapsto (M_1 v_1 \cdot M_2[v_1/a] v_2) \mid v_1 \in V_1, v_2 \in V_2[v_1/a]\}$$

Definition 3.

$$(C_1, M_1) \otimes a.(C_2, M_2) \triangleq (C, M)$$

where

$$C \triangleq \{(i, j) \mid i \in C_1, j \in C_2[i/a]\} \triangleq \sum i \in C_1, C_2$$

$$M \triangleq \{(i, j) \mapsto (M_1 i \cdot M_2[i/a] j) \mid i \in C_1, j \in C_2[i/a]\}$$

Definition 4 (Marginals of a dynamic distribution). Marginals are defined as follows:

$$1. \mathbb{M}_1((\sum a \in V_1, V_2), M) \triangleq (V_m, M_m)$$

where

$$V_m \triangleq V_1$$

$$M_m \triangleq \{v_1 \mapsto \sum_{v_2 \in V_2} (M(v_1, v_2)) \mid v_1 \in V_1\}$$

$$2. \mathbb{M}_2((\sum a \in V_1, V_2), M) \triangleq (V_m, M_m)$$

where

$$V_m \triangleq \bigcup_{v_1 \in V_1} V_2[v_1/a]$$

$$M_m \triangleq \{v_2 \mapsto \sum_{v_1 \in V_1} (M(v_1, v_2)) \mid v_1 \in V_1, v_2 \in V_2[v_1/a]\}$$

Definition 5. $\mu_1 \geq \mu_2 \triangleq \pi_1(\mu_1) = \pi_1(\mu_2)$ and $\forall i \in \pi_1(\mu_1). \pi_2(\mu_1) i \geq \pi_2(\mu_2) i$

Definition 6 (Coupling).

$$\mu_1 \leftrightarrow \mu_2 \triangleq \nu \text{ s.t.}$$

$$\forall i \in \mu_1. \sum_{j \in \mu_2} \nu_{(i,j)} i = \mu_1 i \text{ and } \forall j \in \mu_2. \sum_{i \in \mu_1} \nu_{(i,j)} j = \mu_2 j$$

Definition 7 (Euclidian norm).

$$\|V_1 - V_2\|_n \triangleq \sqrt[2]{\sum_{0 \leq i < n} (V_{1i} - V_{2i})^2}$$

1.2 Type system

Typing judgment: $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; x : \tau \vdash x : \tau} \text{T-var1} \qquad \frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; x : \tau; . \vdash x : \tau} \text{T-var2} \\
\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; . \vdash () : \mathbf{1}} \text{T-unit} \qquad \frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; . \vdash tt : \mathbf{B}(tt)} \text{T-tt} \\
\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; . \vdash ff : \mathbf{B}(ff)} \text{T-ff} \qquad \frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; . \vdash Z : \mathbf{N}(0)} \text{T-zero} \\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; . \vdash n : \mathbf{N}(n)}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; . \vdash S n : \mathbf{N}(n+1)} \text{T-succ} \\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : \mathbf{N}(n) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_0 : \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; i; \Delta, i+1 = n; \Omega; \Gamma_2, x : \mathbf{N}(i) \vdash e_1 : \tau \quad i \notin \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_1 : \tau} \text{T-matchN} \\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : !\mathbf{N}(n) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_0 : \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; i; \Delta, i+1 = n; \Omega, x : \mathbf{N}(i); \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 : \tau \quad i \notin \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{matchN! } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_1 : \tau} \text{T-matchN!} \\
\frac{\Theta \vdash r : \mathbb{R}}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; . \vdash r : \mathbf{R}(r)} \text{T-real} \qquad \frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; . \vdash nil : L_{i<0} \tau} \text{T-nil} \\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \tau[0/i] \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : L_{i<n+1} \tau[(i+1)/i]}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 :: e_2 : L_{i<n+1} \tau} \text{T-cons} \\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : L_{i<n} \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta, n=0; \Omega; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 : \tau' \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2, h : \tau[0/i], t : L_{i<n-1} \tau[(i+1)/i] \vdash e_2 : \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta, p : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{match } e \text{ with } |nil \mapsto e_1 |h :: t \mapsto e_2 : \tau'} \text{T-match} \\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : !L_{i<n} \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta, n=0; \Omega; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 : \tau' \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega, h : \tau[0/i], t : L_{i<n-1} \tau[(i+1)/i]; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta, p : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{match } e \text{ with } |nil \mapsto e_1 |h :: t \mapsto e_2 : \tau'} \text{T-match!} \\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma, x : \tau_1 \vdash e : \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \lambda x. e : \tau_1 \multimap \tau_2} \text{T-lam}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : \tau_1}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 e_2 : \tau_2} \text{T-app} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau[n/s] \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash n : S}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{Ex } e : \exists s : S . \tau} \text{T-existI} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : \exists s : S . \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta, s : S; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2, x : \tau \vdash e' : \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{letEx } x = e \text{ in } e' : \tau'} \text{T-existE} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau \quad \Psi, \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau <: \tau' \quad \Psi; \Theta \models \Gamma' <: \Gamma \quad \Psi; \Theta \models \Omega' <: \Omega}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega'; \Gamma' \vdash e : \tau'} \text{T-sub} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \tau_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \langle\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle\rangle : \tau_1 \times \tau_2} \text{T-tensorI} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : (\tau_1 \times \tau_2) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2, x : \tau_1, y : \tau_2 \vdash e' : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = e \text{ in } e' : \tau} \text{T-tensorE} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e_1 : \tau_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e_2 : \tau_1}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle : \tau_1 \& \tau_2} \text{T-withI} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (\tau_1 \& \tau_2)}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{fst}(e) : \tau_1} \text{T-fst} \quad \frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (\tau_1 \& \tau_2)}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{snd}(e) : \tau_2} \text{T-snd} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau_1}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{inl}(e) : \tau_1 + \tau_2} \text{T-inl} \quad \frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{inr}(e) : \tau_1 + \tau_2} \text{T-inr} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : (\tau_1 + \tau_2) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2, x : \tau_1 \vdash e_1 : \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2, y : \tau_2 \vdash e_2 : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{case } e \text{ of } x.e_1; y.e_2 : \tau} \text{T-case} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; . \vdash e : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash !e : !\tau} \text{T-expI} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : !\tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega, x : \tau; \Gamma_2 \vdash e' : \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{let } !x = e \text{ in } e' : \tau'} \text{T-expE}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\Psi, \alpha : K; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \Lambda.e : \forall \alpha : K . \tau} \text{T-tabs} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (\forall \alpha : K . \tau) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' : K}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e \bullet : \tau[\tau'/\alpha]} \text{T-tapp} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta, i : S; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \Lambda.e : \forall i : S . \tau} \text{T-iabs} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (\forall i : S . \tau) \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash I : S}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e \bullet : \tau[I/i]} \text{T-iapp} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta, c; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \Lambda.e : (c \Rightarrow \tau)} \text{T-CI} \quad \frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (c \Rightarrow \tau) \quad \Theta; \Delta \models c}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e \bullet : \tau} \text{T-CE} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega, x : \tau; . \vdash e : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; . \vdash \text{fix } x.e : \tau} \text{T-fix} \quad \frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau \quad \Theta; \Delta \models c}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \Lambda.e : (c \& \tau)} \text{T-CAndI} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (c \& \tau) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta, c; \Omega; \Gamma, x : \tau \vdash e' : \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{let } x = e \text{ in } e' : \tau'} \text{T-CAndE} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : [p] \mathbf{1} \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash p \geq p_1 + p_2 \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash p_1 : \mathbb{R}^+ \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash p_2 : \mathbb{R}^+}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{Split } e : ([p_1] \mathbf{1} \times [p_2] \mathbf{1})} \text{T-split}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau[0/a] \quad \delta_0 = (\{0\}, \{0 \mapsto 1\})}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{return } e : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \tau} \text{T-ret} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu_1)} \kappa_1 \tau_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2, x : \tau_1 \vdash e_2 : \mathbb{PC}_{(b \leftarrow \mu_2)} \kappa_2 \tau_2 \quad \kappa \geq \kappa_1 + \sum_{a \in \pi_1(\mu_1)} \pi_2(\mu_1) a \cdot \kappa_2 a}{\mu \geq \mu_1 \otimes a.\mu_2 \quad \Psi; \Theta, c; \Delta, c \in \pi_1(\mu) \vdash \tau_2[\pi_1(c)/a][\pi_2(c)/b] <: \tau \quad \{a, b\} \notin \mu, \kappa, \tau \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa_1 : \mathbb{R}^+ \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa_2 : \mathbb{R}^+} \text{T-bind} \\
\hline
\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{bind } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 : \mathbb{PC}_{(c \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau \\
\\
\frac{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa : \mathbb{R}^+ \quad \delta_0 = (\{0\}, \{0 \mapsto 1\})}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \uparrow^\kappa : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa \mathbf{1}} \text{T-tick} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau[0/a] \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa : \mathbb{R}^+ \quad \delta_0 = (\{0\}, \{0 \mapsto 1\})}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{store } e : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa ([\kappa] \tau)} \text{T-store} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : [\kappa] \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2, x : \tau \vdash e_2 : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} (\kappa + \kappa') \tau' \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa : \mathbb{R}^+ \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa' : \mathbb{R}^+}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa' \tau'} \text{T-release} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(p \ i) \quad \Theta; \Delta \models n > 0 \quad \mu = (\{0 \dots n-1\}, \{i \mapsto p \ i \mid i < n\}) \quad \sum_{i < n} p \ i = 1 \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash p : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{toDist } e : \mathbb{PC}_{(i \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \mathbf{N}(i)} \text{T-toDist} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : !L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(p \ i) \quad \Theta; \Delta \models n > 0 \quad \mu = (\{0 \dots n-1\}, \{i \mapsto p \ i \mid i < n\}) \quad \sum_{i < n} p \ i = 1 \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash p : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{toDist } e : \mathbb{PC}_{(i \leftarrow \mu)} 0 !\mathbf{N}(i)} \text{T-toDist!} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \mathbf{N}(n) \quad \mu = (\{0, \dots, n\}, \{i \mapsto \frac{1}{n+1} \mid i < n+1\})}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{Unif } e : \mathbb{PC}_{(i \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \mathbf{N}(i)} \text{T-Unif} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : [p] \tau_1 \times \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{Swap } e : \tau_1 \times [p] \tau_2} \text{T-swap}
\end{array}$$

Figure 1: Typing rules

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau <: \tau} \text{sub-refl} \qquad \frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau'_1 <: \tau_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_2 <: \tau'_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 \multimap \tau_2 <: \tau'_1 \multimap \tau'_2} \text{sub-arrow} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau'_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_2 <: \tau'_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 \times \tau_2 <: \tau'_1 \times \tau'_2} \text{sub-tensor} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau'_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_2 <: \tau'_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 \& \tau_2 <: \tau'_1 \& \tau'_2} \text{sub-with} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau'_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_2 <: \tau'_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 + \tau_2 <: \tau'_1 + \tau'_2} \text{sub-sum} \qquad \frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau <: \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash !\tau <: !\tau'} \text{sub-Exp} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; i; \Delta, i < n \vdash \tau <: \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash L_{i < n} \tau <: L_{i < n} \tau'} \text{sub-list} \qquad \frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta, s \vdash \tau <: \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \exists s. \tau <: \exists s. \tau'} \text{sub-exist} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi, \alpha; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \forall \alpha. \tau_1 <: \forall \alpha. \tau_2} \text{sub-typePoly} \qquad \frac{\Psi; \Theta; i; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \forall i. \tau_1 <: \forall i. \tau_2} \text{sub-indexPoly} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau_2 \quad \Theta; \Delta \models c_2 \implies c_1}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash c_1 \Rightarrow \tau_1 <: c_2 \Rightarrow \tau_2} \text{sub-constraint} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau_2 \quad \Theta; \Delta \models c_1 \implies c_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash c_1 \& \tau_1 <: c_2 \& \tau_2} \text{sub-CAnd} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau <: \tau' \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash p' \leq p}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash [p] \tau <: [p'] \tau'} \text{sub-potential} \\
\\
\frac{\Theta; \Delta \vdash k : \mathbb{R}^+ \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash k' : \mathbb{R}^+}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash [k](\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) <: ([k'] \tau_1 \multimap [k' + k] \tau_2)} \text{sub-potArrow} \\
\\
\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau <: [0] \tau} \text{sub-potZero} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \exists \alpha : \mu \leftrightarrow \mu' \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa \leq \kappa'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau <: \mathbb{PC}_{(a' \leftarrow \mu')} \kappa' \tau'} \text{sub-coupling}
\end{array}$$

Figure 2: Subtyping

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma <: .} \text{ sub-lBase} \\
\\
\frac{x : \tau' \in \Gamma_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' <: \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1/x <: \Gamma_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1 <: \Gamma_2, x : \tau} \text{ sub-lBase}
\end{array}$$

Figure 3: Γ Subtyping

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Omega <: .} \text{ sub-mBase} \\
\\
\frac{x : \tau' \in \Omega_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' <: \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Omega_1/x <: \Omega_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Omega_1 <: \Omega_2, x : \tau} \text{ sub-mInd}
\end{array}$$

Figure 4: Ω Subtyping

1.3 Operational Semantics

Pure reduction: $e \downarrow_t v$	Forcing reduction: $e \Downarrow_t^{\kappa} (V_d, M_d)$
------------------------------------	---

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{e_1 \downarrow_{t_1} v \quad e_2 \downarrow_{t_2} l}{e_1 :: e_2 \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v :: l} \text{E-cons} \\
\\
\frac{e_1 \downarrow_{t_1} \text{nil} \quad e_2 \downarrow_{t_2} v}{\text{match } e_1 \text{ with } | \text{nil} \mapsto e_2 \mid h :: t \mapsto e_3 \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v} \text{E-matchNil} \\
\\
\frac{e_1 \downarrow_{t_1} v_h :: l \quad e_3[v_h/h][l/t] \downarrow_{t_2} v}{\text{match } e_1 \text{ with } | \text{nil} \mapsto e_2 \mid h :: t \mapsto e_3 \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v} \text{E-matchCons} \quad \frac{e \downarrow_t v}{S e \downarrow_{t+1} S v} \text{E-succ} \\
\\
\frac{e \downarrow_{t_1} Z \quad e_0 \downarrow_{t_2} v}{\text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_2 \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v} \text{E-matchZero} \\
\\
\frac{e \downarrow_{t_1} S v \quad e_1[v/x] \downarrow_{t_2} v}{\text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_2 \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v} \text{E-matchSucc} \\
\\
\frac{e_1 \downarrow_{t_1} v \quad e_2[v/x] \downarrow_{t_2} v'}{e_1; x.e_2 \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v'} \text{E-exist} \quad \frac{e_1 \downarrow_{t_1} \lambda x.e' \quad e'[e_2/x] \downarrow_{t_2} v'}{e_1 e_2 \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v'} \text{E-app} \\
\\
\frac{e_1 \downarrow_{t_1} v_1 \quad e_2 \downarrow_{t_2} v_2}{\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle} \text{E-TI} \quad \frac{e \downarrow_{t_1} \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle \quad e'[v_1/x][v_2/y] \downarrow_{t_2} v}{\text{let } \langle x, y \rangle = e \text{ in } e' \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v} \text{E-TE} \\
\\
\frac{e_1 \downarrow_{t_1} v_1 \quad e_2 \downarrow_{t_2} v_2}{\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle} \text{E-WI} \quad \frac{e \downarrow_t \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle}{\text{fst}(e) \downarrow_{t+1} v_1} \text{E-fst} \quad \frac{e \downarrow_t \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle}{\text{snd}(e) \downarrow_{t+1} v_2} \text{E-snd} \\
\\
\frac{e \downarrow_t v}{\text{inl}(e) \downarrow_{t+1} \text{inl}(v)} \text{E-inl} \quad \frac{e \downarrow_t v}{\text{inr}(e) \downarrow_{t+1} \text{inr}(v)} \text{E-inr} \\
\\
\frac{e \downarrow_{t_1} \text{inl}(v) \quad e'[v/x] \downarrow_{t_2} v'}{\text{case } e \text{ of } x.e'; y.e'' \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} \text{inl}(v')} \text{E-case1} \\
\\
\frac{e \downarrow_{t_1} \text{inr}(v) \quad e''[v/y] \downarrow_{t_2} v''}{\text{case } e \text{ of } x.e'; y.e'' \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} \text{inl}(v'')} \text{E-case2} \\
\\
\frac{e \downarrow_{t_1} !e'' \quad e'[e''/x] \downarrow_{t_2} v}{\text{let } !x = e \text{ in } e' \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v} \text{E-expE} \quad \frac{e[\text{fix } x.e/x] \downarrow_t v}{\text{fix } x.e \downarrow_{t+1} v} \text{E-fix} \quad \frac{e \downarrow_t ()}{\text{split } e \downarrow_{t+1} \langle (), () \rangle} \text{E-split}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{v \in \{(), nil, \lambda y. -, \Lambda. -, !-, \text{return } e, \text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2, \uparrow^-, \text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2, \text{store } e\}}{v \Downarrow_0 v} \text{E-val} \\
\\
\frac{e \Downarrow_{t_1} \Lambda.e' \quad e' \Downarrow_{t_2} v}{e \bullet \Downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v} \text{E-tapp} \qquad \frac{e \Downarrow_{t_1} \Lambda.e' \quad e' \Downarrow_{t_2} v}{e \bullet \Downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v} \text{E-iapp} \\
\\
\frac{e \Downarrow_{t_1} \Lambda.e' \quad e' \Downarrow_{t_1} v}{e \bullet \Downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v} \text{E-CE} \qquad \frac{e_1 \Downarrow_{t_1} v \quad e_2[v/x] \Downarrow_{t_2} v'}{\text{clet } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \Downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v'} \text{E-CAnadE} \\
\\
\frac{}{\uparrow^\kappa \Downarrow_1^\kappa (\{()\}, \{() \mapsto 1\})} \text{E-tick} \qquad \frac{e \Downarrow_t v}{\text{return } e \Downarrow_{t+1}^0 (\{v\}, \{v \mapsto 1\})} \text{E-return} \\
\\
\frac{e_1 \Downarrow_{t_1} v_1 \quad v_1 \Downarrow_{t_2}^{\kappa_1} (V_1, M_1) \quad \forall a \in V_1. e_2[a/x] \Downarrow_{t_a} v_{2a} \wedge v_{2a} \Downarrow_{t_a'}^{\kappa_{2a}} \mu_{2a} \quad t_3 = \max_{a \in V_1} t_a \quad t_4 = \max_{a \in V_1} t_a' \quad \kappa_2 = \sum_{a \in V_1} (M_1 a) \cdot \kappa_{2a} \quad \mu = \mu_1 \otimes a. \mu_{2a}}{\text{bind } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \Downarrow_{t_1+t_2+t_3+t_4+1}^{\kappa_1+\kappa_2} \mathbb{M}_2(\mu)} \text{E-bind} \\
\\
\frac{e \Downarrow_t v}{\text{store } e \Downarrow_{t+1}^0 (\{v\}, \{v \mapsto 1\})} \text{E-store} \\
\\
\frac{e_1 \Downarrow_{t_1} v_1 \quad e_2[v_1/x] \Downarrow_{t_2} v_2 \quad v_2 \Downarrow_{t_3}^\kappa (V, M)}{\text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \Downarrow_{t_1+t_2+t_3+1}^\kappa (V, M)} \text{E-release} \\
\\
\frac{e \Downarrow_t ls \quad ls \neq nil \quad V_d = \{0 \dots |ls| - 1\} \quad M_d = \{i \mapsto ls!!i \mid i \in V_d\}}{\text{toDist } e \Downarrow_{t+1}^0 (V_d, M_d)} \text{E-toDist} \\
\\
\frac{e \Downarrow_t n \quad V_d = \{0 \dots n\} \quad M_d = \{i \mapsto \frac{1}{n+1} \mid i \in V_d\}}{\text{Unif } e \Downarrow_{t+1}^0 (V_d, M_d)} \text{E-unif} \\
\\
\frac{e \Downarrow_t \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle}{\text{Swap } e \Downarrow_{t+1} \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle} \text{E-swap}
\end{array}$$

Figure 5: Evaluation rules

1.4 Model

Definition 8 (Value and expression relation).

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{V}[\mathbf{1}] &\triangleq \{(p, T, ())\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\mathbf{B}(i)] &\triangleq \{(p, T, v) \mid v \in \llbracket \mathbf{B} \rrbracket \wedge i = v\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(0)] &\triangleq \{(p, T, Z)\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(n+1)] &\triangleq \{(p, T, S v) \mid (p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(n)]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\mathbf{R}(i)] &\triangleq \{(p, T, v) \mid v \in \llbracket \mathbf{R} \rrbracket \wedge i = v\} \\
\mathcal{V}[L_{i < 1} \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, nil)\} \\
\mathcal{V}[L_{i < s+1} \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, v :: l) \mid \exists p_1, p_2. p_1 + p_2 \leq p \wedge (p_1, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[0/i]] \wedge \\
&\quad (p_2, T, l) \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < s} \tau[i+1/i]]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \times \tau_2] &\triangleq \{(p, T, \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle) \mid \exists p_1, p_2. p_1 + p_2 \leq p \wedge (p_1, T, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1] \wedge (p_2, T, v_2) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \& \tau_2] &\triangleq \{(p, T, \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle) \mid (p, T, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1] \wedge (p, T, v_2) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\tau_1 + \tau_2] &\triangleq \{(p, T, \text{inl}(v)) \mid (p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1]\} \cup \{(p, T, \text{inr}(v)) \mid (p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2] &\triangleq \{(p, T, \lambda x. e) \mid \forall p', e', T' < T. (p', T', e') \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1] \implies (p + p', T', e[e'/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\!|\tau|] &\triangleq \{(p, T, !e) \mid (0, T, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau]\} \cup \\
&\quad \{(\infty, T, !e) \mid \exists p'. p' > 0 \wedge (p', T, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\forall \alpha. \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, \Lambda. e) \mid \forall T', T' < T. (p, T', e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[\alpha'/\alpha]]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\forall i. \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, \Lambda. e) \mid \forall I, T' < T. (p, T', e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[I/i]]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[c \Rightarrow \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, \Lambda. e) \mid . \models c \implies (p, T, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[c \& \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, v) \mid . \models c \wedge (p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\exists s. \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, \text{Ex } e) \mid \exists s'. (p, T, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[s'/s]]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\llbracket n \rrbracket \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, v) \mid \exists p'. p' + n \leq p \wedge (p', T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\text{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, v) \mid \mu = (C_s, M_s) \wedge \forall \kappa', v', T' < T. \\
&\quad v \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies \\
&\quad \exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]. \\
&\quad 1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\
&\quad \quad \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j)) \\
&\quad 2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}. \\
&\quad a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies \\
&\quad \quad (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]] \\
&\quad b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa\} \\
\mathcal{E}[\tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, e) \mid \forall T' < T, v. e \Downarrow_{T'} v \implies (p, T - T', v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau]\}
\end{aligned}$$

Definition 9 (Interpretation of typing contexts).

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{G}[\Gamma] &= \{(p, T, \rho_l) \mid \exists f : \text{Vars} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+. \\
&\quad (\forall x \in \text{dom}(\Gamma). (f(x), T, \rho_l(x)) \in \mathcal{E}[\Gamma(x)]) \wedge (\sum_{x \in \text{dom}(\Gamma)} f(x) \leq p)\} \\
\mathcal{G}[\Omega] &\triangleq \{(p, T, \rho_m) \mid \exists f : \text{Vars} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+. \forall x \in \text{dom}(\Omega). (f(x), T, \rho_m(x)) \in \mathcal{E}[\Omega(x)] \wedge \\
&\quad \exists x \in \text{dom}(\Omega). f(x) > 0 \implies p = \infty\}
\end{aligned}$$

Definition 10 (Type and index substitutions). $\theta : \text{TypeVar} \rightarrow \text{Type}$, $\iota : \text{IndexVar} \rightarrow \text{Index}$

Lemma 11 (Value monotonicity lemma). $(p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau] \wedge p \leq p' \wedge T' \leq T \implies (p', T', v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau]$

Proof. Proof by induction on τ

□

Lemma 12 (Expression monotonicity lemma). $(p, T, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau] \wedge p \leq p' \wedge T' \leq T \implies (p', T', e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau]$

Proof. From Definition 8 and Lemma 11

□

Theorem 13 (Fundamental theorem). $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau \wedge (p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta \iota] \wedge (p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta \iota] \wedge \cdot \models \Delta \iota \implies (p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_l \rho_m) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta \iota]$.

Proof. Proof by induction on the typing judgment

1. T-var1:

$$\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma, x : \tau \vdash x : \tau} \text{T-var1}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma, x : \tau \theta \iota]$ and $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta \iota]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, x \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta \iota]$

Since we are given that $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma, x : \tau \theta \iota]$ therefore from Definition 9 we know that

$\exists f. (f(x), T, \rho_l(x)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta \iota]$ where $f(x) \leq p_l$

Therefore from Lemma 12 we get $(p_l + p_m, T, x \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta \iota]$

2. T-var2:

$$\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega, x : \tau; \Gamma \vdash x : \tau} \text{T-var2}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma, \theta \iota]$ and $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Omega, x : \tau) \theta \iota]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, x \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta \iota]$

Directly from Definition 9 and Lemma 12.

3. T-unit, T-zero, T-real, T-succ:

Trivial.

4. T-matchN:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : \mathbf{N}(n) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta, n = 0; \Omega; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_0 : \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta, i; \Delta, i + 1 = n; \Omega; \Gamma_2, x : \mathbf{N}(i) \vdash e_1 : \tau \quad i \notin \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_1 : \tau} \text{T-matchN}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_1) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_1) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(\text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_1) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-M0})$$

From Definition 9 and Definition 1 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t

$$(p_{l1}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_1) \theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{l2}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_2) \theta_l]$$

IH1

$$(p_{l1} + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbf{N}(n) \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t' < T. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} v_1 \implies (p_{l1} + p_m, T - t', v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(n) \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_1) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-matchN we know that $\exists t' < t, v_1. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} v_1$.

$$\text{Since } t' < t < T, \text{ therefore we have } (p_{l1} + p_m, T - t', v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(n) \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-M1})$$

2 cases arise:

(a) $v_1 = Z$:

IH2

$$(p_{l2} + p_m, T, e_0 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T. e_0 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_f \implies (p_{l2} + p_m, T - t_1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_1) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-matchN we know that $\exists t_1 < t. e_0 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_f$.

Since $t_1 < t < T$ therefore we have

$$(p_{l2} + p_m, T - t_1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

And from Lemma 11 we get

$$(p_{l_2} + p_{l_1} + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

And finally since $p_l = p_{l_1} + p_{l_2}$ therefore we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

And we are done.

(b) $v_1 = S v$:

From (F-M1) and Definition 8 we know that

$$(p_{l_1} + p_m, T - t', v) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(j) \theta_l] \text{ where } j + 1 = n$$

In this case we know that $j + 1 = n$

IH2

$$(p_{l_2} + p_{l_1} + p_m, T, e_2 \rho_m \rho'_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_{l'}]$$

where

$$\rho'_l = \rho_l \cup \{x \mapsto v\}$$

$$l' = l \cup \{i \mapsto j\}$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T . e_2 \rho_m \rho'_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (p_{l_2} + p_{l_1} + p_m, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_{l'}]$$

Since we know that $(\text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_1) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-matchN we know that $\exists t_2 < t . e_2 \rho_m \rho'_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$.

Since $t_2 < t < T$ therefore we have

$$(p_{l_2} + p_{l_1} + p_m, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_{l'}]$$

From Lemma 11 we get

$$(p_{l_2} + p_{l_1} + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_{l'}]$$

And finally since $p_l = p_{l_1} + p_{l_2}$ therefore we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_{l'}]$$

Since $i \notin \tau$, therefore we also have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

And we are done.

5. T-matchN!:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : \mathbf{N}(n) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta, n = 0; \Omega; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_0 : \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta, i; \Delta, i + 1 = n; \Omega, x : \mathbf{N}(i); \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 : \tau \quad i \notin \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{matchN! } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_1 : \tau} \text{T-matchN!}$$

Similar reasoning as in the T-matchN and T-ExpE cases.

6. T-nil:

$$\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \cdot \vdash nil : L_{i < 0} \tau} \text{T-nil}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma, \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega, \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, nil \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[L_{i < 0} \tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall T' < T, v'. nil \downarrow_{T'} v' \implies (p_l + p_m, T - T', v') \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < 0} \tau \theta_l]$$

This means given some $T' < T, v'$ s.t $nil \downarrow_{T'} v'$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - T', v') \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < 0} \tau \theta_l]$$

From (E-val) we know that $T' = 0$ and $v' = nil$, therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, nil) \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < 0} \tau \theta_l]$$

We get this directly from Definition 8

7. T-cons:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \tau[0/i] \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : L_{i < n} \tau[(i+1)/i]}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 :: e_2 : L_{i < n+1} \tau} \text{T-cons}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2)\theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Omega) \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (e_1 :: e_2) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[L_{i < n+1} \tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v'. (e_1 :: e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v' \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v') \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < n+1} \tau \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v'$ s.t $(e_1 :: e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v'$, it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v') \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < n+1} \tau \theta_l]$$

From (E-cons) we know that $\exists v_f, l. v' = v_f :: l$

Therefore from Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists p_1, p_2. p_1 + p_2 \leq p_l + p_m \wedge (p_1, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[0/i] \theta_l] \wedge (p_2, T - t, l) \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < n} \tau[i+1/i] \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-C0})$$

From Definition 9 and Definition 1 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t

$$(p_{l1}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1)\theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{l2}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2)\theta_l]$$

IH1:

$$(p_{l1}, T, e_1 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T. e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_f \implies (p_{l1}, T - t_1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau]$$

Since we are given that $(e_1 :: e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f :: l$ therefore from E-cons we also know that $\exists t_1 < t. e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_f$

$$\text{Since } t_1 < t < T, \text{ therefore we have } (p_{l1}, T - t_1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-C1})$$

IH2:

$$(p_{l2}, T, e_2 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[L_{i < n} \tau \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T. e_2 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} l \implies (p_{l2}, T - t_2, l) \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < n} \tau \theta_l]$$

Since we are given that $(e_1 :: e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f :: l$ therefore from E-cons we also know that $\exists t_2 < t - t_1. e_2 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} l$

Since $t_2 < t - t_1 < t < T$, therefore we have

$$(p_{l2}, T - t_2, l) \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < n} \tau \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-C2})$$

In order to prove (F-C0) we choose p_1 as p_{l1} and p_2 as p_{l2} and it suffices to prove that

$$(p_{l1}, T - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l] \wedge (p_{l2}, T - t, l) \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < n} \tau \theta_l]$$

Since $t = t_1 + t_2 + 1$ therefore from (F-C1) and Lemma 11 we get $(p_{l1}, T - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$

Similarly from (F-C2) and Lemma 11 we also get $(p_{l2}, T - t, l) \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < n} \tau \theta_l]$

8. T-match:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : L^n \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 : \tau' \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta, n > 0; \Omega; \Gamma_2, h : \tau, t : L^{n-1} \tau \vdash e_2 : \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{match } e \text{ with } |nil \mapsto e_1 |h :: t \mapsto e_2 : \tau'} \text{ T-match}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{match } e \text{ with } |nil \mapsto e_1 |h :: t \mapsto e_2) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\text{match } e \text{ with } |nil \mapsto e_1 |h :: t \mapsto e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t (match e with $|nil \mapsto e_1 |h :: t \mapsto e_2)$ $\rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-M0})$$

From Definition 9 and Definition 1 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t

$$(p_{l1}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1)\theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{l2}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2)\theta_l]$$

IH1

$$(p_{l1} + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[L^n \tau \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t' < T . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} v_1 \implies (p_{l1} + p_m, T - t', v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[L^n \tau \theta_l]$$

Since we know that (match e with $|nil \mapsto e_1 |h :: t \mapsto e_2)$ $\rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-match we know that $\exists t' < t, v_1. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} v_1$.

$$\text{Since } t' < t < T, \text{ therefore we have } (p_{l1} + p_m, T - t', v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[L^n \tau \theta_l]$$

2 cases arise:

(a) $v_1 = nil$:

In this case we know that $n = 0$ therefore

IH2

$$(p_{l2} + p_m, T, e_1 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_f \implies (p_{l2} + p_m, T - t_1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

Since we know that (match e with $|nil \mapsto e_1 |h :: t \mapsto e_2)$ $\rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-match we know that $\exists t_1 < t. e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_f$.

Since $t_1 < t < T$ therefore we have

$$(p_{l2} + p_m, T - t_1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

And from Lemma 11 we get

$$(p_{l2} + p_{l1} + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

And finally since $p_l = p_{l1} + p_{l2}$ therefore we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

And we are done.

(b) $v_1 = v :: l$:

In this case we know that $n > 0$

IH2

$$(p_{l2} + p_{l1} + p_m, T, e_2 \rho_m \rho'_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

where

$$\rho'_l = \rho_l \cup \{h \mapsto v\} \cup \{t \mapsto l\}$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T . e_2 \rho_m \rho'_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (p_{l_2} + p_{l_1} + p_m, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

Since we know that (match e with $|nil \mapsto e_1 \mid h :: t \mapsto e_2$) $\rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-match we know that $\exists t_2 < t . e_2 \rho_m \rho'_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$.

Since $t_2 < t < T$ therefore we have

$$(p_{l_2} + p_{l_1} + p_m, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

From Lemma 11 we get

$$(p_{l_2} + p_{l_1} + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

And finally since $p_l = p_{l_1} + p_{l_2}$ therefore we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

And we are done.

9. T-existI:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau[n/s] \quad \Theta \vdash n : S}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{Ex } e : \exists s : S . \tau} \text{T-existI}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\exists s . \tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\exists s . \tau \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\exists s . \tau \theta_l]$$

Also from From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v_f = (\text{Ex } e) \rho_m \rho_l$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists s' . (p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[s'/s] \theta_l] \tag{F-E0}$$

$$\underline{\text{IH}}: (p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[n/s] \theta_l]$$

We choose s' as n and we get the desired directly from IH.

10. T-existsE:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : \exists s . \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; s; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2, x : \tau \vdash e' : \tau' \quad \Theta \vdash \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash e; x . e' : \tau'} \text{T-existE}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Omega) \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (e; x.e') \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (e; x.e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

This means given soem $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(e; x.e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-EE0})$$

From Definition 9 and Definition 1 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t

$$(p_{l1}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1) \theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{l2}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2) \theta_l]$$

IH1

$$(p_{l1} + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\exists s. \tau \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_1 \implies (p_{l1} + p_m, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{E}[\exists s. \tau \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(e; x.e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-existE we know that $\exists t_1 < t, v_1. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_1$. Therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_m, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\exists s. \tau \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 8 we have

$$\exists s'. (p_{l1} + p_m, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[s'/s] \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-EE1})$$

IH2

$$(p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_m, T, e' \rho'_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta_l']$$

where

$$\rho'_m = \rho_m \cup \{x \mapsto e_1\} \text{ and } l' = l \cup \{s \mapsto s'\}$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T . e' \rho'_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_m, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l']$$

Since we know that $(e; x.e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-existE we know that $\exists t_2 < t. e' \rho'_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$.

Since $t_2 < t < T$ therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_m, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l']$$

Since $p_l = p_{l1} + p_{l2}$ therefore we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l']$$

From Lemma 11 we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l']$$

And finally since we have $\Psi; \Theta \vdash \tau'$ therefore we also have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

And we are done

11. T-lam:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma, x : \tau_1 \vdash e : \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \lambda x. e : (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2)} \text{T-lam}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma, \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\lambda x. e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\lambda x. e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t. $(\lambda x. e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v_f = (\lambda x. e) \rho_m \rho_l$

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, (\lambda x. e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall p', e', T' < T. (p', T', e') \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \theta_l] \implies (p_l + p_m + p', T', e[e'/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \theta_l]$$

This means given some $p', e', T' < T$ s.t. $(p', T', e') \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m + p', T', e[e'/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-L1})$$

From IH we know that

$$(p_l + p_m + p', T, e \rho_m \rho_l') \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \theta_l]$$

where

$$\rho_l' = \rho_l \cup \{x \mapsto e'\}$$

Therefore from Lemma 12 we get the desired

12. T-app:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : \tau_1}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 e_2 : \tau_2} \text{T-app}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Omega) \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, e_1 \ e_2 \ \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \ \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (e_1 \ e_2) \ \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \ \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(e_1 \ e_2) \ \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \ \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-A0})$$

From Definition 9 and Definition 1 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t

$$(p_{l1}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1)\theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{l2}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2)\theta_l]$$

IH1

$$(p_{l1} + p_m, T, e_1 \ \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \ \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T. e_1 \downarrow_{t_1} \lambda x. e \implies (p_{l1} + p_m, T - t_1, \lambda x. e) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \ \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(e_1 \ e_2) \ \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-app we know that $\exists t_1 < t. e_1 \downarrow_{t_1} \lambda x. e$, therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_m, T - t_1, \lambda x. e) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \ \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall p', e_1, T_1 < T - t_1. (p', T_1, e'_1) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \ \theta_l] \implies (p_{l1} + p_m + p', T_1, e[e'_1/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \ \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-A1})$$

IH2

$$(p_{l2} + p_m, T - t_1 - 1, e_2 \ \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \ \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-A2})$$

Instantiating (F-A1) with $p_{l2} + p_m, e_2 \ \rho_m \rho_l$ and $T - t_1 - 1$ we get

$$(p_{l1} + p_m + p_{l2} + p_m, T - t_1 - 1, e[e_2 \ \rho_m \rho_l/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \ \theta_l]$$

Since $p_m = 0$ or $p_m = \infty$, therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_m, T - t_1 - 1, e[e_2 \ \rho_m \rho_l/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \ \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T - t_1 - 1. e[e_2 \ \rho_m \rho_l/x] \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_m, T - t_1 - 1 - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \ \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(e_1 \ e_2) \ \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-app we know that $\exists t_2. e[e_2 \ \rho_m \rho_l/x] \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$ where $t_2 = t - t_1 - 1$, therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_m, T - t_1 - t_2 - 1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \ \theta_l] \text{ where } p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$$

Since from E-app we know that $t = t_1 + t_2 + 1$, therefore we have proved (F-A0)

13. T-sub:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau <: \tau' \quad \Psi; \Theta \models \Gamma' <: \Gamma \quad \Psi; \Theta \models \Omega' <: \Omega}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega'; \Gamma' \vdash e : \tau'} \text{T-sub}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma') \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega') \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta_l]$

Since we are given that $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma') \theta_l]$ therefore from Lemma 17 we also have $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma) \theta_l]$

Similarly since we are given that $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega') \theta_l]$ therefore from Lemma 18 we also have $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega) \theta_l]$

IH:

$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$

We get the desired directly from IH and Lemma 15.

14. T-tensorI:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \tau_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle : (\tau_1 \times \tau_2)} \text{T-tensorI}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Omega) \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 \times \tau_2) \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T . \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_{f_1}, v_{f_2} \rangle \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, \langle v_{f_1}, v_{f_2} \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \times \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T$ s.t $\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_{f_1}, v_{f_2} \rangle$ it suffices to prove that $(p_l + p_m, T - t, \langle v_{f_1}, v_{f_2} \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \times \tau_2) \theta_l]$ (F-TI0)

From Definition 9 and Definition 1 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2} . p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t

$(p_{l1}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1) \theta_l]$ and $(p_{l2}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2) \theta_l]$

IH1:

$(p_{l1} + p_m, T, e_1 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$

Therefore from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_{f_1} \implies (p_{l1} + p_m, T - t_1, v_{f_1}) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

Since we are given that $\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_{f1}, v_{f2} \rangle$ therefore fom E-TI we know that $\exists t_1 < t. e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_{f1}$

Hence we have $(p_{l1} + p_m, T - t_1, v_{f1}) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$ (F-TI1)

IH2:

$(p_{l2} + p_m, T, e_2 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \theta_l]$

Therefore from Definition 8 we have

$\forall t_2 < T. e_2 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_{f2} \implies (p_{l2} + p_m, T - t_2, v_{f2}) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta_l]$

Since we are given that $\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_{f1}, v_{f2} \rangle$ therefore fom E-TI we also know that $\exists t_2 < t. e_2 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_{f2}$ s.t

Since $t_2 < t < T$ therefore we have

$(p_{l2} + p_m, T - t_2, v_{f2}) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta_l]$ (F-TI2)

Applying Lemma 11 on (F-TI1) and (F-TI2) and by using Definition 8 we get the desired (as p_m can only be 0 or ∞).

15. T-tensorE:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : (\tau_1 \times \tau_2) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2, x : \tau_1, y : \tau_2 \vdash e' : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = e \text{ in } e' : \tau} \text{T-tensorE}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$\forall t < T, v_f. (\text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(\text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$ (F-TE0)

From Definition 9 and Definition 1 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t

$(p_{l1}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1) \theta_l]$ and $(p_{l2}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2) \theta_l]$

IH1

$(p_{l1} + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 \times \tau_2) \theta_l]$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$\forall t_1 < T. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \implies (p_{l1} + p_m, T - t_1, \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \times \tau_2) \theta_l]$

Since we know that $(\text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-TE we know that $\exists t_1 < t, v_1, v_2. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle$. Therefore we have

$$(p_{l_1} + p_m, T - t_1, \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 \times \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

From Definition 8 we know that

$$\exists p_1, p_2. p_1 + p_2 \leq p_{l_1} \wedge (p_1, T, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l] \wedge (p_2, T, v_2) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-TE1})$$

IH2

$$(p_{l_2} + p_1 + p_2 + p_m, T, e' \rho_m \rho'_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

where

$$\rho'_l = \rho_l \cup \{x \mapsto v_1\} \cup \{y \mapsto v_2\}$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T. e' \rho_m \rho'_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (p_{l_2} + p_1 + p_2 + p_m, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-TE we know that $\exists t_2 < t. e' \rho_m \rho'_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$. Therefore we have

$$(p_{l_2} + p_1 + p_2 + p_m, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

From Lemma 11 we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

And we are done

16. T-withI:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e_1 : \tau_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e_2 : \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle : (\tau_1 \& \tau_2)} \text{T-withI}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l], (p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 \& \tau_2) \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T. \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_{f_1}, v_{f_2} \rangle \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, \langle v_{f_1}, v_{f_2} \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \& \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

This means given $\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_{f_1}, v_{f_2} \rangle$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, \langle v_{f_1}, v_{f_2} \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \& \tau_2) \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-WI0})$$

IH1:

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e_1 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_{f1} \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v_{f1}) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

Since we are given that $\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_{f1}, v_{f2} \rangle$ therefore from E-WI we know that $\exists t_1 < t . e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_{f1}$

Since $t_1 < t < T$, therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v_{f1}) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-WI1})$$

IH2:

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e_2 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T . e_2 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_{f2} \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_2, v_{f2}) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta_l]$$

Since we are given that $\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_{f1}, v_{f2} \rangle$ therefore from E-WI we also know that $\exists t_2 < t . e_2 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_{f2}$

Since $t_2 < t < T$, therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_2, v_{f2}) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-WI2})$$

Applying Lemma 11 on (F-W1) and (F-W2) we get the desired.

17. T-fst:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (\tau_1 \& \tau_2)}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{fst}(e) : \tau_1} \text{T-fst}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{fst}(e)) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f . (\text{fst}(e)) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(\text{fst}(e)) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-F0})$$

IH

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 \& \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \& \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{fst}(e)) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-fst we know that $\exists t_1 < t . v_1, v_2 . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle$.

Since $t_1 < t < T$, therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1, \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \& \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

From Definition 8 we know that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

Finally using Lemma 11 we also have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

Since from E-fst we know that $v_f = v_1$, therefore we are done.

18. T-snd:

Similar reasoning as in T-fst case above.

19. T-inl:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau_1}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{inl}(e) : \tau_1 + \tau_2} \text{T-inl}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \text{inl}(e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 + \tau_2) \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T . \text{inl}(e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \text{inl}(v) \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, \text{inl}(v)) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 + \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T$ s.t $\text{inl}(e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \text{inl}(v)$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, \text{inl}(v)) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 + \tau_2) \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-IL0})$$

IH:

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e_1 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_{f1} \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v_{f1}) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

Since we are given that $\text{inl}(e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \text{inl}(v)$ therefore fom E-inl we know that

$$\exists t_1 < t . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v$$

$$\text{Hence we have } (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

$$\text{From Lemma 11 we get } (p_l + p_m, T - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

And finally from Definition 8 we get (F-IL0)

20. T-inr:

Similar reasoning as in T-inr case above.

21. T-case:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : (\tau_1 + \tau_2) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2, x : \tau_1 \vdash e_1 : \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2, y : \tau_2 \vdash e_2 : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{case } e \text{ of } x.e_1; y.e_2 : \tau} \text{ T-case}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{case } e \text{ of } x.e_1; y.e_2) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\text{case } e \text{ of } x.e_1; y.e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t. $(\text{case } e \text{ of } x.e_1; y.e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-C0})$$

From Definition 9 and Definition 1 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t.

$$(p_{l1}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1) \theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{l2}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2) \theta_l]$$

IH1

$$(p_{l1} + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 + \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t' < T. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} v_1 \rho_m \rho_l \implies (p_{l1} + p_m, T - t', v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 + \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{case } e \text{ of } x.e_1; y.e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-case we know that $\exists t' < t, v_1.e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} v_1$.

Since $t' < t < T$, therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_m, T - t', v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 + \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

2 cases arise:

(a) $v_1 = \text{inl}(v)$:

IH2

$$(p_{l2} + p_{l1} + p_m, T - t', e_1 \rho_m \rho'_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

where

$$\rho'_l = \rho_l \cup \{x \mapsto v\}$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T - t'. e_1 \rho_m \rho'_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_f \implies (p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_m, T - t' - t_1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{case } e \text{ of } x.e_1; y.e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-case we know that $\exists t_1.e_1 \rho_m \rho'_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_f$ where $t_1 = t - t' - 1$.

Since $t_1 = t - t' - 1 < T - t'$ therefore we have

$$(p_{l_1} + p_{l_2} + p_m, T - t' - t_1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!]$$

From Lemma 11 we get

$$(p_{l_1} + p_{l_2} + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{E}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!]$$

And finally since $p_l = p_{l_1} + p_{l_2}$ therefore we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{E}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!]$$

And we are done.

(b) $v_1 = \text{inr}(v)$:

Similar reasoning as in the `inl` case above.

22. T-ExpI:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \cdot \vdash e : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash !e : !\tau} \text{T-ExpI}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\![\Gamma \theta_l]\!]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\![\Omega \theta_l]\!]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, !e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T. (!e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t (!e) \rho_m \rho_l \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, (!e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!]$$

This means given some $t < T$ s.t $(!e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t (!e) \rho_m \rho_l$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, (!e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!]$$

2 cases arise:

(a) Case $p_m = 0$:

In this case it suffices to prove that $(p_l, T - t, (!e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!]$

IH: $(0, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!]$

Therefore we get the desired directly from IH, Definition 8 and Lemma 12

(b) Case $p_m = \infty$:

In this case it suffices to prove that $(\infty, T - t, (!e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!]$

From Definition 8 it further suffices to prove that

$$\exists p' > 0. (p', T - t, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!]$$

IH: $(\infty, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!]$

We choose p' as ∞ and we get the desired from IH and Lemma 12

23. T-ExpE:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : !\tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; x : \tau; \Gamma_2 \vdash e' : \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{let } !x = e \text{ in } e' : \tau'} \text{T-ExpE}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Omega) \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{let } !x = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta_l]$

(a) $p_m = 0$:

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\text{let } !x = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t. $(\text{let } !x = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-E0})$$

From Definition 9 and Definition 1 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t. $(p_{l1}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1) \theta_l]$ and $(p_{l2}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2) \theta_l]$

IH1

$$(p_{l1}, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} !e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \implies (p_{l1}, T - t_1, !e_1 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{let } !x = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from (E-ExpE) we know that $\exists t_1 < t, e_1. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} !e_1 \rho_m \rho_l$.

Since $t_1 < t < T$, therefore we have

$$(p_{l1}, T - t_1, !e_1 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 two cases arise

$$\text{i. } (0, T - t_1, e_1 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau]$$

IH2

$$(p_{l2}, T - t_1, e' \rho'_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

where

$$\rho'_m = \rho_m \cup \{x \mapsto e_1\}$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T - t_1. e' \rho'_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (p_{l2}, T - t_1 - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{let } !x = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from (E-ExpE)

we know that $\exists t_2. e' \rho'_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$ where $t_2 = t - t_1 - 1$.

Since $t_2 = t - t_1 - 1 < T - t_1$, therefore we have

$$(p_{l2}, T - t_1 - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

From Lemma 12 we get

$$(p_{l2} + p_{l1}, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

And finally since $p_l = p_{l1} + p_{l2}$ therefore we get

$$(p_l, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

And we are done.

ii. $\exists p' > 0. (p', T - t_1, e_1 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau]$:

In this case we know that $p_{l1} = \infty$. This further means that $p_l = \infty$

IH2

$(\infty, T - t_1, e' \rho'_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta_l]$

where

$\rho'_m = \rho_m \cup \{x \mapsto e_1\}$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$\forall t_2 < T - t_1. e' \rho'_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (\infty, T - t_1 - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$

Since we know that $(\text{let } !x = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from (E-ExpE)

we know that $\exists t_2. e' \rho'_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$ where $t_2 = t - t_1 - 1$.

Since $t_2 = t - t_1 - 1 < T - t_1$, therefore we have

$(\infty, T - t_1 - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$

From Lemma 12 we get

$(\infty, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$

And we are done.

(b) $p_m = \infty$:

Similar reasoning.

24. T-tabs:

$$\frac{\Psi, \alpha : K; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \Lambda.e : (\forall \alpha : K . \tau)} \text{ T-tabs}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma, \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\forall \alpha . \tau) \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$\forall t < T, v_f. (\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[(\forall \alpha . \tau) \theta_l]$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v_f = (\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l$

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$(p_l + p_m, T, (\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[(\forall \alpha . \tau) \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$\forall \tau', T' < T. (p_l + p_m, T', e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[\tau'/\alpha] \theta_l]$

This means given some $\tau', T' < T$ it suffices to prove that

$(p_l + p_m, T', e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[\tau'/\alpha] \theta_l]$ (F-TAB0)

From IH we know that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta' \iota]$$

where

$$\theta' = \rho_l \cup \{\alpha \mapsto \tau'\}$$

Therefore from Lemma 12 we get the desired

25. T-tapp:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (\forall \alpha. \tau) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e \square : (\tau[\tau'/\alpha])} \text{T-tapp}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta \iota]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta \iota]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, e \square \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[\tau'/\alpha] \theta \iota]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (e \square) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[\tau'/\alpha] \theta \iota]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t. $(e \square) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[\tau'/\alpha] \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-A0})$$

IH

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\forall \alpha. \tau) \theta \iota]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T. e \downarrow_{t_1} \Lambda. e \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, \Lambda. e) \in \mathcal{V}[(\forall \alpha. \tau) \theta \iota]$$

Since we know that $(e \square) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-tapp we know that $\exists t_1 < t. e \downarrow_{t_1} \Lambda. e$, therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1, \Lambda. e) \in \mathcal{V}[(\forall \alpha. \tau) \theta \iota]$$

Therefore from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall \tau'', T_1 < T - t_1. (p_l + p_m, T_1, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[\tau''/\alpha] \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-A1})$$

Instantiating (F-A1) with the given τ' and $T - t_1 - 1$ we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1 - 1, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[\tau'/\alpha] \theta \iota]$$

From Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T - t_1 - 1. e \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1 - t_2 - 1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[\tau'/\alpha] \theta \iota]$$

Since we know that $(e \square) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-tapp we know that $\exists t_2. e \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$ where $t_2 = t - t_1 - 1$

Since $t_2 = t - t_1 - 1 < T - t_1 - 1$, therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1 - t_2 - 1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[\tau'/\alpha] \theta \iota] \text{ and we are done.}$$

26. T-iabs:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta, i : S; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \Lambda.e : (\forall i : S . \tau)} \text{ T-iabs}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma, \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\forall i . \tau) \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[(\forall i . \tau) \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v_f = (\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l$

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, (\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[(\forall i . \tau) \theta_l]$$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall I, T' < T. (p_l + p_m, T', e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[I/i] \theta_l]$$

This means given some $I, T' < T$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T', e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[I/i] \theta_l] \tag{F-IAB0}$$

From IH we know that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_{l'}]$$

where

$$l' = \rho_l \cup \{i \mapsto I\}$$

Therefore from Lemma 12 we get the desired

27. T-iapp:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (\forall i : S . \tau) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash I : S}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e [] : (\tau[I/i])} \text{ T-iapp}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, e [] \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[I/i] \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (e []) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[I/i] \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(e []) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[I/i] \theta_l] \tag{F-A0}$$

IH

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\forall i.\tau) \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . e \downarrow_{t_1} \Lambda.e \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, \Lambda.e) \in \mathcal{V}[(\forall i.\tau) \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(e \square) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-tapp we know that $\exists t_1 < t.e \downarrow_{t_1} \Lambda.e$, therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1, \Lambda.e) \in \mathcal{V}[(\forall i.\tau) \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall I, T_1 < T - t_1 . (p_l + p_m, T_1, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[I/i] \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-IAP1})$$

Instantiating (F-IAP1) with the given I and $T - t_1 - 1$ we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1 - 1, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[I/i] \theta_l]$$

From Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T - t_1 - 1 . e \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1 - t_2 - 1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[I/i] \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(e \square) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-iapp we know that $\exists t_2 . e \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$ where $t_2 = t - t_1 - 1$

Since $t_2 = t - t_1 - 1 < T - t_1 - 1$, therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1 - t_2 - 1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[I/i] \theta_l] \text{ and we are done.}$$

28. T-CI:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta, c; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \Lambda.e : (c \Rightarrow \tau)} \text{T-CI}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(0, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$ and $\models \Delta \iota$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \Lambda.e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(c \Rightarrow \tau) \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall v, t < T . \Lambda.e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[(c \Rightarrow \tau) \theta_l]$$

This means given some $v, t < T$ s.t $\Lambda.e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v$ and from (E-val) we know that $v = \Lambda.e \rho_m \rho_l$ and $t = 0$ therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, \Lambda.e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[(c \Rightarrow \tau) \theta_l]$$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$. \models c \iota \implies (p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

This means given that $. \models c \iota$ it suffices to prove that

$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!]$

IH $(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!]$

We get the desired directly from IH

29. T-CE:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (c \Rightarrow \tau) \quad \Theta; \Delta \models c}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e [] : \tau} \text{ T-CE}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\![\Gamma \theta_l]\!]$, $(0, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\![\Omega \theta_l]\!]$ and $\models \Delta \iota$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, e [] \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall v_f, t < T . (e []) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!]$$

This means given some $v_f, t < T$ s.t $(e []) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!] \quad (\text{F-Tap0})$$

IH

$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\![c \Rightarrow \tau \theta_l]\!]$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall v', t' < T . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{v'} \implies (p_l + p_m, v') \in \mathcal{V}[\![c \Rightarrow \tau \theta_l]\!]$$

Since we know that $(e []) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-CE we know that $\exists t' < t . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} \Lambda . e'$, an since $t' < t < T$ therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t', \Lambda . e') \in \mathcal{V}[\![c \Rightarrow \tau \theta_l]\!]$$

Therefore from Definition 8 we have

$$. \models c \iota \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t', e' \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!]$$

Since we are given $\Theta; \Delta \models c$ and $. \models \Delta \iota$ therefore we know that $. \models c \iota$. Hence we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t', e' \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall v'_f, t'' < T - t' . (e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t''} v'_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t' - t'', v'_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!] \quad (\text{F-CE1})$$

Since from E-CE we know that $e' \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore we know that $\exists t'' . e' \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t''} v_f$ s.t $t = t' + t'' + 1$

Therefore instantiating (F-CE1) with the given v_f and t'' we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t' - t'', v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\![\tau \theta_l]\!]$$

Since $t = t' + t'' + 1$ therefore from Lemma 11 we get the desired.

30. T-CAndI:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau \quad \Theta; \Delta \models c}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (c \& \tau)} \text{T-CAndI}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(0, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, e, \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[c \& \tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall v_f, t < T . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[c \& \tau \theta_l]$$

This means given some $v_f, t < T$ s.t $e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[c \& \tau \theta_l]$$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$. \models c_l \wedge (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

Since we are given that $. \models \Delta_l$ and $\Theta; \Delta \models c$ therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-CAI0})$$

$$\underline{\text{IH:}} (p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t' < T . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t', v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

Since we are given that $e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-CAI1})$$

We get the desired from (F-CAI1)

31. T-CAndE:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : (c \& \tau) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta, c; \Omega; \Gamma_2, x : \tau \vdash e' : \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{clet } x = e \text{ in } e' : \tau'} \text{T-CAndE}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Omega) \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{clet } x = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall v_f, t < T . (\text{clet } x = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

This means given soem $v_f, t < T$ s.t $(\text{clet } x = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-CAE0})$$

From Definition 9 and Definition 1 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t
 $(p_{l1}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1)\theta_l]$ and $(p_{l2}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2)\theta_l]$

IH1

$$(p_{l1} + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[c\&\tau \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_1 \implies (p_{l1} + p_m, T - t_1 v_1) \in \mathcal{E}[c\&\tau \theta_l]$$

Since we know that (clet $x = e$ in e') $\rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-CAndE we know that $\exists v_1, t_1 < t. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_1$. Therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_m, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[c\&\tau \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 8 we have

$$. \models c_l \wedge (p_{l1} + p_m, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-CAE1})$$

IH2

$$(p_{l2} + p_{l1} + p_m, T, e' \rho_m \rho'_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

where

$$\rho'_l = \rho_l \cup \{x \mapsto v_1\}$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T . e' \rho_m \rho'_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (p_{l2} + p_{l1} + p_m, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

Since we know that (clet $x = e$ in e') $\rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-CAndE we know that $\exists t_2 < t. e' \rho'_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$.

Therefore we have

$$(p_{l2} + p_{l1} + p_m, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

Since $p_l = p_{l1} + p_{l2}$ therefore we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

And finally from From Lemma 11 we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

And we are done.

32. T-fix:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega, x : \tau; \cdot \vdash e : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \cdot \vdash \text{fix}x.e : \tau} \text{T-fix}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\cdot]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{fix}x.e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$ (F-FX0)

From Definition 9 we know that $(0, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\cdot]$

Claim: $(p_m, T, (\text{fix}x.e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$

Proof

We induct on T

Base case, $T = 1$:

It suffices to prove that $(p_m, 1, (\text{fix}x.e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$

This means from Definition 8 it suffices to prove

$$\forall t < 1. (\text{fix}x.e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v \implies (p_m, 1 - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau]$$

This further means that given $t < 1$ s.t $(\text{fix}x.e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_m, 1 - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau]$$

Since from E-fix we know that minimum value of t can be 1 therefore $t < 1$ is not possible and the goal holds vacuously.

Inductive case:

IH: $(p_m, T - 1, (\text{fix}x.e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$

Therefore from Definition 9 we have

$$(p_m, T - 1, \rho'_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega, x : \tau \theta_l] \text{ where } \rho'_m = \rho_m \cup \{x \mapsto \text{fix}x.e \rho_m\}$$

Applying Definition 8 on (F-FX0) it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T. (\text{fix}x.e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T$ s.t $\text{fix}x.e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-FX0.0})$$

Since p_m can only 0 or ∞ . Therefore from IH of outer induction we have

$$(p_m, T - 1, e \rho'_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t' < T - 1. e \rho'_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} v_f \implies (p_m, T - 1 - t', v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $\text{fix } x.e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-fix we know that $\exists t' = t - 1$ s.t $e \rho'_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} v_f$

Since $t < T$ therefore $t' = t - 1 < T - 1$ hence we have

$$(p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

Therefore we are done.

33. T-ret:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau[0/a] \quad \delta_0 = (\{0\}, \{0 \mapsto 1\})}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{return } e : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \tau} \text{T-ret}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \text{return } e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\text{return } e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \tau \theta_l]$$

It means we are given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(\text{return } e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v_f = (\text{return } e) \rho_m \rho_l$.

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{return } e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \tau \theta_l]$$

From Definition 8 it further suffices to prove that

$$\forall \kappa', t' < T .$$

$$(\text{return } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa$$

This means given some $T' < T$ s.t $(\text{return } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^0 (V_d, M_d)$ it suffices to prove that

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies \\
& \quad (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]] \\
& b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa
\end{aligned} \tag{F-R0}$$

IH

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[0/a] \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T. (e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{t_1} v \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[0/a] \theta_l]$$

Since we know that (return e) $\rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^0 \nu$ therefore from (E-ret) we know that $\exists t_1. e \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{t_1} v$ s.t. $\nu = (\{v\}, \{v \mapsto 1\})$ and $T' = t_1 + 1$ (F-R1)

and therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[0/a] \theta_l] \tag{F-R11}$$

Let $\rho' = \{\{0, v\}, \{(0, v) \mapsto 1\}\}$

In order to prove (F-R0) we choose ρ as ρ'

$$\begin{aligned}
& (a) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\
& \quad \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j)): \\
& \quad \text{Trivial}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (b) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}. \\
& \quad a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T, V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]] \\
& \quad b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa:
\end{aligned}$$

We choose p_0 as $p_l + p_m$, it suffices to prove that

$$\bullet \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T, V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]]:$$

It suffices to prove that $(p_0, T - T', V_d(0)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(0)/a]]$

It further suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - T', v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(0)/a]]$$

We get this directly from (F-R11)

$$\bullet (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa:$$

It suffices to prove that

$$(\rho'(C_s(0), V_d(0)) \cdot p_0) + \kappa' \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa$$

It further suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m) + \kappa' \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa$$

Since we know that $\kappa = \kappa' = 0$ therefore we need to show that

$$(p_l + p_m) \leq p_l + p_m$$

We are done.

34. T-bind:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu_1)} \kappa_1 \tau_1 \\ \Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2, x : \tau_1 \vdash e_2 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(b \leftarrow \mu_2)} \kappa_2 \tau_2 \\ \kappa \geq \kappa_1 + \sum_{a \in \pi_1(\mu_1)} \pi_2(\mu_1) a \cdot \kappa_2 a \quad \mu \geq \mu_1 \otimes a \cdot \mu_2 \end{array}}{\Psi; \Theta, c; \Delta, c \in \pi_1(\mu) \vdash \tau_2[\pi_1(c)/a][\pi_2(c)/b] <: \tau \quad \{a, b\} \notin \mu, \kappa, \tau} \text{T-bind} \\ \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{bind } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(c \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2)\theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Omega) \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(c \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v. (\text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_t v \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(c \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v$ s.t $(\text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_t v$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v = (\text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2 \rho_m \rho_l)$

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2 \rho_m \rho_l)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(c \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$\forall \kappa', T' < T$.

$$(\text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2 \rho_m \rho_l) \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies \\ (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/c]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq (p_l + p_m) + \kappa$$

This means given some $\kappa', T' < T$ s.t $(\text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2 \rho_m \rho_l) \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d)$ and we need to prove that

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies \\ (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/c]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq (p_l + p_m) + \kappa \quad (\text{F-B0})$$

From Definition 9 and Definition 1 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t
 $(p_{l1}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1)\theta_l]$ and $(p_{l2}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2)\theta_l]$

IH1

$$(p_{l1} + p_m, T, e_1 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu_1)} \kappa_1 \tau_1 \theta_l]$$

From Definition 8 it means we have

$$\forall t_1 < T. (e_1) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{t_1} v_{m1} \implies (p_{l1} + p_m, T - t_1, v_{m1}) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu_1)} \kappa_1 \tau_1 \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\mathbf{bind} \ e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^{s'} v_f$ therefore from E-bind we know that $\exists t_1 < T', v_{m1}. (e_1) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{t_1} v_{m1}$.

Since $t_1 < T' < T$, therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_m, T - t_1, v_{m1}) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu_1)} \kappa_1 \tau_1 \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we are given that

$$\forall \kappa'_1, t'_1 < T - t_1.$$

$$v_{m1} \Downarrow_{t'_1}^{\kappa'_1} (V_{d1}, M_{d1}) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho_1 : (C_{s1} \times V_{d1}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i_1 < |C_{s1}|. \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho(C_{s1}(i_1), V_{d1}(j_1) = M_{s1}(C_{s1}(i_1)) \wedge \forall j_1 < |V_{d1}|. \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \rho(C_{s1}(i_1), V_{d1}(j_1)) = M_{d1}(V_{d1}(j_1))$$

$$2) \exists p_0^1, \dots, p_{|V_{d1}|-1}^1.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_{s1}|, j < |V_{d1}|. \rho_1(C_{s1}(i), V_{d1}(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j^1, T - t_1 - t'_1, V_{d1}(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1[C_{s1}(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1}(i), V_{d1}(j)) \cdot p_j^1) + \kappa'_1 \leq (p_{l1} + p_m) + \kappa_1$$

Since we know that $(\mathbf{bind} \ e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'} v_f$ therefore from E-bind we know that $\exists t'_1 < T - t_1. (v_{m1}) \Downarrow_{t'_1}^{\kappa'_1} (V_{d1}, M_{d1})$.

Therefore we have

$$\exists \rho_1 : (C_{s1} \times V_{d1}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i_1 < |C_{s1}|. \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho(C_{s1}(i_1), V_{d1}(j_1) = M_{s1}(C_{s1}(i_1)) \wedge \forall j_1 < |V_{d1}|. \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \rho(C_{s1}(i_1), V_{d1}(j_1)) = M_{d1}(V_{d1}(j_1))$$

$$2) \exists p_0^1, \dots, p_{|V_{d1}|-1}^1.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_{s1}|, j < |V_{d1}|. \rho_1(C_{s1}(i), V_{d1}(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j^1, T - t_1 - t'_1, V_{d1}(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1[C_{s1}(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1}(i), V_{d1}(j)) \cdot p_j^1) + \kappa'_1 \leq (p_{l1} + p_m) + \kappa_1$$

(F-B1)

IH2

$$\forall i_1 < |C_{s1}|. \forall j_1 < |V_{d1}|. (p_{l2} + p_{j_1}^1 + p_m, T - t_1 - t'_1, e_2 \rho_m \cup \rho'_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\mathbb{PC}_{(b \leftarrow \mu_2)} \kappa_2 \tau_2) \theta_l']$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \iota' &= \iota \cup \{a \mapsto C_{s1}(i_1)\} \\ \rho_l' &= \rho_l \cup \{x \mapsto V_{d1}(j_1)\} \end{aligned}$$

From Definition 8 it means we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\forall i_1 < |C_{s1}|. \forall j_1 < |V_{d1}|. \\ &\forall t_{2,j_1} < T - t_1 - t_1'. (e_2) \rho_m \rho_l' \Downarrow_{t_{2,j_1}} v_{m_{2,j_1}} \implies \\ &(p_{l2} + p_{j_1}^1 + p_m, T - t_1 - t_1' - t_{2,j_1}, v_{m_{2,j_1}}) \in \mathcal{V}[(\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(b \leftarrow \mu_2)} \kappa_2 \tau_2) \theta \iota'] \end{aligned}$$

Since we know that $(\text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'} \nu$ therefore from E-bind we know that $\forall i_1 < |C_{s1}|. \forall j_1 < |V_{d1}|. \exists t_{2,j_1} < T' - t_1 - t_1'. (e_2) \rho_m \rho_l' \Downarrow_{t_{2,j_1}} v_{m_{2,j_1}}$.

Therefore we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\forall i_1 < |C_{s1}|. \forall j_1 < |V_{d1}|. \\ &(p_{l2} + p_{j_1}^1 + p_m, T - t_1 - t_1' - t_{2,j_1}, v_{m_{2,j_1}}) \in \mathcal{V}[(\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(b \leftarrow \mu_2)} \kappa_2 \tau_2) \theta \iota'] \end{aligned}$$

Let $\mu_2 \iota' = (C_{s_{2,i_1}}, M_{s_{2,i_1}})$. From Definition 8 we are given that

$$\begin{aligned} &\forall i_1 < |C_{s1}|. \forall j_1 < |V_{d1}|. \\ &\forall \kappa_{2,j_1}', t_{2,j_1}' < T - t_1 - t_1' - t_{2,j_1}. \\ &v_{m_{2,j_1}} \Downarrow_{t_{2,j_1}'}^{\kappa_{2,j_1}'} (V_{d_{2,j_1}}, M_{d_{2,j_1}}) \implies \\ &\exists \rho_{2,i_1,j_1} : (C_{s_{2,i_1}} \times V_{d_{2,j_1}}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]. \\ &1) \forall i_2 < |C_{s_{2,i_1}}|. \sum_{j_2 < |V_{d_{2,j_1}}|} \rho(C_{s_{2,i_1}}(i_2), V_{d_{2,j_1}}(j_2)) = M_{s_{2,i_1}}(C_{s_{2,i_1}}(i_2)) \wedge \\ &\quad \forall j_2 < |V_{d_{2,j_1}}|. \sum_{i_2 < |C_{s_{2,i_1}}|} \rho(C_{s_{2,i_1}}(i_2), V_{d_{2,j_1}}(j_2)) = M_{d_{2,j_1}}(V_{d_{2,j_1}}(j_2)) \\ &2) \exists p_0^{2,j_1}, \dots, p_{|V_{d_{2,j_1}}|-1}^{2,j_1}. \\ &\quad a) \forall i < |C_{s_{2,i_1}}|. j < |V_{d_{2,j_1}}|. \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s_{2,i_1}}(i), V_{d_{2,j_1}}(j)) \neq 0 \implies \\ &\quad \quad (p_j^{2,j_1}, T - t_1 - t_1' - t_{2,j_1}, V_{d_{2,j_1}}(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_2[C_{s_{2,i_1}}(i)/b]) \theta \iota'] \\ &\quad b) \left(\sum_{i < |C_{s_{2,i_1}}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d_{2,j_1}}|} \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s_{2,i_1}}(i), V_{d_{2,j_1}}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa_{2,j_1}' \leq \\ &\quad \quad p_{l2} + p_{j_1}^1 + p_m + \kappa_2 \iota' \end{aligned}$$

Since we know that $(\text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'} \nu_f$ therefore from E-bind we know that $\forall i_1 < |C_{s1}|. \forall j_1 < |V_{d1}|.$

$$\begin{aligned} &\exists t_{2,j_1}' < (T' - t_1 - t_1' - t_{2,j_1}), \kappa_{2,j_1}' \text{ s.t.} \\ &v_{m_{2,j_1}} \Downarrow_{t_{2,j_1}'}^{\kappa_{2,j_1}'} (V_{d_{2,j_1}}, M_{d_{2,j_1}}). \end{aligned}$$

This means we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\forall i_1 < |C_{s1}|. \forall j_1 < |V_{d1}|. \\ &\exists \rho_{2,i_1,j_1} : (C_{s_{2,i_1}} \times V_{d_{2,j_1}}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1) \quad & \forall i_2 < |C_{s_2, i_1}| \cdot \sum_{j_2 < |V_{d_2, j_1}|} \rho \left(C_{s_2, i_1}(i_2), V_{d_2, j_1}(j_2) \right) = M_{s_2, i_1} \left(C_{s_2, i_1}(i_2) \right) \wedge \\
& \forall j_2 < |V_{d_2, j_1}| \cdot \sum_{i_2 < |C_{s_2, i_1}|} \rho \left(C_{s_2, i_1}(i_2), V_{d_2, j_1}(j_2) \right) = M_{d_2, j_1} \left(V_{d_2, j_1}(j_2) \right) \\
2) \quad & \exists p_0^{2, j_1}, \dots, p_{|V_{d_2, j_1}|-1}^{2, j_1} \\
& a) \quad \forall i < |C_{s_2, i_1}|, j < |V_{d_2, j_1}| \cdot \rho_{2, i_1, j_1} \left(C_{s_2, i_1}(i), V_{d_2, j_1}(j) \right) \neq 0 \implies \\
& \quad (p_j^{2, j_1}, T - t_1 - t'_1 - t'_{2, j_1}, V_{d_2, j_1}(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_2[C_{s_2, i_1}(i)/b]) \theta l'] \\
& b) \quad \left(\sum_{i < |C_{s_2, i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d_2, j_1}|} \rho_{2, i_1, j_1} \left(C_{s_2, i_1}(i), V_{d_2, j_1}(j) \right) \cdot p_j^{2, j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2, j_1} \leq \\
& \quad p_{l2} + p_{j_1}^1 + p_m + \kappa_2 l' \tag{F-B2}
\end{aligned}$$

We know that $(C_s, M_s) = (\mu_1 \otimes a.\mu_2)$, $(V_d, M_d) = \mathbb{M}_2(\nu_1 \otimes a.\nu_2)$

This means from Definition 3 we have

$$\begin{aligned}
C_s & \triangleq \{(c_1, c_2) \mid c_1 \in C_{s_1}, c_2 \in C_{s_2}[i/a]\} \\
M_s & \triangleq \{(c_1, c_2) \mapsto (M_{s_1} c_1 \cdot M_{s_2}[c_1/a] c_2) \mid c_1 \in C_{s_1}, c_2 \in C_{s_2}[c_1/a]\} \tag{F-B3}
\end{aligned}$$

Let $(V'_d, M'_d) = (\nu_1 \otimes a.\nu_2)$, from Definition 2 we know that

$$\begin{aligned}
V'_d & \triangleq \{(v_1, v_2) \mid v_1 \in V_{d_1}, v_2 \in V_{d_2}[v_1/a]\} \triangleq \sum V_{d_1} V_{d_2} \\
M'_d & \triangleq \{(v_1, v_2) \mapsto (M_{d_1} v_1 \cdot M_2[v_1/a] v_2) \mid v_1 \in V_{d_1}, v_2 \in V_{d_2}[v_1/a]\} \tag{F-B4.1}
\end{aligned}$$

This means from Definition 4 we have

$$\begin{aligned}
V_d & \triangleq \{v_2 \mid v_1 \in V_{d_1}, v_2 \in V_{d_2}[v_1/a]\} \\
M_d & \triangleq \{v_2 \mapsto \sum_{v_1 \in \{v' \mid v' \in V_{d_1}, v_2 \in V_{d_2}[v'/a]\}} (M_{d_1} v_1 \cdot M_{d_2}[v_1/a] v_2) \mid v_2 \in V_d\} \tag{F-B4}
\end{aligned}$$

In order to prove (F-B0) we need to find a $\rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]$.

We define

$$\rho' \triangleq \{((c_1, c_2), v_2) \mapsto \sum_{v_1 \in \{v' \mid v' \in V_{d_1}, v_2 \in V_{d_2}[v'/a]\}} (\rho_1 c_1 v_1) \cdot (\rho_{2, c_1, v_1} c_2 v_2) \mid (c_1, c_2) \in C_s, v_2 \in V_d\} \tag{F-B5}$$

We also define

$$\rho'' \triangleq \{((c_1, c_2), (v'_1, v'_2)) \mapsto (\rho_1 c_1 v'_1) \cdot (\rho_{2, c_1, v'_1} c_2 v'_2) \mid (c_1, c_2) \in C_s \wedge (v'_1, v'_2) \in V'_d\} \tag{F-B6}$$

We choose this ρ' as the required ρ

$$\begin{aligned}
1) \quad & \forall i < |C_s| \cdot \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\
& \forall j < |V_d| \cdot \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j)):
\end{aligned}$$

To prove: $\forall i < |C_s| \cdot \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i))$

This means given some $i < |C_s|$ it suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i))$$

Let $C_s(i) = (c_1, c_2)$, from (F-B3) it further suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'((c_1, c_2), V_d(j)) = M_{s1} c_1 \cdot M_{s2}[c_1/a] c_2$$

From (F-B5) it further suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{j < |V_d|} \sum_{k < |S_1|} (\rho_1 c_1 (V_{d1}(k))) \cdot (\rho_{2,i,k} c_2 V_d(j)) = M_{s1} c_1 \cdot M_{s2}[c_1/a] c_2$$

where

$$S_1 = \{v' \mid v' \in V_{d1}, v \in V_{d2}[v'/a]\}$$

Swapping the summations

$$\sum_{k < |V_{d1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2}[V_{d1}(k)/a]|} (\rho_1 c_1 (V_{d1}(k))) \cdot (\rho_{2,i,k} c_2 V_d(j)) = M_{s1} c_1 \cdot M_{s2}[c_1/a] c_2$$

Simplifying

$$\sum_{k < |V_{d1}|} (\rho_1 c_1 (V_{d1}(k))) \cdot \sum_{j < |V_{d2}[V_{d1}(k)/a]|} (\rho_{2,i,k} c_2 V_d(j)) = M_{s1} c_1 \cdot M_{s2}[c_1/a] c_2$$

We get the desired from (F-B1) and (F-B2)

To prove: $\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$

This means given some $j < |V_d|$ it suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

This means from (F-B5) we need to prove that

$$\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{k < |V_{d1}|} (\rho_1 c_1 V_{d1}(k)) \cdot (\rho_{2,c_1,V_{d1}(k)} c_2 V_d(j)) =$$

$$\sum_{k < |V_{d1}|} (M_{d1} V_{d1}(k)) \cdot (M_{d2,V_{d1}(k)} V_d(j))$$

where $C_s(i) = (c_1, c_2)$

It further suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{k < |V_{d1}|} \sum_{i < |C_s|} (\rho_1 c_1 V_{d1}(k)) \cdot (\rho_{2,c_1,V_{d1}(k)} c_2 V_d(j)) =$$

$$\sum_{k < |V_{d1}|} (M_{d1} V_{d1}(k)) \cdot (M_{d2,V_{d1}(k)} V_d(j))$$

where $C_s(i) = (c_1, c_2)$

We get the desired by taking the marginal over V_{d1} on both sides of the Claim proved below.

Claim:

$$\forall j < |V'_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} (\rho_1 c_1 v_1) \cdot (\rho_{2,c_1,v_1} c_2 v_2) = M'_d(V'_d(j))$$

where $C_s(i) = (c_1, c_2)$ and $V'_d(j) = (v_1, v_2)$

Proof

This means given some $j < |V'_d|$, it suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{i < |C_s|} \cdot (\rho_1 \ c_1 \ v_1) \cdot (\rho_{2,c_1,v_1} \ c_2 \ v_2) = M'_d(V'_d(j))$$

This means from (F-B4.1) it suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{i < |C_s|} \cdot (\rho_1 \ c_1 \ v_1) \cdot (\rho_{2,c_1,v_1} \ c_2 \ v_2) = (M_{d1} v_1) \cdot (M_{d2,v_1} v_2)$$

where $C_s(i) = (c_1, c_2)$ and $V'_d(j) = (v_1, v_2)$

From (F-B3), it further suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{i1 < |C_{s1}|} \cdot \sum_{i2 < |C_{s2,i1}|} \cdot (\rho_1 \ c_1 \ v_1) \cdot (\rho_{2,c_1,v_1} \ c_2 \ v_2) = (M_{d1} v_1) \cdot (M_{d2,v_1} v_2)$$

where $C_{s1}(i1) = c_1$, $C_{s2,i1}(i2) = c_2$ and $V'_d(j) = (v_1, v_2)$

This means we need to prove

$$\sum_{i1 < |C_{s1}|} \cdot (\rho_1 \ c_1 \ v_1) \cdot \sum_{i2 < |C_{s2,i1}|} \cdot (\rho_{2,c_1,v_1} \ c_2 \ v_2) = (M_{d1} v_1) \cdot (M_{d2,v_1} v_2)$$

where $C_{s1}(i1) = c_1$, $C_{s2,i1}(i2) = c_2$ and $V'_d(j) = (v_1, v_2)$

We get this directly from (F-B1) and (F-B2)

□

- 2) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$.
- a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d| \cdot \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/c]]$
- b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa$:

From (F-B2) we know that $\forall i_1 < |C_{s1}|$ and $\forall j_1 < |V_{d1}|$, $\exists p_0^{2,j_1}, \dots, p_{|V_{d2,j_1}|-1}^{2,j_1}$.

We choose these potentials as $p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$

To prove:

$$\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d| \cdot \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/c]]$$

This means given $i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|$ s.t. $\rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0$, we need to prove that

$$(p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/c]]$$

Let $C_s(i) = (c_1, c_2)$ and $V_d(j) = v_2$.

From Definition 8 and (F-B3) we know that

$$\exists i_{c1}, i_{c2} \text{ s.t. } C_{s1} \ i_{c1} = c_1 \text{ and } C_{s2}[c_1/a] \ i_{c2} = c_2$$

Similarly from Definition 8 and (F-B4) we know that

$$\exists j_{v1}, j_{v2}, v_1 \text{ s.t. } V_{d1} \ j_{v1} = v_1 \text{ and } V_{d2}[v_1/a] \ j_{v2} = v_2$$

We need to prove that

$$(p_{j_{v2}}^{2,j_{v1}}, T - T', v_2) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[(c_1, c_2)/c]]$$

Also since $\rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0$, therefore from (F-B5) we know that

$$\rho_{j_{v2}}^{2,j_{v1}}(c_2, v_2) \neq 0$$

Therefore from (F-B2) we know that
 $(p_{j_2}^{2,j_1}, T - t_1 - t'_1 - t'_{2,j_1}, v_2) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2[c_2/b] \ell']$

We get the desired using monotonicity (Lemma 11) and subtyping (Lemma 14)

To prove:

$$\left(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j \right) + \kappa' \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa$$

From (F-B2) we know that

$$\forall i_1 < |C_{s1}|. \forall j_1 < |V_{d1}|.$$

$$\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \cdot \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2,j_1} \leq p_{l2} + p_{j_1}^1 + p_m + \kappa_2 \ell'$$

Taking expectation over ρ_1

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \cdot \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2,j_1} \right) \\ & \leq \\ & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \left(p_{l2} + p_{j_1}^1 + p_m + \kappa_2 \ell' \right) \end{aligned}$$

Add κ'_1 to both sides

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \cdot \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_1 \\ & \leq \\ & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \left(p_{l2} + p_{j_1}^1 + p_m + \kappa_2 \ell' \right) + \kappa'_1 \end{aligned}$$

Expanding RHS

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \cdot \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_1 \\ & \leq \\ & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot p_{l2} + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \\ & p_{j_1}^1 + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot p_m + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \kappa_2 \ell' + \kappa'_1 \end{aligned}$$

Simplifying RHS

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \cdot \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_1 \\ & \leq \end{aligned}$$

$$p_{l2} + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot p_{j_1}^1 + p_m + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \kappa_2 \iota' + \kappa_1'$$

Since from (F-B1) we know that $(\sum_{i < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1}(i), V_{d1}(j)) \cdot p_{(i,j)}^1) + \kappa_1' \leq (p_{l1} + p_m) + \kappa_1$, therefore we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \cdot \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa_{2,j_1}' \right) + \kappa_1' \\ & \leq \\ & p_{l2} + p_m + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \kappa_2 \iota' + (p_{l1} + p_m) + \kappa_1 \end{aligned}$$

Since p_m can only be either 0 or ∞ , it further simplifies to

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa_{2,j_1}' \right) + \kappa_1' \\ & \leq \\ & p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_m + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \kappa_2 \iota' + \kappa_1 \end{aligned}$$

Rewriting

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa_{2,j_1}' \right) + \kappa_1' \\ & \leq \\ & p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_m + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \left(\sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \right) \cdot (\kappa_2 \iota') + \kappa_1 \end{aligned}$$

Simplifying using (1) of Definition 8

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \cdot \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa_{2,j_1}' \right) + \kappa_1' \\ & \leq \\ & p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_m + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} M_{s1}(C_{s1} i_1) \cdot \kappa_2 \iota' + \kappa_1 \end{aligned}$$

Using T-bind we can further simplify it to

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \cdot \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa_{2,j_1}' \right) + \kappa_1' \\ & \leq \\ & p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_m + \kappa \end{aligned}$$

Simplifying on the LHS

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} \ i_1)(V_{d_1} \ j_1) \cdot \sum_{i < |C_{s_2, i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d_2, j_1}|} \rho_{2, i_1, j_1}(C_{s_2, i_1}(i), V_{d_2, j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2, j_1} \right) \\
& + \left(\sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} \ i_1)(V_{d_1} \ j_1) \cdot \kappa'_{2, j_1} \right) \\
& + \kappa'_1 \\
& \leq \\
& p_{l_1} + p_{l_2} + p_m + \kappa
\end{aligned}$$

Rewriting on the LHS (swapping the summation in the second summand)

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} \ i_1)(V_{d_1} \ j_1) \cdot \sum_{i < |C_{s_2, i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d_2, j_1}|} \rho_{2, i_1, j_1}(C_{s_2, i_1}(i), V_{d_2, j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2, j_1} \right) \\
& + \left(\sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} \ i_1)(V_{d_1} \ j_1) \cdot \kappa'_{2, j_1} \right) \\
& + \kappa'_1 \\
& \leq \\
& p_{l_1} + p_{l_2} + p_m + \kappa
\end{aligned}$$

Using Definition 8 (on the second summand)

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} \ i_1)(V_{d_1} \ j_1) \cdot \sum_{i < |C_{s_2, i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d_2, j_1}|} \rho_{2, i_1, j_1}(C_{s_2, i_1}(i), V_{d_2, j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2, j_1} \right) \\
& + \left(\sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} M_{d_1}(V_{d_1} \ j_1) \cdot \kappa'_{2, j_1} \right) \\
& + \kappa'_1 \\
& \leq \\
& p_{l_1} + p_{l_2} + p_m + \kappa
\end{aligned}$$

Using the cost inequality from the T-bind typing rule

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} \ i_1)(V_{d_1} \ j_1) \cdot \sum_{i < |C_{s_2, i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d_2, j_1}|} \rho_{2, i_1, j_1}(C_{s_2, i_1}(i), V_{d_2, j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2, j_1} \right) \\
& + \kappa' \\
& \leq \\
& p_{l_1} + p_{l_2} + p_m + \kappa
\end{aligned}$$

Rewriting

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{i < |C_{s_2, i_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d_2, j_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} \ i_1)(V_{d_1} \ j_1) \cdot \rho_{2, i_1, j_1}(C_{s_2, i_1}(i), V_{d_2, j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2, j_1} \right) \\
& + \kappa' \\
& \leq \\
& p_{l_1} + p_{l_2} + p_m + \kappa
\end{aligned}$$

Rewriting

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{i_2 < |C_{s_2, i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \sum_{j_1 < |S_1|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} \ i_1)(V_{d_1} \ j_1) \cdot \rho_{2, i_1, j_1}(C_{s_2, i_1}(i_2), V_{d_2, j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2, j_1} \right) \\
& + \kappa'
\end{aligned}$$

$$\leq \\ p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_m + \kappa$$

where

$$S1 = \{v' \mid v' \in V_{d1}, v \in V_{d2}[v'/a]\}$$

Rewriting

$$\left(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'((c_1, c_2), v) \cdot p_j \right) + \kappa' \\ \leq \\ p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_m + \kappa$$

where

$$(c_1, c_2) = C_s \ i$$

$$v = V_d \ j$$

35. T-store:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau[0/a] \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa : \mathbb{R}^+ \quad \delta_0 = (\{0\}, \{0 \mapsto 1\})}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{store } e : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa ([\kappa] \tau)} \text{ T-store}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \text{store } e \ \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa ([\kappa] \tau) \ \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v. (\text{store } e) \ \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa ([\kappa] \tau) \ \theta_l]$$

This means we are given some $t < T, v$ s.t $(\text{store } e) \ \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v = (\text{store } e) \ \rho_m \rho_l$

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{store } e) \ \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa ([\kappa] \tau) \ \theta_l]$$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall \kappa', T' < T.$$

$$(\text{store } e) \ \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[[[\kappa] \tau][C_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa$$

This means given some $T' < T$ s.t. (store e) $\rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d)$. Also, from e-store we know that $\kappa' = 0$. It suffices to prove that

$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]$.

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

2) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$.

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[[([\kappa] \tau)[C_s(i)/a]]] \\ b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) \leq p + \kappa \quad (\text{F-S0})$$

IH

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[\tau[0/a] \theta_l]]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T. (e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{t_1} v \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau[0/a] \theta_l]]$$

Since we know that (store e) $\rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^0 \nu$ therefore from (E-ret) we know that $\exists t_1. e \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{t_1} v$ s.t. $\nu = (\{v\}, \{v \mapsto 1\})$ and $T' = t_1 + 1$ (F-S1)

and therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau[0/a] \theta_l]] \quad (\text{F-S11})$$

Let $\rho' = \{(0, v) \mapsto 1\}$

In order to prove (F-S0) we choose ρ as ρ'

$$(a) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j)):$$

Trivial

(b) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$.

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \\ \mathcal{V}[[([\kappa] \tau)[C_s(i)/a]]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa:$$

We choose p_0 as $p_l + p_m + \kappa$, it suffices to prove that

$$\bullet \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \\ \mathcal{V}[[([\kappa] \tau)[C_s(i)/a]]]:$$

It suffices to prove that $(p_l + p_m + \kappa, T - T', V_d(0)) \in \mathcal{V}[[([\kappa] \tau)[C_s(0)/a]]]$

From Definition 8 it further suffices to prove that

$$\exists p'. p' + \kappa \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa \wedge (p', T - T', v) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau[0/a]]]$$

We choose p' as $p_l + p_m$. It suffices to prove that

$$- p_l + p_m + \kappa \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa:$$

Trivial

$$- (p_l + p_m, T - T', v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[0/a]]$$

We get this directly from (F-S11) and Lemma 11

$$\bullet (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) \leq p + \kappa:$$

It suffices to prove that

$$(\rho'(C_s(0), V_d(0)) \cdot p_0) \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa$$

It further suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m) \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa$$

Trivial.

36. T-release:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : [\kappa] \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2, x : \tau \vdash e_2 : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} (\kappa + \kappa') \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa' \tau'} \text{T-release}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2)\theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Omega)\theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa' \tau' \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v. (\text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa' \tau' \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v$ s.t $(\text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v = (\text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \rho_m \rho_l)$

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa' \tau' \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$\forall \kappa'', T' < T$.

$$((\text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l) \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa''} (V_d, M_d) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$$

$$\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies$$

$$(p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau'[C_s(i)/c]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq (p_l + p_m) + \kappa'$$

This means given some $\kappa'', T' < T$ s.t $((\text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l) \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa''} (V_d, M_d)$ and we need to prove that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]. \\
& 1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\
& \quad \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j)) \\
& 2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}. \\
& \quad a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies \\
& \quad \quad (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau'[C_s(i)/c]] \\
& \quad b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq (p_l + p_m) + \kappa' \quad (\text{F-R0})
\end{aligned}$$

From Definition 9 and Definition 1 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t
 $(p_{l1}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1)\theta_l]$ and $(p_{l2}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2)\theta_l]$

IH1

$$(p_{l1} + p_m, T, e_1 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[\kappa] \tau \theta_l]$$

From Definition 8 it means we have

$$\forall t_1 < T. (e_1) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_1 \implies (p_{l1} + p_m, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[[\kappa] \tau \theta_l]$$

Since we know that (release $x = e_1$ in e_2) $\rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa''} v_f$ therefore from E-release we know that $\exists t_1 < T', v_1. (e_1) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_1$.

Since $t_1 < T' < T$, therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_m, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[[\kappa] \tau \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we are given that

$$\exists p'_1. p'_1 + \kappa \leq p_{l1} + p_m \wedge (p'_1, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1] \quad (\text{F-R1})$$

IH2

$$(p_{l2} + p'_1 + p_m, T - t_1, e_2 \rho_m \rho_l \cup \{x \mapsto v_1\}) \in \mathcal{E}[\text{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} (\kappa + \kappa') \tau' \theta_l]$$

From Definition 8 it means we have

$$\forall t_2 < T - t_1. (e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \cup \{x \mapsto v_1\} \downarrow_{t_2} v_{m2} \implies (p_{l2} + p_m + p'_1, T - t_1 - t_2, v_{m2}) \in \mathcal{V}[\text{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} (\kappa + \kappa') \tau' \theta_l]$$

Since we know that (release $x = e_1$ in e_2) $\rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa''} v_f$ therefore from E-release we know that $\exists t_2 < T' - t_1 < T - t_1. (e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \cup \{x \mapsto v_1\} \downarrow_{t_2} v_{m2}$. This means we have

$$(p_{l2} + p_m + p'_1, T - t_1 - t_2, v_{m2}) \in \mathcal{V}[\text{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} (\kappa + \kappa') \tau' \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we are given that

$$\forall \kappa_2, t'_2 < T - t_1 - t_2.$$

$$v_{m2} \downarrow_{t'_2}^{\kappa_2} (V_d, M_d) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho' : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$$

$$\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

2) $\exists p'_0, \dots, p'_{|V_d|-1}$.

a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p'_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau'[C_s(i)/a]]$

b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa_2 \leq (p_{l2} + p_m + p'_1) + (\kappa + \kappa')$

Since we know that (release $x = e_1$ in e_2) $\rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} \nu$ therefore from E-release we know that $\exists t'_2, \kappa_2, v_{m2} \Downarrow_{t'_2}^{\kappa_2} (V_d, M_d)$ s.t. $t'_2 = T' - t_1 - t_2 - 1$ and $\kappa_2 = \kappa''$

Since $t'_2 = T' - t_1 - t_2 < T - t_1 - t_2$, therefore we have

$$\exists \rho' : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

1) $\forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$
 $\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$

2) $\exists p'_0, \dots, p'_{|V_d|-1}$.

a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p'_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau'[C_s(i)/a]]$

b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa_2 \leq (p_{l2} + p_m + p'_1) + (\kappa + \kappa')$ (F-R2)

In order to prove (F-R0) we choose ρ as ρ' . It suffices to prove that

- $\forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$
 $\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j)):$
 Directly from (F-R2)
 - $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$.
- a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau'[C_s(i)/c]]$
- b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq (p_l + p_m) + \kappa':$

We choose $p'_0, \dots, p'_{|V_d|-1}$ as $p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$

– Proof of (a)

Given: $i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|$ s.t. $\rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0$

To prove: $(p'_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau'[C_s(i)/c]]$

Directly from (F-R2)

– Proof of (b)

From (F-R2) we are given that

$$(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa'' \leq (p_{l2} + p_m + p'_1) + (\kappa + \kappa')$$

Since from (F-R1) we know that $p'_1 + \kappa \leq p_{l1} + p_m$ therefore we have

$$(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa'' \leq p_{l2} + p_m + p_{l1} + p_m + \kappa'$$

Simplifying we get

$$(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa'' \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa'$$

We are done.

37. T-tick:

$$\frac{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa : \mathbb{R}^+ \quad \delta_0 = (\{0\}, \{0 \mapsto 1\})}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \uparrow^\kappa : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa \mathbf{1}} \text{ T-tick}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l, T, \uparrow^\kappa \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa \mathbf{1} \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v. (\uparrow^\kappa \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v \implies (p_l, T - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa \mathbf{1} \theta_l])$$

This means we are given some $t < T, v$ s.t. $(\uparrow^\kappa \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v = \uparrow^\kappa$

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l, T, (\uparrow^\kappa \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa \mathbf{1} \theta_l])$$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$\forall \kappa', t' < T$.

$$(\uparrow^\kappa \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{1}[C_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa$$

This means we are given some $T' < T$ s.t. $(\uparrow^\kappa \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d)$ it suffices to prove that

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{1}[C_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa \quad (\text{F-T0})$$

From E-tick we know that $\kappa' = \kappa$ and $(V_d, M_d) = (\{()\}, \{() \mapsto 1\})$

Let $\rho' = \{(0, ()) \mapsto 1\}$

In order to prove (F-T0) we choose ρ as ρ'

$$(a) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j)):$$

Trivial

(b) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$.
 a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d| \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{1}[C_s(i)/a]]$

b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa$:

We choose p_0 as $p_l + p_m$, it suffices to prove that

- $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d| \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{1}[C_s(i)/a]]$:

It suffices to prove that $(p_0, T - T', V_d(0)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{1}[C_s(0)/a]]$

It further suffices to prove that

$(p_l + p_m, T - T', ()) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{1}]$

We get this directly from Definition 8

- $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa$:

It suffices to prove that

$(\rho'(C_s(0), V_d(0)) \cdot p_0) + \kappa \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa$

It further suffices to prove that

$(p_l + p_m) + \kappa \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa$

Trivial.

38. T-split:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : [p] \mathbf{1} \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash p \geq p_1 + p_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{Split } e : ([p_1] \mathbf{1} \times [p_2] \mathbf{1})} \text{ T-split}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \text{Split } e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}([p_1] \mathbf{1} \times [p_2] \mathbf{1}) \theta_l$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$\forall T' < T, v'. \text{Split } e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{T'} v' \implies (p_l + p_m, T - T', v') \in \mathcal{V}([p_1] \mathbf{1} \times [p_2] \mathbf{1}) \theta_l$

This means given some $T' < T, v'$ s.t. $\text{Split } e \downarrow_{T'} v'$ it suffices to prove that

$(p_l + p_m, T - T', v') \in \mathcal{V}([p_1] \mathbf{1} \times [p_2] \mathbf{1}) \theta_l$

From (E-split) we know that $v' = \langle\langle (), () \rangle\rangle$, therefore it suffices to prove that

$(p_l + p_m, T - T', \langle\langle (), () \rangle\rangle) \in \mathcal{V}([p_1] \mathbf{1} \times [p_2] \mathbf{1}) \theta_l$

This means from Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$\exists p'_1, p'_2. p'_1 + p'_2 \leq p_l + p_m \wedge (p'_1, T, ()) \in \mathcal{V}([p_1] \mathbf{1}) \wedge (p'_2, T, ()) \in \mathcal{V}([p_2] \mathbf{1})$ (F-S0)

IH

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[[p] \mathbf{1}] \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall T'' < T, v'' . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{T''} v'' \implies (p_l + p_m, T - T'', v'') \in \mathcal{V}[[[p] \mathbf{1}] \theta_l]$$

Since we know that **Split** $e \downarrow_{T'} \langle (), () \rangle$, therefore from E-split we know that $\exists t' . e \downarrow_{t'} \langle (), () \rangle$ s.t. $T' = t' + 1$

$$\text{Therefore we have } (p_l + p_m, T - T'', v'') \in \mathcal{V}[[[p] \mathbf{1}] \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\exists p' . p' + p \leq p_l + p_m \wedge (p', T, ()) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{1}]$$

Since from T-split we know that $p \geq p_1 + p_2$ therefore we also know that

$$p_l + p_m \geq p_1 + p_2 \tag{F-S1}$$

In order to prove (F-S0) we choose p_1 for p'_1 and p_2 for p'_2 . It suffices to prove

- $p_1 + p_2 \leq p_l + p_m$:
From (F-S1)
- $(p_1, T, ()) \in \mathcal{V}[[[p_1] \mathbf{1}]$:
Directly from Definition 8
- $(p_2, T, ()) \in \mathcal{V}[[[p_2] \mathbf{1}]$:
Directly from Definition 8

39. T-toDist:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(p \ i) \\ \Theta; \Delta \models n > 0 \quad \mu = (\{0 \dots n - 1\}, \{i \mapsto p \ i \mid i < n\}) \\ 0 \leq \sum_{i < n} (p \ i) \leq 1 \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash p : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \end{array}}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{toDist } e : \mathbb{PC}_{(i \leftarrow \mu)} \ 0 \ \mathbf{N}(i)} \text{ T-toDist}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \text{toDist } e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \ 0 \ \mathbf{N}(i) \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f . (\text{toDist } e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \ 0 \ \mathbf{N}(i) \theta_l]$$

It means we are given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(\text{toDist } e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v_f = (\text{toDist } e) \rho_m \rho_l$.

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{toDist } e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\text{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \mathbf{N}(i) \theta_t]$$

From Definition 8 it further suffices to prove that

$$\forall \kappa', t' < T .$$

$$(\text{toDist } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p_l + p_m$$

This means given some $T' < T$ s.t. $(\text{toDist } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^0 (V_d, M_d)$ it suffices to prove that

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) \leq p_l + p_m \quad (\text{F-TD0})$$

IH

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbf{L}_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(p \ i) \theta_t]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . (e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{L}_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(p \ i) \theta_t]$$

Since we know that $(\text{toDist } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^0 (V_d, M_d)$ therefore from (E-toDist) we know that $\exists t_1. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} ls$ s.t. $V_d = (\{0 \dots |ls| - 1\}, M_d = \{i \mapsto ls!!i \mid i \in V_d\})$ and $T' = t_1 + 1$ (F-R1)

$$\text{and therefore we have } (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, ls) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{L}_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(p \ i) \theta_t] \quad (\text{F-R11})$$

Also since $n > 0$ therefore from Definition 8 we know that

$$\exists p'_0 \dots p'_{n-1} \text{ s.t.}$$

$$p'_0 + \dots + p'_{n-1} \leq p_l + p_m \text{ and}$$

$$(p'_0, T - t_1, v_0) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{R}(p \ 0) \theta_t]$$

...

$$(p'_{n-1}, T - t_1, v_{n-1}) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{R}(p \ (n - 1)) \theta_t] \quad (\text{F-TD1})$$

where

$$ls = v_0 :: \dots :: v_{n-1}$$

We know that

$$C_s = V_d = \{0 \dots n - 1\} \text{ and } M_s = M_d = \{i \mapsto p \ i \mid i < n\}$$

Let ρ' be the diagonal coupling s.t. $\forall i, j \in C_s$

$$\begin{aligned} \rho'(i, j) &= M_s(C_s(i)) && \text{when } i = j \\ \rho'(i, j) &= 0 && \text{otherwise} \end{aligned}$$

In order to prove (F-R0) we choose ρ as ρ'

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(a)} \quad &\forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ &\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j)): \\ &\text{Trivial} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(b)} \quad &\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}. \\ &a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T, V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/a]] \\ &b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa: \end{aligned}$$

We choose $p'_0 \dots p'_{n-1}$ as the required potentials, it suffices to prove that

$$\bullet \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p'_j, T, V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/i]]:$$

Given some $i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|$ s.t. $\rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0$

It suffices to prove that $(p'_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/i]]$

Directly from Definition 8 (nat case)

$$\bullet (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) \leq p_l + p_m:$$

We get the desired from (F-TD1) and the chosen coupling.

40. T-toDist!:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : !L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(p \ i) \quad \Theta; \Delta \models n > 0 \quad \mu = (\{0 \dots n - 1\}, \{i \mapsto p \ i \mid i < n\}) \quad \sum_{i < n} p \ i = 1 \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash p : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{toDist } e : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(i \leftarrow \mu)} \ 0 \ !\mathbf{N}(i)} \text{ T-toDist!}$$

Similar reasoning as in the T-toDist and T-ExpI cases.

41. T-unif:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \mathbf{N}(n) \quad \mu = (\{0, \dots, n\}, \{i \mapsto \frac{1}{n+1} \mid i < n+1\})}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{Unif } e : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(i \leftarrow \mu)} \ 0 \ \mathbf{N}(i)} \text{ T-Unif}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta \iota]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta \iota]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \text{Unif } e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{PC}_{(i \leftarrow \mu)} \ 0 \ \mathbf{N}(i) \ \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\text{Unif } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(i \leftarrow \mu)} \ 0 \ \mathbf{N}(i) \ \theta_l]$$

It means we are given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(\text{Unif } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_t v_f$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v_f = (\text{Unif } e) \rho_m \rho_l$.

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{Unif } e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(i \leftarrow \mu)} \ 0 \ \mathbf{N}(i) \ \theta_l]$$

From Definition 8 it further suffices to prove that

$$\forall \kappa', t' < T .$$

$$(\text{Unif } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p_l + p_m$$

This means given some $T' < T$ s.t $(\text{Unif } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^0 (V_d, M_d)$ it suffices to prove that

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) \leq p_l + p_m \quad (\text{F-TD0})$$

IH

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbf{N}(n) \ \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . (e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{t_1} v \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(n) \ \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{Unif } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^0 (V_d, M_d)$ therefore from (E-unif) we know that $\exists t_1. e \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{t_1} v$ s.t. $T' = t_1 + 1$ (F-R1)

$$\text{and therefore we have } (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(n) \ \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-R11})$$

Also, from Definition 8, we know that $v = n$

Therefore, we have

$$C_s = V_d = \{0 \dots n\} \text{ and } M_s = M_d = \{i \mapsto \frac{1}{n+1} \mid i < n + 1\}$$

Let ρ' be the diagonal coupling s.t. $\forall i, j \in C_s$

$$\begin{aligned}\rho'(i, j) &= M_s(C_s(i)) && \text{when } i = j \\ \rho'(i, j) &= 0 && \text{otherwise}\end{aligned}$$

In order to prove (F-R0) we choose ρ as ρ'

$$\begin{aligned}\text{(a)} \quad \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) &= M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) &= M_d(V_d(j)): \\ \text{Trivial}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{(b)} \quad \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}. \\ \text{a)} \quad \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 &\implies (p_j, T, V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/a]] \\ \text{b)} \quad (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' &\leq p_l + p_m + \kappa:\end{aligned}$$

We choose $p_l + p_m$ as the required potentials, it suffices to prove that

$$\bullet \quad \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_l + p_m, T, V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/i]]:$$

Given some $i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|$ s.t. $\rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0$

It suffices to prove that $(p_l + p_m, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/i]]$

Directly from Definition 8 (nat case)

$$\bullet \quad (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot (p_l + p_m)) \leq p_l + p_m:$$

Trivial.

42. T-swap:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : [p] \tau_1 \times \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{Swap } e : \tau_1 \times [p] \tau_2} \text{T-swap}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{Swap } e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 \times [p] \tau_2) \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_1, v_2. (\text{Swap } e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \times [p] \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_1, v_2$ s.t. $(\text{Swap } e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \times [p] \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists p_1, p_2. p_1 + p_2 \leq p_l + p_m \wedge (p_1, T - t, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l] \wedge (p_2, T - t, v_2) \in \mathcal{V}[p \tau_2 \theta_l] \\ \text{(F-TSW0)}$$

IH

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[[p] \tau_1 \times \tau_2] \theta \iota]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v \implies (p_{l1} + p_m, T - t_1, v) \in \mathcal{V}[[[p] \tau_1 \times \tau_2] \theta \iota]$$

Since we know that $(\text{Swap } e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle$ therefore from E-swap we know that $\exists t_1 < t, v_1, v_2 . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle$. Therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1, \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[[[p] \tau_1 \times \tau_2] \theta \iota]$$

From Definition 8 we know that

$$\exists p'_1, p'_2 . p'_1 + p'_2 \leq p_l + p_m \wedge (p'_1, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[[[p] \tau_1] \theta \iota] \wedge (p'_2, T - t_1, v_2) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau_2] \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-TSW1})$$

Since $(p'_1, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[[[p] \tau_1] \theta \iota]$ therefore from Definition 8 we know that

$$\exists p' . p' + p \leq p'_1 \wedge (p', T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau_1] \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-TSW2})$$

In order to prove (F-TSW0) we choose p_1 as p' and p_2 as $p'_2 + p$ it suffices to prove that

- $p' + p'_2 + p \leq p_l + p_m$:
We get this directly from (F-TSW1) and (F-TSW2)
- $(p', T - t, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau_1] \theta \iota]$:
Directly from (T-SW1) and Lemma 11
- $(p'_2 + p, T - t, v_2) \in \mathcal{V}[[[p] \tau_2] \theta \iota]$:

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists p'' . p'' + p \leq p'_2 + p \wedge (p'', T - t, v_2) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau_2] \theta \iota]$$

We choose p'' as p'_2 , we get the desired from (F-TSW2) and Lemma 11

□

Lemma 14 (Value subtyping lemma). $\forall \Psi, \Theta, \Delta, \tau, \tau', \theta, \iota.$

$$\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau <: \tau' \wedge . \models \Delta \iota \implies \mathcal{V}[[\tau] \theta \iota] \subseteq \mathcal{V}[[\tau'] \theta \iota]$$

Proof. Proof by induction on the subtyping relation

- Case sub-refl:
Trivial.
- Case sub-arrow:
Direct proof using Definition 8, IHs and 15

- Case sub-tensor:
Direct proof using Definition 8, IHs.
- Case sub-with:
Direct proof using Definition 8, IHs.
- Case sub-sum:
Direct proof using Definition 8, IHs.
- Case sub-Exp:
Direct proof using Definition 8, 15 and IH.
- Case sub-list:
Direct proof using Definition 8, IH.
- Case sub-exist:
Direct proof using Definition 8, IH.
- Case sub-typePoly:
Direct proof using Definition 8, IH.
- Case sub-indexPoly:
Direct proof using Definition 8, IH.
- Case sub-constraint:
Direct proof using Definition 8, IH.
- Case sub-CAnd:
Direct proof using Definition 8, IH.
- Case sub-potArrow:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash k'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash [k](\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) <: ([k'] \tau_1 \multimap [k' + k] \tau_2)} \text{ sub-potArrow}$$

To prove: $\forall (p, T, \lambda x.e) \in \mathcal{V}[[[k](\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2)] \theta \iota]. (p, T, \lambda x.e) \in \mathcal{V}[[[k'] \tau_1 \multimap [k' + k] \tau_2] \theta \iota]$

This means given some $(p, T, \lambda x.e) \in \mathcal{V}[[[k](\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2)] \theta \iota]$ we need to prove $(p, T, \lambda x.e) \in \mathcal{V}[[[k'] \tau_1 \multimap [k' + k] \tau_2] \theta \iota]$

From Definition 30 we are given that

$$\exists p'. p' + k \leq p \wedge (p', T, \lambda x.e) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-SPA0})$$

Again from Definition 30 we know that

$$\forall p''', e', T' < T . (p''', T', e') \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \theta \iota] \implies (p' + p''', T', e[e'/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \theta \iota]$$

(F-SPA1)

Also from Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall p'', e'', T'' < T . (p'', T'', e'') \in \mathcal{E}[[k'] \tau_1 \theta \iota] \implies (p + p'', T'', e[e''/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[[k + k'] \tau_2 \theta \iota]$$

This means given some $p'', e'', T'' < T$ s.t. $(p'', T'', e'') \in \mathcal{E}[[k'] \tau_1 \theta \iota]$ we need to prove $(p + p'', T'', e[e''/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[[k + k'] \tau_2 \theta \iota]$ (F-SPA2)

Applying Definition 30 on (F-SPA2) we get

$$\forall v_f, t' < T'' . e[e''/x] \Downarrow_{t'} v_f \implies (p + p'', T'' - t', v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[k + k'] \tau_2 \theta \iota]$$

This means that given some $v_f, t' < T''$ s.t. $e[e''/x] \Downarrow_{t'} v_f$ and we need to prove that

$$(p + p'', T'' - t', v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[k + k'] \tau_2 \theta \iota]$$

This means From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists p_2'', p_2'' + (k + k') \leq (p + p'') \wedge (p_2'', T'' - t', v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta \iota] \} \quad (\text{F-SPA4})$$

Also since we are given that $(p'', T'', e'') \in \mathcal{E}[[k'] \tau_1 \theta \iota]$ we apply Definition 30 on it to obtain

$$\forall t < T'' . e'' \Downarrow_t v' \implies (p'', T'' - t, v') \in \mathcal{V}[[k'] \tau_1 \theta \iota]$$

Also since we are given that $e[e''/x] \Downarrow_{t'} v_f$ therefore we also know that

$$\exists t'' < t' < T'' . e'' \Downarrow_{t''} v''$$

Instantiating with t'', v'' we get $(p'', T'' - t'', v'') \in \mathcal{V}[[k'] \tau_1 \theta \iota]$

Again using Definition 30 we know that we are given

$$\exists p_1'', p_1'' + k' \leq p'' \wedge (p_1'', T'' - t'', v'') \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-SPA3})$$

Since $(p_1'', T'' - t'', v'') \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta \iota]$ therefore from Definition 30 we also have

$$(p_1'', T'' - t'', v'') \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \theta \iota]$$

Instantiating (F-SPA1) with $p_1'', v'', T'' - t''$ we get

$$(p' + p_1'', T'' - t'', e[v''/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \theta \iota]$$

From Definition 30 this means that

$$\forall t''' < T'' - t'', v_f . e[v''/x] \Downarrow v_f \implies (p' + p_1'', T'' - t'' - t''', v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta \iota]$$

(F-SPA4.1)

Since we know that $e[e''/x] \Downarrow_{t'} v_f$ therefore we also know that $\exists t''' . e[v''/x] \Downarrow_{t'''} v_f$
s.t. $t''' + t'' \leq t'$

Since we already know that $\exists t'' < t' < T'' . e'' \Downarrow_{t''} v''$ therefore we have $t'' + t''' \leq t' < T''$.

Instantiating (F-SPA4.1) with t''' we get

$$(p' + p_1'', T'' - t'' - t''', v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-SPA5})$$

Since from (F-SPA0) we know that

$$p' + k \leq p$$

And from (F-SPA3) we know that

$$p_1'' + k' \leq p''$$

We add the two to get

$$p' + p_1'' + k + k' \leq p + p'' \quad (\text{F-SPA6})$$

In order to prove (F-SPA4) we choose p_2'' as $p' + p_1''$

and we get the desired from (F-SPA6) and (F-SPA5) and Lemma 33

- Case sub-potZero:
Direct proof using Definition 30.
- Case sub-potential:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau <: \tau' \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash n' \leq n}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash [n] \tau <: [n'] \tau'} \text{ sub-potential}$$

Given: $(p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}([p] \tau) \theta \iota$

To prove: $(p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}([n'] \tau') \theta \iota$

This means from Definition 8 we are given that

$$\exists p_1 . p_1 + n\theta \iota \leq p \wedge (p_1, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau] \theta \iota \quad (\text{sub-P0})$$

Similarly from Definition 8 we are required to prove

$$\exists p_2 . p_2 + n'\theta \iota \leq p \wedge (p_2, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau'] \theta \iota \quad (\text{sub-P1})$$

Choosing p_1 from (sub-P0), we get the desired from (sub-P0) and the fact that $n'\theta \iota \leq n\theta \iota$

- Case sub-coupling:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \exists \alpha : \mu \leftrightarrow \mu' \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa \leq \kappa'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau < : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a' \leftarrow \mu')} \kappa' \tau'} \text{ sub-coupling}$$

Given: $(p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[(\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau) \theta \iota]$

To prove: $(p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[(\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a' \leftarrow \mu')} \kappa' \tau') \theta \iota]$

Let's $\mu = (C_s, M_s)$ and $\mu' = (C'_s, M'_s)$

This means from Definition 8 we are given that

$$\forall \kappa', V_d, M_d, T' < T .$$

$$v \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa \quad (\text{sub-C0})$$

Similarly from Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall \kappa'', V'_d, M'_d, T'' < T .$$

$$v \Downarrow_{T''}^{\kappa''} (V'_d, M'_d) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho' : (C'_s \times V'_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C'_s|. \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j) = M'_s(C'_s(i)) \wedge \forall j < |V'_d|. \sum_{i < |C'_s|} \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) = M'_d(V'_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p'_0, \dots, p'_{|V'_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C'_s|, j < |V'_d|. \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p'_j, T - T'', V'_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau'[C'_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C'_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa$$

This means given some $\kappa'', V'_d, M'_d, T'' < T$ s.t. $v \Downarrow_{T''}^{\kappa''} (V'_d, M'_d)$, it suffices to prove that

$$\exists \rho' : (C'_s \times V'_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C'_s|. \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) = M'_s(C'_s(i)) \wedge \forall j < |V'_d|. \sum_{i < |C'_s|} \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) = M'_d(V'_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p'_0, \dots, p'_{|V'_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C'_s|, j < |V'_d|. \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p'_j, T - T'', V'_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau'[C'_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C'_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa \quad (\text{sub-C1})$$

Instantiating (sub-C0) with the given $\kappa'', V'_d, M'_d, T''$ we get

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V'_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V'_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$$

$$\forall j < |V'_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V'_d(j)) = M'_d(V'_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V'_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V'_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V'_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T'', V'_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V'_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa \quad (\text{sub-C2})$$

Since we are given α a coupling b/w μ and μ' therefore from Definition 6 we know that $\exists \alpha' : \mu' \leftrightarrow \mu$

In order to prove (sub-C1) we need to find a coupling b/w (C'_s, M'_s) and (V'_d, M'_d)

Let us define

$$\beta : (C'_s \times V'_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]$$

$$\beta(c', v') \triangleq \sum_{c \in C_s} (\alpha'(c', c) \cdot \rho(c, v')) / M_s(c)$$

In order to prove (sub-C1) we choose ρ' as β

$$1. \forall i < |C'_s|. \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) = M'_s(C'_s(i))$$

$$\forall j < |V'_d|. \sum_{i < |C'_s|} \beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) = M'_d(V'_d(j)):$$

$$\text{To prove: } \forall i < |C'_s|. \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) = M'_s(C'_s(i))$$

This means for an arbitrary $i < |C'_s|$ it suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{j < |V'_d|} \beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) = M'_s(C'_s(i))$$

From the definition of β , it further suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{j < |V'_d|} \sum_{c \in C_s} \alpha'(C'_s(i), c) \cdot \rho(c, V'_d(j)) / M_s(c) = M'_s(C'_s(i))$$

Interchanging terms and summation on LHS, it suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{c \in C_s} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho(c, V'_d(j)) \cdot \alpha'(C'_s(i), c) / M_s(c) = M'_s(C'_s(i))$$

Simplifying LHS using (sub-C2), it suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{c \in C_s} M_s(c) \cdot \alpha'(C'_s(i), c) / M_s(c) = M'_s(C'_s(i))$$

Simplifying LHS, it suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{c \in C_s} \alpha'(C'_s(i), c) = M'_s(C'_s(i))$$

Since α' is a coupling so we are done.

$$\text{To prove: } \forall j < |V'_d|. \sum_{i < |C'_s|} \beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) = M'_d(V'_d(j))$$

Similar reasoning as above.

2. $\exists p'_0, \dots, p'_{|V'_d|-1}$.
- a) $\forall i < |C'_s|, j < |V'_d|. \beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p'_j, T - T'', V'_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C'_s(i)/a]]$
- b) $(\sum_{i < |C'_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa'' \leq p' + \kappa$

We choose the potentials $p_0, \dots, p_{|V'_d|-1}$ (from sub-C2) as the required potentials

We need prove:

- $\forall i < |C'_s|, j < |V'_d|. \beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T'', V'_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C'_s(i)/a]]$:

This means given some $i < |C'_s|, j < |V'_d|$ s.t. $\beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \neq 0$

It suffices to prove that

$$(p_j, T - T'', V'_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C'_s(i)/a]]$$

Since $\beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \neq 0$ therefore from the definition of β we know that $\exists i' < |C_s|$ s.t. $\rho(C_s(i'), V'_d(j)) \neq 0$

Therefore from (sub-C2) we get

$$(p_j, T - T'', V'_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i')/a]]$$

Since α is a coupling b/w (C_s, M_s) and (C'_s, M'_s) therefore from IH we get the desired.

- $(\sum_{i < |C'_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa$:

Using the definition of β , it suffices to prove that

$$(\sum_{i < |C'_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \sum_{k < |C_s|} (\alpha'(C'_s(i), C_s(k)) \cdot \rho(C_s(k), V'_d(j))) / M_s(C_s(k)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa$$

Rearranging summation on the LHS, it suffices to prove that

$$(\sum_{k < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \sum_{i < |C'_s|} (\alpha'(C'_s(i), C_s(k)) \cdot \rho(C_s(k), V'_d(j))) / M_s(C_s(k)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa$$

Since α' is a coupling, it suffices to prove that

$$(\sum_{k < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} M_s(C_s(k)) \cdot \rho(C_s(k), V'_d(j)) / M_s(C_s(k)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa$$

Simplifying on the LHS, it suffices to prove that

$$(\sum_{k < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho(C_s(k), V'_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa$$

We get this directly from (sub-C2).

□

Lemma 15 (Expression subtyping lemma). $\forall \Psi, \Theta, \tau, \tau'$.

$$\Psi; \Theta \vdash \tau <: \tau' \implies \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta \iota] \subseteq \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta \iota]$$

Proof. Directly from Definition 8 and Lemma 14

□

Lemma 16 (Γ Subtyping: domain containment). $\forall p, \rho_l, \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2.$

$$\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1 <: \Gamma_2 \implies \forall x : \tau \in \Gamma_2. x : \tau' \in \Gamma_1 \wedge \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' <: \tau$$

Proof. Proof by induction on $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1 <: \Gamma_2$

1. sub-lBase:

$$\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1 <: .} \text{sub-lBase}$$

To prove: $\forall x : \tau' \in (.). x : \tau \in \Gamma_1 \wedge \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' <: \tau$

Trivial

2. sub-lInd:

$$\frac{x : \tau' \in \Gamma_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' <: \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1/x <: \Gamma_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1 <: \Gamma_2, x : \tau} \text{sub-lBase}$$

To prove: $\forall y : \tau \in \Gamma_2. y : \tau \in \Gamma_1 \wedge \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' <: \tau$

This means given some $y : \tau \in (\Gamma_2, x : \tau)$ it suffices to prove that

$$y : \tau \in \Gamma_1 \wedge \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' <: \tau$$

The following cases arise:

- $y = x$:

In this case we are given that $x : \tau' \in \Gamma_1 \wedge \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' <: \tau$

Therefore we are done

- $y \neq x$:

Since we are given that $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1/x <: \Gamma_2$ therefore we get the desired from IH

□

Lemma 17 (Γ subtyping lemma). $\forall \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2, \theta, \iota.$

$$\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1 <: \Gamma_2 \implies \mathcal{G}[\Gamma_1 \theta \iota] \subseteq \mathcal{G}[\Gamma_2 \theta \iota]$$

Proof. Proof by induction on $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1 <: \Gamma_2$

1. sub-lBase:

$$\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma <: .} \text{sub-lBase}$$

To prove: $\forall (p, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma_1 \theta \iota]. (p, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma_2 \theta \iota]$

This means given some $(p, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\Gamma_1\theta_l]$ it suffices to prove that $(p, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\cdot]$

From Definition 9 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists f : \mathcal{V}ars \rightarrow \mathcal{P}. (\forall x \in \mathbf{dom}(\cdot). (f(x), T, \rho_l(x)) \in \mathcal{E}[\Gamma(x)]) \wedge (\sum_{x \in \mathbf{dom}(\cdot)} f(x) \leq p)$$

We choose f as a constant function $f' = 0$ and we get the desired

2. sub-Ind:

$$\frac{x : \tau' \in \Gamma_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' <: \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1/x <: \Gamma_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1 <: \Gamma_2, x : \tau} \text{sub-lBase}$$

To prove: $\forall (p, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma_1\theta_l]. (p, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma_2, x : \tau]$

This means given some $(p, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma_1\theta_l]$ it suffices to prove that $(p, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma_2, x : \tau]$

This means from Definition 9 we are given that

$$\exists f : \mathcal{V}ars \rightarrow \mathcal{P}.$$

$$(\forall x \in \mathbf{dom}(\Gamma_1). (f(x), T, \rho_l(x)) \in \mathcal{E}[\Gamma(x)]) \quad (\text{L0})$$

$$(\sum_{x \in \mathbf{dom}(\Gamma_1)} f(x) \leq p) \quad (\text{L1})$$

Similarly from Definition 9 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists f' : \mathcal{V}ars \rightarrow \mathcal{P}. (\forall y \in \mathbf{dom}(\Gamma_2, x : \tau). (f'(y), T, \rho_l(y)) \in \mathcal{E}[\Gamma(y)]) \wedge (\sum_{y \in \mathbf{dom}(\Gamma_2, x : \tau)} f'(y) \leq p)$$

We choose f' as f and it suffices to prove that

$$(a) \forall y \in \mathbf{dom}(\Gamma_2, x : \tau). (f(y), T, \rho_l(y)) \in \mathcal{E}[\Gamma(y)]:$$

This means given some $y \in \mathbf{dom}(\Gamma_2, x : \tau)$ it suffices to prove that

$$(f(y), T, \rho_l(y)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2] \text{ where say } \Gamma(y) = \tau_2$$

From Lemma 16 we know that

$$y : \tau_1 \in \Gamma_1 \wedge \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau_2$$

By instantiating (L0) with the given y

$$(f(y), T, \rho_l(y)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1]$$

Finally from Lemma 15 we also get $(f(y), T, \rho_l(y)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2]$

And we are done

$$(b) (\sum_{y \in \mathbf{dom}(\Gamma_2, x : \tau)} f(y) \leq p):$$

From (L1) we know that $(\sum_{x \in \mathbf{dom}(\Gamma_1)} f(x) \leq p)$ and since from Lemma 16 we know that $\mathbf{dom}(\Gamma_2, x : \tau) \subseteq \mathbf{dom}(\Gamma_1)$ therefore we also have

$$(\sum_{y \in \mathbf{dom}(\Gamma_2, x : \tau)} f(y) \leq p)$$

□

Lemma 18 (Ω subtyping lemma). $\forall \Omega_1, \Omega_2, \theta, \iota.$

$$\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Omega_1 <: \Omega_2 \implies \mathcal{G}[\Omega_1 \theta \iota] \subseteq \mathcal{G}[\Omega_2 \theta \iota]$$

Proof. Similar reasoning as in the Γ subtyping lemma (Lemma 17). □

Theorem 19 (Soundness). $\vdash e : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau \wedge e \Downarrow_t^{\kappa'} \nu \implies \kappa' \leq \kappa$

Proof. From Theorem 13 we know that $(0, t + 1, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau]$

From Definition 8 this means we have

$$\forall t' < t + 1, v. (e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{t'} v \implies (0, t + 1 - t', v) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau]$$

From the evaluation relation we know that $e \Downarrow_0$, therefore we have

$$(0, t + 1 - t', e) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall \kappa', V_d, M_d, T' < T.$$

$$v \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$$

$$\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa$$

Since we are given that $e \Downarrow_t^{\kappa'} \nu$ therefore we know that

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$$

$$\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa \tag{S0}$$

Since $p = 0$ and all $p_0 \dots p_{|V_d|-1}$ are positive real numbers. Therefore we get the desired from (S0,b) □

Theorem 20 (Soundness with potentials). $\vdash e : [\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau \wedge e () \Downarrow_{t_1} - \Downarrow_{t_2}^{\kappa'} \nu \implies \kappa' \leq \kappa$

Proof. From Theorem 13 we know that $(0, t_1 + t_2 + 2, e) \in \mathcal{E}[[\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau]$

From Definition 8 this means we have

$$\forall t' < t_1 + t_2 + 2, v. e \Downarrow_{t'} v \implies (0, t_1 + t_2 + 2 - t', v) \in \mathcal{V}[[\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau] \tag{S0}$$

Since we know that $e () \Downarrow_{t_1}$ - therefore from E-app we know that $\exists e'. e \Downarrow_{t_1} \lambda x. e'$

Instantiating (S0) with $t_1, \lambda x. e'$ we get $(0, t_2 + 2, \lambda x. e') \in \mathcal{V}[[\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau]$

$$\forall p', e'', t'' < t_2 + 2. (p', t'', e'') \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1] \implies (p', t'', e'[e''/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau] \quad (\text{S1})$$

Instantiating (S1) with $\kappa, (), t_2 + 1$ we get $(\kappa, t_2 + 1, e'[()/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau]$

This means again from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t' < t_2 + 1. e'[()/x] \Downarrow_{t'} v' \implies (\kappa, t_2 + 1 - t', v') \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau]$$

From E-val we know that $v' = e'[()/x]$ and $t' = 0$ therefore we have

$$(\kappa, t_2 + 1, e'[()/x]) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall \kappa', V_d, M_d, T' < T.$$

$$e'[()/x] \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$$

$$\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq \kappa + 0$$

Since we are given that $e () \downarrow_{t_1} - \Downarrow_{t_2}^{\kappa'} \nu$ therefore we know that

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$$

$$\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq \kappa + 0 \quad (\text{S2})$$

Since $p = 0$ and all $p_0 \dots p_{|V_d|-1}$ are positive real numbers. Therefore we get the desired from (S2,b)

□

2 Development with coeffects

2.1 Syntax

Expressions	$e ::= v \mid x \mid S e \mid e_1 e_2 \mid e :: e \mid \text{let } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \mid \text{if } e \ e_1 \ e_2$ $\langle\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle\rangle \mid \text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \mid$ $\langle e, e \rangle \mid \text{fst}(e) \mid \text{snd}(e) \mid$ $\text{inl}(e) \mid \text{inr}(e) \mid \text{case } e \text{ of } x.e; y.e \mid$ $\text{let}!x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \mid \text{Split } e \mid \text{Swap } e \mid \text{toDist } e \mid \text{Purify } e$
Values	$v ::= () \mid \text{tt} \mid \text{ff} \mid Z \mid r \mid$ $\lambda x.e \mid \langle\langle v_1, v_2 \rangle\rangle \mid \langle v, v \rangle \mid \text{inl}(e) \mid \text{inr}(e) \mid !e \mid \text{nil} \mid$ $\text{return } e \mid \text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2 \mid$ $\uparrow^I \mid \text{store } e \mid \text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2$
Static Distribution	$\mu ::= (C_s, M_s)$ <p>$C_s =$ Finite set of indices over natural numbers $M_s : C_s \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$</p>
Dynamic Distribution	$\nu ::= (V_d, M_d)$ <p>$V_d =$ Finite set of values $M_d : V_d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$</p>
Types	$\tau ::= \mathbf{1} \mid \mathbf{B}(I) \mid \mathbf{N}(I) \mid \mathbf{R}(I) \mid L_{i < I} \tau \mid$ $\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2 \mid \tau_1 \times \tau_2 \mid \tau_1 \& \tau_2 \mid \tau_1 + \tau_2 \mid !_{\Sigma_{a < I} R_a} \tau \mid$ $[I] \tau \mid \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)}^s I \tau$
Index	$I ::= i \mid B \mid N \mid R \mid I + I \mid \lambda_s i : S . I \mid I I \mid \text{if } I \ I \ I \mid I == I$ $\text{exp } I \mid \log I \mid \vec{I} \mid \ I_1 - I_2\ _n \mid \nabla I \mid \sum_{a < I} J \mid \max_{a \leq I} J \mid I/J$
Sort	$S ::= \mathbb{B} \mid \mathbb{N} \mid \mathbb{R} \mid (S, S) \mid S \rightarrow S \mid \mathbb{D}_S \mid \mathbb{S}_S$
Constraints	$c ::= I = I \mid I < I \mid c \Rightarrow c \mid c \wedge c \mid (1 - I) \leq \text{exp } (-I)$
Lin. context for term variables	$\Gamma ::= . \mid \Gamma, x : \tau$
Unres. context for term variables	$\Omega ::= . \mid \Omega, x : \tau$
Unres. context for index variables	$\Theta ::= . \mid \Theta, i : S$
Unres. context for type variables	$\Psi ::= . \mid \Psi, \alpha : K$

Definition 21 (Sum of linear context).

$$\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \triangleq \begin{cases} \Gamma_2 & \Gamma_1 = . \\ (\Gamma'_1 \oplus \Gamma_2), x : \tau & \Gamma_1 = \Gamma'_1, x : \tau \wedge (x : -) \notin \Gamma_2 \\ \text{undefined} & \Gamma_1 = \Gamma'_1, x : \tau \wedge (x : -) \in \Gamma_2 \end{cases}$$

Definition 22 (Binary sum of multiplicity context).

$$\Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2 \triangleq \begin{cases} \Omega_2 & \Omega_1 = . \\ (\Omega'_1 \oplus \Omega_2/x), x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a + R'_a \tau & \Omega_1 = \Omega'_1, x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau \wedge (x : \sum_{a \in I} R'_a \tau) \in \Omega_2 \\ (\Omega'_1 \oplus \Omega_2), x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau & \Omega_1 = \Omega'_1, x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau \wedge (x : -) \notin \Omega_2 \end{cases}$$

Definition 23 (Bounded sum of multiplicity context). $\sum_{a \in I} R \cdot \triangleq .$

$$\sum_{a \in I} R \cdot (\Omega, x : \sum_{b \in J} Q \tau) \triangleq (\sum_{a \in I} R \cdot \Omega), x : \sum_{c \in (I \odot a \cdot J)} R[\pi_1 c/a] \cdot Q[\pi_1 c/a][\pi_2 c/b] \tau[\pi_1 c/a][\pi_2 c/b]$$

where

$$I \odot a \cdot J \triangleq \{(i, j) \mid i \in I, j \in J[i/a]\}$$

Definition 24.

$$(V_1, M_1) \otimes a \cdot (V_2, M_2) \triangleq (V, M)$$

where

$$V \triangleq \{(v_1, v_2) \mid v_1 \in V_1, v_2 \in V_2[v_1/a]\} \triangleq \sum a \in V_1, V_2$$

$$M \triangleq \{(v_1, v_2) \mapsto (M_1 v_1 \cdot M_2[v_1/a] v_2) \mid v_1 \in V_1, v_2 \in V_2[v_1/a]\}$$

Definition 25.

$$(C_1, M_1) \otimes a \cdot (C_2, M_2) \triangleq (C, M)$$

where

$$C \triangleq \{(i, j) \mid i \in C_1, j \in C_2[i/a]\} \triangleq \sum i \in C_1, C_2$$

$$M \triangleq \{(i, j) \mapsto (M_1 i \cdot M_2[i/a] j) \mid i \in C_1, j \in C_2[i/a]\}$$

Definition 26 (Marginals of a dynamic distribution). Marginals are defined as follows:

1. $\mathbb{M}_1((\sum a \in V_1, V_2), M) \triangleq (V_m, M_m)$

where

$$V_m \triangleq V_1$$

$$M_m \triangleq \{v_1 \mapsto \sum_{v_2 \in V_2} (M(v_1, v_2)) \mid v_1 \in V_1\}$$

2. $\mathbb{M}_2((\sum a \in V_1, V_2), M) \triangleq (V_m, M_m)$

where

$$V_m \triangleq \bigcup_{v_1 \in V_1} V_2[v_1/a]$$

$$M_m \triangleq \{v_2 \mapsto \sum_{v_1 \in V_1} (M(v_1, v_2)) \mid v_1 \in V_1, v_2 \in V_2[v_1/a]\}$$

Definition 27. $\mu_1 \geq \mu_2 \triangleq \pi_1(\mu_1) = \pi_1(\mu_2)$ and $\forall i \in \pi_1(\mu_1). \pi_2(\mu_1) i \geq \pi_2(\mu_2) i$

Definition 28 (Coupling).

$$\mu_1 \leftrightarrow \mu_2 \triangleq \nu \text{ s.t.}$$

$$\forall i \in \mu_1. \sum_{j \in \mu_2} \nu_{(i,j)} i = \mu_1 i \text{ and } \forall j \in \mu_2. \sum_{i \in \mu_1} \nu_{(i,j)} j = \mu_2 j$$

Definition 29 (Euclidian norm).

$$\|V_1 - V_2\|_n \triangleq \sqrt{\sum_{0 \leq i < n} (V_{1i} - V_{2i})^2}$$

2.2 Type system

Typing judgment: $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; x : \tau \vdash x : \tau} \text{T-var1} \qquad \frac{\Theta, \Delta \models R_a[J/a] \geq 1 \quad \Theta, \Delta \models J \in I}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega, x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau; \cdot \vdash x : \tau[J/a]} \text{T-var2} \\
\\
\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau; \cdot \vdash !x : !\sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau} \text{T-var3} \qquad \frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \cdot \vdash () : \mathbf{1}} \text{T-unit} \\
\\
\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \cdot \vdash tt : \mathbf{B}(tt)} \text{T-tt} \qquad \frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \cdot \vdash ff : \mathbf{B}(ff)} \text{T-ff} \\
\\
\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \cdot \vdash Z : \mathbf{N}(0)} \text{T-zero} \qquad \frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash n : \mathbf{N}(n)}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash S n : \mathbf{N}(n+1)} \text{T-succ} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : \mathbf{N}(n) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta, n = 0; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_0 : \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta, i; \Delta, i+1 = n; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2, x : \mathbf{N}(i) \vdash e_1 : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_1 : \tau} \text{T-matchN} \\
\\
\frac{\Theta \vdash r : \mathbb{R}}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \cdot \vdash r : \mathbf{R}(r)} \text{T-real} \qquad \frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \cdot \vdash nil : L_{i < 0} \tau} \text{T-nil} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \tau[0/i] \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : L_{i < n+1} \tau[(i+1)/i]}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 :: e_2 : L_{i < n+1} \tau} \text{T-cons} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : L_{i < n} \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta, n = 0; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 : \tau' \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2, h : \tau[0/i], t : L_{i < n-1} \tau[(i+1)/i] \vdash e_2 : \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta, p : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{match } e \text{ with } |nil \mapsto e_1 |h :: t \mapsto e_2 : \tau'} \text{T-match} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma, x : \tau_1 \vdash e : \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \lambda x. e : \tau_1 \multimap \tau_2} \text{T-lam} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : \tau_1}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 e_2 : \tau_2} \text{T-app}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau[n/s] \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash n : S}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{Ex } e : \exists s : S . \tau} \text{T-existI} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : \exists s : S . \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta, s : S; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2, x : \tau \vdash e' : \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{letEx } x = e \text{ in } e' : \tau'} \text{T-existE} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau \quad \Psi, \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau <: \tau' \quad \Psi; \Theta \models \Gamma' <: \Gamma \quad \Psi; \Theta \models \Omega' <: \Omega}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega'; \Gamma' \vdash e : \tau'} \text{T-sub} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \tau_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle : \tau_1 \times \tau_2} \text{T-tensorI} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : (\tau_1 \times \tau_2) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2, x : \tau_1, y : \tau_2 \vdash e' : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = e \text{ in } e' : \tau} \text{T-tensorE} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e_1 : \tau_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e_2 : \tau_1}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle : \tau_1 \& \tau_2} \text{T-withI} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (\tau_1 \& \tau_2)}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{fst}(e) : \tau_1} \text{T-fst} \quad \frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (\tau_1 \& \tau_2)}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{snd}(e) : \tau_2} \text{T-snd} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau_1}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{inl}(e) : \tau_1 + \tau_2} \text{T-inl} \quad \frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{inr}(e) : \tau_1 + \tau_2} \text{T-inr} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : (\tau_1 + \tau_2) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2, x : \tau_1 \vdash e_1 : \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2, y : \tau_2 \vdash e_2 : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{case } e \text{ of } x.e_1; y.e_2 : \tau} \text{T-case} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in S; \Omega; . \vdash e : \tau \quad \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in S \vdash R_a : \mathbf{R}^+}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \sum_{a \in S} R_a \cdot \Omega; . \vdash !e : !\sum_{a \in S} R_a \tau} \text{T-subExpI} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : !\sum_{a \in S} R_a \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2, x : \sum_{a \in S} R_a \tau; \Gamma_2 \vdash e' : \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{let } !x = e \text{ in } e' : \tau'} \text{T-subExpE}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\Psi, \alpha : K; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \Lambda.e : \forall \alpha : K . \tau} \text{T-tabs} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (\forall \alpha : K . \tau) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' : K}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e \bullet : \tau[\tau'/\alpha]} \text{T-tapp} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta, i : S; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \Lambda.e : \forall i : S . \tau} \text{T-iabs} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (\forall i : S . \tau) \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash I : S}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e \bullet : \tau[I/i]} \text{T-iapp} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta, c; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \Lambda.e : (c \Rightarrow \tau)} \text{T-CI} \quad \frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (c \Rightarrow \tau) \quad \Theta; \Delta \models c}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e \bullet : \tau} \text{T-CE} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta, b; \Delta; x : \sum_{a \in S} R_a \tau[M_a/b]; \cdot \vdash e : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{fix } x.e : \tau[J/b]} \text{T-fix} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau \quad \Theta; \Delta \models c}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \Lambda.e : (c \& \tau)} \text{T-CAndI} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma \vdash e : (c \& \tau) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta, c; \Omega_2; \Gamma, x : \tau \vdash e' : \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma \vdash \text{let } x = e \text{ in } e' : \tau'} \text{T-CAndE} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : [p] \mathbf{1} \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash p \geq p_1 + p_2 \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash p_1 : \mathbb{R}^+ \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash p_2 : \mathbb{R}^+}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{Split } e : ([p_1] \mathbf{1} \times [p_2] \mathbf{1})} \text{T-split}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau[0/a] \quad \delta_0 = (\{0\}, \{0 \mapsto 1\})}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{return } e : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \tau} \text{T-ret} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu_1)} \kappa_1 \tau_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta; \Omega'; \Gamma_2, x : \tau_1 \vdash e_2 : \mathbb{PC}_{(b \leftarrow \mu_2)} \kappa_2 \tau_2 \quad \kappa \geq \kappa_1 + \sum_{a \in (\pi_1 \mu_1)} ((\pi_2 \mu_1) a) \cdot \kappa_2 a}{\mu \geq \mu_1 \otimes a. \mu_2 \quad \Psi; \Theta, c; \Delta, c \in \pi_1(\mu) \vdash \tau_2[\pi_1 c/a][\pi_2 c/b] <: \tau \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa_1 : \mathbb{R}^+ \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa_2 : \mathbb{R}^+} \text{T-bind} \\
\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega \oplus \sum_{a \in \pi_1 \mu_1} (\pi_2 \mu_1 a) \cdot \Omega'; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{bind } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 : \mathbb{PC}_{(c \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau} \\
\\
\frac{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa : \mathbb{R}^+ \quad \delta_0 = (\{0\}, \{0 \mapsto 1\})}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \uparrow^\kappa : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa \mathbf{1}} \text{T-tick} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau[0/a] \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa : \mathbb{R}^+ \quad \delta_0 = (\{0\}, \{0 \mapsto 1\})}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{store } e : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa ([\kappa] \tau)} \text{T-store} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : [\kappa] \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2, x : \tau \vdash e_2 : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} (\kappa + \kappa') \tau'}{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa : \mathbb{R}^+ \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa' : \mathbb{R}^+} \text{T-release} \\
\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa' \tau'} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(p \ i) \quad \Theta; \Delta \models n > 0 \quad \mu = (\{0 \dots n-1\}, \{i \mapsto p \ i \mid i < n\}) \quad \sum_{i < n} p \ i = 1 \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash p : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{toDist } e : \mathbb{PC}_{(i \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \mathbf{N}(i)} \text{T-toDist} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : !L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(p \ i) \quad \Theta; \Delta \models n > 0 \quad \mu = (\{0 \dots n-1\}, \{i \mapsto p \ i \mid i < n\}) \quad \sum_{i < n} p \ i = 1 \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash p : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{toDist } e : \mathbb{PC}_{(i \leftarrow \mu)} 0 !\mathbf{N}(i)} \text{T-toDist!} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \mathbf{N}(n) \quad \mu = (\{0, \dots, n\}, \{i \mapsto \frac{1}{n+1} \mid i < n+1\})}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{Unif } e : \mathbb{PC}_{(i \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \mathbf{N}(i)} \text{T-Unif} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : [p] \tau_1 \times \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{Swap } e : \tau_1 \times [p] \tau_2} \text{T-swap} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{Purify } e : \tau[0/a]} \text{T-purify}
\end{array}$$

Figure 6: Typing rules

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau <: \tau} \text{sub-refl} \qquad \frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau'_1 <: \tau_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_2 <: \tau'_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 \multimap \tau_2 <: \tau'_1 \multimap \tau'_2} \text{sub-arrow} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau'_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_2 <: \tau'_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 \times \tau_2 <: \tau'_1 \times \tau'_2} \text{sub-tensor} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau'_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_2 <: \tau'_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 \& \tau_2 <: \tau'_1 \& \tau'_2} \text{sub-with} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau'_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_2 <: \tau'_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 + \tau_2 <: \tau'_1 + \tau'_2} \text{sub-sum} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; i; \Delta, i < n \vdash \tau <: \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash L_{i < n} \tau <: L_{i < n} \tau'} \text{sub-list} \qquad \frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta, s \vdash \tau <: \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \exists s. \tau <: \exists s. \tau'} \text{sub-exist} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi, \alpha; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \forall \alpha. \tau_1 <: \forall \alpha. \tau_2} \text{sub-typePoly} \qquad \frac{\Psi; \Theta, i; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \forall i. \tau_1 <: \forall i. \tau_2} \text{sub-indexPoly} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau_2 \quad \Theta; \Delta \models c_2 \implies c_1}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash c_1 \Rightarrow \tau_1 <: c_2 \Rightarrow \tau_2} \text{sub-constraint} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau_2 \quad \Theta; \Delta \models c_1 \implies c_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash c_1 \& \tau_1 <: c_2 \& \tau_2} \text{sub-CAnd} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in S \vdash \tau <: \tau' \quad \Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in S \vdash R'_a \leq R_a}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \tau <: !_{\sum_{a \in S} R'_a} \tau'} \text{sub-subExp1} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in S \vdash \tau <: \tau' \quad \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in S \vdash R_a : \mathbb{R}^+ \quad S' = \{(c, 0) \mid c \in S\}}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \tau <: !_{\sum_{b \in S'} R_a} \tau' [\pi_1 b/a]} \text{sub-subExp2} \\
\\
\frac{\Theta; \Delta \vdash k : \mathbb{R}^+ \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash k' : \mathbb{R}^+}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash [k](\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) <: ([k'] \tau_1 \multimap [k' + k] \tau_2)} \text{sub-potArrow} \\
\\
\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau <: [0] \tau} \text{sub-potZero} \qquad \frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau <: \tau' \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash p' \leq p}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash [p] \tau <: [p'] \tau'} \text{sub-potential} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in I \vdash \tau <: \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash [\sum_{a \in I} R_a \cdot P_a] !_{\sum_{a \in I} R_a} \tau <: !_{\sum_{a \in I} R_a} [P_a] \tau'} \text{sub-BP1} \\
\\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in I \vdash \tau <: \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash !_{\sum_{a \in I} R_a} [P_a] \tau <: \mathcal{S}[\sum_{a \in I} R_a \cdot P_a] !_{\sum_{a \in I} R_a} \tau'} \text{sub-BP2}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \exists \alpha : \mu \leftrightarrow \mu' \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa \leq \kappa'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau < : \mathbb{PC}_{(a' \leftarrow \mu')} \kappa' \tau'} \text{sub-coupling} \\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; a; \Delta \vdash \tau < : \tau' \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa \leq \kappa' \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \mu \leq \mu'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau < : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu')} \kappa' \tau'} \text{sub-pcMonad}
\end{array}$$

Figure 7: Subtyping

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma < : .} \text{sub-lBase} \\
\frac{x : \tau' \in \Gamma_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' < : \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1/x < : \Gamma_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1 < : \Gamma_2, x : \tau} \text{sub-lInd}
\end{array}$$

Figure 8: Γ Subtyping

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Omega < : .} \text{sub-mBase} \\
\frac{\Psi; \Theta; a; \Delta, a \in I \vdash \tau' < : \tau \quad x : \sum_{a \in I} R'_a \tau' \in \Omega_1 \quad \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in I \models R_a \leq R'_a \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Omega_1/x < : \Omega_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Omega_1 < : \Omega_2, x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau} \text{sub-mInd}
\end{array}$$

Figure 9: Ω Subtyping

2.3 Operational Semantics

Pure reduction: $e \downarrow_t v$	Forcing reduction: $e \Downarrow_t^{\kappa} (V_d, M_d)$
------------------------------------	---

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{e_1 \downarrow_{t_1} v \quad e_2 \downarrow_{t_2} l}{e_1 :: e_2 \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v :: l} \text{E-cons} \\
\\
\frac{e_1 \downarrow_{t_1} \text{nil} \quad e_2 \downarrow_{t_2} v}{\text{match } e_1 \text{ with } |\text{nil} \mapsto e_2 \mid h :: t \mapsto e_3 \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v} \text{E-matchNil} \\
\\
\frac{e_1 \downarrow_{t_1} v_h :: l \quad e_3[v_h/h][l/t] \downarrow_{t_2} v}{\text{match } e_1 \text{ with } |\text{nil} \mapsto e_2 \mid h :: t \mapsto e_3 \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v} \text{E-matchCons} \\
\\
\frac{e \downarrow_{t_1} Z \quad e_0 \downarrow_{t_2} v}{\text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_2 \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v} \text{E-matchZero} \\
\\
\frac{e \downarrow_{t_1} S v \quad e_1[v/x] \downarrow_{t_2} v}{\text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_2 \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v} \text{E-matchSucc} \\
\\
\frac{e_1 \downarrow_{t_1} v \quad e_2[v/x] \downarrow_{t_2} v'}{e_1; x.e_2 \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v'} \text{E-exist} \qquad \frac{e_1 \downarrow_{t_1} \lambda x.e' \quad e'[e_2/x] \downarrow_{t_2} v'}{e_1 e_2 \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v'} \text{E-app} \\
\\
\frac{e_1 \downarrow_{t_1} v_1 \quad e_2 \downarrow_{t_2} v_2}{\langle\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle\rangle \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle} \text{E-TI} \qquad \frac{e \downarrow_{t_1} \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle \quad e'[v_1/x][v_2/y] \downarrow_{t_2} v}{\text{let } \langle x, y \rangle = e \text{ in } e' \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v} \text{E-TE} \\
\\
\frac{e_1 \downarrow_{t_1} v_1 \quad e_2 \downarrow_{t_2} v_2}{\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle} \text{E-WI} \qquad \frac{e \downarrow_t \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle}{\text{fst}(e) \downarrow_{t+1} v_1} \text{E-fst} \qquad \frac{e \downarrow_t \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle}{\text{snd}(e) \downarrow_{t+1} v_2} \text{E-snd} \\
\\
\frac{e \downarrow_t v}{\text{inl}(e) \downarrow_{t+1} \text{inl}(v)} \text{E-inl} \qquad \frac{e \downarrow_t v}{\text{inr}(e) \downarrow_{t+1} \text{inr}(v)} \text{E-inr} \\
\\
\frac{e \downarrow_{t_1} \text{inl}(v) \quad e'[v/x] \downarrow_{t_2} v'}{\text{case } e \text{ of } x.e'; y.e'' \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} \text{inl}(v')} \text{E-case1} \\
\\
\frac{e \downarrow_{t_1} \text{inr}(v) \quad e''[v/y] \downarrow_{t_2} v''}{\text{case } e \text{ of } x.e'; y.e'' \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} \text{inl}(v'')} \text{E-case2} \\
\\
\frac{e \downarrow_{t_1} !e'' \quad e'[e''/x] \downarrow_{t_2} v}{\text{let } !x = e \text{ in } e' \downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v} \text{E-subExpe} \qquad \frac{e[\text{fix } x.e/x] \downarrow_t v}{\text{fix } x.e \downarrow_{t+1} v} \text{E-fix} \\
\\
\frac{e \downarrow_t ()}{\text{split } e \downarrow_{t+1} \langle\langle (), () \rangle\rangle} \text{E-split}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{v \in \{(), nil, \lambda y. _, \Lambda. _, !_, \text{return } e, \text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2, \uparrow^-, \text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2, \text{store } e\}}{v \Downarrow_0 v} \text{E-val} \\
\\
\frac{e \Downarrow_{t_1} \Lambda.e' \quad e' \Downarrow_{t_2} v}{e \bullet \Downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v} \text{E-tapp} \qquad \frac{e \Downarrow_{t_1} \Lambda.e' \quad e' \Downarrow_{t_2} v}{e \bullet \Downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v} \text{E-iapp} \\
\\
\frac{e \Downarrow_{t_1} \Lambda.e' \quad e' \Downarrow_{t_1} v}{e \bullet \Downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v} \text{E-CE} \qquad \frac{e_1 \Downarrow_{t_1} v \quad e_2[v/x] \Downarrow_{t_2} v'}{\text{clet } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \Downarrow_{t_1+t_2+1} v'} \text{E-CAnadE} \\
\\
\frac{}{\uparrow^\kappa \Downarrow_1^\kappa (\{()\}, \{() \mapsto 1\})} \text{E-tick} \qquad \frac{e \Downarrow_t v}{\text{return } e \Downarrow_{t+1}^0 (\{v\}, \{v \mapsto 1\})} \text{E-return} \\
\\
\frac{e_1 \Downarrow_{t_1} v_1 \quad v_1 \Downarrow_{t_2}^{\kappa_1} (V_1, M_1) \quad \forall a \in V_1. e_2[a/x] \Downarrow_{t_a} v_{2a} \wedge v_{2a} \Downarrow_{t_{a'}}^{\kappa_{2a}} \mu_{2a} \quad t_3 = \max_{a \in V_1} t_a \quad t_4 = \max_{a \in V_1} t_{a'} \quad \kappa_2 = \sum_{a \in V_1} (M_1 a) \cdot \kappa_{2a} \quad \mu = \mu_1 \otimes a. \mu_{2a}}{\text{bind } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \Downarrow_{t_1+t_2+t_3+t_4+1}^{\kappa_1+\kappa_2} \mathbb{M}_2(\mu)} \text{E-bind} \\
\\
\frac{e \Downarrow_t v}{\text{store } e \Downarrow_{t+1}^0 (\{v\}, \{v \mapsto 1\})} \text{E-store} \\
\\
\frac{e_1 \Downarrow_{t_1} v_1 \quad e_2[v_1/x] \Downarrow_{t_2} v_2 \quad v_2 \Downarrow_{t_3}^\kappa (V, M)}{\text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \Downarrow_{t_1+t_2+t_3+1}^\kappa (V, M)} \text{E-release} \\
\\
\frac{e \Downarrow_t ls \quad ls \neq nil \quad V_d = \{0 \dots |ls| - 1\} \quad M_d = \{i \mapsto ls!!i \mid i \in V_d\}}{\text{toDist } e \Downarrow_{t+1}^0 (V_d, M_d)} \text{E-toDist} \\
\\
\frac{e \Downarrow_t n \quad V_d = \{0 \dots n\} \quad M_d = \{i \mapsto \frac{1}{n+1} \mid i \in V_d\}}{\text{Unif } e \Downarrow_{t+1}^0 (V_d, M_d)} \text{E-unif} \\
\\
\frac{e \Downarrow_t \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle}{\text{Swap } e \Downarrow_{t+1} \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle} \text{E-swap} \qquad \frac{e \Downarrow_t^0 (\{v\}, \{v \mapsto 1\})}{\text{Purify } e \Downarrow_{t+1} v} \text{E-purify}
\end{array}$$

Figure 10: Evaluation rules

2.4 Model

Definition 30 (Value and expression relation).

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{V}[\mathbf{1}] &\triangleq \{(p, T, ())\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\mathbf{B}(i)] &\triangleq \{(p, T, v) \mid v \in \llbracket \mathbf{B} \rrbracket \wedge i = v\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)] &\triangleq \{(p, T, v) \mid v \in \llbracket \mathbf{N} \rrbracket \wedge i = v\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\mathbf{R}(i)] &\triangleq \{(p, T, v) \mid v \in \llbracket \mathbf{R} \rrbracket \wedge i = v\} \\
\mathcal{V}[L_{i < 1} \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, nil)\} \\
\mathcal{V}[L_{i < s+1} \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, v :: l) \mid \exists p_1, p_2. p_1 + p_2 \leq p \wedge (p_1, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[0/i]] \wedge \\
&\quad (p_2, T, l) \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < s} \tau[i + 1/i]]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \times \tau_2] &\triangleq \{(p, T, \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle) \mid \exists p_1, p_2. p_1 + p_2 \leq p \wedge (p_1, T, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1] \wedge (p_2, T, v_2) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \& \tau_2] &\triangleq \{(p, T, \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle) \mid (p, T, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1] \wedge (p, T, v_2) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\tau_1 + \tau_2] &\triangleq \{(p, T, inl(v)) \mid (p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1]\} \cup \{(p, T, inr(v)) \mid (p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2] &\triangleq \{(p, T, \lambda x. e) \mid \forall p', e', T' < T. (p', T', e') \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1] \implies (p + p', T', e[e'/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\sum_{a \in S} C_a \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, !e) \mid \\
&\quad \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|S|-1}. \sum_{i < |S|} C_a[S(i)/a] \cdot p_i \leq p \wedge \forall i < |S|. (p_i, T, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[S(i)/a]]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\forall \alpha. \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, \Lambda. e) \mid \forall T', T' < T. (p, T', e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[T'/\alpha]]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\forall i. \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, \Lambda. e) \mid \forall I, T' < T. (p, T', e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[I/i]]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[c \implies \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, \Lambda. e) \mid . \models c \implies (p, T, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[c \& \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, v) \mid . \models c \wedge (p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\exists s. \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, \text{Ex } e) \mid \exists s'. (p, T, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[s'/s]]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\llbracket n \rrbracket \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, v) \mid \exists p'. p' + n \leq p \wedge (p', T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau]\} \\
\mathcal{V}[\text{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, v) \mid \mu = (C_s, M_s) \wedge \forall \kappa', v', T' < T. \\
&\quad v \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies \\
&\quad \exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]. \\
&\quad 1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\
&\quad \quad \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j)) \\
&\quad 2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}. \\
&\quad a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies \\
&\quad \quad (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]] \\
&\quad b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa\} \\
\mathcal{E}[\tau] &\triangleq \{(p, T, e) \mid \forall T' < T, v. e \Downarrow_{T'} v \implies (p, T - T', v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau]\}
\end{aligned}$$

Definition 31 (Interpretation of typing contexts).

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{G}[\Gamma] &= \{(p, T, \rho_l) \mid \exists f : \text{Vars} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+. \\
&\quad (\forall x \in \text{dom}(\Gamma). (f(x), T, \rho_l(x)) \in \mathcal{E}[\Gamma(x)]) \wedge (\sum_{x \in \text{dom}(\Gamma)} f(x) \leq p)\} \\
\mathcal{G}[\Omega] &\triangleq \{(p, T, \rho_m) \mid \exists f : \text{Vars} \rightarrow \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+. \\
&\quad (\forall (x : \sum_{a \in S} C_a \tau) \in \Omega. \forall i < |S|. (f \ x \ i, T, \rho_m(x)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[S(i)/a]]) \wedge \\
&\quad (\sum_{x : \sum_{a \in S} C_a \tau \in \Omega} \sum_{i < |S|} C_a[S(i)/a] \cdot f \ x \ i) \leq p\}
\end{aligned}$$

Definition 32 (Type and index substitutions). $\theta : \text{TypeVar} \rightarrow \text{Type}$, $\iota : \text{IndexVar} \rightarrow \text{Index}$

Lemma 33 (Value monotonicity lemma). $(p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau] \wedge p \leq p' \wedge T' \leq T \implies (p', T', v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau]$

Proof. Proof by induction on τ

□

Lemma 34 (Expression monotonicity lemma). $(p, T, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau] \wedge p \leq p' \wedge T' \leq T \implies (p', T', e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau]$

Proof. From Definition 30 and Lemma 33

□

Lemma 35 (Lemma for bounded sum of Ω). $\forall p, \rho_m, I, \Omega$.

$$(p, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\sum_{a \in I} R \cdot \Omega] \implies \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|I|-1}. \sum_{i < |I|} R[I(i)/a] \cdot p_i \leq p \wedge \forall 0 \leq i < |I|. (p_i, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega[I(i)/a]]$$

Proof. Given: $(p, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\sum_{a \in I} R \cdot \Omega]$

When $\Omega = \cdot$

The proof is trivial simply choose p_i as 0 and we are done

When $\Omega(a) = x_0 : \sum_{b_1 \in J_0} Q_0 \tau_0(a), \dots, x_n : \sum_{b_n \in J_n} Q_n \tau_n(a)$

Therefore from Definition 23 and Definition 31 we have

$$\exists f : \mathcal{V}ars \rightarrow Index \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+.$$

$$(\forall (x_j : \sum_{c \in (I \odot a \cdot J_j)} R[\pi_1 c/a] \cdot Q[\pi_1 c/a][\pi_2 c/b_j] \tau_j[\pi_1 c/a][\pi_2 c/b_j]) \in \sum_{a \in I} R \cdot \Omega.$$

$$\forall i \in (I \odot a \cdot J_j).$$

$$(f x_j i, T, \rho_m(x_j)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[i/c]] \wedge$$

$$(\sum_{x_j \in \text{dom}(\sum_{a \in I} R \cdot \Omega)} \sum_{i \in (I \odot a \cdot J_j)} (R[\pi_1 i/a] \cdot Q_j[\pi_1 i/a][\pi_2 i/b_j]) \cdot f x_j i) \leq p \quad (\text{L0})$$

To prove the desired, for each $i \in [0, |I| - 1]$ we choose

$$p_i \text{ as } \sum_{x_j \in \text{dom}(\Omega(I(i)))} \sum_{k \in J_j(I(i))} Q_j \cdot f x_j (I(i), k)$$

We need to prove

$$1. \sum_{i < |I|} R[I(i)/a] \cdot p_i \leq p:$$

It suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{i < |I|} R[I(i)/a] \cdot \sum_{x_j \in \text{dom}(\Omega(i))} \sum_{k \in J_j(i)} Q_j \cdot f x_j (I(i), k) \leq p$$

Since $\text{dom}(\Omega_i) = \text{dom}((\sum_{a \in I} R \cdot \Omega))$, therefore it further suffices to prove that

$$(\sum_{x_j \in \text{dom}(\sum_{a \in I} R \cdot \Omega)} \sum_{i \in (I \odot a \cdot J_j)} (R[\pi_1 i/a] \cdot Q_j[\pi_1 i/a][\pi_2 i/b_j]) \cdot f x_j i) \leq p$$

We get this directly from (L0)

2. $\forall 0 \leq i < |I|. (p_i, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega[I(i)/a]]$:

This means given some $0 \leq i < I$ it suffices to prove that
 $(p_i, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega[I(i)/a]]$

From Definition 31 it further suffices to prove that

$$\begin{aligned} & \exists f' : \mathcal{V}ars \rightarrow Index \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+. \\ & (\forall (x_j : \sum_{b_j \in J_j} Q_j \tau_j) \in \Omega[I(i)/a]. \\ & \forall k \in J_j[I(i)/a]. \\ & (f' x_j k, T, \rho_m(x_j)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_j[I(i)/a][k/b_j]]) \wedge \\ & (\sum_{x_j \in \text{dom}(\Omega[I(i)/a])} \sum_{k \in J_j[I(i)/a]} Q_j[I(i)/a] \cdot f' x_j k) \leq p_i \end{aligned}$$

We choose f' as $\lambda x k. f x (I(i), k)$

We need to prove:

- $(\forall (x_j : \sum_{b_j \in J_j} Q_j \tau_j) \in \Omega[I(i)/a]. \forall k \in J_j[I(i)/a]. (f' x_j k, T, \rho_m(x_j)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_j[I(i)/a][k/b_j]])$:
Directly from (L0)
- $(\sum_{x_j \in \text{dom}(\Omega[I(i)/a])} \sum_{k \in J_j[I(i)/a]} Q_j[I(i)/a] \cdot f' x_j k) \leq p_i$:
Trivial since p_i is $\sum_{x_j \in \text{dom}(\Omega(I(i)))} \sum_{k \in J_j(I(i))} Q_j \cdot f x_j (I(i), k)$

□

Theorem 36 (Fundamental theorem). $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau \wedge (p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta \iota] \wedge (p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta \iota] \wedge . \models \Delta \iota \implies (p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_l \rho_m) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta \iota]$.

Proof. Proof by induction on the typing judgment

1. T-var1:

$$\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; .; x : \tau \vdash x : \tau} \text{T-var1}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(x : \tau) \theta \iota]$ and $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\cdot]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, x \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta \iota]$

Since we are given that $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[x : \tau \theta \iota]$ therefore from Definition 31 we know that

$$\exists f. (f(x), T, \rho_l(x)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-V1})$$

Therefore we get desired from (F-V1) and Lemma 34

2. T-var2:

$$\frac{\Theta, \Delta \models R_a[J/a] \geq 1 \quad \Theta, \Delta \models J \leq I}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau; \cdot \vdash x : \tau[J/a]} \text{T-var2}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\cdot]$ and $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(x : \tau) \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, x \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$

Directly from Definition 31 and Lemma 34.

3. T-var3:

$$\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau; \cdot \vdash !x : !\sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau} \text{T-var3}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\cdot]$ and $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(x : \tau) \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, !x \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau \theta_l]$

Directly from Definition 8 and Definition 31.

4. T-unit, T-zero, T-real, T-succ:

Trivial.

5. T-nil:

$$\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \cdot; \cdot \vdash nil : L_{i < 0} \tau} \text{T-nil}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\cdot]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\cdot]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, nil \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[L_{i < 0} \tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall T' < T, v'. nil \downarrow_{T'} v' \implies (p_l + p_m, T - T', v') \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < 0} \tau \theta_l]$$

This means given some $T' < T, v'$ s.t $nil \downarrow_{T'} v'$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - T', v') \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < 0} \tau \theta_l]$$

From (E-val) we know that $T' = 0$ and $v' = nil$, therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, nil) \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < 0} \tau \theta_l]$$

We get this directly from Definition 30

6. T-cons:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \tau[0/i] \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : L_{i < n} \tau[(i+1)/i]}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 :: e_2 : L_{i < n+1} \tau} \text{T-cons}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2)\theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2)\theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (e_1 :: e_2) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[L_{i < n+1} \tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v'. (e_1 :: e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v' \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v') \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < n+1} \tau \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v'$ s.t $(e_1 :: e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v'$, it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v') \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < n+1} \tau \theta_l]$$

From (E-cons) we know that $\exists v_f, l. v' = v_f :: l$

Therefore from Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists p_1, p_2. p_1 + p_2 \leq p_l + p_m \wedge (p_1, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[0/i] \theta_l] \wedge (p_2, T - t, l) \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < n} \tau[i+1/i] \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-C0})$$

From Definition 31 and Definition 21 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t

$$(p_{l1}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1)\theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{l2}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2)\theta_l]$$

Similarly we also know that $\exists p_{m1}, p_{m2}. p_{m1} + p_{m2} = p_m$ s.t

$$(p_{m1}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1)\theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{m2}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_2)\theta_l]$$

IH1:

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T, e_1 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T. e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_f \implies (p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau]$$

Since we are given that $(e_1 :: e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f :: l$ therefore fom E-cons we also know that $\exists t_1 < t. e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_f$

$$\text{Since } t_1 < t < T, \text{ therefore we have } (p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-C1})$$

IH2:

$$(p_{l2} + p_{m2}, T, e_2 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[L_{i < n} \tau \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T. e_2 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} l \implies (p_{l2} + p_{m2}, T - t_2, l) \in \mathcal{V}[L_{i < n} \tau \theta_l]$$

Since we are given that $(e_1 :: e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f :: l$ therefore from E-cons we also know that $\exists t_2 < t - t_1. e_2 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} l$

Since $t_2 < t - t_1 < t < T$, therefore we have

$$(p_{l_2} + p_{m_2}, T - t_2, l) \in \mathcal{V}[[L_{i < n} \tau \theta_l]] \quad (\text{F-C2})$$

In order to prove (F-C0) we choose p_1 as $p_{l_1} + p_{m_1}$ and p_2 as $p_{l_2} + p_{m_2}$ and it suffices to prove that

$$(p_{l_1} + p_{m_1}, T - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau \theta_l]] \wedge (p_{l_2} + p_{m_2}, T - t, l) \in \mathcal{V}[[L_{i < n} \tau \theta_l]]$$

Since $t = t_1 + t_2 + 1$ therefore from (F-C1) and Lemma 33 we get $(p_{l_1} + p_{m_1}, T - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau \theta_l]]$

Similarly from (F-C2) and Lemma 33 we also get $(p_{l_2} + p_{m_2}, T - t, l) \in \mathcal{V}[[L^n \tau \theta_l]]$

7. T-match:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : L^n \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 : \tau' \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta, n > 0; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2, h : \tau, t : L^{n-1} \tau \vdash e_2 : \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{match } e \text{ with } |nil \mapsto e_1 |h :: t \mapsto e_2 : \tau'} \text{T-match}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2) \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{match } e \text{ with } |nil \mapsto e_1 |h :: t \mapsto e_2) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[\tau' \theta_l]]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\text{match } e \text{ with } |nil \mapsto e_1 |h :: t \mapsto e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau' \theta_l]]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(\text{match } e \text{ with } |nil \mapsto e_1 |h :: t \mapsto e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau' \theta_l]] \quad (\text{F-M0})$$

From Definition 31 and Definition 21 we know that $\exists p_{l_1}, p_{l_2}. p_{l_1} + p_{l_2} = p_l$ s.t

$$(p_{l_1}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_1) \theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{l_2}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_2) \theta_l]$$

Similarly we also know that $\exists p_{m_1}, p_{m_2}. p_{m_1} + p_{m_2} = p_m$ s.t

$$(p_{m_1}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1) \theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{m_2}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_2) \theta_l]$$

IH1

$$(p_{l_1} + p_{m_1}, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[L^n \tau \theta_l]]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t' < T . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} v_1 \implies (p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t', v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[[L^n \tau \theta_l]]$$

Since we know that (match e with $|nil \mapsto e_1 |h :: t \mapsto e_2)$ $\rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-match we know that $\exists t' < t, v_1.e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} v_1$.

Since $t' < t < T$, therefore we have $(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t', v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[[L^n \tau \theta_l]]$

2 cases arise:

(a) $v_1 = nil$:

In this case we know that $n = 0$ therefore

IH2

$$(p_{l2} + p_{m2}, T, e_1 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[\tau' \theta_l]]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_f \implies (p_{l2} + p_{m2}, T - t_1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau' \theta_l]]$$

Since we know that (match e with $|nil \mapsto e_1 |h :: t \mapsto e_2)$ $\rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-match we know that $\exists t_1 < t. e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_f$.

Since $t_1 < t < T$ therefore we have

$$(p_{l2} + p_{m2}, T - t_1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau' \theta_l]]$$

And from Lemma 33 we get

$$(p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2}, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{E}[[\tau' \theta_l]]$$

And we are done.

(b) $v_1 = v :: l$:

In this case we know that $n > 0$

IH2

$$(p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2}, T, e_2 \rho_m \rho'_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[\tau' \theta_l]]$$

where

$$\rho'_l = \rho_l \cup \{h \mapsto v\} \cup \{t \mapsto l\}$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T . e_2 \rho_m \rho'_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2}, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau' \theta_l]]$$

Since we know that (match e with $|nil \mapsto e_1 |h :: t \mapsto e_2)$ $\rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-match we know that $\exists t_2 < t. e_2 \rho_m \rho'_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$.

Since $t_2 < t < T$ therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2}, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau' \theta_l]]$$

From Lemma 33 we get

$$(p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2}, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau' \theta_l]]$$

And we are done.

8. T-matchN:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : \mathbf{N}(n) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta, n = 0; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_0 : \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; i; \Delta, i + 1 = n; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2, x : \mathbf{N}(i) \vdash e_1 : \tau \quad i \notin \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_1 : \tau} \text{T-matchN}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_1) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_1) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t. $(\text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_1) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-M0})$$

From Definition 31 and Definition 21 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t.

$$(p_{l1}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_1) \theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{l2}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_2) \theta_l]$$

Similarly we also know that $\exists p_{m1}, p_{m2}. p_{m1} + p_{m2} = p_m$ s.t.

$$(p_{m1}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1) \theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{m2}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_2) \theta_l]$$

IH1

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbf{N}(n) \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t' < T. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} v_1 \implies (p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t', v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(n) \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_1) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-matchN we know that $\exists t' < t, v_1. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} v_1$.

$$\text{Since } t' < t < T, \text{ therefore we have } (p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t', v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(n) \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-M1})$$

2 cases arise:

(a) $v_1 = Z$:

IH2

$$(p_{l2} + p_m, T, e_0 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T. e_0 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_f \implies (p_{l2} + p_m, T - t_1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

Since we know that ($\text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_1$) $\rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-matchN we know that $\exists t_1 < t. e_0 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_f$.

Since $t_1 < t < T$ therefore we have

$$(p_{l_2} + p_{m_2}, T - t_1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

From Lemma 33 we get

$$(p_{l_1} + p_{l_2} + p_{m_1} + p_{m_2}, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

And we are done.

(b) $v_1 = S v$:

From (F-M1) and Definition 8 we know that

$$(p_{l_1} + p_{m_1}, T - t', v) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(j) \theta_l] \text{ where } j + 1 = n$$

In this case we know that $j + 1 = n$

IH2

$$(p_{l_2} + p_{m_2} + p_{l_1} + p_{m_1}, T, e_2 \rho_m \rho'_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta'_l]$$

where

$$\rho'_l = \rho_l \cup \{x \mapsto v\}$$

$$l' = l \cup \{i \mapsto j\}$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T . e_2 \rho_m \rho'_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (p_{l_2} + p_{m_2} + p_{l_1} + p_{m_1}, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta'_l]$$

Since we know that ($\text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S x) \mapsto e_1$) $\rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-matchN we know that $\exists t_2 < t. e_2 \rho_m \rho'_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$.

Since $t_2 < t < T$ therefore we have

$$(p_{l_2} + p_{m_2} + p_{l_1} + p_{m_1}, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta'_l]$$

From Lemma 33 we get

$$(p_{l_2} + p_{m_2} + p_{l_1} + p_{m_1}, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta'_l]$$

Since $i \notin \tau$, therefore we also have

$$(p_{l_2} + p_{m_2} + p_{l_1} + p_{m_1}, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

And we are done.

9. T-existI:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau[n/s] \quad \Theta \vdash n : S}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{Ex } e : \exists s : S . \tau} \text{T-existI}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\exists s . \tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f.e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\exists s.\tau \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that $(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\exists s.\tau \theta_l]$

Also from From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v_f = (\text{Ex } e) \rho_m \rho_l$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists s'.(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[s'/s] \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-E0})$$

$$\underline{\text{IH}}: (p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[n/s] \theta_l]$$

We choose s' as n and we get the desired directly from IH.

10. T-existsE:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : \exists s.\tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; s; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2, x : \tau \vdash e' : \tau' \quad \Theta \vdash \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash e; x.e' : \tau'} \text{T-existE}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2) \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (e; x.e') \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f.(e; x.e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

This means given soem $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(e; x.e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-EE0})$$

From Definition 31 and Definition 21 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t

$$(p_{l1}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1)\theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{l2}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2)\theta_l]$$

Similarly we also know that $\exists p_{m1}, p_{m2}. p_{m1} + p_{m2} = p_m$ s.t

$$(p_{m1}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1)\theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{m2}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_2)\theta_l]$$

IH1

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\exists s.\tau \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T .e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_1 \implies (p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{E}[\exists s.\tau \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(e; x.e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-existE we know that $\exists t_1 < t, v_1.e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_1$. Therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\exists s. \tau \theta \iota]$$

Therefore from Definition 30 we have

$$\exists s'. (p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[s'/s] \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-EE1})$$

IH2

$$(p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2}, T, e' \rho'_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta \iota']$$

where

$$\rho'_m = \rho_m \cup \{x \mapsto e_1\} \text{ and } \iota' = \iota \cup \{s \mapsto s'\}$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T. e' \rho'_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2}, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta \iota']$$

Since we know that $(e; x.e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-existE we know that $\exists t_2 < t. e' \rho'_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$.

Since $t_2 < t < T$ therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2}, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta \iota']$$

From Lemma 33 we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta \iota']$$

And finally since we have $\Psi; \Theta \vdash \tau'$ therefore we also have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta \iota]$$

And we are done

11. T-lam:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma, x : \tau_1 \vdash e : \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \lambda x. e : (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2)} \text{ T-lam}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma, \theta \iota]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta \iota]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\lambda x. e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \theta \iota]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\lambda x. e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \theta \iota]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(\lambda x. e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v_f = (\lambda x. e) \rho_m \rho_l$

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, (\lambda x. e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \theta \iota]$$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall p', e', T' < T . (p', T', e') \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \theta \iota] \implies (p_l + p_m + p', T', e[e'/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \theta \iota]$$

This means given some $p', e', T' < T$ s.t. $(p', T', e') \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \theta \iota]$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m + p', T', e[e'/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-L1})$$

From IH we know that

$$(p_l + p_m + p', T, e \rho_m \rho'_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \theta \iota]$$

where

$$\rho'_l = \rho_l \cup \{x \mapsto e'\}$$

Therefore from Lemma 34 we get the desired

12. T-app:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : \tau_1}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 e_2 : \tau_2} \text{T-app}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2)\theta \iota]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2) \theta \iota]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, e_1 e_2 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \theta \iota]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f . (e_1 e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta \iota]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t. $(e_1 e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-A0})$$

From Definition 31 and Definition 21 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2} . p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t.

$$(p_{l1}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1)\theta \iota] \text{ and } (p_{l2}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2)\theta \iota]$$

Similarly we also know that $\exists p_{m1}, p_{m2} . p_{m1} + p_{m2} = p_m$ s.t.

$$(p_{m1}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1)\theta \iota] \text{ and } (p_{m2}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_2)\theta \iota]$$

IH1

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T, e_1 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \theta \iota]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . e_1 \downarrow_{t_1} \lambda x . e \implies (p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, \lambda x . e) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \theta \iota]$$

Since we know that $(e_1 e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-app we know that $\exists t_1 < t . e_1 \downarrow_{t_1} \lambda x . e$, therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, \lambda x . e) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \theta \iota]$$

Therefore from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall p', e_1, T_1 < T - t_1. (p', T_1, e'_1) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \theta \iota] \implies (p_{l1} + p_{m1} + p', T_1, e[e'_1/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-A1})$$

IH2

$$(p_{l2} + p_{m2}, T - t_1 - 1, e_2 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-A2})$$

Instantiating (F-A1) with $p_{l2} + p_{m2}$, $e_2 \rho_m \rho_l$ and $T - t_1 - 1$ we get

$$(p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2}, T - t_1 - 1, e[e_2 \rho_m \rho_l/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \theta \iota]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T - t_1 - 1. e[e_2 \rho_m \rho_l/x] \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2}, T - t_1 - 1 - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta \iota]$$

Since we know that $(e_1 e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-app we know that $\exists t_2. e[e_2 \rho_m \rho_l/x] \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$ where $t_2 = t - t_1 - 1$, therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2}, T - t_1 - t_2 - 1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta \iota]$$

Since from E-app we know that $t = t_1 + t_2 + 1$, therefore we have proved (F-A0)

13. T-sub:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau \quad \Psi, \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau <: \tau' \quad \Psi; \Theta \models \Gamma' <: \Gamma \quad \Psi; \Theta \models \Omega' <: \Omega}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega'; \Gamma' \vdash e : \tau'} \text{ T-sub}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma') \theta \iota]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega') \theta \iota]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta \iota]$

Since we are given that $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma') \theta \iota]$ therefore from Lemma 40 we also have $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma) \theta \iota]$

Similarly since we are given that $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega') \theta \iota]$ therefore from Lemma 42 we also have $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega) \theta \iota]$

IH:

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta \iota]$$

We get the desired directly from IH and Lemma 38.

14. T-tensorI:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \tau_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle : (\tau_1 \times \tau_2)} \text{T-tensorI}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2)\theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2)\theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 \times \tau_2)\theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T . \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_{f1}, v_{f2} \rangle \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, \langle v_{f1}, v_{f2} \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \times \tau_2)\theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T$ s.t $\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_{f1}, v_{f2} \rangle$ it suffices to prove that $(p_l + p_m, T - t, \langle v_{f1}, v_{f2} \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \times \tau_2)\theta_l]$ (F-TI0)

From Definition 31 and Definition 21 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2} . p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t

$$(p_{l1}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1)\theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{l2}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2)\theta_l]$$

Similarly we also know that $\exists p_{m1}, p_{m2} . p_{m1} + p_{m2} = p_m$ s.t

$$(p_{m1}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1)\theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{m2}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_2)\theta_l]$$

IH1:

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T, e_1 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_{f1} \implies (p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, v_{f1}) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

Since we are given that $\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_{f1}, v_{f2} \rangle$ therefore fom E-TI we know that $\exists t_1 < t . e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_{f1}$

$$\text{Hence we have } (p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, v_{f1}) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-TI1})$$

IH2:

$$(p_{l2} + p_{m2}, T, e_2 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T . e_2 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_{f2} \implies (p_{l2} + p_{m2}, T - t_2, v_{f2}) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta_l]$$

Since we are given that $\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_{f1}, v_{f2} \rangle$ therefore fom E-TI we also know that $\exists t_2 < t . e_2 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_{f2}$ s.t

Since $t_2 < t < T$ therefore we have

$$(p_{l2} + p_{m2}, T - t_2, v_{f2}) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-TI2})$$

We get the desired from (F-TI1), (F-TI2) and Lemma 33.

15. T-tensorE:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : (\tau_1 \times \tau_2) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2, x : \tau_1, y : \tau_2 \vdash e' : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = e \text{ in } e' : \tau} \text{T-tensorE}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2) \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t. $(\text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-TE0})$$

From Definition 31 and Definition 21 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t.

$$(p_{l1}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1) \theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{l2}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2) \theta_l]$$

Similarly we also know that $\exists p_{m1}, p_{m2}. p_{m1} + p_{m2} = p_m$ s.t.

$$(p_{m1}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1) \theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{m2}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_2) \theta_l]$$

IH1

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 \times \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \implies (p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \times \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-TE we know that $\exists t_1 < t, v_1, v_2. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle$. Therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 \times \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

From Definition 30 we know that

$$\exists p_1, p_2. p_1 + p_2 \leq p_{l1} \wedge (p_1, T, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l] \wedge (p_2, T, v_2) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-TE1})$$

IH2

$$(p_{l2} + p_1 + p_2 + p_{m2}, T, e' \rho_m \rho'_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

where

$$\rho'_l = \rho_l \cup \{x \mapsto v_1\} \cup \{y \mapsto v_2\}$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T . e' \rho_m \rho'_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (p_{l_2} + p_1 + p_2 + p_{m_2}, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-TE we know that $\exists t_2 < t . e' \rho_m \rho'_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$. Therefore we have

$$(p_{l_2} + p_1 + p_2 + p_{m_2}, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

From Lemma 33 we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

And we are done.

16. T-withI:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e_1 : \tau_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e_2 : \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle : (\tau_1 \& \tau_2)} \text{T-withI}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 \& \tau_2) \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T . \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_{f_1}, v_{f_2} \rangle \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, \langle v_{f_1}, v_{f_2} \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \& \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

This means given $\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_{f_1}, v_{f_2} \rangle$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, \langle v_{f_1}, v_{f_2} \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \& \tau_2) \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-WI0})$$

IH1:

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e_1 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_{f_1} \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v_{f_1}) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

Since we are given that $\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_{f_1}, v_{f_2} \rangle$ therefore from E-WI we know that $\exists t_1 < t . e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_{f_1}$

Since $t_1 < t < T$, therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v_{f_1}) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-WI1})$$

IH2:

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e_2 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T . e_2 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_{f_2} \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_2, v_{f_2}) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta_l]$$

Since we are given that $\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_{f_1}, v_{f_2} \rangle$ therefore from E-WI we also know that $\exists t_2 < t . e_2 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_{f_2}$

Since $t_2 < t < T$, therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_2, v_{f2}) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-WI2})$$

Applying Lemma 33 on (F-W1) and (F-W2) we get the desired.

17. T-fst:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (\tau_1 \& \tau_2)}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{fst}(e) : \tau_1} \text{T-fst}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{fst}(e)) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\text{fst}(e)) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(\text{fst}(e)) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-F0})$$

IH

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 \& \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle \rho_m \rho_l \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \& \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{fst}(e)) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-fst we know that $\exists t_1 < t. v_1, v_2. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle$.

Since $t_1 < t < T$, therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1, \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \& \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

From Definition 30 we know that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

Finally using Lemma 33 we also have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

Since from E-fst we know that $v_f = v_1$, therefore we are done.

18. T-snd:

Similar reasoning as in T-fst case above.

19. T-inl:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau_1}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{inl}(e) : \tau_1 + \tau_2} \text{T-inl}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \text{inl}(e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 + \tau_2) \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T . \text{inl}(e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \text{inl}(v) \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, \text{inl}(v) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 + \tau_2) \theta_l])$$

This means given some $t < T$ s.t $\text{inl}(e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \text{inl}(v)$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, \text{inl}(v)) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 + \tau_2) \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-IL0})$$

IH:

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e_1 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . e_1 \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_{f1} \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v_{f1}) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

Since we are given that $\text{inl}(e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \text{inl}(v)$ therefore fom E-inl we know that $\exists t_1 < t . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v$

$$\text{Hence we have } (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

$$\text{From Lemma 33 we get } (p_l + p_m, T - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l]$$

And finally from Definition 30 we get (F-IL0)

20. T-inr:

Similar reasoning as in T-inr case above.

21. T-case:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : (\tau_1 + \tau_2) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2, x : \tau_1 \vdash e_1 : \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2, y : \tau_2 \vdash e_2 : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{case } e \text{ of } x.e_1; y.e_2 : \tau} \text{T-case}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2) \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{case } e \text{ of } x.e_1; y.e_2) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f . (\text{case } e \text{ of } x.e_1; y.e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t (case e of $x.e_1; y.e_2$) $\rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-C0})$$

From Definition 31 and Definition 21 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t

$$(p_{l1}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1)\theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{l2}, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2)\theta_l]$$

Similarly we also know that $\exists p_{m1}, p_{m2}. p_{m1} + p_{m2} = p_m$ s.t

$$(p_{m1}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1)\theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{m2}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_2)\theta_l]$$

IH1

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 + \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t' < T . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} v_1 \rho_m \rho_l \implies (p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t', v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 + \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

Since we know that (case e of $x.e_1; y.e_2$) $\rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-case we know that $\exists t' < t, v_1.e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} v_1$.

Since $t' < t < T$, therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t', v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 + \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

2 cases arise:

(a) $v_1 = \text{inl}(v)$:

IH2

$$(p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2}, T - t', e_1 \rho_m \rho'_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

where

$$\rho'_l = \rho_l \cup \{x \mapsto v\}$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T - t'. e_1 \rho_m \rho'_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_f \implies (p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2}, T - t' - t_1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

Since we know that (case e of $x.e_1; y.e_2$) $\rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-case we know that $\exists t_1.e_1 \rho_m \rho'_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_f$ where $t_1 = t - t' - 1$.

Since $t_1 = t - t' - 1 < T - t'$ therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2}, T - t' - t_1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta_l]$$

From Lemma 33 we get

$$(p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2}, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

And we are done.

(b) $v_1 = \text{inr}(v)$:

Similar reasoning as in the inl case above.

22. T-subExpI:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in S; \Omega; \cdot \vdash e : \tau \quad \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in S \vdash R_a : \mathbf{R}^+}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \sum_{a \in S} R_a \cdot \Omega; \cdot \vdash !e : !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \tau} \text{T-subExpI}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\cdot]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\sum_{a \in S} R_a \cdot \Omega) \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, !e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\cdot]_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T. (!e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t (!e) \rho_m \rho_l \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, (!e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\cdot]_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \tau \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T$ s.t $(!e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t (!e) \rho_m \rho_l$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, (!e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\cdot]_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \tau \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|S|-1}. \sum_{i \in |S|} R_a[S(i)/a] \cdot p_i \leq p \wedge \forall i < |S|. (p_i, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[S(i)/a] \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-SI0})$$

Since we are given that $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\sum_{a \in S} R_a \cdot \Omega) \theta_l]$ therefore from Lemma 35 we know that

$$\exists p'_0, \dots, p'_{|S|-1}. \sum_{i \in |S|} R_a[S(i)/a] \cdot p'_i \leq p \wedge \forall i < |S|. (p'_i, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega[S(i)/a]) \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-SI1})$$

Instantiating IH with each $p'_0 \dots p'_{|S|-1}$ we get

$$(p'_0, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[S(0)/a] \theta_l] \text{ and}$$

...

$$(p'_{|S|-1}, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[S(|S|-1)/a] \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-SI2})$$

In order to prove (F-SI0) we choose $p'_0, \dots, p'_{|S|-1}$ as the required potentials and we get the desired from (F-SI1) and (F-SI2).

23. T-subExpE:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2, x : \sum_{a \in S} R_a \tau; \Gamma_2 \vdash e' : \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{let } !x = e \text{ in } e' : \tau'} \text{T-subExpE}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2) \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{let } !x = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\text{let } !x = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t. $(\text{let } !x = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-SE0})$$

From Definition 31 and Definition 21 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t.

$$(p_{l1}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1)\theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{l2}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2)\theta_l]$$

Similarly we also know that $\exists p_{m1}, p_{m2}. p_{m1} + p_{m2} = p_m$ s.t.

$$(p_{m1}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Omega_1)\theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{m2}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Omega_2)\theta_l]$$

IH1

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\sum_{a \in S} R_a \tau \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} !e_1 \implies (p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, !e_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\sum_{a \in S} R_a \tau \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{let } !x = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from (E-subExpE) we know that $\exists t_1 < t, e_1. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} !e_1 \rho_m \rho_l$.

Since $t_1 < t < T$, therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, !e_1) \in \mathcal{E}[\sum_{a \in S} R_a \tau \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|S|-1}. \sum_{i \in |S|} R_a[S(i)]/a \cdot p_i \leq p_{l1} + p_{m1} \wedge \\ &\forall i < |S|. (p_i, T - t_1, e_1) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[S(i)]/a \theta_l] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{F-SE1})$$

IH2

$$(p_{l2} + p_{m2} + \sum_{i \in |S|} R_a[S(i)]/a \cdot p_i, T - t_1, e' \rho'_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

where

$$\rho'_m = \rho_m \cup \{x \mapsto e_1\}$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T - t_1. e' \rho'_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (p_{l2} + p_{m2} + \sum_{i \in |S|} R_a[S(i)]/a \cdot p_i, T - t_1 - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{let } !x = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from (E-subExpE) we know that $\exists t_2. e' \rho'_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$ where $t_2 = t - t_1 - 1$.

Since $t_2 = t - t_1 - 1 < T - t_1$, therefore we have

$$(p_{l2} + p_{m2} + \sum_{i \in |S|} R_a[S(i)]/a \cdot p_i, T - t_1 - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

Finally using (F-SE1) and Lemma 33 we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T -t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

And we are done.

24. T-tabs:

$$\frac{\Psi, \alpha :K; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \Lambda.e : (\forall \alpha :K .\tau)} \text{ T-tabs}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma, \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\forall \alpha.\tau) \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T -t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[(\forall \alpha.\tau) \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v_f = (\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l$

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, (\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[(\forall \alpha.\tau) \theta_l]$$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall \tau', T' < T. (p_l + p_m, T', e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[\tau'/\alpha] \theta_l]$$

This means given some $\tau', T' < T$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T', e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[\tau'/\alpha] \theta_l] \tag{F-TAB0}$$

From IH we know that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta'_l]$$

where

$$\theta'_l = \rho_l \cup \{\alpha \mapsto \tau'\}$$

Therefore from Lemma 34 we get the desired

25. T-tapp:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (\forall \alpha.\tau) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e [] : (\tau[\tau'/\alpha])} \text{ T-tapp}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, e [] \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[\tau'/\alpha] \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (e \Downarrow) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[\tau'/\alpha] \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t. $(e \Downarrow) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[\tau'/\alpha] \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-A0})$$

IH

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\forall \alpha. \tau) \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T. e \downarrow_{t_1} \Lambda.e \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, \Lambda.e) \in \mathcal{V}[(\forall \alpha. \tau) \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(e \Downarrow) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-tapp we know that $\exists t_1 < t. e \downarrow_{t_1} \Lambda.e$, therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1, \Lambda.e) \in \mathcal{V}[(\forall \alpha. \tau) \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall \tau'', T_1 < T - t_1. (p_l + p_m, T_1, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[\tau''/\alpha] \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-A1})$$

Instantiating (F-A1) with the given τ' and $T - t_1 - 1$ we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1 - 1, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[\tau'/\alpha] \theta_l]$$

From Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T - t_1 - 1. e \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1 - t_2 - 1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[\tau'/\alpha] \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(e \Downarrow) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-tapp we know that $\exists t_2. e \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$ where $t_2 = t - t_1 - 1$

Since $t_2 = t - t_1 - 1 < T - t_1 - 1$, therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1 - t_2 - 1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[\tau'/\alpha] \theta_l] \text{ and we are done.}$$

26. T-iabs:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta, i : S; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \Lambda.e : (\forall i : S. \tau)} \text{T-iabs}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma, \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega, \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\forall i. \tau) \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[(\forall i. \tau) \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t. $(\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v_f = (\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l$

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, (\Lambda.e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[(\forall i.\tau) \theta_l]$$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall I, T' < T. (p_l + p_m, T', e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[I/i] \theta_l]$$

This means given some $I, T' < T$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T', e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[I/i] \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-IAB0})$$

From IH we know that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_{l'}]$$

where

$$l' = \rho_l \cup \{i \mapsto I\}$$

Therefore from Lemma 34 we get the desired

27. T-iapp:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (\forall i : S . \tau) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash I : S}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e [] : (\tau[I/i])} \text{T-iapp}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, e [] \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[I/i] \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (e []) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[I/i] \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t. $(e []) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[I/i] \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-A0})$$

IH

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\forall i.\tau) \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T. e \downarrow_{t_1} \Lambda.e \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, \Lambda.e) \in \mathcal{V}[(\forall i.\tau) \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(e []) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-tapp we know that $\exists t_1 < t. e \downarrow_{t_1} \Lambda.e$, therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1, \Lambda.e) \in \mathcal{V}[(\forall i.\tau) \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall I, T_1 < T - t_1. (p_l + p_m, T_1, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[I/i] \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-IAP1})$$

Instantiating (F-IAP1) with the given I and $T - t_1 - 1$ we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1 - 1, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[I/i] \theta \iota]$$

From Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T - t_1 - 1. e \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1 - t_2 - 1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[I/i] \theta \iota]$$

Since we know that $(e \square) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-iapp we know that $\exists t_2. e \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$ where $t_2 = t - t_1 - 1$

Since $t_2 = t - t_1 - 1 < T - t_1 - 1$, therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1 - t_2 - 1, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[I/i] \theta \iota] \text{ and we are done.}$$

28. T-CI:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta, c; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \Lambda.e : (c \Rightarrow \tau)} \text{ T-CI}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta \iota]$, $(0, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta \iota]$ and $\models \Delta \iota$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \Lambda.e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(c \Rightarrow \tau) \theta \iota]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall v, t < T. \Lambda.e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[(c \Rightarrow \tau) \theta \iota]$$

This means given some $v, t < T$ s.t $\Lambda.e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v$ and from (E-val) we know that $v = \Lambda.e \rho_m \rho_l$ and $t = 0$ therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, \Lambda.e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[(c \Rightarrow \tau) \theta \iota]$$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$. \models c \iota \implies (p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta \iota]$$

This means given that $. \models c \iota$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta \iota]$$

$$\underline{\text{IH}} (p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta \iota]$$

We get the desired directly from IH

29. T-CE:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (c \Rightarrow \tau) \quad \Theta; \Delta \models c}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e \square : \tau} \text{ T-CE}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta \iota]$, $(0, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta \iota]$ and $\models \Delta \iota$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, e \square \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau) \theta \iota]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall v_f, t < T . (e \square) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau) \theta_l]$$

This means given some $v_f, t < T$ s.t. $(e \square) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau) \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-Tap0})$$

IH

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(c \Rightarrow \tau) \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall v', t' < T . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{v'} \implies (p_l + p_m, v') \in \mathcal{V}[(c \Rightarrow \tau) \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(e \square) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-CE we know that $\exists t' < t . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} \wedge .e'$, and since $t' < t < T$ therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t', \wedge .e') \in \mathcal{V}[(c \Rightarrow \tau) \theta_l]$$

Therefore from Definition 30 we have

$$. \models c \iota \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t', e' \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

Since we are given $\Theta; \Delta \models c$ and $. \models \Delta \iota$ therefore we know that $. \models c \iota$. Hence we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t', e' \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall v'_f, t'' < T - t' . (e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t''} v'_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t' - t'', v'_f) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau) \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-CE1})$$

Since from E-CE we know that $e' \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore we know that $\exists t'' . e' \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t''} v_f$ s.t. $t = t' + t'' + 1$

Therefore instantiating (F-CE1) with the given v_f and t'' we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t' - t'', v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau) \theta_l]$$

Since $t = t' + t'' + 1$ therefore from Lemma 33 we get the desired.

30. T-CAndI:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau \quad \Theta; \Delta \models c}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : (c \& \tau)} \text{T-CAndI}$$

Given: $(p_l, T \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(0, T \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[c \& \tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall v_f, t < T . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[c \& \tau \theta_l]$$

This means given some $v_f, t < T$ s.t $e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that
 $(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[c\&\tau \theta_l]]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\cdot \models ct \wedge (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau \theta_l]]$$

Since we are given that $\cdot \models \Delta t$ and $\Theta; \Delta \models c$ therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau \theta_l]] \quad (\text{F-CAI0})$$

$$\underline{\text{IH}}: (p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[\tau \theta_l]]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t' < T . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t', v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau \theta_l]]$$

Since we are given that $e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau \theta_l]] \quad (\text{F-CAI1})$$

We get the desired from (F-CAI1)

31. T-CAndE:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : (c\&\tau) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; c; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2, x : \tau \vdash e' : \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{clet } x = e \text{ in } e' : \tau'} \text{ T-CAndE}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2) \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{clet } x = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[\tau' \theta_l]]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall v_f, t < T . (\text{clet } x = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau' \theta_l]]$$

This means given soem $v_f, t < T$ s.t $(\text{clet } x = e \text{ in } e') \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau' \theta_l]] \quad (\text{F-CAE0})$$

From Definition 31 and Definition 21 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2} . p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t

$$(p_{l1}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_1) \theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{l2}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Gamma_2) \theta_l]$$

Similarly we also know that $\exists p_{m1}, p_{m2} . p_{m1} + p_{m2} = p_m$ s.t

$$(p_{m1}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Omega_1) \theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{m2}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{E}[(\Omega_2) \theta_l]$$

IH1

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[c\&\tau \theta_l]]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_1 \implies (p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1 v_1) \in \mathcal{E}[[c\&\tau \theta_l]]$$

Since we know that (clet $x = e$ in e') $\rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-CAndE we know that $\exists v_1, t_1 < t . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_1$. Therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[[c\&\tau \theta_l]]$$

Therefore from Definition 30 we have

$$\cdot \models c\iota \wedge (p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau \theta_l]] \quad (\text{F-CAE1})$$

IH2

$$(p_{l2} + p_{m2} + p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T, e' \rho_m \rho'_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[\tau' \theta_l]]$$

where

$$\rho'_l = \rho_l \cup \{x \mapsto v_1\}$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_2 < T . e' \rho_m \rho'_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f \implies (p_{l2} + p_{m2} + p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau' \theta_l]]$$

Since we know that (clet $x = e$ in e') $\rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-CAndE we know that $\exists t_2 < t . e' \rho'_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_2} v_f$.

Therefore we have

$$(p_{l2} + p_{m2} + p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_2, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau' \theta_l]]$$

Finally from From Lemma 33 we get

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau' \theta_l]]$$

And we are done.

32. T-fix:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta, b; \Delta; x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau[M_a/b]; \ell\Gamma \vdash e : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; .; \ell\Gamma \vdash \text{fix } x . e : \tau[J/b]} \text{ T-fix}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[[\ell\Gamma]]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[[.]]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{fix } x . e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[\tau[J/b] \theta_l]]$

Since $\ell\Gamma$ is only a context of base types, therefore we also have $(0, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[[\ell\Gamma]]$

Similarly since $\Omega = .$, therefore we also have $(0, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[[.]]$

Claim: $\forall n \geq J. (0, T, \text{fix } x . e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[\tau[n/b] \theta_l]]$

We induct on T

Base case, $T = 1$:

It suffices to prove that

$$\forall n \geq J. (0, 1, (\text{fix } x.e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[n/b] \theta_l]$$

This means given some $n \geq J$, from Definition 8 it suffices to prove

$$\forall t < 1. (\text{fix } x.e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v \implies (0, 1 - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[n/b] \theta_l]$$

This further means that given $t < 1$ s.t $(\text{fix } x.e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v$ it suffices to prove that $(0, 1 - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[n/b] \theta_l]$

Since from E-fix we know that minimum value of t can be 1 therefore $t < 1$ is not possible and the goal holds vacuously.

Inductive case:

$$\text{IH: } \forall n \geq J. (0, T - 1, (\text{fix } x.e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[n/b] \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-FX1})$$

$$\text{We need to prove } \forall n \geq J. (0, T, (\text{fix } x.e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[n/b] \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-FX2})$$

This means given some $n \geq J$, from Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T. (\text{fix } x.e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (0, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[n/b] \theta_l]$$

This further means given some $t < T$ s.t $\text{fix } x.e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that $(0, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[n/b] \theta_l]$ (F-FX3)

Using (F-FX1) for the given n from (F-FX2), from IH of outer induction we have

$$(0, T - 1, e \rho'_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[n/b] \theta_l]$$

where $\rho'_m = \rho_m \cup \{x \mapsto \text{fix } x.e \rho_m\}$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t' < T - 1. e \rho'_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} v_f \implies (0, T - 1 - t', v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[n/b] \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $\text{fix } x.e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore from E-fix we know that $\exists t' = t - 1$ s.t $e \rho'_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t'} v_f$

Since $t < T$ therefore $t' = t - 1 < T - 1$ hence we have

$$(0, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[n/b] \theta_l]$$

Therefore we are done. □

Since we have proved

$\forall n \geq J. (0, T, \text{fix } x.e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[n/b] \theta_l]$

Instantiating n with J we have

$(0, T, \text{fix } x.e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[J/b] \theta_l]$

33. T-ret:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau[0/a] \quad \delta_0 = (\{0\}, \{0 \mapsto 1\})}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{return } e : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \tau} \text{T-ret}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l], (p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \text{return } e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$\forall t < T, v_f. (\text{return } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \tau \theta_l]$

It means we are given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(\text{return } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_t v_f$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v_f = (\text{return } e) \rho_m \rho_l$.

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{return } e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it further suffices to prove that

$\forall \kappa', T' < T$.

$(\text{return } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies$

$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$

1) $\forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$
 $\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j))$

2) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$.

a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]]$

b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa$

This means given some $T' < T$ s.t $(\text{return } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^0 (V_d, M_d)$ it suffices to prove that

$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$

1) $\forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$
 $\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j))$

2) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$.

a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]]$

b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa \quad (\text{F-R0})$

III

$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[0/a] \theta_l]$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . (e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_t v \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[0/a] \theta_l]$$

Since we know that (return e) $\rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^0 \nu$ therefore from (E-ret) we know that $\exists t_1 . e \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{t_1} v$ s.t. $\nu = (\{v\}, \{v \mapsto 1\})$ and $T' = t_1 + 1$ (F-R1)

and therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[0/a] \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-R11})$$

Let $\rho' = \{(0, v) \mapsto 1\}$

In order to prove (F-R0) we choose ρ as ρ'

- (a) $\forall i < |C_s| . \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$
 $\forall j < |V_d| . \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j)):$
 Trivial

- (b) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$
 a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d| . \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T, V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]]$
 b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa:$

We choose p_0 as $p_l + p_m$, it suffices to prove that

- $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d| . \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T, V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]]:$

It suffices to prove that $(p_0, T - T', V_d(0)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(0)/a]]$

It further suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - T', v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(0)/a]]$$

We get this directly from (F-R11)

- $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa:$

It suffices to prove that

$$(\rho'(C_s(0), V_d(0)) \cdot p_0) + \kappa' \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa$$

It further suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m) + \kappa' \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa$$

Since we know that $\kappa = \kappa' = 0$ therefore we need to show that

$$(p_l + p_m) \leq p_l + p_m$$

We are done.

34. T-bind:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu_1)} \kappa_1 \tau_1 \\
\Psi; \Theta; a; \Delta; \Omega'; \Gamma_2, x : \tau_1 \vdash e_2 : \mathbb{PC}_{(b \leftarrow \mu_2)} \kappa_2 \tau_2 \\
\kappa \geq \kappa_1 + \sum_{a \in (\pi_1 \mu_1)} ((\pi_2 \mu_1) a) \cdot \kappa_2 a \\
\frac{\mu \geq \mu_1 \otimes a. \mu_2 \quad \Psi; \Theta; c; \Delta, c \in \pi_1(\mu) \vdash \tau_2[\pi_1 c/a][\pi_2 c/b] <: \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega \oplus \sum_{a \leq |\pi_1 \mu_1|} (\pi_2 \mu_1 a) \cdot \Omega'; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{bind } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 : \mathbb{PC}_{(c \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau} \text{T-bind}
\end{array}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2) \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega \oplus \sum_{a \leq |\mu_1|} (\mu_1 a) \Omega') \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{PC}_{(c \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v. (\text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_t v \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(c \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v$ s.t $(\text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_t v$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v = (\text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2 \rho_m \rho_l)$

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2 \rho_m \rho_l)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(c \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$\forall \kappa', T' < T$.

$$(\text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2 \rho_m \rho_l) \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/c]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq (p_l + p_m) + \kappa$$

This means given some $\kappa', T' < T$ s.t $(\text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2 \rho_m \rho_l) \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d)$ and we need to prove that

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/c]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq (p_l + p_m) + \kappa \quad (\text{F-B0})$$

From Definition 31 and Definition 21 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t

$$(p_{l1}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_1)\theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{l2}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_2)\theta_l]$$

Similarly we also know that

$$\exists p_{m1}, p_{m2} \cdot p_{m1} + p_{m2} = p_m \text{ s.t}$$

$$(p_{m1}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega)\theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{m2}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\sum_{a \leq |\pi_1 \mu_1|} (\pi_2 \mu_1 \ a) \cdot \Omega')\theta_l]$$

Also since $(p_{m2}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\sum_{a \leq |\pi_1 \mu_1|} (\pi_2 \mu_1 \ a) \cdot \Omega' \ \theta_l)]$ therefore from Lemma 35 we know that

$$\begin{aligned} & \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|\pi_1 \mu_1| - 1} \\ & \sum_{i < |\pi_1 \mu_1|} [(\pi_2 \mu_1 \ \pi_1 \mu_1(i))/a] \cdot p_i \leq p_{m2} \wedge \\ & \forall 0 \leq i < |\pi_1 \mu_1|. (p_i, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega'[\pi_1 \mu_1(i)/a]] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{F-B0.0})$$

IH1

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T, e_1 \ \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\text{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu_1)} \ \kappa_1 \ \tau_1 \ \theta_l]$$

From Definition 30 it means we have

$$\forall t_1 < T \ . (e_1) \ \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{t_1} v_{m1} \implies (p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, v_{m1}) \in \mathcal{V}[\text{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu_1)} \ \kappa_1 \ \tau_1 \ \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2) \ \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^s v_f$ therefore from E-bind we know that $\exists t_1 < T', v_{m1} \cdot (e_1) \ \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{t_1} v_{m1}$.

Since $t_1 < T' < T$, therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, v_{m1}) \in \mathcal{V}[\text{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu_1)} \ \kappa_1 \ \tau_1 \ \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 we are given that

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall \kappa'_1, t'_1 < T - t_1. \\ & v_{m1} \Downarrow_{t'_1}^{\kappa'_1} (V_{d1}, M_{d1}) \implies \\ & \exists \rho_1 : (C_{s1} \times V_{d1}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]. \\ & 1) \forall i_1 < |C_{s1}| \cdot \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho(C_{s1}(i_1), V_{d1}(j_1)) \leq M_{s1}(C_{s1}(i_1)) \wedge \\ & \quad \forall j_1 < |V_{d1}| \cdot \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \rho(C_{s1}(i_1), V_{d1}(j_1)) \geq M_{d1}(V_{d1}(j_1)) \\ & 2) \exists p_0^1, \dots, p_{|V_{d1}| - 1}^1. \\ & \quad a) \forall i < |C_{s1}|, j < |V_{d1}| \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1}(i), V_{d1}(j)) \neq 0 \implies \\ & \quad \quad (p_j^1, T - t_1 - t'_1, V_{d1}(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1[C_{s1}(i)/a]] \\ & \quad b) (\sum_{i < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1}(i), V_{d1}(j)) \cdot p_j^1) + \kappa'_1 \leq (p_{l1} + p_{m1}) + \kappa_1 \end{aligned}$$

Since we know that $(\text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2) \ \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'} v_f$ therefore from E-bind we know that $\exists t'_1 < T - t_1 \cdot (v_{m1}) \Downarrow_{t'_1}^{\kappa'_1} (V_{d1}, M_{d1})$.

Therefore we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \exists \rho_1 : (C_{s1} \times V_{d1}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]. \\ & 1) \forall i_1 < |C_{s1}| \cdot \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho(C_{s1}(i_1), V_{d1}(j_1)) \leq M_{s1}(C_{s1}(i_1)) \wedge \\ & \quad \forall j_1 < |V_{d1}| \cdot \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \rho(C_{s1}(i_1), V_{d1}(j_1)) \geq M_{d1}(V_{d1}(j_1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2) \exists p_0^1, \dots, p_{|V_{d_1}|-1}^1. \\
a) \forall i < |C_{s_1}|, j < |V_{d_1}| \cdot \rho_1(C_{s_1}(i), V_{d_1}(j)) \neq 0 \implies \\
\quad (p_j^1, T - t_1 - t'_1, V_{d_1}(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1[C_{s_1}(i)/a]] \\
b) (\sum_{i < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d_1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s_1}(i), V_{d_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^1) + \kappa'_1 \leq (p_{l_1} + p_{m_1}) + \kappa_1
\end{aligned} \tag{F-B1}$$

IH2

$$\forall i_1 < |C_{s_1}| \cdot \forall j_1 < |V_{d_1}| \cdot (p_{l_2} + p_{j_1}^1 + p_{i_1}, T - t_1 - t'_1, e_2 \rho_m \cup \rho'_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(b \leftarrow \mu_2)} \kappa_2 \tau_2) \theta l']$$

where

$$l' = l \cup \{a \mapsto C_{s_1}(i_1)\}$$

$$\rho'_l = \rho_l \cup \{x \mapsto V_{d_1}(j_1)\}$$

From Definition 30 it means we have

$$\begin{aligned}
&\forall i_1 < |C_{s_1}| \cdot \forall j_1 < |V_{d_1}| \cdot \\
&\forall t_{2,j_1} < T - t_1 - t'_1 \cdot (e_2) \rho_m \rho'_l \Downarrow_{t_{2,j_1}} v_{m_{2,j_1}} \implies \\
&(p_{l_2} + p_{j_1}^1 + p_{i_1}, T - t_1 - t'_1 - t_{2,j_1}, v_{m_{2,j_1}}) \in \mathcal{V}[(\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(b \leftarrow \mu_2)} \kappa_2 \tau_2) \theta l']
\end{aligned}$$

Since we know that $(\text{bind } e_1 = x \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'} \nu$ therefore from E-bind we know that $\forall i_1 < |C_{s_1}| \cdot \forall j_1 < |V_{d_1}| \cdot \exists t_{2,j_1} < T' - t_1 - t'_1 \cdot (e_2) \rho_m \rho'_l \Downarrow_{t_{2,j_1}} v_{m_{2,j_1}}$.

Therefore we have

$$\begin{aligned}
&\forall i_1 < |C_{s_1}| \cdot \forall j_1 < |V_{d_1}| \cdot \\
&(p_{l_2} + p_{j_1}^1 + p_{i_1}, T - t_1 - t'_1 - t_{2,j_1}, v_{m_{2,j_1}}) \in \mathcal{V}[(\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(b \leftarrow \mu_2)} \kappa_2 \tau_2) \theta l']
\end{aligned}$$

Let $\mu_2 l' = (C_{s_{2,i_1}}, M_{s_{2,i_1}})$. From Definition 30 we are given that

$$\begin{aligned}
&\forall i_1 < |C_{s_1}| \cdot \forall j_1 < |V_{d_1}| \cdot \\
&\forall \kappa'_{2,j_1}, t'_{2,j_1} < T - t_1 - t'_1 - t_{2,j_1} \cdot
\end{aligned}$$

$$v_{m_{2,j_1}} \Downarrow_{t'_{2,j_1}}^{\kappa'_{2,j_1}} (V_{d_{2,j_1}}, M_{d_{2,j_1}}) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho_{2,i_1,j_1} : (C_{s_{2,i_1}} \times V_{d_{2,j_1}}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1) \forall i_2 < |C_{s_{2,i_1}}| \cdot \sum_{j_2 < |V_{d_{2,j_1}}|} \rho(C_{s_{2,i_1}}(i_2), V_{d_{2,j_1}}(j_2)) \leq M_{s_{2,i_1}}(C_{s_{2,i_1}}(i_2)) \wedge \\
\quad \forall j_2 < |V_{d_{2,j_1}}| \cdot \sum_{i_2 < |C_{s_{2,i_1}}|} \rho(C_{s_{2,i_1}}(i_2), V_{d_{2,j_1}}(j_2)) \geq M_{d_{2,j_1}}(V_{d_{2,j_1}}(j_2))
\end{aligned}$$

$$2) \exists p_0^{2,j_1}, \dots, p_{|V_{d_{2,j_1}}|-1}^{2,j_1}.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
a) \forall i < |C_{s_{2,i_1}}|, j < |V_{d_{2,j_1}}| \cdot \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s_{2,i_1}}(i), V_{d_{2,j_1}}(j)) \neq 0 \implies \\
\quad (p_j^{2,j_1}, T - t_1 - t'_1 - t'_{2,j_1}, V_{d_{2,j_1}}(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_2[C_{s_{2,i_1}}(i)/b]) \theta l']
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
b) \left(\sum_{i < |C_{s_{2,i_1}}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d_{2,j_1}}|} \cdot \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s_{2,i_1}}(i), V_{d_{2,j_1}}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2,j_1} \leq \\
p_{l_2} + p_{j_1}^1 + p_{i_1} + \kappa_2 l'
\end{aligned}$$

Since we know that (bind $e_1 = x$ in e_2) $\rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} v_f$ therefore from E-bind we know that $\forall i_1 < |C_{s1}| \cdot \forall j_1 < |V_{d1}|$.
 $\exists t'_{2,j_1} < (T' - t_1 - t'_1 - t_{2,j_1}), \kappa'_{2,j_1}$ s.t.
 $v_{m_{2,j_1}} \Downarrow_{t'_{2,j_1}}^{\kappa'_{2,j_1}} (V_{d_{2,j_1}}, M_{d_{2,j_1}})$.

This means we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \forall i_1 < |C_{s1}| \cdot \forall j_1 < |V_{d1}|. \\
& \exists \rho_{2,i_1,j_1} : (C_{s_{2,i_1}} \times V_{d_{2,j_1}}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]. \\
& 1) \forall i_2 < |C_{s_{2,i_1}}| \cdot \sum_{j_2 < |V_{d_{2,j_1}}|} \rho(C_{s_{2,i_1}}(i_2), V_{d_{2,j_1}}(j_2)) \leq M_{s_{2,i_1}}(C_{s_{2,i_1}}(i_2)) \wedge \\
& \quad \forall j_2 < |V_{d_{2,j_1}}| \cdot \sum_{i_2 < |C_{s_{2,i_1}}|} \rho(C_{s_{2,i_1}}(i_2), V_{d_{2,j_1}}(j_2)) \geq M_{d_{2,j_1}}(V_{d_{2,j_1}}(j_2)) \\
& 2) \exists p_0^{2,j_1}, \dots, p_{|V_{d_{2,j_1}}|-1}^{2,j_1}. \\
& \quad a) \forall i < |C_{s_{2,i_1}}|, j < |V_{d_{2,j_1}}| \cdot \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s_{2,i_1}}(i), V_{d_{2,j_1}}(j)) \neq 0 \implies \\
& \quad \quad (p_j^{2,j_1}, T - t_1 - t'_1 - t'_{2,j_1}, V_{d_{2,j_1}}(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_2[C_{s_{2,i_1}}(i)/b]) \theta l'] \\
& \quad b) \left(\sum_{i < |C_{s_{2,i_1}}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d_{2,j_1}}|} \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s_{2,i_1}}(i), V_{d_{2,j_1}}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2,j_1} \leq \\
& \quad p_{l_2} + p_{j_1}^1 + p_{i_1} + \kappa_2 l' \tag{F-B2}
\end{aligned}$$

We know that $(C_s, M_s) = (\mu_1 \otimes a.\mu_2)$, $(V_d, M_d) = \mathbb{M}_2(\nu_1 \otimes a.\nu_2)$

This means from Definition 25 we have

$$\begin{aligned}
C_s & \triangleq \{(c_1, c_2) \mid c_1 \in C_{s1}, c_2 \in C_{s2}[i/a]\} \\
M_s & \triangleq \{(c_1, c_2) \mapsto (M_{s1} c_1 \cdot M_{s2}[c_1/a] c_2) \mid c_1 \in C_{s1}, c_2 \in C_{s2}[c_1/a]\} \tag{F-B3}
\end{aligned}$$

Let $(V'_d, M'_d) = (\nu_1 \otimes a.\nu_2)$, from Definition 24 we know that

$$\begin{aligned}
V'_d & \triangleq \{(v_1, v_2) \mid v_1 \in V_{d1}, v_2 \in V_{d2}[v_1/a]\} \triangleq \sum V_{d1} V_{d2} \\
M'_d & \triangleq \{(v_1, v_2) \mapsto (M_{d1} v_1 \cdot M_2[v_1/a] v_2) \mid v_1 \in V_{d1}, v_2 \in V_{d2}[v_1/a]\} \tag{F-B4.1}
\end{aligned}$$

This means from Definition 26 we have

$$\begin{aligned}
V_d & \triangleq \{v_2 \mid v_1 \in V_{d1}, v_2 \in V_{d2}[v_1/a]\} \\
M_d & \triangleq \{v_2 \mapsto \sum_{v_1 \in \{v' \mid v' \in V_{d1}, v_2 \in V_{d2}[v'/a]\}} (M_{d1} v_1 \cdot M_{d2}[v_1/a] v_2) \mid v_2 \in V_d\} \tag{F-B4}
\end{aligned}$$

In order to prove (F-B0) we need to find a $\rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]$.

We define

$$\rho' \triangleq \{((c_1, c_2), v_2) \mapsto \sum_{v_1 \in \{v' \mid v' \in V_{d1}, v_2 \in V_{d2}[v'/a]\}} (\rho_1 c_1 v_1) \cdot (\rho_{2,c_1,v_1} c_2 v_2) \mid (c_1, c_2) \in C_s, v_2 \in V_d\} \tag{F-B5}$$

We also define

$$\rho'' \triangleq \{((c_1, c_2), (v'_1, v'_2)) \mapsto (\rho_1 \ c_1 \ v'_1) \cdot (\rho_{2,c_1,v'_1} \ c_2 \ v'_2) \mid (c_1, c_2) \in C_s \wedge (v'_1, v'_2) \in V'_d\}$$

(F-B6)

We choose this ρ' as the required ρ

$$1) \ \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j)):$$

To prove: $\forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i))$

This means given some $i < |C_s|$ it suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i))$$

Let $C_s(i) = (c_1, c_2)$, from (F-B3) it further suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'((c_1, c_2), V_d(j)) \leq M_{s1} \ c_1 \cdot M_{s2}[c_1/a] \ c_2$$

From (F-B5) it further suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{j < |V_d|} \sum_{k < |S_1|} (\rho_1 \ c_1 \ (V_{d1}(k))) \cdot (\rho_{2,i,k} \ c_2 \ V_d(j)) \leq M_{s1} \ c_1 \cdot M_{s2}[c_1/a] \ c_2$$

where

$$S_1 = \{v' \mid v' \in V_{d1}, v \in V_{d2}[v'/a]\}$$

From (F-B4) we have

$$\sum_{k < |V_{d1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2}[V_{d1}(k)/a]|} (\rho_1 \ c_1 \ (V_{d1}(k))) \cdot (\rho_{2,i,k} \ c_2 \ V_d(j)) \leq M_{s1} \ c_1 \cdot M_{s2}[c_1/a] \ c_2$$

Simplifying

$$\sum_{k < |V_{d1}|} (\rho_1 \ c_1 \ (V_{d1}(k))) \cdot \sum_{j < |V_{d2}[V_{d1}(k)/a]|} (\rho_{2,i,k} \ c_2 \ V_d(j)) \leq M_{s1} \ c_1 \cdot M_{s2}[c_1/a] \ c_2$$

We get the desired from (F-B1) and (F-B2)

To prove: $\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j))$

This means given some $j < |V_d|$ it suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j))$$

This means from (F-B5) we need to prove that

$$\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{k < |V_{d1}|} (\rho_1 \ c_1 \ V_{d1}(k)) \cdot (\rho_{2,c_1,V_{d1}(k)} \ c_2 \ V_d(j)) \geq$$

$$\sum_{k < |V_{d1}|} (M_{d1} V_{d1}(k)) \cdot (M_{d2,V_{d1}(k)} V_d(j))$$

where $C_s(i) = (c_1, c_2)$

It further suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{k < |V_{d1}|} \sum_{i < |C_s|} (\rho_1 \ c_1 \ V_{d1}(k)) \cdot (\rho_{2,c_1,V_{d1}(k)} \ c_2 \ V_d(j)) \geq$$

$$\sum_{k < |V_{d1}|} (M_{d1} V_{d1}(k)) \cdot (M_{d2,V_{d1}(k)} V_d(j))$$

where $C_s(i) = (c_1, c_2)$

We get the desired by taking the marginal over V_{d1} on both sides of the Claim proved below.

Claim:

$$\forall j < |V'_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \cdot (\rho_1 \ c_1 \ v_1) \cdot (\rho_{2,c_1,v_1} \ c_2 \ v_2) \geq M'_d(V'_d(j))$$

where $C_s(i) = (c_1, c_2)$ and $V'_d(j) = (v_1, v_2)$

Proof

This means given some $j < |V'_d|$, it suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{i < |C_s|} \cdot (\rho_1 \ c_1 \ v_1) \cdot (\rho_{2,c_1,v_1} \ c_2 \ v_2) \geq M'_d(V'_d(j))$$

This means from (F-B4.1) it suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{i < |C_s|} \cdot (\rho_1 \ c_1 \ v_1) \cdot (\rho_{2,c_1,v_1} \ c_2 \ v_2) \geq (M_{d1} v_1) \cdot (M_{d2,v_1} v_2)$$

where $C_s(i) = (c_1, c_2)$ and $V'_d(j) = (v_1, v_2)$

From (F-B3), it further suffices to prove that

$$\sum_{i1 < |C_{s1}|} \cdot \sum_{i2 < |C_{s2,i1}|} \cdot (\rho_1 \ c_1 \ v_1) \cdot (\rho_{2,c_1,v_1} \ c_2 \ v_2) \geq (M_{d1} v_1) \cdot (M_{d2,v_1} v_2)$$

where $C_{s1}(i1) = c_1$, $C_{s2,i1}(i2) = c_2$ and $V'_d(j) = (v_1, v_2)$

This means we need to prove

$$\sum_{i1 < |C_{s1}|} \cdot (\rho_1 \ c_1 \ v_1) \cdot \sum_{i2 < |C_{s2,i1}|} \cdot (\rho_{2,c_1,v_1} \ c_2 \ v_2) \geq (M_{d1} v_1) \cdot (M_{d2,v_1} v_2)$$

where $C_{s1}(i1) = c_1$, $C_{s2,i1}(i2) = c_2$ and $V'_d(j) = (v_1, v_2)$

We get this directly from (F-B1) and (F-B2)

□

- 2) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$.
- a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/c]]$
 - b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa$:

From (F-B2) we know that $\forall i1 < |C_{s1}|$ and $\forall j1 < |V_{d1}|$, $\exists p_0^{2,j1}, \dots, p_{|V_{d2,j1}|-1}^{2,j1}$.

We choose these potentials as $p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$

To prove:

$$\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/c]]$$

This means given $i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|$ s.t. $\rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0$, we need to prove that

$$(p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/c]]$$

Let $C_s(i) = (c_1, c_2)$ and $V_d(j) = v_2$.

From Definition 30 and (F-B3) we know that

$$\exists i_{c1}, i_{c2} \text{ s.t. } C_{s1} \ i_{c1} = c_1 \text{ and } C_{s2}[c_1/a] \ i_{c2} = c_2$$

Similarly from Definition 30 and (F-B4) we know that

$$\exists j_{v1}, j_{v2}, v_1 \text{ s.t. } V_{d1} j_{v1} = v_1 \text{ and } V_{d2}[v_1/a] j_{v2} = v_2$$

We need to prove that

$$(p_{j_{v2}}^{2,j_{v1}}, T - T', v_2) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[(c_1, c_2)/c]]$$

Also since $\rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0$, therefore from (F-B5) we know that

$$\rho_{j_{v2}}^{2,j_{v1}}(c_2, v_2) \neq 0$$

Therefore from (F-B2) we know that

$$(p_{j_{v2}}^{2,j_{v1}}, T - t_1 - t'_1 - t'_{2,j_1}, v_2) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2[c_2/b] \ell']$$

We get the desired using monotonicity (Lemma 33) and subtyping (Lemma 37)

To prove:

$$\left(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j \right) + \kappa' \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa$$

From (F-B2) we know that

$$\forall i_1 < |C_{s1}|. \forall j_1 < |V_{d1}|.$$

$$\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2,j_1} \leq p_{l2} + p_{j_1}^1 + p_{i_1} + \kappa_2 \ell'$$

Taking expectation over ρ_1

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2,j_1} \right) \\ & \leq \\ & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \left(p_{l2} + p_{j_1}^1 + p_{i_1} + \kappa_2 \ell' \right) \end{aligned}$$

Add κ'_1 to both sides

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_1 \\ & \leq \\ & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \left(p_{l2} + p_{j_1}^1 + p_{i_1} + \kappa_2 \ell' \right) + \kappa'_1 \end{aligned}$$

Expanding RHS

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1} i_1)(V_{d1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_1 \\ & \leq \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s_1} i_1)(V_{d_1} j_1) \cdot p_{l_2} + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s_1} i_1)(V_{d_1} j_1) \cdot \\ & p_{j_1}^1 + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s_1} i_1)(V_{d_1} j_1) \cdot p_{i_1} + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s_1} i_1)(V_{d_1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \kappa_2 l' + \kappa_1' \end{aligned}$$

Simplifying RHS

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} i_1)(V_{d_1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s_2, i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d_2, j_1}|} \cdot \rho_{2, i_1, j_1}(C_{s_2, i_1}(i), V_{d_2, j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2, j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2, j_1} \right) + \kappa_1' \\ & \leq \\ & p_{l_2} + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} i_1, V_{d_1} j_1) \cdot p_{j_1}^1 + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} i_1, V_{d_1} j_1) \cdot \\ & p_{i_1} + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s_1} i_1)(V_{d_1} j_1) \cdot \kappa_2 l' + \kappa_1' \end{aligned}$$

Since from (F-B1) we know that $(\sum_{i < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d_1}|} \cdot \rho_1(C_{s_1}(i), V_{d_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^1) + \kappa_1' \leq (p_{l_1} + p_{m_1}) + \kappa_1$, therefore we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} i_1)(V_{d_1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s_2, i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d_2, j_1}|} \cdot \rho_{2, i_1, j_1}(C_{s_2, i_1}(i), V_{d_2, j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2, j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2, j_1} \right) + \kappa_1' \\ & \leq \\ & p_{l_2} + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} i_1, V_{d_1} j_1) \cdot p_{i_1} + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} i_1)(V_{d_1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \kappa_2 l' + (p_{l_1} + p_{m_1}) + \kappa_1 \end{aligned}$$

Rearranging terms on the right

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} i_1)(V_{d_1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s_2, i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d_2, j_1}|} \cdot \rho_{2, i_1, j_1}(C_{s_2, i_1}(i), V_{d_2, j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2, j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2, j_1} \right) + \kappa_1' \\ & \leq \\ & p_{l_1} + p_{l_2} + p_{m_1} + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} i_1, V_{d_1} j_1) \cdot p_{i_1} + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} i_1)(V_{d_1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \kappa_2 l' + \kappa_1 \end{aligned}$$

Rewriting

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} i_1)(V_{d_1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s_2, i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d_2, j_1}|} \cdot \rho_{2, i_1, j_1}(C_{s_2, i_1}(i), V_{d_2, j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2, j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2, j_1} \right) + \kappa_1' \\ & \leq \\ & p_{l_1} + p_{l_2} + p_{m_1} + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} i_1, V_{d_1} j_1) \cdot p_{i_1} + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} (\sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} i_1)(V_{d_1} j_1)) \cdot \\ & (\kappa_2 l') + \kappa_1 \end{aligned}$$

Simplifying using (1) in the monadic case of Definition 30

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s_1} i_1)(V_{d_1} j_1) \cdot \\ & \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s_2, i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d_2, j_1}|} \cdot \rho_{2, i_1, j_1}(C_{s_2, i_1}(i), V_{d_2, j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2, j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2, j_1} \right) + \kappa_1' \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq \\ p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1} \ i_1, V_{d1} \ j_1) \cdot p_{i_1} + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} M_{s1}(C_{s1} \ i_1) \cdot \\ \kappa_2 \ l' + \kappa_1$$

Using T-bind we can further simplify it to

$$\sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1} \ i_1)(V_{d1} \ j_1) \cdot \\ \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \cdot \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_1 \\ \leq \\ p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1} \ i_1, V_{d1} \ j_1) \cdot p_{i_1} + \kappa$$

Simplifying further using (F-B0.0) we get

$$\sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1} \ i_1)(V_{d1} \ j_1) \cdot \\ \left(\left(\sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_{2,j_1} \right) + \kappa'_1 \\ \leq \\ p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2} + \kappa$$

Simplifying on the LHS

$$\left(\sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1} \ i_1)(V_{d1} \ j_1) \cdot \sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) \\ + \left(\sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1} \ i_1)(V_{d1} \ j_1) \cdot \kappa'_{2,j_1} \right) \\ + \kappa'_1 \\ \leq \\ p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2} + \kappa$$

Rewriting on the LHS (swapping the summation in the second summand)

$$\left(\sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1} \ i_1)(V_{d1} \ j_1) \cdot \sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) \\ + \left(\sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1} \ i_1)(V_{d1} \ j_1) \cdot \kappa'_{2,j_1} \right) \\ + \kappa'_1 \\ \leq \\ p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2} + \kappa$$

Using Definition 30 (on the second summand)

$$\left(\sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1} \ i_1)(V_{d1} \ j_1) \cdot \sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) \\ + \left(\sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} M_{d1}(V_{d1} \ j_1) \cdot \kappa'_{2,j_1} \right) \\ + \kappa'_1 \\ \leq$$

$$p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2} + \kappa$$

Using the cost inequality from the T-bind typing rule

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1} \ i_1)(V_{d1} \ j_1) \cdot \sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) \\ & + \kappa' \\ & \leq \\ & p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2} + \kappa \end{aligned}$$

Rewriting

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{i < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j_1 < |V_{d1}|} \sum_{j < |V_{d2,j_1}|} \rho_1(C_{s1} \ i_1)(V_{d1} \ j_1) \cdot \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) \\ & + \kappa' \\ & \leq \\ & p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2} + \kappa \end{aligned}$$

Rewriting

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\sum_{i_1 < |C_{s1}|} \sum_{i_2 < |C_{s2,i_1}|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \sum_{j_1 < |S1|} \rho_1(C_{s1} \ i_1)(V_{d1} \ j_1) \cdot \rho_{2,i_1,j_1}(C_{s2,i_1}(i_2), V_{d2,j_1}(j)) \cdot p_j^{2,j_1} \right) \\ & + \kappa' \\ & \leq \\ & p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2} + \kappa \end{aligned}$$

where

$$S1 = \{v' \mid v' \in V_{d1}, v \in V_{d2}[v'/a]\}$$

Rewriting

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'((c_1, c_2), v) \cdot p_j \right) + \kappa' \\ & \leq \\ & p_{l1} + p_{l2} + p_{m1} + p_{m2} + \kappa \end{aligned}$$

where

$$(c_1, c_2) = C_s \ i$$

$$v = V_d \ j$$

35. T-store:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau[0/a] \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa : \mathbb{R}^+ \quad \delta_0 = (\{0\}, \{0 \mapsto 1\})}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{store } e : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \ \kappa \ ([\kappa] \ \tau)} \text{ T-store}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \text{store } e \ \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \ \kappa \ ([\kappa] \ \tau) \ \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v. (\text{store } e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa ([\kappa] \tau) \theta_l]$$

This means we are given some $t < T, v$ s.t. $(\text{store } e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v = (\text{store } e) \rho_m \rho_l$

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{store } e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa ([\kappa] \tau) \theta_l]$$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall \kappa', T' < T .$$

$$(\text{store } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|, \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|, \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|, \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[[[\kappa] \tau][C_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa$$

This means given some $T' < T$ s.t. $(\text{store } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d)$. Also, from e-store we know that $\kappa' = 0$. It suffices to prove that

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|, \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|, \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|, \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[[[\kappa] \tau][C_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) \leq p + \kappa \quad (\text{F-S0})$$

III

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[0/a] \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . (e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[0/a] \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{store } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^0 \nu$ therefore from (E-ret) we know that $\exists t_1. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v$ s.t. $\nu = (\{v\}, \{v \mapsto 1\})$ and $T' = t_1 + 1$ (F-S1)

and therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[0/a] \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-S11})$$

$$\text{Let } \rho' = \{(0, v) \mapsto 1\}$$

In order to prove (F-S0) we choose ρ as ρ'

- (a) $\forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$
 $\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j)):$
 Trivial

- (b) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$

a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in$
 $\mathcal{V}[[[\kappa] \tau][C_s(i)/a]]$

b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa:$

We choose p_0 as $p_l + p_m + \kappa$, it suffices to prove that

- $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in$
 $\mathcal{V}[[[\kappa] \tau][C_s(i)/a]]:$

It suffices to prove that $(p_l + p_m + \kappa, T - T', V_d(0)) \in \mathcal{V}[[[\kappa] \tau][C_s(0)/a]]$

From Definition 30 it further suffices to prove that

$$\exists p'. p' + \kappa \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa \wedge (p', T - T', v) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau][0/a]]$$

We choose p' as $p_l + p_m$. It suffices to prove that

$$- p_l + p_m + \kappa \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa:$$

Trivial

$$- (p_l + p_m, T - T', v) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau][0/a]]$$

We get this directly from (F-S11) and Lemma 33

- $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) \leq p + \kappa:$

It suffices to prove that

$$(\rho'(C_s(0), V_d(0)) \cdot p_0) \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa$$

It further suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m) \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa$$

Trivial.

36. T-release:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : [\kappa] \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2, x : \tau \vdash e_2 : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} (\kappa + \kappa') \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa' \tau'} \text{ T-release}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2)\theta_l], (p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2) \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa' \tau' \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v. (\text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa' \tau' \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v$ s.t $(\text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v = (\text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \rho_m \rho_l)$

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa' \tau' \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall \kappa'', T' < T.$$

$$((\text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l) \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa''} (V_d, M_d) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies \\ (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau'[C_s(i)/c]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq (p_l + p_m) + \kappa'$$

This means given some $\kappa'', T' < T$ s.t $((\text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l) \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa''} (V_d, M_d)$ and we need to prove that

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies \\ (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau'[C_s(i)/c]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq (p_l + p_m) + \kappa' \quad (\text{F-R0})$$

From Definition 31 and Definition 21 we know that $\exists p_{l1}, p_{l2}. p_{l1} + p_{l2} = p_l$ s.t

$$(p_{l1}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_1)\theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{l2}, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Gamma_2)\theta_l]$$

Similarly we also know that

$$\exists p_{m1}, p_{m2}. p_{m1} + p_{m2} = p_m \text{ s.t}$$

$$(p_{m1}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_1)\theta_l] \text{ and } (p_{m2}, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[(\Omega_2)\theta_l]$$

IH1

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T, e_1 \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[\kappa] \tau \theta_l]$$

From Definition 30 it means we have

$$\forall t_1 < T. (e_1) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_1 \implies (p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[[\kappa] \tau \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{release } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa''} v_f$ therefore from E-release we know that $\exists t_1 < T', v_1. (e_1) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v_1$.

Since $t_1 < T' < T$, therefore we have

$$(p_{l1} + p_{m1}, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[[[\kappa] \tau] \theta l]$$

This means from Definition 30 we are given that

$$\exists p'_1 \cdot p'_1 + \kappa \leq p_{l1} + p_{m1} \wedge (p'_1, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau_1]] \quad (\text{F-R1})$$

IH2

$$(p_{l2} + p'_1 + p_{m2}, T - t_1, e_2 \rho_m \rho_l \cup \{x \mapsto v_1\}) \in \mathcal{E}[[\text{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} (\kappa + \kappa') \tau' \theta l]]$$

From Definition 30 it means we have

$$\forall t_2 < T - t_1 \cdot (e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \cup \{x \mapsto v_1\} \downarrow_{t_2} v_{m2} \implies (p_{l2} + p_{m2} + p'_1, T - t_1 - t_2, v_{m2}) \in \mathcal{V}[[\text{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} (\kappa + \kappa') \tau' \theta l]]$$

Since we know that (release $x = e_1$ in e_2) $\rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa''} v_f$ therefore from E-release we know that $\exists t_2 < T' - t_1 < T - t_1 \cdot (e_2) \rho_m \rho_l \cup \{x \mapsto v_1\} \downarrow_{t_2} v_{m2}$. This means we have

$$(p_{l2} + p_{m2} + p'_1, T - t_1 - t_2, v_{m2}) \in \mathcal{V}[[\text{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} (\kappa + \kappa') \tau' \theta l]]$$

This means from Definition 30 we are given that

$$\forall \kappa_2, t'_2 < T - t_1 - t_2.$$

$$v_{m2} \Downarrow_{t'_2}^{\kappa_2} (V_d, M_d) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho' : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s| \cdot \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \forall j < |V_d| \cdot \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p'_0, \dots, p'_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d| \cdot \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p'_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau'[C_s(i)/a]]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa_2 \leq (p_{l2} + p_{m2} + p'_1) + (\kappa + \kappa')$$

Since we know that (release $x = e_1$ in e_2) $\rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} \nu$ therefore from E-release we know that $\exists t'_2, \kappa_2 \cdot v_{m2} \Downarrow_{t'_2}^{\kappa_2} (V_d, M_d)$ s.t. $t'_2 = T' - t_1 - t_2 - 1$ and $\kappa_2 = \kappa''$

Since $t'_2 = T' - t_1 - t_2 < T - t_1 - t_2$, therefore we have

$$\exists \rho' : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s| \cdot \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \forall j < |V_d| \cdot \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p'_0, \dots, p'_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d| \cdot \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p'_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau'[C_s(i)/a]]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa_2 \leq (p_{l2} + p_{m2} + p'_1) + (\kappa + \kappa') \quad (\text{F-R2})$$

In order to prove (F-R0) we choose ρ as ρ' . It suffices to prove that

- $\forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$
 $\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j)):$
 Directly from (F-R2)
- $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$
 - a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in$
 $\mathcal{V}[\tau'[C_s(i)/c]]$
 - b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq (p_l + p_m) + \kappa':$

We choose $p'_0, \dots, p'_{|V_d|-1}$ as $p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$

– Proof of (a)

Given: $i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|$ s.t $\rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0$

To prove: $(p'_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau'[C_s(i)/c]]$

Directly from (F-R2)

– Proof of (b)

From (F-R2) we are given that

$$(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa'' \leq (p_{l2} + p_{m2} + p'_1) + (\kappa + \kappa')$$

Since from (F-R1) we know that $p'_1 + \kappa \leq p_{l1} + p_{m1}$ therefore we have

$$(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa'' \leq p_{l2} + p_{m2} + p_{l1} + p_{m1} + \kappa'$$

Simplifying we get

$$(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa'' \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa'$$

We are done.

37. T-tick:

$$\frac{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa : \mathbb{R}^+ \quad \delta_0 = (\{0\}, \{0 \mapsto 1\})}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \uparrow^\kappa : \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa \mathbf{1}} \text{ T-tick}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l], (p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l, T, \uparrow^\kappa \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa \mathbf{1} \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v. (\uparrow^\kappa \rho_m \rho_l) \downarrow_t v \implies (p_l, T - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[(\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa \mathbf{1}) \theta_l]$$

This means we are given some $t < T, v$ s.t $(\uparrow^\kappa \rho_m \rho_l) \downarrow_t v$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v = \uparrow^\kappa$

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l, T, (\uparrow^\kappa \rho_m \rho_l)) \in \mathcal{V}[(\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa \mathbf{1}) \theta_l]$$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

- $\forall \kappa', t' < T$.
- $(\uparrow^\kappa) \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies$
- $\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]$.
- 1) $\forall i < |C_s| \cdot \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$
 $\forall j < |V_d| \cdot \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j))$
 - 2) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$.
 - a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d| \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{1}[C_s(i)/a]]$
 - b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa$

This means we are given some $T' < T$ s.t. $(\uparrow^\kappa) \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d)$ it suffices to prove that

- $\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]$.
- 1) $\forall i < |C_s| \cdot \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$
 $\forall j < |V_d| \cdot \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j))$
 - 2) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$.
 - a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d| \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{1}[C_s(i)/a]]$
 - b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa$ (F-T0)

From E-tick we know that $\kappa' = \kappa$ and $(V_d, M_d) = (\{()\}, \{() \mapsto 1\})$

Let $\rho' = \{(0, ()) \mapsto 1\}$

In order to prove (F-T0) we choose ρ as ρ'

- (a) $\forall i < |C_s| \cdot \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$
 $\forall j < |V_d| \cdot \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j)):$
 Trivial
- (b) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$.
 - a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d| \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in$
 $\mathcal{V}[\mathbf{1}[C_s(i)/a]]$
 - b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa:$

We choose p_0 as $p_l + p_m$, it suffices to prove that

- $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d| \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in$
 $\mathcal{V}[\mathbf{1}[C_s(i)/a]]:$

It suffices to prove that $(p_0, T - T', V_d(0)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{1}[C_s(0)/a]]$

It further suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - T', ()) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{1}]$$

We get this directly from Definition 30

- $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa:$

It suffices to prove that

$$(\rho'(C_s(0), V_d(0)) \cdot p_0) + \kappa \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa$$

It further suffices to prove that
 $(p_l + p_m) + \kappa \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa$

Trivial.

38. T-split:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : [p] \mathbf{1} \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash p \geq p_1 + p_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{Split } e : ([p_1] \mathbf{1} \times [p_2] \mathbf{1})} \text{T-split}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \text{Split } e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[[p_1] \mathbf{1} \times [p_2] \mathbf{1}] \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall T' < T, v'. \text{Split } e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{T'} v' \implies (p_l + p_m, T - T', v') \in \mathcal{V}[[[p_1] \mathbf{1} \times [p_2] \mathbf{1}] \theta_l]$$

This means given some $T' < T, v'$ s.t. $\text{Split } e \downarrow_{T'} v'$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - T', v') \in \mathcal{V}[[[p_1] \mathbf{1} \times [p_2] \mathbf{1}] \theta_l]$$

From (E-split) we know that $v' = \langle\langle(), ()\rangle\rangle$, therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - T', \langle\langle(), ()\rangle\rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[[[p_1] \mathbf{1} \times [p_2] \mathbf{1}] \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists p'_1, p'_2. p'_1 + p'_2 \leq p_l + p_m \wedge (p'_1, T, ()) \in \mathcal{V}[[[p_1] \mathbf{1}]] \wedge (p_2, T, ()) \in \mathcal{V}[[[p_2] \mathbf{1}]] \quad (\text{F-S0})$$

IH

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[[p] \mathbf{1}] \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall T'' < T, v''. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{T''} v'' \implies (p_l + p_m, T - T'', v'') \in \mathcal{V}[[[p] \mathbf{1}] \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $\text{Split } e \downarrow_{T'} \langle\langle(), ()\rangle\rangle$, therefore from E-split we know that

$$\exists t'. e \downarrow_{t'} \langle\langle(), ()\rangle\rangle \text{ s.t. } T' = t' + 1$$

$$\text{Therefore we have } (p_l + p_m, T - T'', v'') \in \mathcal{V}[[[p] \mathbf{1}] \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\exists p'. p' + p \leq p_l + p_m \wedge (p', T, ()) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{1}]$$

Since from T-split we know that $p \geq p_1 + p_2$ therefore we also know that

$$p_l + p_m \geq p_1 + p_2 \quad (\text{F-S1})$$

In order to prove (F-S0) we choose p_1 for p'_1 and p_2 for p'_2 . It suffices to prove

- $p_1 + p_2 \leq p_l + p_m$:
From (F-S1)
- $(p_1, T, ()) \in \mathcal{V}[[p_1] \mathbf{1}]$:
Directly from Definition 30
- $(p_2, T, ()) \in \mathcal{V}[[p_2] \mathbf{1}]$:
Directly from Definition 30

39. T-toDist:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(p \ i) \quad \Theta; \Delta \models n > 0 \quad \mu = (\{0 \dots n-1\}, \{i \mapsto p \ i \mid i < n\}) \quad \sum_{i < n} p \ i = 1 \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash p : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{toDist } e : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(i \leftarrow \mu)} \mathbf{0} \ \mathbf{N}(i)} \text{ T-toDist}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[[\Gamma \theta_l]]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[[\Omega \theta_l]]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \text{toDist } e \ \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \mathbf{0} \ \mathbf{N}(i) \ \theta_l]]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\text{toDist } e) \ \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \mathbf{0} \ \mathbf{N}(i) \ \theta_l]]$$

It means we are given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t. $(\text{toDist } e) \ \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_t v_f$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v_f = (\text{toDist } e) \ \rho_m \rho_l$.

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{toDist } e) \ \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \mathbf{0} \ \mathbf{N}(i) \ \theta_l]]$$

From Definition 30 it further suffices to prove that

$$\forall \kappa', t' < T.$$

$$(\text{toDist } e) \ \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/a]]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p_l + p_m$$

This means given some $T' < T$ s.t. $(\text{toDist } e) \ \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^0 (V_d, M_d)$ it suffices to prove that

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j))$$

- 2) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$.
a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/a]]$
b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) \leq p_l + p_m$ (F-TD0)

IH

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbf{L}_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(p \ i) \ \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T. (e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{L}_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(p \ i) \ \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{toDist } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^0 (V_d, M_d)$ therefore from (E-toDist) we know that $\exists t_1. e \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{t_1} l s$ s.t. $V_d = (\{0 \dots |l s| - 1\}, M_d = \{i \mapsto l s!! i \mid i \in V_d\})$ and $T' = t_1 + 1$ (F-R1)

$$\text{and therefore we have } (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, l s) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{L}_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(p \ i) \ \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-R11})$$

Also since $n > 0$ therefore from Definition 30 we know that

$$\exists p'_0 \dots p'_{n-1} \text{ s.t.}$$

$$p'_0 + \dots + p'_{n-1} \leq p_l + p_m \text{ and}$$

$$(p'_0, T - t_1, v_0) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{R}(p \ 0) \ \theta_l]$$

...

$$(p'_{n-1}, T - t_1, v_{n-1}) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{R}(p \ (n - 1)) \ \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-TD1})$$

where

$$l s = v_0 :: \dots :: v_{n-1}$$

We know that

$$C_s = V_d = \{0 \dots n - 1\} \text{ and } M_s = M_d = \{i \mapsto p \ i \mid i < n\}$$

Let ρ' be the diagonal coupling s.t.

$$\begin{aligned} \rho'(i, j) &= M_s(C_s(i)) \quad \text{when } i = j \\ \rho'(i, j) &= 0 \quad \text{otherwise} \end{aligned}$$

In order to prove (F-R0) we choose ρ as ρ'

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(a)} \quad &\forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\ &\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j)): \\ &\text{Trivial} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{(b)} \quad \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \quad \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T, V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) \quad (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa:$$

We choose $p'_0 \dots p'_{n-1}$ as the required potentials, it suffices to prove that

- $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p'_j, T, V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/i]]$:
 Given some $i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|$ s.t. $\rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0$
 It suffices to prove that $(p'_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/i]]$
 Directly from Definition 30 (nat case)
- $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) \leq p_l + p_m$:
 We get the desired from (F-TD1) and the chosen coupling.

40. T-unif:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \mathbf{N}(n) \quad \mu = (\{0, \dots, n\}, \{i \mapsto \frac{1}{n+1} \mid i < n+1\})}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{Unif } e : \mathbb{P}\mathbf{C}_{(i \leftarrow \mu)} \mathbf{0} \mathbf{N}(i)} \text{ T-Unif}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, \text{Unif } e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{P}\mathbf{C}_{(i \leftarrow \mu)} \mathbf{0} \mathbf{N}(i) \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\text{Unif } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{P}\mathbf{C}_{(i \leftarrow \mu)} \mathbf{0} \mathbf{N}(i) \theta_l]$$

It means we are given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(\text{Unif } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_t v_f$. From E-val we know that $t = 0$ and $v_f = (\text{Unif } e) \rho_m \rho_l$.

Therefore it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{Unif } e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{P}\mathbf{C}_{(i \leftarrow \mu)} \mathbf{0} \mathbf{N}(i) \theta_l]$$

From Definition 30 it further suffices to prove that

$$\forall \kappa', t' < T.$$

$$(\text{Unif } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies$$

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$$

$$\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

$$a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/a]]$$

$$b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p_l + p_m$$

This means given some $T' < T$ s.t $(\text{Unif } e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^0 (V_d, M_d)$ it suffices to prove that

$$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1].$$

$$1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$$

$$\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$$

$$2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$$

- a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/a]]$
b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) \leq p_l + p_m$ (F-TD0)

IH

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbf{N}(n) \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T. (e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(n) \theta_l]$$

Since we know that (Unif e) $\rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{T'}^0 (V_d, M_d)$ therefore from (E-unif) we know that $\exists t_1. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v$ s.t. $T' = t_1 + 1$ (F-R1)

$$\text{and therefore we have } (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(n) \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-R11})$$

Also, from Definition 30, we know that $v = n$

Therefore, we have

$$C_s = V_d = \{0 \dots n\} \text{ and } M_s = M_d = \{i \mapsto \frac{1}{n+1} \mid i < n + 1\}$$

Let ρ' be the diagonal coupling s.t. $\forall i, j \in C_s$

$$\begin{aligned} \rho'(i, j) &= M_s(C_s(i)) && \text{when } i = j \\ \rho'(i, j) &= 0 && \text{otherwise} \end{aligned}$$

In order to prove (F-R0) we choose ρ as ρ'

- (a) $\forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$
 $\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j)):$
Trivial

- (b) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}.$
a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T, V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/a]]$
b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p_l + p_m + \kappa:$

We choose $p_l + p_m$ as the required potentials, it suffices to prove that

- $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_l + p_m, T, V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/i]]:$

Given some $i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|$ s.t. $\rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0$

It suffices to prove that $(p_l + p_m, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbf{N}(i)[C_s(i)/i]]$

Directly from Definition 30 (nat case)

- $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho'(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot (p_l + p_m)) \leq p_l + p_m:$
Trivial.

41. T-swap:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : [p] \tau_1 \times \tau_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{Swap } e : \tau_1 \times [p] \tau_2} \text{T-swap}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\Gamma \theta_l]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta_l]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{Swap } e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[(\tau_1 \times [p] \tau_2) \theta_l]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_1, v_2. (\text{Swap } e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \times [p] \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_1, v_2$ s.t $(\text{Swap } e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t, \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \times [p] \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists p_1, p_2. p_1 + p_2 \leq p_l + p_m \wedge (p_1, T - t, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l] \wedge (p_2, T - t, v_2) \in \mathcal{V}[[p] \tau_2 \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-TSW0})$$

IH

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[[p] \tau_1 \times \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t_1 < T . e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} v \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t_1, v) \in \mathcal{V}[[p] \tau_1 \times \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

Since we know that $(\text{Swap } e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle$ therefore from E-swap we know that $\exists t_1 < t, v_1, v_2. e \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_{t_1} \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle$. Therefore we have

$$(p_l + p_m, T - t_1, \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle) \in \mathcal{V}[[p] \tau_1 \times \tau_2) \theta_l]$$

From Definition 30 we know that

$$\exists p'_1, p'_2. p'_1 + p'_2 \leq p_l + p_m \wedge (p'_1, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[[p] \tau_1 \theta_l] \wedge (p'_2, T - t_1, v_2) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-TSW1})$$

Since $(p'_1, T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[[p] \tau_1 \theta_l]$ therefore from Definition 30 we know that

$$\exists p'. p' + p \leq p'_1 \wedge (p', T - t_1, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta_l] \quad (\text{F-TSW2})$$

In order to prove (F-TSW0) we choose p_1 as p' and p_2 as $p'_2 + p$ it suffices to prove that

- $p' + p'_2 + p \leq p_l + p_m$:

We get this directly from (F-TSW1) and (F-TSW2)

- $(p', T - t, v_1) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta \iota]$:
Directly from (T-SW1) and Lemma 33
- $(p'_2 + p, T - t, v_2) \in \mathcal{V}[[p] \tau_2 \theta \iota]$:

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that
 $\exists p'' . p'' + p \leq p'_2 + p \wedge (p'', T - t, v_2) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta \iota]$

We choose p'' as p'_2 , we get the desired from (F-TSW2) and Lemma 33

42. T-purify:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash \text{Purify } e : \tau[0/a]} \text{T-purify}$$

Given: $(p_l, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\Gamma \theta \iota]$, $(p_m, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega \theta \iota]$

To prove: $(p_l + p_m, T, (\text{Purify } e) \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[0/a] \theta \iota]$

From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall t < T, v_f. (\text{Purify } e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[0/a]]$$

This means given some $t < T, v_f$ s.t $(\text{Purify } e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ it suffices to prove that
 $(p_l + p_m, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[0/a]]$ (F-P0)

$$\underline{\text{IH}} (p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \tau \theta \iota]$$

This means from Definition 8 we have

$$\forall t' < T, v'. (e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v' \implies (p_l + p_m, T - t', v') \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \tau \theta \iota]$$

Since we know that $(\text{Purify } e) \rho_m \rho_l \downarrow_t v_f$ therefore we know that

$$(p_l + p_m, T, e \rho_m \rho_l) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \tau \theta \iota]$$

Since both static and dynamic distributions are point distributions therefore the only coupling that can satisfy the requirements of 1) of Definition 8 is $\rho = \{(0, v_f) \mapsto 1\}$

$$\text{From 2a) of Definition 8 we know that } \exists p_0 (p_0, T - t, v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[0/a]] \quad (\text{F-P1})$$

and from 2b) we know that $p_0 \leq p_l + p_m$

Therefore we get the desired from Lemma 33

□

Lemma 37 (Value subtyping lemma). $\forall \Psi, \Theta, \Delta, \tau, \tau', \theta, \iota.$
 $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau <: \tau' \wedge . \models \Delta \iota \implies \mathcal{V}[\tau \theta \iota] \subseteq \mathcal{V}[\tau' \theta \iota]$

Proof. Proof by induction on the subtyping relation

- Case sub-refl:
Trivial.
- Case sub-arrow:
Direct proof using Definition 30, IHs and 38
- Case sub-tensor:
Direct proof using Definition 30, IHs.
- Case sub-with:
Direct proof using Definition 30, IHs.
- Case sub-sum:
Direct proof using Definition 30, IHs.
- Case sub-Exp:
Direct proof using Definition 30, 38 and IH.
- Case sub-list:
Direct proof using Definition 30, IH.
- Case sub-exist:
Direct proof using Definition 30, IH.
- Case sub-typePoly:
Direct proof using Definition 30, IH.
- Case sub-indexPoly:
Direct proof using Definition 30, IH.
- Case sub-constraint:
Direct proof using Definition 30, IH.
- Case sub-CAnd:
Direct proof using Definition 30, IH.
- Case sub-subExp1:
Direct proof using Definition 30, IH.
- Case sub-subExp2:
Direct proof using Definition 30, IH.

- Case sub-potArrow:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash k'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash [k](\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) <: ([k'] \tau_1 \multimap [k' + k] \tau_2)} \text{sub-potArrow}$$

To prove: $\forall (p, T, \lambda x.e) \in \mathcal{V}[[[k](\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2)] \theta \iota]. (p, T, \lambda x.e) \in \mathcal{V}[[[k'] \tau_1 \multimap [k' + k] \tau_2] \theta \iota]$

This means given some $(p, T, \lambda x.e) \in \mathcal{V}[[[k](\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2)] \theta \iota]$ we need to prove $(p, T, \lambda x.e) \in \mathcal{V}[[[k'] \tau_1 \multimap [k' + k] \tau_2] \theta \iota]$

From Definition 30 we are given that

$$\exists p'. p' + k \leq p \wedge (p', T, \lambda x.e) \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-SPA0})$$

Again from Definition 30 we know that

$$\forall p''', e', T' < T. (p''', T', e') \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \theta \iota] \implies (p' + p''', T', e[e'/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-SPA1})$$

Also from Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\forall p'', e'', T'' < T. (p'', T'', e'') \in \mathcal{E}[[k'] \tau_1 \theta \iota] \implies (p + p'', T'', e[e''/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[[k + k'] \tau_2 \theta \iota]$$

This means given some $p'', e'', T'' < T$ s.t. $(p'', T'', e'') \in \mathcal{E}[[k'] \tau_1 \theta \iota]$ we need to prove $(p + p'', T'', e[e''/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[[k + k'] \tau_2 \theta \iota]$ (F-SPA2)

Applying Definition 30 on (F-SPA2) we get

$$\forall v_f, t' < T''. e[e''/x] \Downarrow_{t'} v_f \implies (p + p'', T'' - t', v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[k + k'] \tau_2 \theta \iota]$$

This means that given some $v_f, t' < T''$ s.t. $e[e''/x] \Downarrow_{t'} v_f$ and we need to prove that

$$(p + p'', T'' - t', v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[[k + k'] \tau_2 \theta \iota]$$

This means From Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists p_2''. p_2'' + (k + k') \leq (p + p'') \wedge (p_2'', T'' - t', v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-SPA4})$$

Also since we are given that $(p'', T'', e'') \in \mathcal{E}[[k'] \tau_1 \theta \iota]$ we apply Definition 30 on it to obtain

$$\forall t < T'', v'. e'' \Downarrow_t v' \implies (p'', T'' - t, v') \in \mathcal{V}[[k'] \tau_1 \theta \iota]$$

Also since we are given that $e[e''/x] \Downarrow_{t'} v_f$ therefore we also know that

$$\exists t'' < t' < T''. e'' \Downarrow_{t''} v''$$

Instantiating with t'', v'' we get $(p'', T'' - t'', v'') \in \mathcal{V}[[k'] \tau_1 \theta \iota]$

Again using Definition 30 we know that we are given

$$\exists p_1'', p_1'' + k' \leq p'' \wedge (p_1'', T'' - t'', v'') \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-SPA3})$$

Since $(p_1'', T'' - t'', v'') \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_1 \theta \iota]$ therefore from Definition 30 we also have

$$(p_1'', T'' - t'', v'') \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1 \theta \iota]$$

Instantiating (F-SPA1) with $p_1'', v'', T'' - t''$ we get

$$(p' + p_1'', T'' - t'', e[v''/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2 \theta \iota]$$

From Definition 30 this means that

$$\forall t''' < T'' - t'', v_f.e[v''/x] \Downarrow_{t''} v_f \implies (p' + p_1'', T'' - t'' - t''', v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-SPA4.1})$$

Since we know that $e[v''/x] \Downarrow_{t''} v_f$ therefore we also know that $\exists t''' . e[v''/x] \Downarrow_{t''} v_f$ s.t. $t''' + t'' \leq t'$

Since we already know that $\exists t'' < t' < T'' . e'' \Downarrow_{t''} v''$ therefore we have $t'' + t''' \leq t' < T''$.

Instantiating (F-SPA4.1) with t''' we get

$$(p' + p_1'', T'' - t'' - t''', v_f) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau_2 \theta \iota] \quad (\text{F-SPA5})$$

Since from (F-SPA0) we know that

$$p' + k \leq p$$

And from (F-SPA3) we know that

$$p_1'' + k' \leq p''$$

We add the two to get

$$p' + p_1'' + k + k' \leq p + p'' \quad (\text{F-SPA6})$$

In order to prove (F-SPA4) we choose p_2'' as $p' + p_1''$

and we get the desired from (F-SPA6) and (F-SPA5) and Lemma 33

- Case sub-potZero:
Direct proof using Definition 30.
- Case sub-potential:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau <: \tau' \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash n' \leq n}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash [n] \tau <: [n'] \tau'} \text{ sub-potential}$$

Given: $(p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[[p] \tau \theta \iota]$

To prove: $(p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[[[n'] \tau'] \theta \iota]$

This means from Definition 30 we are given that

$$\exists p_1. p_1 + n\theta \iota \leq p \wedge (p_1, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau] \theta \iota] \quad (\text{sub-P0})$$

Similarly from Definition 30 we are required to prove

$$\exists p_2. p_2 + n'\theta \iota \leq p \wedge (p_2, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau' \theta \iota]] \quad (\text{sub-P1})$$

Choosing p_1 from (sub-P0), we get the desired from (sub-P0) and the fact that $n'\theta \iota \leq n\theta \iota$

- Case sub-BP1:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in I \vdash \tau <: \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash [\sum_{a \in I} R_a \cdot P_a] !_{\sum_{a \in I} R_a} \tau <: !_{\sum_{a \in I} R_a} [P_a] \tau'} \text{ sub-BP1}$$

Given: $(p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[[\sum_{a \in I} R_a \cdot P_a] !_{\sum_{a \in I} R_a} \tau \theta \iota]$

To prove: $(p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[[!_{\sum_{a \in I} R_a} [P_a] \tau' \theta \iota]$

This means from Definition 30 we are given that

$$\exists p'. p' + (\sum_{a \in I} R_a \cdot P_a \iota) \leq p \wedge (p', T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[[!_{\sum_{a \in I} R_a} \tau \theta \iota]] \quad (\text{sub-P0})$$

Also since we have $(p', T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[[!_{\sum_{a \in I} R_a} \tau \theta \iota]]$, therefore we know that $\exists e. v =!e$ and from Definition 30 we also know that

$$\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|I|-1}. \sum_{i < |I|} R_a[I(i)/a] \cdot p_i \leq p' \wedge \forall i < |I|. (p_i, T, e) \in \mathcal{E}[[\tau][I(i)/a] \theta \iota] \quad (\text{sub-P1})$$

Since $\forall i < |I|. (p_i, T, e) \in \mathcal{E}[[\tau][I(i)/a] \theta \iota]$, therefore we know that

$$\forall i < |I|. \forall T' < T, v'. e \downarrow_{T'} v' \implies (p_i, T - T', v') \in \mathcal{V}[[\tau][I(i)/a] \theta \iota] \quad (\text{sub-P1.1})$$

Since we know that $v =!e$, therefore from Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists p'_0, \dots, p'_{|I|-1}. \sum_{i \in |I|} R_a[I(i)/a] \cdot p'_i \leq p \wedge \forall i < |I|. (p'_i, T, e) \in \mathcal{E}[[[P_a] \tau'][I(i)/a] \theta \iota] \quad (\text{sub-P2})$$

To prove the above we choose p'_i as $p_i + P_a[I(i)/a]$ from (sub-P) and we need to prove

– $\sum_{i \in |I|} R_a[I(i)/a] \cdot (p_i + P_a[I(i)/a]\iota) \leq p$:

This means we need to prove that

$$\sum_{i \in |I|} R_a[I(i)/a] \cdot p_i + \sum_{i \in |I|} R_a[I(i)/a] \cdot P_a[I(i)/a]\iota \leq p$$

We get the desired directly from (sub-P0) and (sub-P1)

– $\forall i < |I|. ((p_i + P_a[I(i)/a]\iota), T, e) \in \mathcal{E}[[[P_a] \tau'] [I(i)/a] \theta \iota]$:

This means given some $i < |I|$ we need to show that

$$(p_i + P_a[I(i)/a]\iota, T, e) \in \mathcal{E}[[[P_a] \tau'] [I(i)/a] \theta \iota]$$

From Definition 30, it suffices to prove that

$$\forall T' < T, v'. e \downarrow_{T'} v' \implies (p_i + P_a[I(i)/a]\iota, T - T', v') \in \mathcal{V}[[[P_a] \tau'] [I(i)/a] \theta \iota]$$

This means given some $T' < T, v'$ s.t. $e \downarrow_{T'} v'$ and we need to show that

$$(p_i + P_a[I(i)/a]\iota, T - T', v') \in \mathcal{V}[[[P_a] \tau'] [I(i)/a] \theta \iota]$$

Again from Definition 30, it suffices to prove that

$$\exists p_i''. p_i'' + P_a[I(i)/a] \iota \leq (p_i + P_a[I(i)/a]\iota) \wedge (p_i'', T - T', v') \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau') [I(i)/a] \theta \iota]$$

We choose p_i'' as p_i (from sub-P1), we need to show

$$* p_i + P_a[I(i)/a] \iota \leq (p_i + P_a[I(i)/a]\iota):$$

Trivial.

$$* (p_i, T - T', v') \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau') [I(i)/a] \theta \iota]:$$

Instantiating (sub-P1.1) with the given T', v' we get

$$(p_i, T - T', v') \in \mathcal{V}[(\tau) [I(i)/a] \theta \iota]$$

We get the desired from IH.

- Case sub-BP2:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta, a \leq I \vdash \tau <: \tau'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash !_{\sum_{a \in I} R_a} [P_a] \tau <: [\sum_{a \in I} R_a \cdot P_a] !_{\sum_{a \in I} R_a} \tau'} \text{ sub-BP2}$$

Given: $(p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[[!_{\sum_{a \in I} R_a} [P_a] \tau] \theta \iota]$

To prove: $(p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[[[\sum_{a \in I} R_a \cdot P_a] !_{\sum_{a \in I} R_a} \tau] \theta \iota]$

This means from Definition 30 we know that $\exists e.v =!e$ s.t.

$$\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|I|-1}. \sum_{i < |I|} R_a[I(i)/a] \cdot p_i \leq p \wedge \forall i < |I|. (p_i, T, e) \in \mathcal{E}[[[P_a] \tau] [I(i)/a] \theta \iota]$$

(sub-P0)

Since we have $\forall i < |I|. (p_i, T, e) \in \mathcal{E}[[[P_a] \tau] [I(i)/a] \theta \iota]$, therefore from Definition 30 we also know that

$$\forall i < |I|. \forall T' < T, v'. e \downarrow_{T'} v' \implies (p_i, T - T', v) \in \mathcal{V}[[[P_a] \tau] [I(i)/a] \theta \iota] \quad (\text{sub-P1})$$

Similarly from Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists p'. p' + (\sum_{a \in I} R_a \cdot P_a \iota) \leq p \wedge (p', T, !e) \in \mathcal{V}[\![\sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau' \theta \iota]\!] \quad (\text{sub-P2})$$

This means from Definition 30 we have to show

$$\exists p''_0, \dots, p''_{|I|-1}. \sum_{i < |I|} R_a[I(i)/a] \cdot p''_i \leq p' \wedge \forall i < |I|. (p''_i, T, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\!(\tau')[I(i)/a] \theta \iota]\!]$$

(sub-P2.1)

Further since we are required to prove $\forall i < |I|. (p''_i, T, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\!(\tau')[I(i)/a] \theta \iota]\!$. This means we will have to show

$$\forall i < |I|. \forall T' < T, v'. e' \downarrow_{T'} v' \implies (p''_i, T - T', v') \in \mathcal{V}[\!(\tau')[I(i)/a] \theta \iota]\!$$

This means give some $i < |I|, T' < T, v'$ s.t $e' \downarrow_{T'} v'$ it suffices to prove that

$$(p''_i, T - T', v') \in \mathcal{V}[\!(\tau')[I(i)/a] \theta \iota]\!]$$

(sub-P2.2)

Instantiating (sub-P1) with the given $i < |I|, T' < T, v'$ we get

$$(p_i, T - T', v) \in \mathcal{V}[\!(P_a \tau)[I(i)/a] \theta \iota]\!$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\exists p'_i. p'_i + P_a[I(i)/a] \iota \leq p_i \wedge (p'_i, T, v') \in \mathcal{V}[\!\tau[I(i)/a] \theta \iota]\!]$$

(sub-P1.1)

To prove the required we choose p' (in sub-P2) as $\sum_{i < |I|} R_a[I(i)/a] \iota \cdot p'_i$ and p''_i (in sub-P2.1) as p'_i (from sub-P1.1). Now, we need to show the following

$$- \sum_{i < |I|} R_a[I(i)/a] \iota \cdot p'_i + (\sum_{a \in I} R_a \cdot P_a \iota) \leq p:$$

This means we are required to prove

$$\sum_{i < |I|} R_a[I(i)/a] \iota \cdot p'_i + (\sum_{i < |I|} R_a[I(i)/a] \cdot P_a[I(i)/a] \iota) \leq p$$

This further means it suffices to prove

$$\sum_{i < |I|} R_a[I(i)/a] \iota \cdot (p'_i + P_a[I(i)/a] \iota) \leq p$$

Using (sub-P1.1) it further suffices to show that

$$\sum_{i < |I|} R_a[I(i)/a] \iota \cdot p_i \leq p$$

We get this from (sub-P0)

$$- \sum_{i < |I|} R_a[I(i)/a] \cdot p'_i \leq \sum_{a \in I} R_a \cdot p'_i:$$

Trivial.

$$- (p'_i, T - T', v') \in \mathcal{V}[\!(\tau')[I(i)/a] \theta \iota]\!]:$$

Directly from (sub-P1.1) and IH.

- Case sub-pcmonad:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta \vdash \tau <: \tau' \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa \leq \kappa' \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \mu \leq \mu'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau <: \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu')} \kappa' \tau'} \text{ sub-pcMonad}$$

Given: $(p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[(\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau) \theta \iota]$

To prove: $(p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[(\mathbb{PC}_{(a' \leftarrow \mu')} \kappa' \tau') \theta \iota]$

Let's $\mu = (C_s, M_s)$ and $\mu' = (C'_s, M'_s)$

This means from Definition 30 we are given that

$\forall \kappa', V_d, M_d, T' < T$.

$v \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies$

$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]$.

1) $\forall i < |C_s| \cdot \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$
 $\forall j < |V_d| \cdot \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j))$

2) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$.

a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d| \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]]$

b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa$ (sub-M0)

Similarly from Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$\forall \kappa'', V'_d, M'_d, T'' < T$.

$v \Downarrow_{T''}^{\kappa''} (V'_d, M'_d) \implies$

$\exists \rho' : (C'_s \times V'_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]$.

1) $\forall i < |C'_s| \cdot \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \leq M'_s(C'_s(i)) \wedge$
 $\forall j < |V'_d| \cdot \sum_{i < |C'_s|} \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \geq M'_d(V'_d(j))$

2) $\exists p'_0, \dots, p'_{|V'_d|-1}$.

a) $\forall i < |C'_s|, j < |V'_d| \cdot \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p'_j, T - T'', V'_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau'[C'_s(i)/a]]$

b) $(\sum_{i < |C'_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa$

This means given some $\kappa'', V'_d, M'_d, T'' < T$ s.t. $v \Downarrow_{T''}^{\kappa''} (V'_d, M'_d)$, it suffices to prove that

$\exists \rho' : (C'_s \times V'_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]$.

1) $\forall i < |C'_s| \cdot \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \leq M'_s(C'_s(i)) \wedge$
 $\forall j < |V'_d| \cdot \sum_{i < |C'_s|} \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \geq M'_d(V'_d(j))$

2) $\exists p'_0, \dots, p'_{|V'_d|-1}$.

a) $\forall i < |C'_s|, j < |V'_d| \cdot \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p'_j, T - T'', V'_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau'[C'_s(i)/a]]$

b) $(\sum_{i < |C'_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa'$ (Sub-M1)

Instantiating (Sub-M0) with the given $\kappa'', V'_d, M'_d, T''$ we get

$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V'_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]$.

1) $\forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V'_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$

$\forall j < |V'_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V'_d(j)) \geq M'_d(V'_d(j))$

2) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V'_d|-1}$.

a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V'_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V'_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T'', V'_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]]$

b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V'_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa$ (Sub-M2)

In order to prove (sub-M1) we choose the given ρ (from sub-M2) as an instance for ρ' , it suffices to prove that

– $\forall i < |C'_s|. \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \leq M'_s(C'_s(i))$

$\forall j < |V'_d|. \sum_{i < |C'_s|} \rho(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \geq M'_d(V'_d(j))$:

Directly from (sub-M2) and Definition 27

– $\exists p'_0, \dots, p'_{|V'_d|-1}$.

a) $\forall i < |C'_s|, j < |V'_d|. \rho(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p'_j, T - T'', V'_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau'[C'_s(i)/a]]$

b) $(\sum_{i < |C'_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa'$:

We choose the given potentials from (sub-M2).

Proof directly from (sub-M2) and Definition 27

- Case sub-coupling:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \exists \alpha : \mu \leftrightarrow \mu' \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \kappa \leq \kappa'}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau < : \mathbb{PC}_{(a' \leftarrow \mu')} \kappa' \tau'} \text{ sub-coupling}$$

Given: $(p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[(\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau) \theta \iota]$

To prove: $(p, T, v) \in \mathcal{V}[(\mathbb{PC}_{(a' \leftarrow \mu')} \kappa' \tau') \theta \iota]$

Let's $\mu = (C_s, M_s)$ and $\mu' = (C'_s, M'_s)$

This means from Definition 30 we are given that

$\forall \kappa', V_d, M_d, T' < T$.

$v \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies$

$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]$.

1) $\forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$

$\forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j))$

2) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d| \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 &\implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]] \\
b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' &\leq p + \kappa \quad (\text{sub-C0})
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly from Definition 30 it suffices to prove that

$$\begin{aligned}
&\forall \kappa'', V'_d, M'_d, T'' < T. \\
&v \Downarrow_{T''}^{\kappa''} (V'_d, M'_d) \implies \\
&\exists \rho' : (C'_s \times V'_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]. \\
&1) \forall i < |C'_s| \cdot \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \leq M'_s(C'_s(i)) \wedge \\
&\quad \forall j < |V'_d| \cdot \sum_{i < |C'_s|} \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \geq M'_d(V'_d(j)) \\
&2) \exists p'_0, \dots, p'_{|V'_d|-1}. \\
&a) \forall i < |C'_s|, j < |V'_d| \cdot \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p'_j, T - T'', V'_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau'[C'_s(i)/a']] \\
&b) (\sum_{i < |C'_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \cdot \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa
\end{aligned}$$

This means given some $\kappa'', V'_d, M'_d, T'' < T$ s.t. $v \Downarrow_{T''}^{\kappa''} (V'_d, M'_d)$, it suffices to prove that

$$\begin{aligned}
&\exists \rho' : (C'_s \times V'_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]. \\
&1) \forall i < |C'_s| \cdot \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \leq M'_s(C'_s(i)) \wedge \\
&\quad \forall j < |V'_d| \cdot \sum_{i < |C'_s|} \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \geq M'_d(V'_d(j)) \\
&2) \exists p'_0, \dots, p'_{|V'_d|-1}. \\
&a) \forall i < |C'_s|, j < |V'_d| \cdot \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p'_j, T - T'', V'_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau'[C'_s(i)/a']] \\
&b) (\sum_{i < |C'_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \cdot \rho'(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa' \quad (\text{sub-C1})
\end{aligned}$$

Instantiating (sub-C0) with the given $\kappa'', V'_d, M'_d, T''$ we get

$$\begin{aligned}
&\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]. \\
&1) \forall i < |C_s| \cdot \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\
&\quad \forall j < |V_d| \cdot \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M'_d(V'_d(j)) \\
&2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}. \\
&a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d| \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T'', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]] \\
&b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa \quad (\text{sub-C2})
\end{aligned}$$

Since we are given α a coupling b/w μ and μ' therefore from Definition 28 we know that $\exists \alpha' : \mu' \leftrightarrow \mu$

In order to prove (sub-C1) we need to find a coupling b/w (C'_s, M'_s) and (V'_d, M'_d)

Let us define

$$\begin{aligned}
&\beta : (C'_s \times V'_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1] \\
&\beta(c', v') \triangleq \sum_{c \in C_s} (\alpha'(c', c) \cdot \rho(c, v')) / M_s(c)
\end{aligned}$$

In order to prove (sub-C1) we choose ρ' as β

1. $\forall i < |C'_s| \cdot \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \leq M'_s(C'_s(i))$
 $\forall j < |V'_d| \cdot \sum_{i < |C'_s|} \beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \geq M'_d(V'_d(j))$:

To prove: $\forall i < |C'_s| \cdot \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \leq M'_s(C'_s(i))$

This means for an arbitrary $i < |C'_s|$ it suffices to prove that
 $\sum_{j < |V'_d|} \beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \leq M'_s(C'_s(i))$

From the definition of β , it further suffices to prove that
 $\sum_{j < |V'_d|} \sum_{c \in C_s} \alpha'(C'_s(i), c) \cdot \rho(c, V'_d(j)) / M_s(c) \leq M'_s(C'_s(i))$

Interchanging terms and summation on LHS, it suffices to prove that
 $\sum_{c \in C_s} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho(c, V'_d(j)) \cdot \alpha'(C'_s(i), c) / M_s(c) \leq M'_s(C'_s(i))$

Simplifying LHS using (sub-C2), it suffices to prove that
 $\sum_{c \in C_s} M_s(c) \cdot \alpha'(C'_s(i), c) / M_s(c) \leq M'_s(C'_s(i))$

Simplifying LHS, it suffices to prove that
 $\sum_{c \in C_s} \alpha'(C'_s(i), c) \leq M'_s(C'_s(i))$

Since α' is a coupling so we are done.

To prove: $\forall j < |V'_d| \cdot \sum_{i < |C'_s|} \beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \geq M'_d(V'_d(j))$

Similar reasoning as above.

2. $\exists p'_0, \dots, p'_{|V'_d|-1}$.
a) $\forall i < |C'_s|, j < |V'_d| \cdot \beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p'_j, T - T'', V'_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C'_s(i)/a]]$
b) $(\sum_{i < |C'_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \cdot p'_j) + \kappa'' \leq p' + \kappa$

We choose the potentials $p_0, \dots, p_{|V'_d|-1}$ (from sub-C2) as the required potentials

We need prove:

- $\forall i < |C'_s|, j < |V'_d| \cdot \beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T'', V'_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C'_s(i)/a]]$:

This means given some $i < |C'_s|, j < |V'_d|$ s.t. $\beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \neq 0$

It suffices to prove that

$$(p_j, T - T'', V'_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C'_s(i)/a]]$$

Since $\beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \neq 0$ therefore from the definition of β we know that
 $\exists i' < |C_s|$ s.t. $\rho(C_s(i'), V'_d(j)) \neq 0$

Therefore from (sub-C2) we get

$$(p_j, T - T'', V'_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i')/a]]$$

Since α is a coupling b/w (C_s, M_s) and (C'_s, M'_s) therefore we know that
 $\exists j'$ s.t. $\alpha(i', j') > 0$ therefore using ι as $\iota \cup \{a \mapsto i', a' \mapsto j'\}$ we get the desired from from IH.

$$- (\sum_{i < |C'_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \cdot \beta(C'_s(i), V'_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa:$$

Using the definition of β , it suffices to prove that

$$(\sum_{i < |C'_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \sum_{k < |C_s|} (\alpha'(C'_s(i), C_s(k)) \cdot \rho(c, V'_d(j))) / M_s(C_s(k)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa$$

Rearranging summation on the LHS, it suffices to prove that

$$(\sum_{k < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \sum_{i < |C'_s|} (\alpha'(C'_s(i), C_s(k)) \cdot \rho(C_s(k), V'_d(j))) / M_s(C_s(k)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa$$

Since α' is a coupling, it suffices to prove that

$$(\sum_{k < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} M_s(C_s(k)) \cdot \rho(C_s(k), V'_d(j)) / M_s(C_s(k)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa$$

Simplifying on the LHS, it suffices to prove that

$$(\sum_{k < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V'_d|} \rho(C_s(k), V'_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa'' \leq p + \kappa$$

We get this directly from (sub-C2). □

Lemma 38 (Expression subtyping lemma). $\forall \Psi, \Theta, \tau, \tau'$.

$$\Psi; \Theta \vdash \tau <: \tau' \implies \mathcal{E}[\tau \theta_l] \subseteq \mathcal{E}[\tau' \theta_l]$$

Proof. Directly from Definition 30 and Lemma 37 □

Lemma 39 (Γ Subtyping: domain containment). $\forall p, \rho_l, \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2$.

$$\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1 <: \Gamma_2 \implies \forall x : \tau \in \Gamma_2. x : \tau' \in \Gamma_1 \wedge \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' <: \tau$$

Proof. Proof by induction on $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1 <: \Gamma_2$

1. sub-lBase:

$$\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1 <: .} \text{sub-lBase}$$

To prove: $\forall x : \tau' \in (.). x : \tau \in \Gamma_1 \wedge \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' <: \tau$

Trivial

2. sub-lInd:

$$\frac{x : \tau' \in \Gamma_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' <: \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1/x <: \Gamma_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1 <: \Gamma_2, x : \tau} \text{sub-lBase}$$

To prove: $\forall y : \tau \in \Gamma_2. y : \tau \in \Gamma_1 \wedge \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' <: \tau$

This means given some $y : \tau \in (\Gamma_2, x : \tau)$ it suffices to prove that

$$y : \tau \in \Gamma_1 \wedge \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' <: \tau$$

The following cases arise:

- $y = x$:

In this case we are given that $x : \tau' \in \Gamma_1 \wedge \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' <: \tau$

Therefore we are done

- $y \neq x$:

Since we are given that $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1/x <: \Gamma_2$ therefore we get the desired from IH

□

Lemma 40 (Γ subtyping lemma). $\forall \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2, \theta, \iota.$

$$\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1 <: \Gamma_2 \implies \mathcal{G}[\Gamma_1\theta\iota] \subseteq \mathcal{G}[\Gamma_2\theta\iota]$$

Proof. Proof by induction on $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1 <: \Gamma_2$

1. sub-lBase:

$$\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma <: .} \text{ sub-lBase}$$

To prove: $\forall (p, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma_1\theta\iota]. (p, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma_2]$

This means given some $(p, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\Gamma_1\theta\iota]$ it suffices to prove that $(p, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{E}[\Gamma_2]$

From Definition 31 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists f : \mathcal{V}ars \rightarrow \mathcal{P}. (\forall x \in \mathbf{dom}(\cdot). (f(x), T, \rho_l(x)) \in \mathcal{E}[\Gamma(x)]) \wedge (\sum_{x \in \mathbf{dom}(\cdot)} f(x) \leq p)$$

We choose f as a constant function $f' = 0$ and we get the desired

2. sub-lInd:

$$\frac{x : \tau' \in \Gamma_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau' <: \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1/x <: \Gamma_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Gamma_1 <: \Gamma_2, x : \tau} \text{ sub-lBase}$$

To prove: $\forall (p, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma_1\theta\iota]. (p, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma_2, x : \tau]$

This means given some $(p, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma_1\theta\iota]$ it suffices to prove that $(p, T, \rho_l) \in \mathcal{G}[\Gamma_2, x : \tau]$

This means from Definition 31 we are given that

$$\exists f : \mathcal{V}ars \rightarrow \mathcal{P}.$$

$$(\forall x \in \mathbf{dom}(\Gamma_1). (f(x), T, \rho_l(x)) \in \mathcal{E}[\Gamma(x)]) \quad (\text{L0})$$

$$(\sum_{x \in \mathbf{dom}(\Gamma_1)} f(x) \leq p) \quad (\text{L1})$$

Similarly from Definition 31 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists f' : \mathcal{V}ars \rightarrow \mathcal{P}. (\forall y \in \mathbf{dom}(\Gamma_2, x : \tau). (f'(y), T, \rho_l(y)) \in \mathcal{E}[\Gamma(y)]) \wedge (\sum_{y \in \mathbf{dom}(\Gamma_2, x : \tau)} f'(y) \leq p)$$

We choose f' as f and it suffices to prove that

(a) $\forall y \in \text{dom}(\Gamma_2, x : \tau). (f(y), T, \rho_l(y)) \in \mathcal{E}[\Gamma(y)]$:

This means given some $y \in \text{dom}(\Gamma_2, x : \tau)$ it suffices to prove that $(f(y), T, \rho_l(y)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2]$ where say $\Gamma(y) = \tau_2$

From Lemma 39 we know that

$$y : \tau_1 \in \Gamma_1 \wedge \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau_2$$

By instantiating (L0) with the given y

$$(f(y), T, \rho_l(y)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1]$$

Finally from Lemma 38 we also get $(f(y), T, \rho_l(y)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_2]$

And we are done

(b) $(\sum_{y \in \text{dom}(\Gamma_2, x : \tau)} f(y) \leq p)$:

From (L1) we know that $(\sum_{x \in \text{dom}(\Gamma_1)} f(x) \leq p)$ and since from Lemma 39 we know that $\text{dom}(\Gamma_2, x : \tau) \subseteq \text{dom}(\Gamma_1)$ therefore we also have

$$(\sum_{y \in \text{dom}(\Gamma_2, x : \tau)} f(y) \leq p)$$

□

Lemma 41 (Ω Subtyping: domain containment). $\forall \Psi, \Theta, \Delta, \Omega_1 \oplus \Omega_2$.

$$\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Omega_1 <: \Omega_2 \implies$$

$$\forall x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau \in \Omega_2. x : \sum_{a \in I} R'_a \tau' \in \Omega_1 \wedge$$

$$\Theta, a; \Delta, a \in I \models R_a \leq R'_a \wedge$$

$$\Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in I \vdash \tau' <: \tau$$

Proof. Proof by induction on $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Omega_1 <: \Omega_2$

1. sub-mBase:

$$\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Omega <: .} \text{sub-mBase}$$

Trivial

2. sub-mInd:

$$\frac{x : \sum_{a \in I} R'_a \tau' \in \Omega_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in I \vdash \tau' <: \tau \quad \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in I \models R_a \leq R'_a \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Omega_1/x <: \Omega_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Omega_1 <: \Omega_2, x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau} \text{sub-mInd}$$

To prove: $\forall y : \sum_{a \in J} R''_a \tau'' \in (\Omega_2, x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau). y : \sum_{a \in J} R'_a \tau' \in \Omega_1 \wedge \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in J \models R''_a \leq R'_a \wedge \Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in J \vdash \tau' <: \tau''$

This means we need to prove that given some $y : \sum_{a \in J} R''_a \tau'' \in (\Omega_2, x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau)$ it suffices to prove that

$y : \sum_{a \in I} R'_a \tau' \in \Omega_1 \wedge \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in J \models R''_a \leq R'_a \wedge \Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in I \vdash \tau' <: \tau''$

The following cases arise:

- $y : \sum_{a \in J} R''_a \tau'' = x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau$:

In this case we are given that

$$x : \sum_{a \in I} R'_a \tau' \in \Omega_1 \wedge \Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in I \vdash \tau' <: \tau \wedge \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in I \models R_a \leq R'_a$$

Therefore we are done.

- $y : \sum_{a \in J} R''_a \tau'' \neq x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau$:

Since we are given that $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Omega_1/x <: \Omega_2$ therefore we get the desired from IH

□

Lemma 42 (Ω subtyping lemma). $\forall \Omega_1, \Omega_2, \theta, \iota$.

$$\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Omega_1 <: \Omega_2 \implies \mathcal{G}[\Omega_1 \theta \iota] \subseteq \mathcal{G}[\Omega_2 \theta \iota]$$

Proof. Proof by induction on $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Omega_1 <: \Omega_2$

1. sub-mBase:

$$\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Omega <: .} \text{ sub-mBase}$$

To prove: $\forall (p, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega_1 \theta \iota]. (p, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\cdot]$

This means given some $(p, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega_1 \theta \iota]$ it suffices to prove that $(p, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\cdot]$

From Definition 31 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists f : \text{Vars} \rightarrow \text{Index} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+. (\forall (x : \sum_{a \in S} C_a \tau) \in .. \forall i \in S. (f \ x \ i, T, \rho_m(x)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[i/a]]) \wedge (\sum_{x: \sum_{a \in S} C_a \tau \in ..} \sum_{i \in S} C_i \cdot f \ x \ i) \leq p$$

We choose f as a constant function $f' - = 0$ and we get the desired

2. sub-mInd:

$$\frac{x : \sum_{a \in I} R'_a \tau' \in \Omega_1 \quad \Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in I \vdash \tau' <: \tau \quad \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in I \models R_a \leq R'_a \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Omega_1/x <: \Omega_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Omega_1 <: \Omega_2, x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau} \text{ sub-mInd}$$

To prove: $\forall (p, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega_1 \theta \iota]. (p, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega_2, x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau]$

This means given some $(p, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega_1 \theta \iota]$ it suffices to prove that $(p, T, \rho_m) \in \mathcal{G}[\Omega_2, x : \sum_{a \in I} R_a \tau]$

This means from Definition 31 we are given that

$$\exists f : \mathcal{V}ars \rightarrow \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+.$$

$$(\forall (x : \sum_{a \in S} C_a \tau) \in \Omega_1. \forall i < |S|. (f \ x \ i, T, \rho_m(x)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau[S(i)/a]]) \quad (\text{L0})$$

$$(\sum_{x : \sum_{a \in S} C_a \tau \in \Omega_1} \sum_{i < |S|} C_a[S(i)/a] \cdot f \ x \ i) \leq p \quad (\text{L1})$$

Similarly from Definition 31 it suffices to prove that

$$\exists f' : \mathcal{V}ars \rightarrow \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+. (\forall (y : \sum_{a \in S} C_a \tau_y) \in \Omega_2, x : - \tau. \forall i < |S|. (f \ y \ i, T, \rho_m(y)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_y[S(i)/a]]) \wedge (\sum_{y : \sum_{a \in S} C_a \tau \in \Omega_2, x : - \tau} \sum_{i < |S|} C_a[S(i)/a] \cdot f' \ y \ i) \leq p$$

We choose f' as f and it suffices to prove that

$$(a) (\forall (y : \sum_{a \in S} C_a \tau_y) \in \Omega_2, x : \tau. \forall i < |S|. (f \ y \ i, T, \rho_m(y)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_y[S(i)/a]]):$$

This means given some $(y : \sum_{a \in S} C_a \tau_y) \in \Omega_2, x : \tau$ and some $i < |S|$ it suffices to prove that

$$(f \ y \ i, T, \rho_m(y)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_y[S(i)/a]]$$

From Lemma 41 we know that

$$y : \sum_{a \in S} C'_a \tau_1 \in \Omega_1 \wedge \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in S \vdash C_a \leq C'_a \wedge \Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in S \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau_y$$

Instantiating (L0) with the given y and i we get

$$(f \ y \ i, T, \rho_m(y)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1[S(i)/a]]$$

Finally using Lemma 38 we also get

$$(f \ y \ i, T, \rho_m(y)) \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_y[S(i)/a]]$$

$$(b) (\sum_{y : \sum_{a \in S} C_a \tau \in \Omega_2, x : - \tau} \sum_{i < |S|} C_i[S(i)/a] \cdot f' \ y \ i) \leq p:$$

From Lemma 41 we know that

$$\forall y : \sum_{a \in S} C_a \tau \in (\Omega_2, x : - \tau). y : \sum_{a \in S} C'_a \tau_1 \in \Omega_1 \wedge \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in S \vdash C_a \leq C'_a \wedge \Psi; \Theta, a; \Delta, a \in S \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau_y$$

And since from (L1) we know that $(\sum_{x : \sum_{a \in S} C_a \tau \in \Omega_1} \sum_{i < |S|} C_i[S(i)/a] \cdot f \ x \ i) \leq p$, therefore we also have

$$(\sum_{x : \sum_{a \in S} C_a \tau \in \Omega_2, x : \tau} \sum_{i < |S|} C_i[S(i)/a] \cdot f \ x \ i) \leq p$$

□

Theorem 43 (Soundness). $\vdash e : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau \wedge e \Downarrow_t^{\kappa'} \nu \implies \kappa' \leq \kappa$

Proof. From Theorem 36 we know that $(0, t + 1, e) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau]$

From Definition 30 this means we have

$$\forall t' < t + 1, v. (e) \rho_m \rho_l \Downarrow_{t'} e \implies (0, t + 1 - t', v) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau]$$

From the evaluation relation we know that $e \Downarrow_0 e$, therefore we have

$$(0, t + 1 - t', e) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \forall \kappa', V_d, M_d, T' < T . \\
& v \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies \\
& \exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]. \\
& 1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\
& \quad \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j)) \\
& 2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}. \\
& \quad a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]] \\
& \quad b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa
\end{aligned}$$

Since we are given that $e \Downarrow_t^{\kappa'} \nu$ therefore we know that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]. \\
& 1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \leq M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge \\
& \quad \forall j < |V_d|. \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \geq M_d(V_d(j)) \\
& 2) \exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}. \\
& \quad a) \forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d|. \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]] \\
& \quad b) (\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq p + \kappa \tag{S0}
\end{aligned}$$

Since $p = 0$ and all $p_0 \dots p_{|V_d|-1}$ are positive real numbers. Therefore we get the desired from (S0,b) □

Theorem 44 (Soundness with potentials). $\vdash e : [\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau \wedge e () \downarrow_{t_1} - \downarrow_{t_2}^{\kappa'} \nu \implies \kappa' \leq \kappa$

Proof. From Theorem 36 we know that $(0, t_1 + t_2 + 2, e) \in \mathcal{E}[[[\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau]]$

From Definition 30 this means we have

$$\forall t' < t_1 + t_2 + 2, v.e \downarrow_{t'} v \implies (0, t_1 + t_2 + 2 - t', v) \in \mathcal{V}[[[\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau]] \tag{S0}$$

Since we know that $e () \downarrow_{t_1} -$ therefore from E-app we know that $\exists e'. e \downarrow_{t_1} \lambda x.e'$

Instantiating (S0) with $t_1, \lambda x.e'$ we get $(0, t_2 + 2, \lambda x.e') \in \mathcal{V}[[[\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau]]$

$$\forall p', e'', t'' < t_2 + 2. (p', t'', e'') \in \mathcal{E}[\tau_1] \implies (p', t'', e'[e''/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau] \tag{S1}$$

Instantiating (S1) with $\kappa, (), t_2 + 1$ we get $(\kappa, t_2 + 1, e'[()/x]) \in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau]$

This means again from Definition 30 we have

$$\forall t' < t_2 + 1. e'[()/x] \downarrow_{t'} v' \implies (\kappa, t_2 + 1 - t', v') \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau]$$

From E-val we know that $v' = e'[()/x]$ and $t' = 0$ therefore we have

$$(\kappa, t_2 + 1, e'[()/x]) \in \mathcal{V}[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau]$$

This means from Definition 30 we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \forall \kappa', V_d, M_d, T' < T . \\
& e'[()/x] \Downarrow_{T'}^{\kappa'} (V_d, M_d) \implies \\
& \exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]. \\
& 1) \forall i < |C_s|. \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge
\end{aligned}$$

- $\forall j < |V_d| \cdot \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$
 2) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$.
 a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d| \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]]$
 b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq \kappa + 0$

Since we are given that $e() \downarrow_{t_1} - \downarrow_{t_2}^{\kappa'} \nu$ therefore we know that

$\exists \rho : (C_s \times V_d) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0, 1]$.

1) $\forall i < |C_s| \cdot \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_s(C_s(i)) \wedge$

$\forall j < |V_d| \cdot \sum_{i < |C_s|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) = M_d(V_d(j))$

2) $\exists p_0, \dots, p_{|V_d|-1}$.

a) $\forall i < |C_s|, j < |V_d| \cdot \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \neq 0 \implies (p_j, T - T', V_d(j)) \in \mathcal{V}[\tau[C_s(i)/a]]$

b) $(\sum_{i < |C_s|} \sum_{j < |V_d|} \rho(C_s(i), V_d(j)) \cdot p_j) + \kappa' \leq \kappa + 0$ (S2)

Since $p = 0$ and all $p_0 \dots p_{|V_d|-1}$ are positive real numbers. Therefore we get the desired from (S2,b)

□

3 Embedding ℓ RPCF

3.1 Type translation

ℓ RPCF types

$$\begin{array}{ll} \text{Linear refinement types} & \sigma, \tau \triangleq \text{Nat}(a \mid \Phi_a) \mid \sigma \otimes \tau \mid \rho \\ \text{Arrow types} & \rho \triangleq \sigma \multimap \mu \mid \forall a : \Phi_a. \rho_a \\ \text{Dynamic distribution types} & \mu \triangleq \{P_a : \sigma_a \mid a \leq I\} \end{array}$$

Type translation

$$\begin{array}{ll} \langle \text{Nat}(a \mid \Phi_a) \rangle & \triangleq \exists a : \mathbb{N}. \Phi(a) \wedge \mathbf{N}(a) \\ \langle \text{Nat}(I) \rangle & \triangleq \mathbf{N}(I) \\ \langle \sigma \otimes \tau \rangle & \triangleq \langle \sigma \rangle \times \langle \tau \rangle \\ \langle \sigma \multimap \mu \rangle & \triangleq \langle \sigma \rangle \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(b \leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\llbracket 1 \rrbracket \langle \mu \rangle), \text{ where } b \notin \langle \mu \rangle \\ \langle \forall a : \Phi_a. \rho_a \rangle & \triangleq \forall a : S. \Phi(a) \Rightarrow \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(b \leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} \langle \rho_a \rangle, \text{ where } b \notin \langle \rho_a \rangle \\ \langle \{P_a : \sigma_a \mid a \leq I\} \rangle & \triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(b \leftarrow \nu)} \mathbf{0} \langle \sigma[b/a] \rangle \\ & \text{where} \\ & \nu = (C, M) \\ & C = \{a \mid a \leq I\} \\ & M = \{a \mapsto P_a \mid a \leq I\} \end{array}$$

Judgment translation

$$\boxed{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma \mid \Theta \vdash_R e_r : \zeta \rightsquigarrow \cdot; \phi; \Phi; \langle \Gamma \rangle; \langle \Theta \rangle \vdash e_a : [R] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(b \leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} \langle \zeta \rangle, \text{ where } b \notin \langle \zeta \rangle}$$

Definition 45 (Linear context translation).

$$\begin{array}{ll} \langle \cdot \rangle & = \cdot \\ \langle x : \tau, \Gamma \rangle & = x : \langle \tau \rangle, \langle \Gamma \rangle \end{array}$$

Definition 46 (Valuation context translation).

$$\begin{array}{ll} \langle \cdot \rangle & = \cdot \\ \langle x : \{R_a : \tau_a \mid a \leq I\}, \Theta \rangle & = x : \sum_{a \in S} R_a \langle \tau_a \rangle, \langle \Theta \rangle \\ & \text{where} \\ & S \triangleq \{a \mid a \leq I\} \end{array}$$

3.2 Term translation

$$\begin{array}{c} \frac{}{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma, x : \sigma \mid \Theta \vdash_0 x : \sigma \rightsquigarrow \lambda p. \text{return } x} \text{Var} \\ \frac{\phi; \Phi \models R_a[J/a] \geq 1 \quad \phi; \Phi \models J \leq I}{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma \mid y : \{R_a : \sigma_a \mid a \leq I\} \vdash_0 y : \sigma[J/a] \rightsquigarrow \lambda p. \text{return } y} \text{Rvar} \end{array}$$

$$\frac{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma, x : \sigma | \Theta \vdash_R t : \mu \rightsquigarrow t_t}{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_{R+1} \lambda x. t : \sigma \multimap \mu \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{ Abs}$$

$$\begin{aligned} E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. \text{return } E_1 \\ E_1 &\triangleq \lambda x. \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 \\ E_2 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_3 \\ E_3 &\triangleq \text{bind } r = t_t p_1 \text{ in store } r \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_R v : \sigma \multimap \mu \rightsquigarrow v_t \quad \phi; \Phi; \Delta | \Psi \vdash_{R'} w : \sigma \rightsquigarrow w_t}{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma, \Delta | \Theta + \Psi \vdash_{R+R'} v w : \mu \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{ App}$$

$$\begin{aligned} E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. E_1 \\ E_1 &\triangleq \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 \\ E_2 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_3 \\ E_3 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_2 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_4 \\ E_4 &\triangleq \text{bind } l = v_t p_1 \text{ in } E_5 \\ E_5 &\triangleq \text{bind } u = w_t p_2 \text{ in } E_{5.1} \\ E_{5.1} &\triangleq \text{bind } r' = l u \text{ in } E_6 \\ E_6 &\triangleq \text{release } r = r' \text{ in } E_7 \\ E_7 &\triangleq \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^1 \text{ in } E_8 \\ E_8 &\triangleq \text{return } r \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\phi, b; \Phi; \ell\Gamma | y : \{R_a : \rho[M_a/b] \mid a < I\} \vdash_R v : \rho \rightsquigarrow v_t \quad Q[J/b] \geq 1 + R + \sum_{a < I} R_a \cdot Q[M_a/b]}{\phi; \Phi; \ell\Gamma | \Theta \vdash_{Q[J/b]} \text{fix } y. v : \rho \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{ Fix}$$

$$\begin{aligned} E_0 &\triangleq \text{fix } Y. \lambda p. E_1 \\ E_1 &\triangleq \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 \\ E_2 &\triangleq \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^1 \text{ in } E_3 \\ E_3 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_4 \\ E_4 &\triangleq \text{bind } y' = (\text{convert } Y) ((\lambda u. !()) p_1) \text{ in } E_5 \\ E_5 &\triangleq \text{let } !y = y' \text{ in } E_6 \\ E_6 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_2 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_7 \\ E_7 &\triangleq v_t p_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\phi, b; \Delta; \Gamma, \Delta | \Theta \vdash_R t : \{P_a : \sigma_a \mid a \leq I\} \rightsquigarrow t_t \quad \phi, a; \Phi, a \leq I; \Gamma, \Delta, x : \sigma_a | y : \nu_a \vdash_{R_a} u : \mu_a \rightsquigarrow u_t}{\phi; \Delta; \Gamma, \Delta | \Theta + (y : \sum_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot \nu_a) \vdash_{1+R+\sum_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot R_a} \text{let } x = t \text{ in } u : \sum_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot \mu_a \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{ Let}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. \text{return } E_1 \\
E_1 &\triangleq \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 \\
E_2 &\triangleq \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^1 \text{ in } E_3 \\
E_3 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_4 \\
E_4 &\triangleq \text{bind } l = t_t p_1 \text{ in } E_5 \\
E_5 &\triangleq \text{bind } x = l \text{ in } E_6 \\
E_6 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_2 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_7 \\
E_7 &\triangleq \text{bind } r = u_t p_2 \text{ in } r
\end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{}{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_1 \text{Unif} : \text{Nat}(I) \multimap \left\{ \frac{1}{I+1} : \text{Nat}(a) \mid a \leq I \right\} \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{Unif}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. E_1 \\
E_1 &\triangleq \text{return } (\lambda n. E_1) \\
E_2 &\triangleq \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_3 \\
E_3 &\triangleq \text{store}(\text{Unif } n)
\end{aligned}$$

where, $\text{Unif } n \triangleq \text{toDist}[0 \dots n]$

$$\frac{\phi; \Phi \models \Phi_a[0/a]}{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_0 0 : \text{Nat}(a | \Phi_a) \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{Zero}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. E_1 \\
E_1 &\triangleq \text{return } (Ex.\Lambda.Z)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_R v : \text{Nat}(a | \Phi_a) \rightsquigarrow v_t}{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_R s(v) : \text{Nat}(b | \Phi_a[b-1/a], b \neq 0) \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{Succ}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. E_1 \\
E_1 &\triangleq \text{bind } v' = v_t p \text{ in } E_2 \\
E_2 &\triangleq \text{letEx } r = v' \text{ in } E_3 \\
E_3 &\triangleq \text{let } r' = r \text{ in } E_4 \\
E_4 &\triangleq \text{return } (Ex.\Lambda.S (r'))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_{R_1} v : \text{Nat}(a | \Phi_a) \rightsquigarrow v_t \quad \phi, b; \Phi, \Phi_a[b+1/a] \models \Phi' \quad \phi; \Phi, \Phi_a[0/a]; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_{R_2} t : \mu \rightsquigarrow t_t \quad \phi; \Phi, \Phi'; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_{R_2} w : \text{Nat}(b | \Phi_a[b+1/a]) \multimap \mu \rightsquigarrow w_t}{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_{1+R_1+R_2} \text{match } v \text{ with } \{0 \mapsto t \mid s \mapsto w\} : \mu \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{Match}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. E_1 \\
E_1 &\triangleq \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 \\
E_{1.1} &\triangleq \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^1 \text{ in } E_2 \\
E_2 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_3 \\
E_3 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_2 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_4 \\
E_4 &\triangleq \text{bind } m = v_t p_1 \text{ in } E_5 \\
E_5 &\triangleq \text{letEx } m' = m \text{ in } E_6 \\
E_6 &\triangleq \text{letAnd } m'' = m' \text{ in } E_7 \\
E_7 &\triangleq \text{matchN } m'', Z \mapsto E_8, (S x) \mapsto E_9 \\
E_8 &\triangleq t_t p_2 \\
E_9 &\triangleq \text{bind } w' = w_t p_2 \text{ in } E_{9.1} \\
E_{9.1} &\triangleq \text{let } w'' = w' \text{ (Ex.}\Lambda.x) \text{ in } w''
\end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_{R_1} v : \sigma \rightsquigarrow v_t \quad \phi; \Phi; \Delta | \Psi \vdash_{R_2} w : \tau \rightsquigarrow w_t}{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma, \Delta | \Theta + \Psi \vdash_{R_1+R_2} \langle v, w \rangle : \sigma \otimes \tau \rightsquigarrow E_0} \otimes_i$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. E_1 \\
E_1 &\triangleq \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 \\
E_2 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_3 \\
E_3 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_2 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_4 \\
E_4 &\triangleq \text{bind } v' = v_t p_1 \text{ in } E_5 \\
E_6 &\triangleq \text{bind } w' = w_t p_2 \text{ in } E_7 \\
E_7 &\triangleq \text{return } \langle v', w' \rangle
\end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_{R_1} v : \sigma \otimes \tau \rightsquigarrow v_t \quad \phi; \Phi; \Delta, x : \sigma, y : \tau | \Psi \vdash_{R_2} w : \mu \rightsquigarrow w_t}{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma, \Delta | \Theta + \Psi \vdash_{1+R_1+R_2} \text{let } \langle x, y \rangle = v \text{ in } t : \mu \rightsquigarrow E_0} \otimes_e$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. E_1 \\
E_1 &\triangleq \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 \\
E_{2.0} &\triangleq \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^1 \text{ in } E_2 \\
E_2 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_3 \\
E_3 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_2 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_4 \\
E_4 &\triangleq \text{bind } m = v_t p_1 \text{ in } E_5 \\
E_5 &\triangleq \text{let} \langle x, y \rangle = m \text{ in } w_t p_2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma, x : \sigma | \Theta \vdash_{R_a} v : \rho \rightsquigarrow v_t}{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_{\max(a: \Phi_a) R_a} v : \forall a : \Phi_a. \rho \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{Gen}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. \text{return } (\Lambda. \Lambda. E_1) \\
E_1 &\triangleq \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 \\
E_2 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_3 \\
E_3 &\triangleq v_t p_1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\phi; \Phi \models \Phi_a[I/a] \quad \phi; \Phi; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_R v : \forall a : \Phi_a \cdot \rho_a \rightsquigarrow v_t}{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_R v : \rho_a[I/a] \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{Inst} \\
\\
\begin{array}{l}
E_0 \triangleq \lambda p. E_1 \\
E_1 \triangleq \text{bind } v' = v_t \ p \text{ in } E_2 \\
E_2 \triangleq \text{return } (v' \ \{ \} \ \{ \})
\end{array} \\
\\
\frac{\phi; \Delta; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_R t : \nu \rightsquigarrow t_t \quad \phi; \Delta \vdash (\Gamma' | \Theta') \sqsubseteq (\Gamma | \Theta) \quad \phi; \Delta \vdash \nu \sqsubseteq \mu \quad \phi; \Delta \vdash R \leq R'}{\phi; \Delta; \Gamma' | \Theta' \vdash_{R'} t : \mu \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{Coerce} \\
\\
\begin{array}{l}
E_0 \triangleq \lambda p. E_1 \\
E_1 \triangleq \text{let} \langle p', - \rangle = \text{Split } p \text{ in } E_2 \\
E_2 \triangleq \text{bind } x = (t'_t \ p') \text{ in } E_3 \\
E_3 \triangleq \text{return } (f \ x)
\end{array}
\end{array}$$

3.3 Type preservation

Theorem 47 (Type preservation: ℓ RPCF to Probabilistic λ -amor). If $\phi; \Delta; \Gamma; \Theta \vdash_R e : \zeta$ in ℓ RPCF then there exists e' such that $\phi; \Delta; \Gamma; \Theta \vdash_R e : \zeta \rightsquigarrow e'$ such that there is a derivation of $\cdot; \phi; \Delta; (\Gamma); (\Theta) \vdash e' : [R] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(b \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\zeta)$ in Probabilistic λ -amor .

Proof. Proof by induction on the $\Theta; \Delta; \Gamma \vdash_I e : \tau$

- var:

$$\frac{}{\phi; \Delta; \Gamma, x : \sigma | \Theta \vdash_0 x : \sigma \rightsquigarrow \lambda p. \text{return } x} \text{Var}$$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\phi; \Delta; (\Gamma), x : (\sigma), p : [0] \mathbf{1}; (\Theta) \vdash x : (\sigma)}{\phi; \Delta; (\Gamma), x : (\sigma), p : [0] \mathbf{1}; (\Theta) \vdash x : (\sigma)[0/a] \quad a \notin (\sigma)}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Gamma), x : (\sigma), p : [0] \mathbf{1}; (\Theta) \vdash \text{return } x : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(b \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\sigma)}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Gamma), x : (\sigma); (\Theta) \vdash \lambda p. \text{return } x : [0] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(b \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\sigma)}$$

- Rvar:

$$\frac{\phi; \Phi \models R_a[J/a] \geq 1 \quad \phi; \Phi \models J \leq I}{\phi; \Delta; \Gamma | y : \{R_a : \sigma_a | a \leq I\} \vdash_0 y : \sigma[J/a] \rightsquigarrow \lambda p. \text{return } y} \text{Rvar}$$

$$S \triangleq \{a \mid a < I\}$$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\phi; \Phi \models R_a[J/a] \geq 1 \quad \phi; \Phi \models J \in S}{\phi; \Delta; (\Gamma), p : [0] \mathbf{1}; y : \Sigma_{a \in S} R_a (\sigma_a) \vdash y : (\sigma_a)[J/a]}{\phi; \Delta; (\Gamma), p : [0] \mathbf{1}; y : \Sigma_{a \in S} R_a (\sigma_a) \vdash y : (\sigma_a[J/a])} \text{Lemma 55}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Gamma), p : [0] \mathbf{1}; y : (\{R_a : \sigma_a | a \leq I\}) \vdash \text{return } y : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(b \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\sigma_a[J/a])}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Gamma); y : (\{R_a : \sigma_a | a \leq I\}) \vdash \lambda p. \text{return } y : [0] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(b \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\sigma_a[J/a])}$$

- Abs:

$$\frac{\phi; \Delta; \Gamma, x : \tau_1 | \Theta \vdash_R t : \tau_2 \rightsquigarrow t_t}{\phi; \Delta; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_{R+1} \lambda x. t : \tau_1 \multimap \tau_2 \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{Abs}$$

$$\begin{aligned} E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. \text{return } E_1 \\ E_1 &\triangleq \lambda x. \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 \\ E_2 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_3 \\ E_3 &\triangleq \text{bind } r = t_t p_1 \text{ in store } r \end{aligned}$$

D2:

$$\frac{}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); r : (\tau_2) \vdash \text{store } r : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{1} ([\mathbf{1}] (\tau_2))}$$

D1.2:

$$\frac{}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); p_1 : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash p_1 : [R] \mathbf{1}}$$

D1.1:

$$\frac{}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), x : (\tau_1) \vdash t_t : [R] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\tau_2)} \text{IH}$$

D1:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{D1.1 \quad D1.2}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), x : (\tau_1), p_1 : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash t_t p_1 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\tau_2)} \quad D2}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), x : (\tau_1), p_1 : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{bind } r = t_t p_1 \text{ in store } r : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes \dots \delta_0)} \mathbf{1} [\mathbf{1}] (\tau_2)} \quad \text{coupling}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), x : (\tau_1), p_1 : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_3 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{1} [\mathbf{1}] (\tau_2)}$$

D0:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{D1}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) \vdash \text{store } () : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} R ([R] \mathbf{1})}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), x : (\tau_1) \vdash E_2 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes \dots \delta_0)} (R + 1) [\mathbf{1}] (\tau_2)} \quad \text{coupling}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), x : (\tau_1) \vdash E_2 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} (R + 1) [\mathbf{1}] (\tau_2)}$$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{D0}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : [R + 1] \mathbf{1} \vdash p : [R + 1] \mathbf{1}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : [R + 1] \mathbf{1}, x : (\tau_1) \vdash \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 : (\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} [\mathbf{1}] (\tau_2))}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : [R + 1] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_1 : ((\tau_1) \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} [\mathbf{1}] (\tau_2))}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : [R + 1] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{return } E_1 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} ((\tau_1) \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} [\mathbf{1}] (\tau_2))}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) \vdash \lambda p. \text{return } E_1 : [R + 1] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} ((\tau_1) \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} [\mathbf{1}] (\tau_2))}$$

• App:

$$\frac{\phi; \Delta; \Gamma_1 | \Theta_1 \vdash_R v : \sigma \multimap \mu \rightsquigarrow v_t \quad \phi; \Delta; \Gamma_2 | \Theta_2 \vdash_{R'} w : \sigma \rightsquigarrow w_t}{\phi; \Delta; \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 | \Theta_1 + \Theta_2 \vdash_{R+R'} v w : \mu \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{App}$$

Let $\Gamma = \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2$ and $\Theta = \Theta_1 + \Theta_2$

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. E_1 \\
E_1 &\triangleq \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 \\
E_2 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_3 \\
E_3 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_2 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_4 \\
E_4 &\triangleq \text{bind } l = v_t p_1 \text{ in } E_5 \\
E_5 &\triangleq \text{bind } u = w_t p_2 \text{ in } E_{5.1} \\
E_{5.1} &\triangleq \text{bind } r' = l u \text{ in } E_6 \\
E_6 &\triangleq \text{release } r = r' \text{ in } E_7 \\
E_7 &\triangleq \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^1 \text{ in } E_8 \\
E_8 &\triangleq \text{return } r
\end{aligned}$$

D6:

$$\frac{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; r : \langle \mu \rangle \vdash \text{return } r : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \langle \mu \rangle}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; r : \langle \mu \rangle \vdash E_8 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \langle \mu \rangle}$$

D5:

$$\frac{\frac{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; \cdot \vdash \uparrow^1 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 1 \mathbf{1}}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; r : \langle \mu \rangle \vdash \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^1 \text{ in } E_8 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes _ \delta_0)} 1 \langle \mu \rangle} \quad D6}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; r : \langle \mu \rangle \vdash E_7 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 1 \langle \mu \rangle} \text{ coupling}$$

D4:

$$\frac{\frac{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; r' : [1] \langle \mu \rangle \vdash r' : [1] \langle \mu \rangle}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; r' : [1] \langle \mu \rangle \vdash \text{release } r = r' \text{ in } E_7 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \langle \mu \rangle} \quad D5}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; r' : [1] \langle \mu \rangle \vdash E_6 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \langle \mu \rangle}$$

D4.0:

$$\frac{\frac{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; l : \langle \sigma \multimap \mu \rangle, u : \langle \sigma \rangle \vdash l u : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 ([1] \langle \mu \rangle)}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; l : \langle \sigma \multimap \mu \rangle, u : \langle \sigma \rangle \vdash \text{bind } r' = l u \text{ in } E_6 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes _ \delta_0)} 0 \langle \mu \rangle} \quad D4}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; l : \langle \sigma \multimap \mu \rangle, u : \langle \sigma \rangle \vdash E_{5.1} : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \langle \mu \rangle} \text{ coupling}$$

D3.2:

$$\frac{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; p_2 : [R'] \mathbf{1} \vdash p_2 : [R'] \mathbf{1}}{}$$

D3.1:

$$\frac{\phi; \Delta; \langle \Theta_2 \rangle; \langle \Gamma_2 \rangle \vdash w_t : [R'] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \langle \sigma \rangle}{\phi; \Delta; \langle \Theta_2 \rangle; \langle \Gamma_2 \rangle \vdash w_t : [R'] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \langle \sigma \rangle}$$

D3:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{D3.1 \quad D3.2}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p2 : [R'] \mathbf{1} \vdash w_t p_2 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\sigma)}{D4.0}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p2 : [R'] \mathbf{1}, l : (\sigma \multimap \mu) \vdash \text{bind } u = w_t p_2 \text{ in } E_{5.1} : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes _ \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu)}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p2 : [R'] \mathbf{1}, l : (\sigma \multimap \mu) \vdash E_5 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu)} \text{ coupling}$$

D2.2:

$$\overline{\phi; \Delta; .; p1 : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash p1 : [R] \mathbf{1}}$$

D2.1:

$$\overline{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1); (\Gamma_1) \vdash v_t : [R] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\sigma \multimap \mu)}$$

D2:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{D2.1 \quad D2.2}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1); (\Gamma_1), p1 : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash v_t p_1 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\sigma \multimap \mu)}{D3}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p1 : [R] \mathbf{1}, p2 : [R'] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{bind } l = v_t p_1 \text{ in } E_5 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes _ \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu)}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p1 : [R] \mathbf{1}, p2 : [R'] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_4 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu)} \text{ coupling}$$

D1:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{D2}{\phi; \Delta; .; . \vdash \text{store}() : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} R ([R'] \mathbf{1})}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p1 : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{bind } p_2 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_4 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes _ \delta_0)} R' (\mu)}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p1 : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_3 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} R' (\mu)} \text{ coupling}$$

D0:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{D1}{\phi; \Delta; .; . \vdash \text{store}() : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} R ([R] \mathbf{1})}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), \vdash \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_3 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes _ \delta_0)} (R + R') (\mu)}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), \vdash E_2 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} (R + R') (\mu)} \text{ coupling}$$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{D0}{\phi; \Delta; .; p : [(R + R')] \mathbf{1} \vdash p : [(R + R')] \mathbf{1}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : [(R + R')] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu)}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) \vdash \lambda p. E_1 : [(R + R')] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu)}$$

- Fix:

$$\frac{\phi, b; \Delta; \ell\Gamma | y : \{R_a : \rho[M_a/b] \mid a < I\} \vdash_R v : \rho \rightsquigarrow v_t \quad Q[J/b] \geq 1 + R + \sum_{a < I} R_a \cdot Q[M_a/b]}{\phi; \Delta; \ell\Gamma | \Theta \vdash_{Q[J/b]} \text{fix } y.v : \rho \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{Fix}$$

$$\begin{aligned} E_0 &\triangleq \text{fix } Y.\lambda p.E_1 \\ E_1 &\triangleq \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 \\ E_2 &\triangleq \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^1 \text{ in } E_3 \\ E_3 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_4 \\ E_4 &\triangleq \text{bind } y' = (\text{convert } Y) ((\lambda u.!)()) p_1 \text{ in } E_5 \\ E_5 &\triangleq \text{let } !y = y' \text{ in } E_6 \\ E_6 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_2 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_7 \\ E_7 &\triangleq v_t p_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} T_0 &= [Q] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho) \\ S &= \{a \mid a < I\} \\ T_{c0} &= \mathbf{1} \multimap !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \mathbf{1} \\ T_{c0.1} &= [0] (\mathbf{1} \multimap !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \mathbf{1}) \\ T_{c1} &= [(\sum_{a \leq I} R_a \cdot Q[M_a/b])] \mathbf{1} \multimap [(\sum_{a \leq I} R_a \cdot Q[M_a/b])] !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \mathbf{1} \end{aligned}$$

D5.2:

$$\overline{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; p_2 : ([R] \mathbf{1}) \vdash p_2 : ([R] \mathbf{1})}$$

D5.1:

$$\frac{\overline{\phi; \Delta; y : \sum_{a \in S} R_a \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho[M_a/b]); \cdot \vdash v_t : ([R] \mathbf{1}) \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)}}{\phi; \Delta; y : \sum_{a \in S} R_a \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)[M_a/b]; \cdot \vdash v_t : ([R] \mathbf{1}) \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)} \text{IH} \quad \text{Lemma 55}$$

D5:

$$\frac{\overline{\overline{D5.1} \quad \overline{D5.2}}}{\phi; \Delta; y : \sum_{a \in S} R_a \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)[M_a/b]; p_2 : ([R] \mathbf{1}) \vdash v_t p_2 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)} \quad \frac{\phi; \Delta; y : \sum_{a \in S} R_a \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)[M_a/b]; p_2 : ([R] \mathbf{1}) \vdash E_7 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)}$$

D4:

$$\frac{\overline{\overline{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; \cdot \vdash \text{store}() : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} R ([R] \mathbf{1})} \quad D5}}{\phi; \Delta; y : \sum_{a \in S} R_a \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)[M_a/b]; \cdot \vdash \text{bind } p_2 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_7 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} R (\rho)} \quad \frac{\phi; \Delta; y : \sum_{a \in S} R_a \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)[M_a/b]; \cdot \vdash E_6 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} R (\rho)}$$

D3.0:

$$\frac{}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; y' :!_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)[M_a/b] \vdash y' :!_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)[M_a/b]}$$

D3:

$$\frac{\frac{}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; y' :!_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)[M_a/b] \vdash \text{let } !y = y' \text{ in } E_6 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} R (\rho)}{D3.0} \quad D4}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; y' :!_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)[M_a/b] \vdash E_5 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} R (\rho)}$$

Dc2:

$$\frac{}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot \vdash T_{c0.1} <: T_{c1}} \text{ sub-potArrow}$$

Dc1:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{}{\phi, a; \Delta; a \in S; \cdot \vdash () : \mathbf{1}}{T\text{-unit}}}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; \cdot; u : \mathbf{1} \vdash !() :!_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \mathbf{1}} T\text{-subExpI, T-sub}}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; \cdot; \cdot \vdash \lambda u. !() : T_{c0}} T\text{-lam}$$

Dc:

$$\frac{Dc1 \quad \frac{}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot \vdash T_{c0} <: T_{c0.1}} \text{ sub-potZero} \quad T\text{-sub} \quad Dc2}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; \cdot; \cdot \vdash \lambda u. !() : T_{c0.1}} T\text{-sub} \quad T\text{-sub}$$

D2.2:

$$\frac{Dc \quad \frac{}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; p1 : [(\sum_{a \in S} R_a \cdot Q[M_a/b])] \mathbf{1} \vdash p1 : [(\sum_{a \in S} R_a \cdot Q[M_a/b])] \mathbf{1}}{Dc} \quad T\text{-sub}}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; p1 : [(\sum_{a \in S} R_a \cdot Q[M_a/b])] \mathbf{1} \vdash (\lambda u. !()) p1 : [(\sum_{a \in S} R_a \cdot Q[M_a/b])] (!_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \mathbf{1})} T\text{-sub}}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; p1 : [(\sum_{a \in S} R_a \cdot Q[M_a/b])] \mathbf{1} \vdash (\lambda u. !()) p1 :!_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} ([Q[M_a/b]] \mathbf{1})} T\text{-sub}$$

D2.1:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{}{\phi; \Delta; Y :!_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} T_0[M_a/b]; \cdot \vdash Y :!_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} ([Q] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho))[M_a/b]}{D2.1} \quad D2.2}{\phi; \Delta; Y :!_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} T_0[M_a/b]; \cdot \vdash Y :!_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} ([Q[M_a/b]] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)[M_a/b])} T\text{-sub}}{\phi; \Delta; Y :!_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} T_0[M_a/b]; \cdot \vdash \text{convert } Y :!_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} [Q[M_a/b]] \mathbf{1} \multimap !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)[M_a/b]} T\text{-sub}$$

D2.0:

$$\frac{D2.1 \quad D2.2}{\phi; \Delta; Y :!_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} T_0[M_a/b]; p1 : [(\sum_{a \in S} R_a \cdot Q[M_a/b])] \mathbf{1} \vdash (\text{convert } Y) ((\lambda u. !()) p1) :!_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)[M_a/b]} T\text{-sub}$$

D2:

$$\frac{\frac{D2.0 \quad D3}{\phi; \Delta; Y : \sum_{a \in S} R_a T_0[M_a/b]; p1 : [(\sum_{a \leq I} R_a \cdot Q[M_a/b])] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{bind } y = (\text{convert } Y) ((\lambda u.!)()) p1 \text{ in } E_5 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} (R) (\rho)}}{\phi; \Delta; Y : \sum_{a \in S} R_a T_0[M_a/b]; p1 : [(\sum_{a \leq I} R_a \cdot Q[M_a/b])] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_4 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} (R) (\rho)}}$$

D1:

$$\frac{\frac{\phi; \Delta; .; . \vdash \text{store}() : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} (\sum_{a \leq I} R_a \cdot Q[M_a/b]) ((\sum_{a \leq I} R_a \cdot Q[M_a/b]) \mathbf{1})}{D2}}{\phi; \Delta; Y : \sum_{a \in S} R_a T_0[M_a/b]; . \vdash \text{bind } p1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_4 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} (R + \sum_{a \leq I} R_a \cdot Q[M_a/b]) (\rho)}}{\phi; \Delta; Y : \sum_{a \in S} R_a T_0[M_a/b]; . \vdash E_3 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} (R + \sum_{a \leq I} R_a \cdot Q[M_a/b]) (\rho)}}$$

D0:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\phi; \Delta; .; . \vdash \uparrow^1 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{1} \mathbf{1}}{D1}}{\phi; \Delta; Y : \sum_{a \in S} R_a T_0[M_a/b]; . \vdash \text{bind } - = \uparrow^1 \text{ in } E_3 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} (1 + R + \sum_{a \leq I} R_a \cdot Q[M_a/b]) (\rho)}}{\phi; \Delta; Y : \sum_{a \in S} R_a T_0[M_a/b]; . \vdash E_2 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} (1 + R + \sum_{a \leq I} R_a \cdot Q[M_a/b]) (\rho)}}{\phi; \Delta; Y : \sum_{a \in S} R_a T_0[M_a/b]; . \vdash E_2 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} Q[J/b] (\rho)}}$$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{\phi; \Delta; .; p : [Q[J/b]] \mathbf{1} \vdash p : [Q[J/b]] \mathbf{1}}{D0}}{\phi; \Delta; Y : \sum_{a \in S} R_a T_0[M_a/b]; p : [Q[J/b]] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{release } - = p \text{ in } E_2 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)}}{\phi; \Delta; Y : \sum_{a \in S} R_a T_0[M_a/b]; p : [Q[J/b]] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_1 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)}}{\phi; \Delta; Y : \sum_{a \in S} R_a T_0[M_a/b]; . \vdash \lambda p. E_1 : T_0}}{\frac{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) \vdash \text{fix } Y. \lambda p. E_1 : ([Q] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho))[J/b]}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) \vdash \text{fix } Y. \lambda p. E_1 : [Q[J/b]] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)[J/b]} \text{Lemma 55}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) \vdash \text{fix } Y. \lambda p. E_1 : [Q[J/b]] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho)[J/b]}}$$

• Let:

$$\frac{\frac{\phi, b; \Delta; \Gamma, \Delta | \Theta \vdash_R t : \{P_a : \sigma_a \mid a \leq I\} \rightsquigarrow t_t}{\phi, a; \Phi, a \leq I; \Gamma, \Delta, x : \sigma_a | y : \nu_a \vdash_{R_a} u : \mu_a \rightsquigarrow u_t}}{\phi; \Delta; \Gamma, \Delta | \Theta + (y : \sum_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot \nu_a) \vdash_{1+R+\sum_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot R_a} \text{let } x = t \text{ in } u : \sum_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot \mu_a \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{Let}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. \text{return } E_1 \\
E_1 &\triangleq \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 \\
E_2 &\triangleq \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^1 \text{ in } E_3 \\
E_3 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_4 \\
E_4 &\triangleq \text{bind } l = t_t p_1 \text{ in } E_5 \\
E_5 &\triangleq \text{bind } x = l \text{ in } E_6 \\
E_6 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_2 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_7 \\
E_7 &\triangleq \text{bind } r = u_t p_2 \text{ in } r \\
\mu_a &\triangleq \{Q_{ab} : \tau_{ab} \mid b < J_a\} \\
\mu_{t1} &\triangleq (C_1, M_1) \\
&\text{where} \\
&C_1 = \{a \mid a \leq I\} \\
&M_1 = \{a \mapsto P_a \mid a \leq I\} \\
\mu_{t2} &\triangleq (C_2, M_2) \\
&\text{where} \\
&C_2 = \{b \mid b \leq J_a\} \\
&M_2 = \{b \mapsto Q_{ab} \mid b \leq J_a\} \\
T_{ih1} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \mu_{t1})} 0 \langle \sigma_a \rangle \\
T_{ih2} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \mu_{t2})} 0 \langle \tau_{ab} \rangle \\
T_0 &\triangleq T_p \multimap T_r \\
T_p &\triangleq [1 + R + \sum_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot R_a] \mathbf{1} \\
T_r &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(b \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \langle \sum_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot \mu_a \rangle
\end{aligned}$$

D6:

$$\frac{}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; r : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \mu'_{t2})} 0 \langle \tau_{ab} \rangle \vdash r : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \mu_{t2})} 0 \langle \tau_{ab} \rangle}$$

D5.2:

$$\frac{}{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; p_2 : [R_a] \mathbf{1} \vdash p_2 : [R_a] \mathbf{1}}$$

D5.1:

$$\frac{}{\phi; \Delta; \langle y : \nu_a \rangle; \langle \Delta \rangle, x : \langle \sigma_a \rangle \vdash u_t : [R_a] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \langle \mu_a \rangle}$$

D5:

$$\frac{
\frac{
\frac{
D5.1 \quad D5.2
}{\phi; \Delta; \langle y : \nu_a \rangle; \langle \Delta \rangle, x : \langle \sigma_a \rangle, p_2 : [R_a] \mathbf{1} \vdash u_t p_2 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \langle \mu_a \rangle}
}{\phi; \Delta; \langle y : \nu_a \rangle; \langle \Delta \rangle, x : \langle \sigma_a \rangle, p_2 : [R_a] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{bind } r = u_t p_2 \text{ in } r : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes _ \mu_{t2})} 0 \langle \tau_{ab} \rangle}
}{\phi; \Delta; \langle y : \nu_a \rangle; \langle \Delta \rangle, x : \langle \sigma_a \rangle, p_2 : [R_a] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_7 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \mu_{t2})} 0 \langle \tau_{ab} \rangle}
\quad D6$$

D4:

$$\frac{\frac{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; \cdot \vdash \text{store}() : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} R_a ([R_a] \mathbf{1})}{\phi; \Delta; (y : \nu_a); (\Delta), x : (\sigma_a) \vdash \text{bind } p_2 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_7 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes \cdot \mu_{t_2})} R_a (\tau_{ab})} \quad D5}{\phi; \Delta; (y : \nu_a); (\Delta), x : (\sigma_a) \vdash E_6 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \mu_{t_2})} R_a (\tau_{ab})}$$

D3:

$$\frac{\frac{\phi; \Delta; (y : \nu_a); (\Delta), l : T_{ih1} \vdash l : T_{ih1}}{\phi; \Delta; (y : \nu_a); (\Delta), l : T_{ih1} \vdash \text{bind } x = l \text{ in } E_6 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \mu_{t_1} \otimes a \cdot \mu_{t_2})} (\Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot R_a) (\tau_{ab})} \quad D4}{\phi; \Delta; (y : \nu_a); (\Delta), l : T_{ih1} \vdash E_5 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \mu_{t_1} \otimes a \cdot \mu_{t_2})} (\Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot R_a) (\tau_{ab})} \text{ bind}$$

D2.2:

$$\phi; \Delta; \cdot; p_1 : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash p_1 : [R] \mathbf{1}$$

D2.1:

$$\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) \vdash t_t : [R] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} T_{ih1}$$

D2:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{D2.1 \quad D2.2}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p_1 : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash t_t p_1 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} T_{ih1}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta, (y : \Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot \nu_a)); (\Gamma, \Delta), p_1 : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{bind } l = t_t p_1 \text{ in } E_5 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes \cdot (\mu_{t_1} \otimes a \cdot \mu_{t_2}))} (\Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot R_a) (\tau_{ab})} \quad D3}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta, (y : \Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot \nu_a)); (\Gamma, \Delta), p_1 : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_4 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow (\mu_{t_1} \otimes a \cdot \mu_{t_2}))} (\Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot R_a) (\tau_{ab})}$$

D1:

$$\frac{\frac{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; \cdot \vdash \text{store}() : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} R ([R] \mathbf{1})}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta, (y : \Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot \nu_a)); (\Gamma, \Delta) \vdash \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_4 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes \cdot (\mu_{t_1} \otimes a \cdot \mu_{t_2}))} (R + \Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot R_a) (\tau_{ab})} \quad D2}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta, (y : \Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot \nu_a)); (\Gamma, \Delta) \vdash E_3 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow (\mu_{t_1} \otimes a \cdot \mu_{t_2}))} (R + \Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot R_a) (\tau_{ab})}$$

D0:

$$\frac{\frac{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; \cdot \vdash \uparrow^1 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{1} \mathbf{1}}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta, (y : \Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot \nu_a)); (\Gamma, \Delta) \vdash \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^1 \text{ in } E_3 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes \cdot (\mu_{t_1} \otimes a \cdot \mu_{t_2}))} (1 + R + \Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot R_a) (\tau_{ab})} \quad D1}{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta, (y : \Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot \nu_a)); (\Gamma, \Delta) \vdash E_2 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow (\mu_{t_1} \otimes a \cdot \mu_{t_2}))} (1 + R + \Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot R_a) (\tau_{ab})}$$

Main derivation:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\overline{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; p : T_p \vdash p : T_p} \quad D0 \\
\hline
\phi; \Delta; (\Theta, (y : \Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot \nu_a)); (\Gamma, \Delta), p : \vdash \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 : \\
\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(_ \leftarrow (\mu_{t1} \otimes a, \mu_{t2}))} 0 (\tau_{ab}) \\
\hline
\phi; \Delta; (\Theta, (y : \Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot \nu_a)); (\Gamma, \Delta), p : T_p \vdash E_1 : (\Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot \mu_a) \quad \text{coupling} \\
\hline
\phi; \Delta; (\Theta, (y : \Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot \nu_a)); (\Gamma, \Delta), p : T_p \vdash \text{return } E_1 : T_r \\
\hline
\phi; \Delta; (\Theta, (y : \Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot \nu_a)); (\Gamma, \Delta) \vdash \lambda p. \text{return } E_1 : T_0 \\
\hline
\phi; \Delta; (\Theta, (y : \Sigma_{a \leq I} P_a \cdot \nu_a)); (\Gamma, \Delta) \vdash E_0 : T_0
\end{array}$$

• Unif:

$$\overline{\phi; \Delta; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_1 \text{Unif} : \text{Nat}(I) \multimap \left\{ \frac{1}{I+1} : \text{Nat}(a) \mid a \leq I \right\}} \rightsquigarrow E_0 \quad \text{Unif}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. E_1 \\
E_1 &\triangleq \text{return } (\lambda n. E_1) \\
E_2 &\triangleq \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_3 \\
E_3 &\triangleq \text{store}(\text{Unif } n)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
T_0 &\triangleq [1] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(_ \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\text{Nat}(I) \multimap \left\{ \frac{1}{I+1} : \text{Nat}(a) \mid a \leq I \right\}) \\
T_{0.0} &\triangleq [1] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(_ \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\mathbf{N}(I) \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(_ \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 ([1] T_{0.1})) \\
T_{0.00} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(_ \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\mathbf{N}(I) \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(_ \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 ([1] T_{0.1})) \\
T_{0.01} &\triangleq \mathbf{N}(I) \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(_ \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 ([1] T_{0.1}) \\
T_{0.02} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(_ \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 ([1] T_{0.1}) \\
T_{0.1} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu_u)} 0 \mathbf{N}(a) \\
\mu_u &\triangleq (C, M)
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
C &= \{a \mid a \leq I\} \\
M &= \{a \mapsto \frac{1}{I+1} \mid a \leq I\}
\end{aligned}$$

D0:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\overline{\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), n : \mathbf{N}(I) \vdash (\text{Unif } n) : T_{0.1}} \\
\hline
\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), n : \mathbf{N}(I) \vdash \text{store}(\text{Unif } n) : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(_ \leftarrow \delta_0)} 1 ([1] T_{0.1}) \\
\hline
\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), n : \mathbf{N}(I) \vdash E_3 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(_ \leftarrow \delta_0)} 1 ([1] T_{0.1})
\end{array}$$

Main derivation:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\overline{\phi; \Delta; \cdot; p : [1] \mathbf{1} \vdash p : [1] \mathbf{1}} \quad D0 \\
\hline
\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : [1] \mathbf{1}, n : \mathbf{N}(I) \vdash \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_3 : T_{0.02} \\
\hline
\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : [1] \mathbf{1}, n : \mathbf{N}(I) \vdash E_2 : T_{0.02} \\
\hline
\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : [1] \mathbf{1}, n : \mathbf{N}(I) \vdash (\lambda n. E_2) : T_{0.01} \\
\hline
\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : [1] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{return } (\lambda n. E_2) : T_{0.00} \\
\hline
\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : [1] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_1 : T_{0.00} \\
\hline
\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) \vdash \lambda p. E_1 : T_{0.0} \\
\hline
\phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) \vdash E_0 : T_0
\end{array}$$

• Zero:

$$\frac{\phi; \Delta \models \Phi_a[0/a]}{\phi; \Delta; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_0 0 : \text{Nat}(a | \Phi_a) \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{Zero}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. E_1 \\
E_1 &\triangleq \text{return } (Ex.\Lambda.Z)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
T_0 &\triangleq [0] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}C_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \langle \text{Nat}(a | \Phi_a) \rangle \\
T_1 &\triangleq [0] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}C_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\exists a : \mathbb{N}. \Phi(a) \wedge \mathbf{N}(a)) \\
T_2 &\triangleq \mathbb{P}C_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\exists a : \mathbb{N}. \Phi(a) \wedge \mathbf{N}(a)) \\
T_3 &\triangleq \exists a : \mathbb{N}. \Phi(a) \wedge \mathbf{N}(a) \\
T_4 &\triangleq \Phi(a) \wedge \mathbf{N}(a)
\end{aligned}$$

Main derivation:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\overline{\cdot; \phi; \Delta; \cdot; \vdash Z : \mathbf{N}(0)} \quad \overline{\phi; \Delta \models \Phi_a[0/a]} \\
\hline
\cdot; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : [0] \mathbf{1} \vdash \Lambda.Z : T_4[0/a] \\
\hline
\cdot; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : [0] \mathbf{1} \vdash (Ex.\Lambda.Z) : T_3 \\
\hline
\cdot; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : [0] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{return } (Ex.\Lambda.Z) : T_2 \\
\hline
\cdot; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : [0] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_1 : T_2 \\
\hline
\cdot; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) \vdash \lambda p. E_1 : T_1 \\
\hline
\cdot; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) \vdash E_0 : T_0
\end{array}$$

• Succ:

$$\frac{\phi; \Delta; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_R v : \text{Nat}(a | \Phi_a) \rightsquigarrow v_t}{\phi; \Delta; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_R s(v) : \text{Nat}(b | \Phi_a[b - 1/a], b \neq 0) \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{Succ}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. E_1 \\
E_1 &\triangleq \text{bind } v' = v_t p \text{ in } E_2 \\
E_2 &\triangleq \text{letEx } r = v' \text{ in } E_3 \\
E_3 &\triangleq \text{let } r' = r \text{ in } E_4 \\
E_4 &\triangleq \text{return } (Ex.\Lambda.S (r'))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
T_0 &\triangleq [R] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\llbracket Nat(b) \Phi_a[b - 1/a], b \neq 0 \rrbracket) \\
T_1 &\triangleq [R] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\exists b. \Phi_a[b - 1/a] \wedge b \neq 0 \wedge \mathbf{N}(b)) \\
T_2 &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\exists b. \Phi_a[b - 1/a] \wedge b \neq 0 \wedge \mathbf{N}(b)) \\
T_{2.0} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes \dots \delta_0)} 0 (\exists b. \Phi_a[b - 1/a] \wedge b \neq 0 \wedge \mathbf{N}(b)) \\
T_3 &\triangleq \exists b. \Phi_a[b - 1/a] \wedge b \neq 0 \wedge \mathbf{N}(b) \\
T_4 &\triangleq \exists a. \Phi(a) \wedge \mathbf{N}(a) \\
T_5 &\triangleq \Phi(a) \wedge \mathbf{N}(a)
\end{aligned}$$

D4:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi, a; \Delta, \Phi(a) \models \Phi(a)}$$

D3:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi, a; \Delta, \Phi(a); (\Theta); (\Gamma), r' : \mathbf{N}(a) \vdash S (r') : \mathbf{N}(a + 1)}$$

D2.0:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi, a; \Delta, \Phi(a) \models a + 1 : \mathbb{N}}$$

D2:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{D3 \quad D4}{.; \phi, a; \Delta, \Phi(a); (\Theta); (\Gamma), r' : \mathbf{N}(a) \vdash \Lambda.S (r') : T_5[b - 1/a]}{.; \phi, a; \Delta, \Phi(a); (\Theta); (\Gamma), r' : \mathbf{N}(a) \vdash (Ex.\Lambda.S (r')) : T_3} \quad D2.0}{.; \phi, a; \Delta, \Phi(a); (\Theta); (\Gamma), r' : \mathbf{N}(a) \vdash \text{return } (Ex.\Lambda.S (r')) : T_2}}{.; \phi, a; \Delta, \Phi(a); (\Theta); (\Gamma), r' : \mathbf{N}(a) \vdash E_4 : T_2}$$

D1:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{D2}{.; \phi, a; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), r : T_5 \vdash r : T_5}}{.; \phi, a; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), r : T_5 \vdash \text{let } r' = r \text{ in } E_4 : T_2}}{.; \phi, a; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), r : T_5 \vdash E_3 : T_2}$$

D0:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{D1}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), v' : T_4 \vdash v' : T_4}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), v' : T_4 \vdash \text{letEx } r = v' \text{ in } E_3 : T_2}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), v' : T_4 \vdash E_2 : T_2}$$

D0.1:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; p : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash p : [R] \mathbf{1}}$$

D0.0:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) \vdash v_t : [R] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(-\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \langle \text{Nat}(a | \Phi_a) \rangle} \text{IH}$$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{D0.0 \quad D0.1}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash v_t p : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(-\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \langle \text{Nat}(a | \Phi_a) \rangle}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{bind } v' = v_t p \text{ in } E_2 : T_{2,0}}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_1 : T_2}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) \vdash \lambda p. E_1 : T_1}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) \vdash E_0 : T_0} D0$$

• Match:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \phi; \Phi; \Gamma_1 | \Theta_1 \vdash_{R_1} v : \text{Nat}(a | \Phi_a) \rightsquigarrow v_t \\ \phi, b; \Phi, \Phi_a[b + 1/a] \models \Phi' \quad \phi; \Phi, \Phi_a[0/a]; \Gamma_2 | \Theta_2 \vdash_{R_2} t : \mu \rightsquigarrow t_t \\ \phi; \Phi, \Phi'; \Gamma_2 | \Theta_2 \vdash_{R_2} w : \text{Nat}(b | \Phi_a[b + 1/a]) \multimap \mu \rightsquigarrow w_t \end{array}}{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 | \Theta_1 + \Theta_2 \vdash_{1+R_1+R_2} \text{match } v \text{ with } \{0 \mapsto t \mid s \mapsto w\} : \mu \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{Match}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} E_0 \triangleq \lambda p. E_1 \\ E_1 \triangleq \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 \\ E_{1.1} \triangleq \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^1 \text{ in } E_2 \\ E_2 \triangleq \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_3 \\ E_3 \triangleq \text{bind } p_2 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_4 \\ E_4 \triangleq \text{bind } m = v_t p_1 \text{ in } E_5 \\ E_5 \triangleq \text{letEx } m' = m \text{ in } E_6 \\ E_6 \triangleq \text{letAnd } m'' = m' \text{ in } E_7 \\ E_7 \triangleq \text{matchN } m'', Z \mapsto E_8, (S x) \mapsto E_9 \\ E_8 \triangleq t_t p_2 \\ E_9 \triangleq \text{bind } w' = w_t p_2 \text{ in } E_{9.1} \\ E_{9.1} \triangleq \text{let } w'' = w' (Ex. \Lambda. x) \text{ in } w'' \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
T_0 &\triangleq [1 + R_1 + R_2] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow\delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu) \\
T_1 &\triangleq [1 + R_1 + R_2] \mathbf{1} \\
T_2 &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow\delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu) \\
T_3 &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow\delta_0)} (1 + R_1 + R_2) (\mu) \\
T_{i1} &\triangleq [R_1] \mathbf{1} \multimap T_{i1.1} \\
T_{i1.1} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow\delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\text{Nat}(a|\Phi_a)) \\
T_{i1.2} &\triangleq \exists a : \mathbb{N}. \Phi(a) \wedge \mathbf{N}(a) \\
T_{i1.3} &\triangleq \Phi(a) \wedge \mathbf{N}(a) \\
T_{i2} &\triangleq [R_2] \mathbf{1} \multimap T_{i2.1} \\
T_{i2.1} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow\delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu) \\
T_{i3} &\triangleq [R_2] \mathbf{1} \multimap T_{i3.1} \\
T_{i3.1} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow\delta_0)} \mathbf{0} T_{i3.2} \\
T_{i3.2} &\triangleq (\text{Nat}(b|\Phi_a[b + 1/a])) \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow\delta_0)} \mathbf{0} ([1] (\mu)) \\
T_{i3.3} &\triangleq \exists b : \mathbb{N}. \Phi(b + 1) \wedge \mathbf{N}(b) \\
T_{i3.4} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow\delta_0)} \mathbf{0} ([1] (\mu))
\end{aligned}$$

D5.24:

$$\frac{.; \phi, a, i; \Delta, \Phi(a), i + 1 = a; .; w'' : T_{i3.4} \vdash w'' : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow\delta_0)} \mathbf{0} ([1] (\mu))}{.; \phi, a, i; \Delta, \Phi(a), i + 1 = a; .; w'' : T_{i3.4} \vdash w'' : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow\delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu)}$$

D5.232:

$$\frac{.; \phi, a, i; \Delta, \Phi(a), i + 1 = a; .; x : \mathbf{N}(i) \vdash \Lambda.x : \Phi(b + 1) \wedge \mathbf{N}(b)[i/b]}{.; \phi, a, i; \Delta, \Phi(a), i + 1 = a; .; x : \mathbf{N}(i) \vdash (Ex.\Lambda.x) : T_{i3.3}}$$

D5.231:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi, a, i; \Delta, \Phi(a), i + 1 = a; .; w' : T_{i3.2} \vdash w' : T_{i3.2}}$$

D5.230:

$$\frac{D5.231 \quad D5.232}{.; \phi, a, i; \Delta, \Phi(a), i + 1 = a; .; x : \mathbf{N}(i), w' : T_{i3.2} \vdash w' (Ex.\Lambda.x) : T_{i3.4}}$$

D5.23:

$$\frac{D5.230 \quad D5.24}{.; \phi, a, i; \Delta, \Phi(a), i + 1 = a; .; x : \mathbf{N}(i), w' : T_{i3.2} \vdash \text{let } w'' = w' (Ex.\Lambda.x) \text{ in } w'' : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow\delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu)}$$

$$\frac{}{.; \phi, a, i; \Delta, \Phi(a), i + 1 = a; .; x : \mathbf{N}(i), w' : T_{i3.2} \vdash E_{9.1} : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow\delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu)}$$

D5.22:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi, a, i; \Delta, \Phi(a), i + 1 = a; .; p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1} \vdash p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}}$$

D5.21:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi, a, i; \Delta, \Phi(a), i + 1 = a; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), x : \mathbf{N}(i) \vdash w_t : T_{i3}}$$

D5.20:

$$\frac{D5.21 \quad D5.22}{.; \phi, a, i; \Delta, \Phi(a), i + 1 = a; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}, x : \mathbf{N}(i) \vdash w_t p_2 : T_{i3.1}}$$

D5.2:

$$\frac{D5.20 \quad D5.23}{.; \phi, a, i; \Delta, \Phi(a), i + 1 = a; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}, x : \mathbf{N}(i) \vdash \text{bind } w' = w_t p_2 \text{ in } E_{9.1} : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu)}$$

$$\frac{}{.; \phi, a, i; \Delta, \Phi(a), i + 1 = a; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}, x : \mathbf{N}(i) \vdash E_9 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu)}$$

D5.12:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi, a; \Delta, \Phi(0); .; p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1} \vdash p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}}$$

D5.11:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi, a; \Delta, \Phi(0); (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2) \vdash t_t : T_{i2}}$$

D5.1:

$$\frac{D5.11 \quad D5.12}{.; \phi, a; \Delta, \Phi(0); (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1} \vdash t_t p_2 : T_{i2.1}}$$

$$\frac{}{.; \phi, a; \Delta, \Phi(0); (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_8 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu)}$$

D5:

$$\frac{D5.1 \quad D5.2}{.; \phi, a; \Delta, \Phi(a); .; m'' : \mathbf{N}(a) \vdash m'' : \mathbf{N}(a)}$$

$$\frac{}{.; \phi, a; \Delta, \Phi(a); (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}, m'' : \mathbf{N}(a) \vdash \text{matchN } m'', Z \mapsto E_8, (S x) \mapsto E_9 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu)}$$

$$\frac{}{.; \phi, a; \Delta, \Phi(a); (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}, m'' : \mathbf{N}(a) \vdash E_7 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu)}$$

D4:

$$\frac{D5}{.; \phi, a; \Delta; .; m' : T_{i1.3} \vdash m' : T_{i1.3}}$$

$$\frac{}{.; \phi, a; \Delta; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}, m' : T_{i1.3} \vdash \text{letAnd } m'' = m' \text{ in } E_7 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu)}$$

$$\frac{}{.; \phi, a; \Delta; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}, m' : T_{i1.3} \vdash E_6 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} (\mu)}$$

D3:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; m : T_{i1.2} \vdash m : T_{i1.2}}{D4}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}, m : T_{i1.2} \vdash \text{letEx } m' = m \text{ in } E_6 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\mu)}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}, m : T_{i1.2} \vdash E_5 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\mu)}}$$

D2.2:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1} \vdash p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1}}$$

D2.1:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1); (\Gamma_1) \vdash v_t : T_{i1}}$$

D2:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{}{D2.1} \quad \frac{}{D2.2}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1); (\Gamma_1), p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1} \vdash v_t p_1 : T_{i1.1}}{D3}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2), p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1}, p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{bind } m = v_t p_1 \text{ in } E_5 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\mu)}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2), p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1}, p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_4 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\mu)}}$$

D1:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; . \vdash \text{store}() : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} (R_2) [R_2] \mathbf{1}}{D2}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2), p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{bind } p_2 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_4 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} (R_2) (\mu)}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2), p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_3 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} (R_2) (\mu)}}$$

D0:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; . \vdash \text{store}() : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} (R_1) [R_1] \mathbf{1}}{D1}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2) \vdash \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_3 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} (R_1 + R_2) (\mu)}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2) \vdash E_2 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} (R_1 + R_2) (\mu)}}$$

D0.0:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; . \vdash \uparrow^1 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 1 \mathbf{1}}{D0}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2) \vdash \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^1 \text{ in } E_2 : T_3}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2) \vdash E_{1.1} : T_3}}$$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; p : T_1 \vdash p : T_1}}{D0.0}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2), p : T_1 \vdash \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_{1.1} : T_2}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2), p : T_1 \vdash E_1 : T_2}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2) \vdash \lambda p. E_1 : T_0}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2) \vdash E_0 : T_0}}$$

- Pair-I:

$$\frac{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma_1 | \Theta_1 \vdash_{R_1} v : \sigma \rightsquigarrow v_t \quad \phi; \Phi; \Gamma_2 | \Theta_2 \vdash_{R_2} w : \tau \rightsquigarrow w_t}{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 | \Theta_1 + \Theta_2 \vdash_{R_1+R_2} \langle v, w \rangle : \sigma \otimes \tau \rightsquigarrow E_0} \otimes_i$$

$$\begin{aligned} E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. E_1 \\ E_1 &\triangleq \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 \\ E_2 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_3 \\ E_3 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_2 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_4 \\ E_4 &\triangleq \text{bind } v' = v_t p_1 \text{ in } E_5 \\ E_5 &\triangleq \text{bind } w' = w_t p_2 \text{ in } E_6 \\ E_6 &\triangleq \text{return } \langle v', w' \rangle \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} T_0 &\triangleq T_1 \multimap T_2 \\ T_1 &\triangleq [(R_1 + R_2)] \mathbf{1} \\ T_2 &\triangleq \mathbb{P}C_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 ((\sigma) \times (\tau)) \\ T_3 &\triangleq \mathbb{P}C_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} (R_1 + R_2) ((\sigma) \times (\tau)) \\ T_{i1} &\triangleq [R_1] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}C_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 ((\sigma)) \\ T_{i1.1} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}C_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 ((\sigma)) \end{aligned}$$

D4:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{.; \phi; \Delta; .; v' : (\sigma), w' : (\tau) \vdash \langle v', w' \rangle : (\sigma) \times (\tau)}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; v' : (\sigma), w' : (\tau) \vdash \text{return } \langle v', w' \rangle : \mathbb{P}C_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 ((\sigma) \times (\tau))}}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; v' : (\sigma), w' : (\tau) \vdash E_6 : \mathbb{P}C_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 ((\sigma) \times (\tau))}}$$

D3.2:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1} \vdash p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}}$$

D3.1:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2) \vdash w_t : T_{i2}}$$

D3:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{D3.1 \quad D3.2}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1} \vdash w_t p_2 : T_{i2.1}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}, v' : (\sigma) \vdash \text{bind } w' = w_t p_2 \text{ in } E_6 : \mathbb{P}C_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 ((\sigma) \times (\tau))}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}, v' : (\sigma) \vdash E_5 : \mathbb{P}C_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 ((\sigma) \times (\tau))}} D4$$

D2.2:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1} \vdash p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1}}$$

D2.1:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1); (\Gamma_1) \vdash v_t : T_{i1}}$$

D2:

$$\frac{\frac{D2.1 \quad D2.2}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1); (\Gamma_1), p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1} \vdash v_t \ p_1 : T_{i1.1}} \quad D3}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2), p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1}, p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{bind } v' = v_t \ p_1 \text{ in } E_5 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} ((\sigma) \times (\tau))} \quad \frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2), p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1}, p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_4 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} ((\sigma) \times (\tau))}}$$

D1:

$$\frac{\frac{D2}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; . \vdash \text{store}() : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} R_2 [R_2] \mathbf{1}} \quad \frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2), p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{bind } p_2 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_4 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} R_2 ((\sigma) \times (\tau))}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2), p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_3 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} R_2 ((\sigma) \times (\tau))}$$

D0:

$$\frac{\frac{D1}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; . \vdash \text{store}() : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} R_1 [R_1] \mathbf{1}} \quad \frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2) \vdash \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_3 : T_3}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2) \vdash E_2 : T_3}$$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{D0}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; p : T_1 \vdash p : T_1} \quad \frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2), p : T_1 \vdash \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 : T_2} \quad \frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2), p : T_1 \vdash E_1 : T_2}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2) \vdash \lambda p. E_1 : T_0} \quad \frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2) \vdash E_0 : T_0}}$$

• Pair-E:

$$\frac{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma_1 | \Theta_1 \vdash_{R_1} v : \sigma \otimes \tau \rightsquigarrow v_t \quad \phi; \Phi; \Gamma_2, x : \sigma, y : \tau | \Theta_2 \vdash_{R_2} w : \mu \rightsquigarrow w_t}{\phi; \Phi; \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 | \Theta_1 + \Theta_2 \vdash_{1+R_1+R_2} \text{let } \langle x, y \rangle = v \text{ in } t : \mu \rightsquigarrow E_0} \otimes_e$$

$$\begin{aligned} E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. E_1 \\ E_1 &\triangleq \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 \\ E_{2.0} &\triangleq \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^1 \text{ in } E_2 \\ E_2 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_3 \\ E_3 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_2 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_4 \\ E_4 &\triangleq \text{bind } m = v_t \ p_1 \text{ in } E_5 \\ E_5 &\triangleq \text{let } \langle x, y \rangle = m \text{ in } w_t \ p_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
T_0 &\triangleq T_1 \multimap T_2 \\
T_1 &\triangleq [1 + R_1 + R_2] \mathbf{1} \\
T_2 &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(-\leftarrow\delta_0)} 0 (\langle\mu\rangle) \\
T_3 &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(-\leftarrow\delta_0)} (1 + R_1 + R_2) (\langle\mu\rangle) \\
T_4 &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(-\leftarrow\delta_0)} (R_1 + R_2) (\langle\mu\rangle) \\
T_5 &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(-\leftarrow\delta_0)} (R_2) (\langle\mu\rangle) \\
T_{i1} &\triangleq [R_1] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(-\leftarrow\delta_0)} 0 (\langle\sigma\rangle \times \langle\tau\rangle) \\
T_{i1.1} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(-\leftarrow\delta_0)} 0 (\langle\sigma\rangle \times \langle\tau\rangle) \\
T_{i1.2} &\triangleq (\langle\sigma\rangle \times \langle\tau\rangle) \\
T_{i2} &\triangleq [R_2] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(-\leftarrow\delta_0)} 0 (\langle\mu\rangle)
\end{aligned}$$

D6:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1} \vdash p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}}$$

D5:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), x : \langle\sigma\rangle, y : \langle\tau\rangle \vdash w_t : T_{i2}}$$

D4.2:

$$\frac{\frac{D5 \quad D6}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}, x : \langle\sigma\rangle, y : \langle\tau\rangle \vdash w_t \quad p_2 : T_2}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}, x : \langle\sigma\rangle, y : \langle\tau\rangle \vdash w_t \quad p_2 : T_2}}$$

D4.1:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; m : T_{i1.2} \vdash m : T_{i1.2}}$$

D4:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{D4.1 \quad D4.2}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}, m : T_{i1.2} \vdash \text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = m \text{ in } w_t \quad p_2 : T_2}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}, m : T_{i1.2} \vdash E_5 : T_2}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_2), p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1}, m : T_{i1.2} \vdash E_5 : T_2}}$$

D3.2:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1} \vdash p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1}}$$

D3.1:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1); (\Gamma_1) \vdash v_t : T_{i1}}$$

D3:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{D3.1 \quad D3.2}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1); (\Gamma_1), p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1} \vdash v_t \quad p_1 : T_{i1.1}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2), p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1}, p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{bind } m = v_t \quad p_1 \text{ in } E_5 : T_2}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2), p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1}, p_2 : [R_2] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_4 : T_2}}{D4}}$$

D2:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{.; \phi; \Delta; .; . \vdash \text{store}() : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(-\leftarrow \delta_0)} R_2 ([R_2] \mathbf{1})}{D3}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2), p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{bind } p_2 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_4 : T_5}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2), p_1 : [R_1] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_3 : T_5}}$$

D1:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{.; \phi; \Delta; .; . \vdash \text{store}() : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(-\leftarrow \delta_0)} R_1 ([R_1] \mathbf{1})}{D2}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2) \vdash \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_3 : T_4}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2) \vdash E_2 : T_4}}$$

D0:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{.; \phi; \Delta; .; . \vdash \uparrow^1 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(-\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{1} \mathbf{1}}{D1}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2) \vdash \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^1 \text{ in } E_2 : T_3}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2) \vdash E_{2.0} : T_3}}$$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{.; \phi; \Delta; .; p : T_1 \vdash p : T_1}{D0}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2), p : T_1 \vdash \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_{2.0} : T_2}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2), p : T_1 \vdash E_1 : T_2}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2) \vdash \lambda p. E_1 : T_0}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta_1), (\Theta_2); (\Gamma_1), (\Gamma_2) \vdash E_0 : T_0}}$$

• Gen:

$$\frac{\phi, a; \Delta, \Phi_a; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_{R_a} v : \rho \rightsquigarrow v_t}{\phi; \Delta; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_{\max(a; \Phi_a) R_a} v : \forall a : \Phi_a. \rho \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{Gen}$$

$$\begin{aligned} E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. \text{return } (\Lambda. \Lambda. E_1) \\ E_1 &\triangleq \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_2 \\ E_2 &\triangleq \text{bind } p_1 = \text{store}() \text{ in } E_3 \\ E_3 &\triangleq v_t p_1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. E_1 \\
E_1 &\triangleq \text{bind } v' = v_t p \text{ in } E_2 \\
E_2 &\triangleq \text{return } (v' \{ \} \{ \})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
T_0 &\triangleq T_1 \multimap T_2 \\
T_1 &\triangleq [R] \mathbf{1} \\
T_2 &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho_a[I/a]) \\
T_{2.0} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho_a)[I/a] \\
T_i &\triangleq [R] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\forall a : \Phi_a \cdot \rho_a) \\
T_{i.1} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\forall a : \Phi_a \cdot \rho_a) \\
T_{i.2} &\triangleq \forall a. \Phi(a) \Rightarrow (\rho_a)
\end{aligned}$$

D0:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{.; \phi; \Delta; .; v' : v' \{ \} \{ \} : (\rho_a)[I/a]}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; v' : T_{i.2} \vdash \text{return } (v' \{ \} \{ \}) : T_{2.0}}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; v' : T_{i.2} \vdash E_2 : T_{2.0}}}{D0}$$

D0.1:

$$\frac{.; \phi; \Delta; .; p : T_1 \vdash p : T_1}{D0.1}$$

D0.0:

$$\frac{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) \vdash v_t : T_i}{D0.0}$$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{D0.0 \quad D0.1}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : T_1 \vdash v_t p : T_{i.1}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : T_1 \vdash \text{bind } v' = v_t p \text{ in } E_2 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho_a)[I/a]}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : T_1 \vdash \text{bind } v' = v_t p \text{ in } E_2 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\rho_a)[I/a]}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma), p : T_1 \vdash E_1 : T_2} \text{ Lemma 55}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) \vdash \lambda p. E_1 : T_0}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) \vdash E_0 : T_0}$$

• Coerce:

$$\frac{\phi; \Delta; \Gamma | \Theta \vdash_R t : \nu \rightsquigarrow t_t \quad \phi; \Delta \vdash \nu \sqsubseteq \mu \quad \phi; \Delta \vdash R \leq R'}{\phi; \Delta; \Gamma' | \Theta' \vdash_{R'} t : \mu \rightsquigarrow E_0} \text{Coerce}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &\triangleq \lambda p. E_1 \\
E_1 &\triangleq \text{let}\langle p', - \rangle = \text{Split } p \text{ in } E_2 \\
E_2 &\triangleq \text{bind } x = (t'_t p') \text{ in } E_3 \\
E_3 &\triangleq \text{return } (f x)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
T_0 &\triangleq [R'] \mathbf{1} \multimap T_2 \\
T_1 &\triangleq [R'] \mathbf{1} \\
T_2 &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \langle \mu \rangle
\end{aligned}$$

D4:

$$\frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; p' : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash p' : [R] \mathbf{1}}$$

D3:

$$\frac{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) : \vdash t_t : [R] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \langle \nu \rangle \quad \text{IH}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta'); (\Gamma') : \vdash t'_t : [R] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \langle \nu \rangle} \text{Lemma 52}$$

D2:

$$\frac{D3 \quad D4}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta'); (\Gamma') \vdash t'_t p' : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 \langle \nu \rangle}$$

D1:

$$\frac{\phi; \Delta \vdash \nu \sqsubseteq \mu}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; . \vdash f : \langle \nu \rangle \multimap \langle \mu \rangle} \text{Lemma 53}$$

D0.0:

$$\frac{D1 \quad \frac{.; \phi; \Delta; .; x : \langle \nu \rangle \vdash x : \langle \nu \rangle}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; x : \langle \nu \rangle \vdash (f x) : \langle \mu \rangle}}{.; \phi; \Delta; .; x : \langle \nu \rangle \vdash \text{return } (f x) : T_2}$$

D0:

$$\frac{D2 \quad D0.0}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta'); (\Gamma'), p' : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{bind } x = (t'_t p') \text{ in return } (f x) : T_2} \frac{}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta'); (\Gamma'), p' : [R] \mathbf{1} \vdash E_2 : T_2}$$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{.; \phi; \Delta; .; p : T_1 \vdash \text{Split } p : [R] \mathbf{1} \times - \quad D0}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta'); (\Gamma'), p : T_1 \vdash \text{let}\langle p', - \rangle = \text{Split } p \text{ in } E_2 :}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta'); (\Gamma'), p : T_1 \vdash E_1 : T_2}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta'); (\Gamma') \vdash \lambda p. E_1 : T_0}}{.; \phi; \Delta; (\Theta'); (\Gamma') \vdash E_0 : T_0}$$

□

Definition 48 (Coercion function). $\text{convert } F \ X \triangleq \text{let } !f = F \text{ in let } !x = X \text{ in } !(f \ x)$

Lemma 49 (Convert is well-typed). $\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \cdot \vdash \text{convert} :$

$$!_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \multimap !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \tau_1 \multimap !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \tau_2$$

Proof. Let $S' = \{(a, 0) \mid a \in S\}$

D2.2

$$\frac{}{\cdot; a; a \in S; x : \sum_{b \in \{0\}} 1 \tau_1[a + b/a]; \cdot \vdash x : \tau_1}$$

D2.1:

$$\frac{}{\cdot; a; a \in S; f : \sum_{b \in \{0\}} 1 (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2)[a + b/a]; \cdot \vdash f : \tau_1 \multimap \tau_2}$$

D2:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{D2.1 \quad D2.2}{\cdot; a; a \in S; f : \sum_{b \in \{0\}} 1 (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2)[a + b/a], x : \sum_{b \in \{0\}} 1 \tau_1[a + b/a]; \cdot \vdash (f \ x) : \tau_2} \quad \cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \sum_{a \in S} R_a \cdot f : \sum_{b \in \{0\}} 1 (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2)[a + b/a], x : \sum_{b \in \{0\}} 1 \tau_1[a + b/a]; \cdot \vdash \text{!(f x)} : !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \tau_2}{\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; f : \sum_{a \in S'} R_a (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2), x : \sum_{a \in S} R_a \tau_1; \cdot \vdash \text{!(f x)} : !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \tau_2} \text{T-subExpI}}{\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; f : \sum_{a \in S} R_a (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2), x : \sum_{a \in S} R_a \tau_1; \cdot \vdash \text{!(f x)} : !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \tau_2} \text{Definition 23}$$

T-sub

D1:

$$\frac{\frac{\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; f : \sum_{a \in S} R_a (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2); X : !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \tau_1 \vdash \text{!(f x)}}{\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; f : \sum_{a \in S} R_a (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2); \cdot \vdash \text{let } !x = X \text{ in } !(f \ x)} D2}{\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; f : \sum_{a \in S} R_a (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2); \cdot \vdash \text{let } !x = X \text{ in } !(f \ x)}$$

D0:

$$\frac{\frac{\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \cdot; F : !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \vdash F : !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2)}{\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \cdot; F : !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \vdash \text{let } !f = F \text{ in let } !x = X \text{ in } !(f \ x)} \text{T-var1} \quad D1}{\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \cdot; F : !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \vdash \text{let } !f = F \text{ in let } !x = X \text{ in } !(f \ x)}$$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{D0}{\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \cdot; F : !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \vdash \lambda X. \text{let } !f = F \text{ in let } !x = X \text{ in } !(f \ x)}}{\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \vdash \lambda F. \lambda X. \text{let } !f = F \text{ in let } !x = X \text{ in } !(f \ x) : !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \multimap !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \tau_1 \multimap !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \tau_2} D0}{\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \vdash \lambda F. \lambda X. \text{let } !f = F \text{ in let } !x = X \text{ in } !(f \ x) : !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} (\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \multimap !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \tau_1 \multimap !_{\sum_{a \in S} R_a} \tau_2}$$

□

Lemma 50 (Substitution lemma for Γ). $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma', x : \tau \vdash e : \sigma \wedge$

$$\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \cdot; \Gamma'' \vdash e' : \tau \wedge \text{dom}(\Gamma') \cap \text{dom}(\Gamma'') = \emptyset$$

\implies

$$\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma' \oplus \Gamma'' \vdash e[e'/z] : \sigma$$

Proof. Proof by induction on $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma, x : \sigma \vdash e : \tau$. We describe some of the cases of the proofs, other cases are similar.

- Case T-var1:

$$\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; x : \tau \vdash x : \tau} \text{T-var1}$$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma' \vdash e' : \tau} \text{Given}$$

- T-var2, T-unit, T-tt, T-ff, T-zero, T-real, T-nil: Vacuous
- T-succ:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash n : \mathbf{N}(n)}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash S n : \mathbf{N}(n+1)} \text{T-succ}$$

Let $\Gamma = \Gamma', x : \tau$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma' \oplus \Gamma'' \vdash n[e'/x] : \mathbf{N}(n)} \text{IH}}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma' \oplus \Gamma'' \vdash S n[e'/x] : \mathbf{N}(n+1)} \text{T-succ}$$

- T-matchN:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : \mathbf{N}(n) \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta, n = 0; \Omega; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_0 : \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta, i; \Delta, i + 1 = n; \Omega, y : \mathbf{N}(i); \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S y) \mapsto e_1 : \tau} \text{T-matchN}$$

Two cases arise

- $x \in \Gamma_1$:

Let $\Gamma_1 = \Gamma', x : \tau$

D0:

$$\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma' \oplus \Gamma'' \vdash e[e'/x] : \mathbf{N}(n)} \text{IH}$$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{D0 \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta, n = 0; \Omega; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_0 : \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta, i; \Delta, i + 1 = n; \Omega, y : \mathbf{N}(i); \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 : \tau}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma' \oplus \Gamma_2 \oplus \Gamma'' \vdash \text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S y) \mapsto e_1[e'/x] : \tau} \text{T-matchN}$$

– $x \in \Gamma_2$:

Let $\Gamma_2 = \Gamma', x : \tau$

D2:

$$\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta, i; \Delta, i + 1 = n; \Omega; \Gamma', y : \mathbf{N}(i) \oplus \Gamma'' \vdash e_1[e'/x] : \tau} \text{IH2}$$

D1:

$$\frac{}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta, n = 0; \Omega; \Gamma' \oplus \Gamma'' \vdash e_0[e'/x] : \tau} \text{IH1}$$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : \mathbf{N}(n) \quad D1 \quad D2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma' \oplus \Gamma_2 \oplus \Gamma'' \vdash \text{matchN } e, Z \mapsto e_0, (S y) \mapsto e_1[e'/x] : \tau} \text{T-matchN}$$

• T-cons:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \tau[0/i] \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : L_{i < n+1} \tau[(i+1)/i]}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1, \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 :: e_2 : L_{i < n+1} \tau} \text{T-cons}$$

Two cases arise

– $x \in \Gamma_1$:

Let $\Gamma_1 = \Gamma', x : \tau$

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma' \oplus \Gamma'' \vdash e_1[e'/x] : \tau[0/i] \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : L_{i < n+1} \tau[(i+1)/i]}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1, \Omega_2; \Gamma' \oplus \Gamma_2 \vdash e_1 :: e_2[e'/x] : L_{i < n+1} \tau} \text{T-cons}$$

– $x \in \Gamma_2$:

Let $\Gamma_2 = \Gamma', x : \tau$

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \tau[0/i] \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_2; \Gamma' \oplus \Gamma'' \vdash e_2[e'/x] : L_{i < n+1} \tau[(i+1)/i]}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1, \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \oplus \Gamma' \oplus \Gamma'' \vdash e_1 :: e_2[e'/x] : L_{i < n+1} \tau} \text{T-cons}$$

• T-sub:

$$\frac{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega; \Gamma_2 \vdash e : \tau \quad \Psi; \Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau <: \tau' \quad \Psi; \Theta \models \Gamma_1 <: \Gamma_2 \quad \Psi; \Theta \models \Omega_1 <: \Omega_2}{\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash e : \tau'} \text{T-sub}$$

Let $\Gamma_1 = \Gamma', x : \tau$

From Fig 8 two cases arise:

– sub-lBase:

In this case we know that there is no free x in e and we get the desired from T-sub.

– sub-lInd:

In this case we get the desired from IH and T-sub.

□

Lemma 51 (Substitution lemma for Ω). $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega, x : \sum_{a \leq I} R_a \sigma; \Gamma \vdash e : \tau \wedge \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega'; \cdot \vdash !e' : !\sum_{a \leq J} R_a \sigma \wedge \text{dom}(\Omega) \cap \text{dom}(\Omega') = \emptyset \wedge I \leq J$
 \implies
 $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; \Omega', \Omega; \Gamma \vdash e[e'/x] : \tau$

Proof. Similar reasoning as in Lemma 50.

□

Lemma 52 (Subtyping context lemma). $\Theta; \Delta \vdash (\Gamma' | \Theta') \sqsubseteq (\Gamma | \Theta) \wedge \Psi; \Theta; \Delta; (\Theta); (\Gamma) \vdash e : \tau$
 \implies
 $\exists e'$ in Probabilistic λ -amor s.t. $\Psi; \Theta; \Delta; (\Theta'); (\Gamma') \vdash e' : \tau$

Proof. Directly using Lemma 50, Lemma 51 and Lemma 53

□

Lemma 53 (Subtyping lemma). $\Theta; \Delta \vdash \sigma \sqsubseteq \tau \implies \exists f$ in Probabilistic λ -amor s.t. $\cdot; \Theta; \Delta; \cdot; \cdot \vdash f : (\sigma) \multimap (\tau)$

Proof. Proof by induction on the $\Theta; \Delta \vdash \sigma \sqsubseteq \tau$ relation

• Case NAT:

$$\frac{\Theta, a; \Delta, \Phi_1 \models \Phi_2}{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \text{Nat}(a | \Phi_1) \sqsubseteq \text{Nat}(a | \Phi_2)}$$

To prove: $\exists f : (\text{Nat}(a | \Phi_1)) \multimap (\text{Nat}(a | \Phi_2))$

We choose $\lambda x.x$ as the function. This can be type checked using sub-exist and sub-CAnd.

• Case ARR:

$$\frac{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau \sqsubseteq \sigma \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash \mu \sqsubseteq \nu}{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \sigma \multimap \mu \sqsubseteq \tau \multimap \nu}$$

To prove: $\exists f : (\sigma \multimap \mu) \multimap (\tau \multimap \nu)$

From IH1 and IH2 we have

$f_{i1} : (\tau) \multimap (\sigma)$

$$f_{i2} : \langle \mu \rangle \multimap \langle \nu \rangle$$

We choose $\lambda f_1 t. f_{i2} f_1 (f_{i1} t)$ as the required function.

where

$$f_1 : \langle \sigma \rangle \multimap \langle \mu \rangle$$

- Case \otimes :

$$\frac{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \sigma_1 \sqsubseteq \tau_1 \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash \sigma_2 \sqsubseteq \tau_2}{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_2 \sqsubseteq \tau_1 \otimes \tau_2}$$

To prove: $\exists f : \langle \sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_2 \rangle \multimap \langle \tau_1 \otimes \tau_2 \rangle$

From IH1 and IH2 we have

$$f_{i1} : \langle \sigma_1 \rangle \multimap \langle \tau_1 \rangle$$

$$f_{i2} : \langle \sigma_2 \rangle \multimap \langle \tau_2 \rangle$$

We choose $\lambda p. \text{let} \langle x, y \rangle = p$ in E_1 as the required function.

where

$$E_1 \triangleq \langle f_{i1} x, f_{i2} y \rangle$$

$$f_1 : \langle \sigma_1 \rangle \times \langle \sigma_2 \rangle$$

- Case \forall -L:

$$\frac{\Theta; \Delta \models \Phi_a[I/a] \quad \Theta; \Delta \vdash \sigma_a[I/a] \sqsubseteq \tau}{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \forall a : \Phi_a. \sigma_a \sqsubseteq \tau}$$

To prove: $\exists f : \langle \forall a : \Phi_a. \sigma_a \rangle \multimap \langle \tau \rangle$

From IH we have $f_i : \langle \sigma_a[I/a] \rangle \multimap \langle \tau \rangle$

We choose $\lambda q. f_i (\text{Purify } (q \{ \} \{ \}))$ as the required function.

- Case \forall -R:

$$\frac{\Theta, a; \Delta, \Phi_a \vdash \sigma_a \sqsubseteq \tau}{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \sigma_a \sqsubseteq \forall a : \Phi_a. \tau}$$

To prove: $\exists f : \langle \sigma_a \rangle \multimap \langle \forall a : \Phi_a. \tau \rangle$

From IH we have $f_i : \langle \sigma_a \rangle \multimap \langle \tau \rangle$

We choose $\lambda s. \Lambda. \Lambda. \text{return } f_i s$ as the required function.

- Case CONV:

$$\frac{\sigma \triangleright \forall a : \Phi_a . \sigma_a \quad \Theta, a; \Delta, \Phi_a \vdash \tau \sqsubseteq \forall a : \Phi_a . \sigma_a \multimap \mu}{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau \sqsubseteq \sigma \multimap \mu}$$

To prove: $\exists f : (\tau) \multimap (\sigma) \multimap (\mu)$

From IH we have $f_i : (\tau) \multimap (\forall a : \Phi_a . \sigma_a) \multimap (\mu)$

Also from Lemma 54 we know that we have $f : (\sigma) \multimap (\forall a : \Phi_a . \sigma_a)$

We choose $\lambda t . \lambda s . (f_i t) (f s)$ as the required function.

- Case COUPLING:

$$\frac{\Theta; \Delta \vdash S \triangleleft \langle \mu \& \nu \rangle \text{ for some index term } S}{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \mu \sqsubseteq \nu}$$

To prove: $\exists f : (\mu) \multimap (\nu)$

We choose $\lambda x . x$ as the required function and type check it using the sub-coupling rule

□

Lemma 54 (Conversion lemma). $\Theta; \Delta \vdash \sigma \triangleright \tau \implies$

$\exists f$ in Probabilistic λ -amor s.t. $\cdot; \Theta; \Delta; \cdot; \cdot \vdash f : (\sigma) \multimap (\tau)$

Proof. Proof by induction on the $\Theta; \Delta \vdash \sigma \triangleright \tau$ relation

- Case 1:

$$\overline{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \text{Nat}(a|\Phi) \triangleright \exists a : \Phi . \text{Nat}(a)}$$

To prove: $\exists f : (\text{Nat}(a|\Phi)) \multimap (\exists a : \Phi . \text{Nat}(a))$

We choose $\lambda x . x$ as the required function and type check it using the sub-exist and sub-CAnd rules.

- Case 2:

$$\frac{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \sigma \triangleright \exists a : \Phi . \sigma'}{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \sigma \otimes \tau \triangleright \exists a : \Phi . (\sigma' \otimes \tau)}$$

To prove: $\exists f : (\sigma \otimes \tau) \multimap (\exists a : \Phi . (\sigma' \otimes \tau))$

From IH we have $f_i : (\sigma) \multimap (\exists a : \Phi . \sigma')$

We choose $\lambda p. \text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = p$ in E_1 as the required function.

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &\triangleq \text{letEx } z = f_i x \text{ in } E_2 \\ E_2 &\triangleq \text{Ex}.\Lambda.\langle z, y \rangle \end{aligned}$$

- Case 3:

$$\frac{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \tau \triangleright \exists a : \Phi.\tau'}{\Theta; \Delta \vdash \sigma \otimes \tau \triangleright \exists a : \Phi.(\sigma \otimes \tau')}$$

To prove: $\exists f : (\sigma \otimes \tau) \multimap (\exists a : \Phi.(\sigma \otimes \tau'))$

From IH we have $f_i : (\tau) \multimap (\exists a : \Phi.\tau')$

We choose $\lambda p. \text{let}\langle x, y \rangle = p$ in E_1 as the required function.

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &\triangleq \text{letEx } z = f_i y \text{ in } E_2 \\ E_2 &\triangleq \text{Ex}.\Lambda.\langle x, z \rangle \end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 55 (Index Substitution lemma). $\forall \tau, \sigma, \mu \in \ell\text{RPCF}$.

1. $\langle \tau \rangle [J/b] = \langle \tau [J/b] \rangle$
2. $\langle \sigma \rangle [J/b] = \langle \sigma [J/b] \rangle$
3. $\langle \mu \rangle [J/b] = \langle \mu [J/b] \rangle$

Proof. By simultaneous induction on τ, σ, μ

Proof of statement 1

1. $\tau = \text{Nat}(a|\Phi_a)$:

$$\begin{aligned} &\langle \text{Nat}(a|\Phi_a) \rangle [J/b] \\ &= \langle \exists a : \mathbb{N}.\Phi(a) \wedge \mathbf{N}(a) \rangle [J/b] \\ &= \langle \exists a : \mathbb{N}.\Phi(a)[J/b] \wedge \mathbf{N}(a)[J/b] \rangle \\ &= \langle \text{Nat}(a|\Phi_a)[J/b] \rangle \end{aligned}$$

2. $\tau = \tau_1 \otimes \tau_2$:

$$\begin{aligned} &\langle \tau_1 \otimes \tau_2 \rangle [J/b] \\ &= \langle (\tau_1) \times (\tau_2) \rangle [J/b] \\ &= \langle \tau_1 \rangle [J/b] \times \langle \tau_2 \rangle [J/b] \\ &= \langle \tau_1 [J/b] \otimes \tau_2 [J/b] \rangle \\ &= \langle \tau_1 \otimes \tau_2 \rangle [J/b] \end{aligned}$$

3. $\tau = \sigma$:

From proof of statement 2

Proof of statement 2

- $\rho = \tau' \multimap \mu$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & ((\tau' \multimap \mu) [J/b]) \\
 = & ((\tau') \multimap ([1] (\mu))) [J/b] \\
 = & (\tau' [J/b] \multimap ([1] (\mu) [J/b])) \\
 = & (\tau' [J/b] \multimap ([1] (\mu [J/b]))) \quad (\text{From proof of statement 1 and 3}) \\
 = & (\tau' [J/b] \multimap \mu [J/b])
 \end{aligned}$$
- $\rho = \forall a : \Phi_a . \rho_a$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & ((\forall a : \Phi_a . \rho_a) [J/b]) \\
 = & (\forall a . \Phi_a \Rightarrow (\rho_a)) [J/b] \\
 = & \forall a . \Phi_a [J/b] \Rightarrow (\rho_a [J/b]) \\
 = & \forall a . \Phi_a [J/b] \Rightarrow (\rho_a [J/b]) \quad (\text{From IH}) \\
 = & (\forall a : \Phi_a [J/b] . \rho_a [J/b])
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof of statement 3

- $\mu = \{P_a : \sigma_a \mid a \leq I\}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & ((\{P_a : \sigma_a \mid a \leq I\}) [J/b]) \\
 = & (\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(c \leftarrow \nu)} 0 (\sigma [c/a])) [J/b] \\
 = & \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(c \leftarrow \nu')} 0 ((\sigma [c/a]) [J/b]) \\
 = & \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(c \leftarrow \nu')} 0 ((\sigma [c/a] [J/b])) \quad (\text{From proof of statement 1}) \\
 = & ((\{P_a [J/b] : \sigma_a [J/b] \mid a \leq I [J/b]\})) \\
 = & ((\{P_a : \sigma_a \mid a \leq I\} [J/b]))
 \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\nu = (C, M)$$

$$C = \{a \mid a \leq I\}$$

$$M = \{a \mapsto P_a \mid a \leq I\}$$

$$\nu' = (C', M')$$

$$C' = \{a \mid a \leq I [J/b]\}$$

$$M' = \{a \mapsto P_a [J/b] \mid a \leq I [J/b]\}$$

□

4 Examples

4.1 Randomized Response

```

1  RR : ∀v : ℕ, v' : ℕ, k : ℕ.
2      !N(v)
3      ↪ !N(v')
4      ↪ !N(k)
5      ↪ [(2 -  $\frac{1}{2^{k-1}}$ )] 1
6      ↪ PC(a←δ₀) 0 (∃v'' : ℕ. N(v''))
7  fix RR.Λ.Λ.Λ.λ vl vl' n p.
8      let! vlu = vl in
9      let! vl'u = vl' in
10     let! nu = n in
11     matchN nu
12     , Z ↪ return (Ex vl'u)
13     , S n' ↪
14     release _ = p in
15     bind _ = ↑1 in
16     bind x = Unif 1 in
17     matchN x
18     , Z ↪ bind p' = Store () in f !vlu !vl'u !n' p'
19     , S x' ↪ return (Ex vlu)

```

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &\triangleq \text{fix } RR.\Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\lambda \text{ vl vl' n p}.E_1 \\
E_1 &\triangleq \text{let! } vl_u = vl \text{ in } E_2 \\
E_2 &\triangleq \text{let! } vl'_u = vl' \text{ in } E_3 \\
E_3 &\triangleq \text{let! } n_u = n \text{ in } E_4 \\
E_4 &\triangleq \text{matchN } n_u, Z \mapsto E_5, S n' \mapsto E_6 \\
E_5 &\triangleq \text{return (Ex } vl'_u) \\
E_6 &\triangleq \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_{7.1} \\
E_{7.1} &\triangleq \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^1 \text{ in } E_{7.2} \\
E_{7.2} &\triangleq \text{bind } x = \text{Unif } 1 \text{ in } E_{7.3} \\
E_{7.3} &\triangleq \text{matchN } x, Z \mapsto E_8, S x' \mapsto E_9 \\
E_8 &\triangleq \text{bind } p' = \text{Store } () \text{ in } f !vl_u !vl'_u !n' p' \\
E_9 &\triangleq \text{return (Ex } vl_u)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
T_0 &\triangleq \forall v : \mathbb{N}, v' : \mathbb{N}, k : \mathbb{N}. T_1 \\
T_1 &\triangleq T_{vl} \multimap T_{v'l'} \multimap T_k \multimap T_p \multimap T_r \\
T_{vl} &\triangleq !\mathbf{N}(v) \\
T_{v'l'} &\triangleq !\mathbf{N}(v') \\
T_k &\triangleq !\mathbf{N}(k) \\
T_p &\triangleq [(2 - \frac{1}{2^{k-1}})] \mathbf{1} \\
T_r &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\exists v'' : \mathbb{N}. \mathbf{N}(v'')) \\
T_{r1} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} (2 - \frac{1}{2^{k-1}}) (\exists v'' : \mathbb{N}. \mathbf{N}(v'')) \\
T_{r2} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} (1 - \frac{1}{2^{k-1}}) (\exists v'' : \mathbb{N}. \mathbf{N}(v'')) \\
T_{r2'} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu'')} (1 - \frac{1}{2^{k-1}}) (\exists v'' : \mathbb{N}. \mathbf{N}(v'')) \\
T_{r3} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \kappa(a) (\exists v'' : \mathbb{N}. \mathbf{N}(v'')) \\
\mu &\triangleq \{(0, 1), (0 \mapsto 0.5, 1 \mapsto 0.5)\} \\
\kappa(a) &\triangleq \text{if } a = 0 \text{ then } (2 - \frac{1}{2^{k-2}}) \text{ else } 0 \\
T_{r3'} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu')} \kappa(a) (\exists v'' : \mathbb{N}. \mathbf{N}(v'')) \\
\mu' &\triangleq \delta_0 \otimes \delta_0 \\
\mu'' &\triangleq \mu \otimes \delta_0
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\Theta_0 &\triangleq v : \mathbb{N}, v' : \mathbb{N}, k : \mathbb{N} \\
\Theta_1 &\triangleq v : \mathbb{N}, v' : \mathbb{N}, k : \mathbb{N}, j : \mathbb{N} \\
\Delta_0 &\triangleq j + 1 = k
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\Omega_0 &\triangleq RR : T_0 \\
\Omega_1 &\triangleq RR : T_0, vl_u : \mathbf{N}(v) \\
\Omega_2 &\triangleq RR : T_0, vl_u : \mathbf{N}(v), vl'_u : \mathbf{N}(v') \\
\Omega_3 &\triangleq RR : T_0, vl_u : \mathbf{N}(v), vl'_u : \mathbf{N}(v'), n_u : \mathbf{N}(k) \\
\Omega_4 &\triangleq RR : T_0, vl_u : \mathbf{N}(v), vl'_u : \mathbf{N}(v'), n_u : \mathbf{N}(k), n' : \mathbf{N}(j)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\Gamma_0 &\triangleq vl : T_{vl}, v'l' : T_{v'l'}, n : T_n, p : T_p \\
\Gamma_1 &\triangleq v'l' : T_{v'l'}, n : T_n, p : T_p \\
\Gamma_2 &\triangleq n : T_n, p : T_p \\
\Gamma_3 &\triangleq p : T_p \\
\Gamma_4 &\triangleq x : \mathbf{N}(a) \\
\Gamma_5 &\triangleq p' : [(2 - \frac{1}{2^{k-2}})] \mathbf{1}
\end{aligned}$$

D9:

$$\frac{.; \Theta_1, i; \Delta_0, i + 1 = a; \Omega_4; x' : \mathbf{N}(i) \vdash \text{return } (\text{Ex } vl_u) : T_r}{.; \Theta_1, i; \Delta_0, i + 1 = a; \Omega_4; x' : \mathbf{N}(i) \vdash E_9 : T_{r3}}$$

D8.1:

$$\frac{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_0, a = 0; \Omega_4; \Gamma_5 \vdash f !vl_u !vl'_u !n' p' : T_r}{.}$$

D8.0:

$$\frac{.}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_0, a = 0; \Omega_4; . \vdash \text{Store } () : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} (2 - \frac{1}{2^{k-2}}) ([(2 - \frac{1}{2^{k-2}})] \mathbf{1})}$$

D8:

$$\frac{\frac{D8.0 \quad D8.1}{\frac{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_0, a = 0; \Omega_4; \cdot \vdash \text{bind } p' = \text{Store } () \text{ in } f !vl_u !vl'_u !n' p' : T_{r3'}}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_0, a = 0; \Omega_4; \cdot \vdash \text{bind } p' = \text{Store } () \text{ in } f !vl_u !vl'_u !n' p' : T_{r3}} \text{sub-coupling}}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_0, a = 0; \Omega_4; \cdot \vdash E_8 : T_{r3}}$$

D7:

$$\frac{\frac{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_0; \Omega_4; x : \mathbf{N}(a) \vdash x : \mathbf{N}(a)}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_0; \Omega_4; \Gamma_4 \vdash \text{matchN } x, Z \mapsto E_8, S _ \mapsto E_9 : T_{r3}}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_0; \Omega_4; \Gamma_4 \vdash E_{7.3} : T_{r3}} \quad D8 \quad D9$$

D6:

$$\frac{\frac{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_0; \Omega_4; \cdot \vdash \text{Unif } 1 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \mathbf{N}(a)}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_0; \Omega_4; \cdot \vdash \text{bind } x = \text{Unif } 1 \text{ in } E_{7.3} : T_{r2'}}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_0; \Omega_4; \cdot \vdash \text{bind } x = \text{Unif } 1 \text{ in } E_{7.3} : T_{r2}} \text{sub-coupling} \quad D7$$

D5:

$$\frac{\frac{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_0; \Omega_4; \cdot \vdash \uparrow^1 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 1 \mathbf{1}}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_0; \Omega_4; \cdot \vdash \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^1 \text{ in } E_{7.2} : T_{r1}}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_0; \Omega_4; \cdot \vdash E_{7.1} : T_{r1}} \quad D6$$

D4:

$$\frac{\frac{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_0; \Omega_4; \Gamma_3 \vdash p : T_p}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_0; \Omega_4; \Gamma_3 \vdash \text{release } _ = p \text{ in } E_{7.1} : T_r}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_0; \Omega_4; \Gamma_3 \vdash E_6 : T_r} \quad D5$$

D3:

$$\frac{\frac{.; \Theta_0; \cdot; \Omega_3; \Gamma_3 \vdash (\text{Ex } vl'_u) : \exists v'' : \mathbb{N}. \mathbf{N}(v'') \quad \Theta_0; \cdot \vdash v' : \mathbb{N}}{.; \Theta_0; \cdot; \Omega_3; \Gamma_3 \vdash \text{return } (\text{Ex } vl'_u) : T_r}{.; \Theta_0; \cdot; \Omega_3; \Gamma_3 \vdash E_5 : T_r}}$$

D2:

$$\frac{\frac{.; \Theta_0; \cdot; \Omega_3; \cdot \vdash n_u : \mathbf{N}(k)}{.; \Theta_0; \cdot; \Omega_3; \Gamma_3 \vdash \text{matchN } n_u, Z \mapsto E_5, S n' \mapsto E_6 : T_r}{.; \Theta_0; \cdot; \Omega_3; \Gamma_3 \vdash E_4 : T_r} \quad D3 \quad D4$$

D1:

$$\frac{\frac{.; \Theta_0; \cdot; \Omega_2; n : T_k \vdash n : T_k}{.; \Theta_0; \cdot; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{let! } n_u = n \text{ in } E_4 : T_r}{.; \Theta_0; \cdot; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash E_3 : T_r} \quad D2$$

D0:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_1; vl' : T_{vl'} \vdash vl' : T_{vl'}}{D1}}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash \text{let! } vl'_u = vl' \text{ in } E_3 : T_r}}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash E_2 : T_r}$$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_0; vl : T_{vl} \vdash vl : T_{vl}}{D0}}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_0; \Gamma_0 \vdash \text{let! } vl_u = vl \text{ in } E_2 : T_r}}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_0; \Gamma_0 \vdash E_1 : T_r}}{.; .; .; \Omega_0; . \vdash \Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\lambda vl vl' n p.E_1 : T_0}}{.; .; .; . \vdash \text{fix } RR.\Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\lambda vl vl' n p.E_1 : T_0}$$

Theorem 56 (Expected loss of RR). The expected cost of RR is bounded by $(2 - \frac{1}{2^{k-1}})$

Proof. Directly from the typing derivation of RR . □

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}[loss_t] &= \sum_{i < n} \mathbb{P}[selecting\ i] \cdot loss_i(t) \\
&= \sum_{i < n} \frac{w_i(t)}{\phi(t)} \cdot loss_i(t) \\
&= \frac{1}{\phi(t)} \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot loss_i(t) \\
\phi(t+1) &= \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot (1 - \eta \cdot loss_i(t)) \\
&= \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) - \eta \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot loss_i(t) \\
&= \phi(t)(1 - \eta \cdot \mathbb{E}[loss_t]) \\
&\leq \phi(t) \cdot \exp(-\eta \cdot \mathbb{E}[loss_t]) \\
\mathbb{E}[loss_t] &\leq \frac{\log \phi(t) - \log \phi(t+1)}{\eta}
\end{aligned}$$

Figure 11: Constraints for RWM

<pre> 1 makePred : ∀n : ℕ, adv : ℕ → ℬ, η : ℝ⁺, 2 ans : ℬ, w : ℕ → ℝ⁺. 3 ∀p : ℝ⁺. (p ≥ EL) ⇒ [p] 1 ⇝ 4 L_{i < n} B(adv i) ⇝ L_{i < n} R(w i) ⇝ 5 PC_(a ← δ₀) 0 (B) 6 makePred ≐ Λ.Λ.Λ.Λ.Λ.Λ.Λ.λ po advs wts. 7 let! wts_u = wts in 8 letEx phi = sum !wts_u in 9 let! phi_u = phi in 10 let! prob_u = map !(λx.x/phi_u) !wts_u in 11 release _ = po in 12 bind x = toDist prob_u in 13 let pred = lookup x advs in 14 bind _ = ↑(loss (adv x') ans) in 15 return (Ex pred) </pre>	<pre> EL ≐ ∑_{i < n} (prob i) · (loss (adv i) (ans)) prob ≐ λi.(w i)/φ loss ≐ λfs.if f == s then 0 else 1 φ ≐ ∑_{i < n} w i </pre>
--	--

Typing for *makePred*

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &\triangleq \text{let! } wts_u = wts \text{ in } E_1 \\
E_1 &\triangleq \text{letEx } phi = \text{sum } !wts_u \text{ in } E_2 \\
E_2 &\triangleq \text{let! } phi_u = phi \text{ in } E_3 \\
E_3 &\triangleq \text{let! } prob_u = \text{map } !(\lambda x.x/phi_u) \text{ !}wts_u \text{ in } E_4 \\
E_4 &\triangleq \text{release } _ = po \text{ in } E_5 \\
E_5 &\triangleq \text{bind } x = \text{toDist } prob_u \text{ in } E_6 \\
E_6 &\triangleq \text{let } pred = \text{lookup } x \text{ advs in } E_7 \\
E_7 &\triangleq \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^{|\text{adv } x' - \text{ans}|} \text{ in } E_8 \\
E_8 &\triangleq \text{return } (Ex \text{ pred})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\Theta &\triangleq n : \mathbb{N}, \text{adv} : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{B}, \eta : \mathbb{R}^+, \text{ans} : \mathbb{B}, w : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \\
\Theta_1 &\triangleq \Theta, \phi : \mathbb{R}^+ \\
\Delta &\triangleq p \geq EL \\
\Delta_1 &\triangleq p \geq EL, \phi \\
\Delta_2 &\triangleq p \geq EL, \phi, x' \\
\Gamma &\triangleq po : T_p, \text{advs} : !T_a, wts : !T_w \\
\Gamma_1 &\triangleq po : T_p, \text{advs} : !T_a \\
\Gamma_2 &\triangleq \text{advs} : !T_a \\
\Gamma_3 &\triangleq \text{advs} : !T_a, x : \mathbf{N}(x') \\
\Gamma_4 &\triangleq \text{pred} : \mathbf{B}(\text{adv } x') \\
\Omega_1 &\triangleq wts_u : T_w, phi_u : \mathbf{R}(\phi) \\
\Omega_2 &\triangleq wts_u : T_w, phi_u : \mathbf{R}(\phi), prob_u : L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(pr \ i)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
T_0 &\triangleq \forall n : \mathbb{N}, \text{adv} : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{B}, \eta : \mathbb{R}^+, \text{ans} : \mathbb{B}, w : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+. T_1 \\
T_1 &\triangleq \forall p : \mathbb{R}^+. (p \geq EL) \Rightarrow T_2 \\
T_2 &\triangleq T_p \multimap !T_a \multimap !T_w \multimap T_r \\
T_p &\triangleq [p] \mathbf{1} \\
T_a &\triangleq L_{i < n} \mathbf{B}(\text{adv } i) \\
T_w &\triangleq L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(w \ i) \\
T_r &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbf{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\mathbf{B}) \\
\mu_{1.1} &\triangleq (\{0, \dots, n-1\}, \{i \mapsto pr \ i \mid i < n\}) \\
\mu_1 &\triangleq \mu_{1.1} \otimes x'.\delta_0 \\
\mu_{1.2} &\triangleq \delta_0 \otimes _.\delta_0 \\
pr &\triangleq \lambda i.w \ i/\phi
\end{aligned}$$

D7:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\cdot; \Theta_1; \Delta_2; \Omega_2; \Gamma_4 \vdash \text{pred} : \mathbf{B}(\text{adv } x')}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \Delta_2; \Omega_2; \Gamma_4 \vdash Ex \text{ pred} : \mathbf{B}}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \Delta_2; \Omega_2; \Gamma_4 \vdash \text{return } (Ex \text{ pred}) : T_r}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \Delta_2; \Omega_2; \Gamma_4 \vdash E_8 : T_r}$$

D6:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_2; \Omega_2; \cdot \vdash \uparrow^{|adv\ x' - ans|} : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(_ \leftarrow \delta_0)} |adv\ x' - ans| \mathbf{1}} \quad D7 \\
\frac{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_2; \Omega_2; \Gamma_4 \vdash \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^{|adv\ x' - ans|} \text{ in } E_8 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(_ \leftarrow \mu_{1.2})} |adv\ x' - ans| \mathbf{B}}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_2; \Omega_2; \Gamma_4 \vdash \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^{|adv\ x' - ans|} \text{ in } E_8 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(_ \leftarrow \delta_0)} |adv\ x' - ans| \mathbf{B}} \\
\frac{}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_2; \Omega_2; \Gamma_4 \vdash E_7 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(_ \leftarrow \delta_0)} |adv\ x' - ans| \mathbf{B}}
\end{array}$$

D5:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_2; \Omega_2; \Gamma_3 \vdash \text{lookup } x \text{ advs} : \mathbf{B}(adv\ x')} \quad D6 \\
\frac{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_2; \Omega_2; \Gamma_3 \vdash \text{let } pred = \text{lookup } x \text{ advs} \text{ in } E_7 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(_ \leftarrow \delta_0)} |adv\ x' - ans| \mathbf{B}}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_2; \Omega_2; \Gamma_3 \vdash E_6 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(_ \leftarrow \delta_0)} |adv\ x' - ans| \mathbf{B}}
\end{array}$$

D4.0:

$$\frac{}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_1; \Omega_2; \cdot \vdash \text{prob}_u : L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(pr\ i)}$$

D4:

$$\begin{array}{c}
D4.0 \quad \mu_{1.1} = (\{0, \dots, n-1\}, \{i \mapsto pr\ i \mid i < n\}) \quad \sum_{i < n} pr\ i = 1 \\
\frac{}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_1; \Omega_2; \cdot \vdash \text{toDist } \text{prob}_u : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(x' \leftarrow \mu_{1.1})} 0 \mathbf{N}(x')} \quad D5 \\
\frac{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_1; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{bind } x = \text{toDist } \text{prob}_u \text{ in } E_6 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(c \leftarrow \mu_1)} EL \mathbf{B}}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_1; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{bind } x = \text{toDist } \text{prob}_u \text{ in } E_6 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(c \leftarrow \delta_0)} p \mathbf{B}} \\
\frac{}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_1; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash E_5 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(c \leftarrow \delta_0)} p \mathbf{B}}
\end{array}$$

D3:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_1; \Omega_2; po : \vdash po : T_p} \quad D4 \\
\frac{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_1; \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \vdash \text{release } _ = po \text{ in } E_5 : T_r}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_1; \Omega_2; \Gamma_1 \vdash E_4 : T_r}
\end{array}$$

D2:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_1; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash \text{map } !(\lambda x.x/phi_u) !wts_u : !L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(pr\ i)} \quad D3 \\
\frac{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_1; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash \text{let! } \text{prob}_u = \text{map } !(\lambda x.x/phi_u) !wts_u \text{ in } E_4 : T_r}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_1; \Omega_1; \Gamma_1 \vdash E_3 : T_r}
\end{array}$$

D1:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_1; wts_u : T_w; phi : !\mathbf{R}(\phi) \vdash phi : !\mathbf{R}(\phi)} \quad D2 \\
\frac{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_1; wts_u : T_w; \Gamma_1, phi : !\mathbf{R}(\phi) \vdash \text{let! } phi_u = phi \text{ in } E_3 : T_r}{.; \Theta_1; \Delta_1; wts_u : T_w; \Gamma_1, phi : !\mathbf{R}(\phi) \vdash E_2 : T_r}
\end{array}$$

D0:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\cdot; \Theta; \Delta; wts_u : T_w; \Gamma_1 \vdash \text{sum } !wts_u : \exists \phi. !\mathbf{R}(\phi)}{\cdot; \Theta; \Delta; wts_u : T_w; \Gamma_1 \vdash \text{letEx } phi = \text{sum } !wts_u \text{ in } E_2 : T_r}}{\cdot; \Theta; \Delta; wts_u : T_w; \Gamma_1 \vdash E_1 : T_r}}{D1}$$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{\cdot; \Theta; \cdot; \cdot; wts : !T_w \vdash wts : !T_w}{\cdot; \Theta; \cdot; \cdot; \Gamma \vdash \text{let! } wts_u = wts \text{ in } E_1 : T_r}}{\cdot; \Theta; \cdot; \cdot; \Gamma \vdash E_0 : T_r}}{\cdot; \Theta; \cdot; \cdot; \cdot \vdash \lambda \text{ po advs } wts.E_0 : T_1}}{\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \cdot \vdash \Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\lambda \text{ po advs } wts.E_0 : T_0}}{D0}$$

Typing for *rw*m

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{0,0} &\triangleq \Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\lambda \textit{ round experts eta}.E_{0,1} \\
E_{0,1} &\triangleq \Lambda.\lambda \textit{ wts } p.E_0 \\
E_0 &\triangleq \textit{ let! round}_u = \textit{ round in } E_1 \\
E_1 &\triangleq \textit{ let! experts}_u = \textit{ experts in } E_2 \\
E_2 &\triangleq \textit{ let! eta}_u = \textit{ eta in } E_3 \\
E_3 &\triangleq \textit{ let! wts}_u = \textit{ wts in } E_4 \\
E_4 &\triangleq \textit{ matchN round}_u, Z \mapsto E_5, S \textit{ rnd} \mapsto E_6 \\
E_5 &\triangleq \textit{ let}\langle x, y \rangle = \textit{ Swap } (p, \textit{ nil}) \textit{ in } E_{5,1} \\
E_{5,1} &\triangleq \textit{ return } (\text{Ex } \Lambda.\Lambda. y) \\
E_6 &\triangleq \textit{ let! advs}_u = \textit{ getAdvice } \{ \} \textit{ !round}_u \textit{ !experts}_u \textit{ in } E_{6,1} \\
E_{6,1} &\triangleq \textit{ let } \langle \textit{ here, later} \rangle = \textit{ Split } p \textit{ in } E_{6,2} \\
E_{6,2} &\triangleq \textit{ bind } pr = \textit{ makePred } \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \textit{ here !advs}_u \textit{ !wts}_u \textit{ in } E_{6,3} \\
E_{6,3} &\triangleq \textit{ let !ans}_u = \textit{ getAnswer } \{ \} \{ \} \textit{ !round}_u \textit{ in } E_{6,5} \\
E_{6,5} &\triangleq \textit{ letEx } nw = \textit{ changeWeights } \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \textit{ !wts}_u \textit{ !advs}_u \textit{ !ans}_u \textit{ !eta}_u \textit{ in } E_{6,6} \\
E_{6,6} &\triangleq \textit{ bind } rec = \textit{ rw}m \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \textit{ !rnd !experts}_u \textit{ !eta}_u \{ \} \textit{ nw later in } E_{6,7} \\
E_{6,7} &\triangleq \textit{ letEx } rec' = \textit{ rec in } E_{7,0} \\
E_{7,0} &\triangleq \textit{ bind } r = E_{7,1} \textit{ in return } (Ex r) \\
E_{7,1} &\triangleq \textit{ release } prs = \textit{ rec}' \textit{ in Store } (pr :: prs)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\Theta &\triangleq r : \mathbb{N}, n : \mathbb{N}, adv : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{B}, \eta : \mathbb{R}^+, ans : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{B} \\
\Theta_1 &\triangleq \Theta, w : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \\
\Theta_2 &\triangleq \Theta_1, r' : \mathbb{N} \\
\Theta_3 &\triangleq \Theta_2, w' : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \\
\Theta_4 &\triangleq \Theta_2, w' : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+, w'' : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \\
\Delta &\triangleq r' + 1 = r \\
\Gamma &\triangleq round : T_r, experts : T_{exp}, eta : T_\eta \\
\Gamma_1 &\triangleq round : T_r, experts : T_{exp}, eta : T_\eta, p : T_p, wts : T_w \\
\Gamma_2 &\triangleq experts : T_{exp}, eta : T_\eta, p : T_p, wts : T_w \\
\Gamma_3 &\triangleq eta : T_\eta, p : T_p, wts : T_w \\
\Gamma_4 &\triangleq p : T_p \\
\Gamma_{4.0} &\triangleq x : \mathbf{1}, y : [\log (\sum_{i \leq n} w' i) / \eta] (L_{i < 0} \mathbf{B}) \\
\Gamma_5 &\triangleq here : [p_1] \mathbf{1}, later : [p_2] \mathbf{1} \\
\Gamma_6 &\triangleq later : [p_2] \mathbf{1}, pr : \mathbf{B} \\
\Gamma_7 &\triangleq later : [p_2] \mathbf{1}, pr : \mathbf{B} \\
\Gamma_8 &\triangleq later : [p_2] \mathbf{1}, pr : \mathbf{B}, nw : !L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(w' i) \\
\Gamma_9 &\triangleq pr : \mathbf{B}, rec : T_{5.2} \\
\Gamma_{10} &\triangleq pr : \mathbf{B}, rec' : T_{5.3} \\
\Gamma_{11} &\triangleq pr : \mathbf{B}, prs : \\
\Omega &\triangleq rwm : T_0 \\
\Omega_1 &\triangleq \Omega, round_u : T_r \\
\Omega_2 &\triangleq \Omega_1, experts_u : T_{exp} \\
\Omega_3 &\triangleq \Omega_2, eta_u : T_\eta \\
\Omega_4 &\triangleq \Omega_3, wts_u : T_w \\
\Omega_5 &\triangleq \Omega_4, rnd : \mathbf{N}(r'), \\
\Omega_6 &\triangleq \Omega_5, advs_u : L_{i < n} \mathbf{B}(adv i) \\
\Omega_7 &\triangleq \Omega_6, ans_u : \mathbf{B}(ans r)
\end{aligned}$$

T_0	$\triangleq \forall r : \mathbb{N}, n : \mathbb{N}, adv : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{B}, \eta : \mathbb{R}^+. T_1$
T_1	$\triangleq !T_r \multimap !T_{exp} \multimap !T_\eta \multimap T_2$
T_r	$\triangleq \mathbf{N}(r)$
T_{exp}	$\triangleq L_{i < n}(\mathbf{N}(i) \multimap \mathbf{B}(adv\ i))$
T_η	$\triangleq \mathbf{R}(\eta)$
T_w	$\triangleq L_{i < n} (w\ i \geq 1/(1 - \eta)^r \ \& \ \mathbf{R}(w\ i))$
T_2	$\triangleq \forall w : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+. T_3$
T_3	$\triangleq !T_w \multimap T_p \multimap T_5$
T_p	$\triangleq [\log (\sum_{i \leq n} w\ i) / \eta] \mathbf{1}$
T_4	$\triangleq \mathbf{1} \times [\log (\sum_{i \leq n} w\ i) / \eta] (L_{i < 0} \mathbf{B})$
T_5	$\triangleq \text{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\exists w' : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+. [\log (\sum_{i \leq n} w'\ i) / \eta] (L_{i < r} \mathbf{B}))$
$T_{5.1}$	$\triangleq \text{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\exists w' : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+. [\log (\sum_{i \leq n} w'\ i) / \eta] (L_{i < r'} \mathbf{B}))$
$T_{5.2}$	$\triangleq (\exists w' : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+. [\log (\sum_{i \leq n} w'\ i) / \eta] (L_{i < r'} \mathbf{B}))$
$T_{5.3}$	$\triangleq [\log (\sum_{i \leq n} w'\ i) / \eta] (L_{i < r'} \mathbf{B})$
$T_{5.4}$	$\triangleq \text{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} (\log (\sum_{i \leq n} w'\ i) / \eta) [(\log (\sum_{i \leq n} w'\ i) / \eta)] (L_{i < r} \mathbf{B})$
$T_{5.5}$	$\triangleq \text{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 [(\log (\sum_{i \leq n} w'\ i) / \eta)] (L_{i < r} \mathbf{B})$
$T_{5.6}$	$\triangleq [(\log (\sum_{i \leq n} w'\ i) / \eta)] (L_{i < r} \mathbf{B})$
$T_{5.7}$	$\triangleq \exists w''. [(\log (\sum_{i \leq n} w'' i) / \eta)] (L_{i < r} \mathbf{B})$
$T_{5.8}$	$\triangleq \text{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\exists w''. [(\log (\sum_{i \leq n} w'' i) / \eta)] (L_{i < r} \mathbf{B}))$
ϕ	$\triangleq \sum_{i < n} w\ i$
$prob$	$\triangleq \lambda i. (w\ i) / \phi$
ϕ'	$\triangleq \sum_{i < n} w'\ i$
$loss$	$\triangleq \lambda f s. \text{if } f == s \text{ then } 0 \text{ else } 1$
EL	$\triangleq \sum_{i < n} (prob\ i) \cdot (loss\ (adv\ i))\ (ans\ r)$
p_1	$\triangleq (\log \phi - \log \phi') / \eta$
p_2	$\triangleq \log \phi' / \eta$

D2.3:

$$\frac{}{.; \Theta_4; \Delta; \Omega_7; \Gamma_{11} \vdash \text{Store } (pr :: prs) : T_{5.4}}$$

D2.2:

$$\frac{}{.; \Theta_4; \Delta; \Omega_7; rec' : T_{5.3} \vdash rec' : T_{5.3}}$$

D2.1:

$$\frac{\frac{D2.2 \quad D2.3}{.; \Theta_4; \Delta; \Omega_7; \Gamma_{10} \vdash \text{release } prs = rec' \text{ in Store } (pr :: prs) : T_{5.5}}{.; \Theta_4; \Delta; \Omega_7; \Gamma_{10} \vdash E_{7.1} : T_{5.5}}}$$

D2.0:

$$\frac{\frac{D2.1 \quad \frac{.; \Theta_4; \Delta; \Omega_7; r : T_{5.6} \vdash (Ex\ r) : T_{5.7}}{.; \Theta_4; \Delta; \Omega_7; r : T_{5.6} \vdash \text{return } (Ex\ r) : T_{5.8}}}{.; \Theta_4; \Delta; \Omega_7; \Gamma_{10} \vdash \text{bind } r = E_{7.1} \text{ in return } (Ex\ r) : T_{5.8}}}{.; \Theta_4; \Delta; \Omega_7; \Gamma_{10} \vdash E_{7.0} : T_{5.8}}$$

D1.8:

$$\frac{\overline{.; \Theta_3; \Delta; \Omega_7; rec : T_{5.2} \vdash rec : T_{5.2}} \quad D2.0}{.; \Theta_3; \Delta; \Omega_7; \Gamma_9 \vdash \text{letEx } rec' = rec \text{ in } E_{7.0} : T_{5.8}}$$

D1.71:

$$\overline{.; \Theta_3; \Delta; \Omega_7; later : [p_2] \mathbf{1}, nw : !L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(w' i) \vdash rwm \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} rnd !experts_u !eta_u \{ \} later nw : T_{5.1}}$$

D1.7:

$$\frac{\overline{D1.71 \quad D1.8}}{.; \Theta_3; \Delta; \Omega_7; \Gamma_8 \vdash \text{bind } rec = rwm \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} !rnd !experts_u !eta_u \{ \} later nw \text{ in } E_{6.7} : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes \dots \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} T_{5.7}}$$

$$\frac{.; \Theta_3; \Delta; \Omega_7; \Gamma_8 \vdash \text{bind } rec = rwm \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} !rnd !experts_u !eta_u \{ \} later nw \text{ in } E_{6.7} : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} T_{5.7}}{.; \Theta_3; \Delta; \Omega_7; \Gamma_8 \vdash E_{6.6} : T_{5.8}}$$

D1.61:

$$\overline{.; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_7; \cdot \vdash \text{changeWeights } \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} !wts_u !adv_u !ans_u !eta_u : \exists w' . !L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(w' i)}$$

D1.6:

$$\frac{\overline{D1.61 \quad D1.7}}{.; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_7; \Gamma_7 \vdash \text{letEx } nw = \text{changeWeights } \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} !wts_u !adv_u !ans_u !eta_u \text{ in } E_{6.6} : T_{5.8}}$$

$$\frac{.; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_7; \Gamma_7 \vdash E_{6.5} : T_{5.8}}$$

D1.4:

$$\frac{\overline{.; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_6; \cdot \vdash \text{getAnswer } \{ \} \{ \} !round_u : !\mathbf{B}(ans r)} \quad D1.6}{.; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_6; \Gamma_6 \vdash \text{let! } ans_u = \text{getAnswer } \{ \} \{ \} !round_u \text{ in } E_{6.4} : T_{5.8}}$$

$$\frac{.; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_6; \Gamma_6 \vdash E_{6.3} : T_5}$$

D1.3:

$$\overline{Fig.11}$$

$$\overline{.; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_6; here : [p_1] \mathbf{1} \vdash \text{makePred } \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} here advs !w : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} \mathbf{B}}$$

D1.2:

$$\frac{\overline{D1.3 \quad D1.4}}{.; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_6; \Gamma_5 \vdash \text{bind } pr = \text{makePred } \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} here !adv_u !wts_u \text{ in } E_{6.3} : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes \dots \delta_0)} \mathbf{0} T_{5.7}}$$

$$\frac{.; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_6; \Gamma_5 \vdash \text{bind } pr = \text{makePred } \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} here !adv_u !wts_u \text{ in } E_{6.3} : T_{5.8}}{.; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_6; \Gamma_5 \vdash E_{6.2} : T_{5.8}}$$

D1.1:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\cdot; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_6; p : T_p \vdash \text{split } p : [p_1] \mathbf{1} \times [p_2] \mathbf{1}}{\cdot; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_6; \Gamma_4 \vdash \text{let } \langle \text{here}, \text{later} \rangle = \text{Split } p \text{ in } E_{6.2} : T_{5.8}}{\cdot; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_6; \Gamma_4 \vdash E_{6.1} : T_{5.8}}}{\cdot; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_5; \cdot \vdash \text{getAdvice } \{ \} !\text{round}_u !\text{experts}_u !L_{i < n} \mathbf{B}(\text{adv } i)}$$

D1.0:

$$\frac{\cdot; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_5; \cdot \vdash \text{getAdvice } \{ \} !\text{round}_u !\text{experts}_u !L_{i < n} \mathbf{B}(\text{adv } i)}{\cdot; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_5; \Gamma_4 \vdash \text{let! } \text{adv}_u = \text{getAdvice } \{ \} !\text{round}_u !\text{experts}_u \text{ in } E_{6.1} : T_{5.8}}$$

D1:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{D1.0 \quad D1.1}{\cdot; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_5; \Gamma_4 \vdash \text{let! } \text{adv}_u = \text{getAdvice } \{ \} !\text{round}_u !\text{experts}_u \text{ in } E_{6.1} : T_{5.8}}{\cdot; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_5; \Gamma_4 \vdash E_6 : T_{5.8}}}{\cdot; \Theta_2; \Delta; \Omega_5; \cdot \vdash \text{getAdvice } \{ \} !\text{round}_u !\text{experts}_u !L_{i < n} \mathbf{B}(\text{adv } i)}$$

D0.01:

$$\frac{\frac{\cdot; \Theta_1; r = 0; \Omega_4; \Gamma_{4.0} \vdash \text{return } (\text{Ex } y) : T_{5.8}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; r = 0; \Omega_4; \Gamma_{4.0} \vdash E_{5.1} : T_{5.8}}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; r = 0; \Omega_4; \Gamma_{4.0} \vdash E_{5.1} : T_{5.8}}$$

D0:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\cdot; \Theta_1; r = 0; \Omega_4; \Gamma_4 \vdash \text{Swap } (p, \text{nil}) : T_4}{\cdot; \Theta_1; r = 0; \Omega_4; \Gamma_4 \vdash \text{let} \langle x, y \rangle = \text{Swap } (p, \text{nil}) \text{ in } E_{5.1} : T_{5.8}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; r = 0; \Omega_4; \Gamma_4 \vdash \text{let} \langle x, y \rangle = \text{Swap } (p, \text{nil}) \text{ in } E_{5.1} : T_{5.8}}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; r = 0; \Omega_4; \Gamma_4 \vdash \text{let} \langle x, y \rangle = \text{Swap } (p, \text{nil}) \text{ in } E_{5.1} : T_{5.8}}$$

D0.3:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_4; \cdot \vdash \text{round}_u : T_r}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_4; \Gamma_4 \vdash \text{matchN } \text{round}_u, Z \mapsto E_5, S \text{ rnd} \mapsto E_6 : T_{5.8}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_4; \Gamma_4 \vdash \text{matchN } \text{round}_u, Z \mapsto E_5, S \text{ rnd} \mapsto E_6 : T_{5.8}}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_4; \Gamma_4 \vdash \text{matchN } \text{round}_u, Z \mapsto E_5, S \text{ rnd} \mapsto E_6 : T_{5.8}}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_4; \Gamma_4 \vdash E_4 : T_{5.8}}$$

D0.2:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_3; \text{wts} !T_w \vdash \text{wts} !T_w}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_3; \Gamma_3 \vdash \text{let! } \text{wts}_u = \text{wts} \text{ in } E_4 : T_{5.8}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_3; \Gamma_3 \vdash \text{let! } \text{wts}_u = \text{wts} \text{ in } E_4 : T_{5.8}}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_3; \Gamma_3 \vdash \text{let! } \text{wts}_u = \text{wts} \text{ in } E_4 : T_{5.8}}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_3; \Gamma_3 \vdash E_3 : T_{5.8}}$$

D0.1:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_2; \text{eta} !T_\eta \vdash \text{eta} !T_\eta}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_2; \Gamma_3 \vdash \text{let! } \text{eta}_u = \text{eta} \text{ in } E_3 : T_{5.8}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_2; \Gamma_3 \vdash \text{let! } \text{eta}_u = \text{eta} \text{ in } E_3 : T_{5.8}}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_2; \Gamma_3 \vdash \text{let! } \text{eta}_u = \text{eta} \text{ in } E_3 : T_{5.8}}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_2; \Gamma_3 \vdash E_2 : T_{5.8}}$$

D0.0:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_1; \text{experts} !T_{\text{exp}} \vdash \text{experts} !T_{\text{exp}}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_1; \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{let! } \text{experts}_u = \text{experts} \text{ in } E_2 : T_{5.8}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_1; \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{let! } \text{experts}_u = \text{experts} \text{ in } E_2 : T_{5.8}}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_1; \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{let! } \text{experts}_u = \text{experts} \text{ in } E_2 : T_{5.8}}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; \cdot; \Omega_1; \Gamma_2 \vdash E_1 : T_{5.8}}$$

Main derivation:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{.; \Theta_1; .; .; \text{round} :!T_r \vdash \text{round} :!T_r} \quad D0.0 \\
\hline
.; \Theta_1; .; \Omega; \Gamma_1 \vdash E_0 : T_5 \\
\hline
.; \Theta; .; \Omega; \Gamma \vdash E_{0.1} : T_2 \\
\hline
.; .; .; \Omega; . \vdash E_{0.0} : T_0 \\
\hline
.; .; .; .; . \vdash \text{fix } rwm.E_{0.0} : T_0
\end{array}$$

Theorem 57 (Expected loss of *rwm*). Let (1) T be the number of rounds for which we want to make predictions with *rwm* (i.e., T is the initial value of *round*), (2) t be a counter over rounds starting from $t = 0$ (so, $t \triangleq T - \text{round}$ and round $t = T$ is an additional trivial round at the end that terminates immediately in the Z case of the algorithm), (3) n be the number of experts, (4) η denote the learning rate, (5) $w_i(t)$ be the weight of the i^{th} expert at the beginning of round t , such that $w_i(t) \geq 1/(1 - \eta)^T$, (6) $\text{loss}(t)$ denote the loss of the algorithm in round t , and (7) $\phi(t) \triangleq \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} w_i(t)$. Then,

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \text{loss}(t) \right] \leq \frac{\log(\phi(0))}{\eta} - \frac{\log(\phi(T))}{\eta}$$

Proof. We know that

- The starting weight of all experts $\geq 1/(1 - \eta)^T$, from the type of *rwm*
- The weight of an expert can atmost reduce by $(1 - \eta)$ in each round, from the type of *changeWeight*

Therefore, the potential in each round will always remain +ve.

Also, from typing derivation we know that expected loss of a single round t is bounded

$$\mathbb{E}[\text{loss}(t)] \leq \frac{\log \phi(t)}{\eta} - \frac{\log \phi(t+1)}{\eta}$$

Hence, using telescopic sum we get

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \text{loss}(t) \right] \leq \frac{\log(\phi(0))}{\eta} - \frac{\log(\phi(T))}{\eta}$$

□

```

1  getAdvice :  $\forall r, n, adv : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{B}. !\mathbf{N}(r) \multimap !L_{i < n}(\mathbf{N}(i) \multimap \mathbf{B}(adv\ i)) \multimap !L_{i < n}\mathbf{B}(adv\ i)$ 
2  getAdvice  $\triangleq \Lambda.\Lambda.\lambda$  round experts. let  $r' = \text{round}$  in map  $!(\lambda e.e\ r')$  experts

1  changeWeights :  $\forall n, r, \eta, a', adv : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{B}, w : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ .
2       $!L_{i < n}(w\ i \geq 1/(1 - \eta)^r \ \& \ \mathbf{R}(w\ i)) \multimap !L_{i < n}\mathbf{B}(adv\ i) \multimap !\mathbf{B}(a') \multimap !\mathbf{R}(\eta) \multimap$ 
3       $\exists w' : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+. L_{i < n}(w'\ i \geq 1/(1 - \eta)^{r-1} \ \& \ \mathbf{R}(w'\ i))$ 
4  changeWeights  $\triangleq$ 
5   $\Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\lambda$  weights advs ans eta.
6  let  $wts_u = \text{weights}$  in
7  let  $advs_u = \text{advs}$  in
8  let  $ans_u = \text{ans}$  in
9  let  $eta_u = \text{eta}$  in
10 match  $!wts_u$  with
11   | nil  $\mapsto$  Ex  $\Lambda.$  nil
12   |  $wt :: wts$   $\mapsto$ 
13       let  $wt' = wt$  in
14       match  $!advs_u$  with
15         | nil  $\mapsto$  fix $x.x$ 
16         |  $a :: as$   $\mapsto$ 
17             letEx  $r = \text{changeWeights}$   $\{\} \{\} \{\} \{\} \{\} \{\} !wts\ !as\ !ans_u\ !eta_u$  in
18             if  $a == ans_u$ 
19             then
20                 Ex  $(\Lambda.wt' :: r)$ 
21             else
22                 Ex  $(\Lambda.wt' * (1 - eta') :: r)$ 

1  getAnswer :  $\forall r, ans. !\mathbf{N}(r) \multimap !\mathbf{B}(ans\ r)$ 

1  map :  $\forall n. !(\tau_1 \multimap \tau_2) \multimap !L_{i < n}\tau_1 \multimap !L_{i < n}\tau_2$ 

1  zip :  $\forall n. !L_{i < n}\tau_1 \multimap !L_{i < n}\tau_2 \multimap !L_{i < n}(\tau_1 \times \tau_2)$ 

1  sum :  $\forall n, R : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}. !L_{i < n}\mathbf{R}(R\ i) \multimap \exists r. !\mathbf{R}(r)$ 

1  lookup :  $\forall n, m, R : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow S. (m < n) \wedge (n > 1) \Rightarrow \mathbf{N}(m) \multimap L_{i < n}\tau(R\ i) \multimap \tau(R\ m)$ 

```


D7.2:

$$\frac{.; \Theta_1; .; \Omega_4; \Gamma_5 \vdash Ex (\Lambda.wt * (1 - eta') :: r') : T_6}{.; \Theta_1; .; \Omega_4; \Gamma_5 \vdash E_{10} : T_6}$$

D7.1:

$$\frac{.; \Theta_1; .; \Omega_4; \Gamma_5 \vdash Ex (\Lambda. wt :: r') : T_6}{.; \Theta_1; .; \Omega_4; \Gamma_5 \vdash E_9 : T_6}$$

D6.2:

$$\frac{\frac{.; \Theta_1; .; \Omega_4; . \vdash ans_u}{.; \Theta_1; .; \Omega_4; \Gamma_5 \vdash \text{if } a == ans_u \text{ then } E_8 \text{ else } E_9} \quad D7.1 \quad D7.2}{.; \Theta_1; .; \Omega_4; \Gamma_5 \vdash E_7 : T_6}$$

D6.1:

$$.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_4; \Gamma_4 \vdash changeWeights \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} !wts_u !adv_u !ans_u !eta_u : T_{rec}$$

D5.2:

$$\frac{D6.1 \quad D6.2}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_4; \Gamma_4 \vdash \text{letEx } r = changeWeights \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} !wts_u !adv_u !ans_u !eta_u \text{ in } E_7 : T_6} \quad ; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_4; \Gamma_4 \vdash E_6 : T_6$$

D5.1:

$$.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_4; . \vdash wt : T_{w1}$$

D4.2:

$$\frac{D5.1 \quad D5.2}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_4; . \vdash \text{let } wt' = wt \text{ in } E_6 : T_6} \quad ; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_4; . \vdash E_{6.0} : T_6$$

D4.1:

$$.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_4; . \vdash \text{fix } x.x : T_6$$

D4.0:

$$.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_3; . \vdash advs : T_{adv}$$

D3.2:

$$\frac{D4.0 \quad D4.1 \quad D4.2}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_3; . \vdash \text{match } advs \text{ with } | \text{nil} \mapsto \text{fix } x.x | a :: as \mapsto E_{6.0} : T_6} \quad ; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_3; . \vdash E_5 : T_6$$

D3.1:

$$\frac{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_3; . \vdash \text{Ex } \Lambda.\text{nil} : T_6}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_3; . \vdash E_4 : T_6}$$

D3.0:

$$\frac{}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_3; . \vdash wts_u : T_w}$$

D3:

$$\frac{D3.0 \quad D3.1 \quad D3.2}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_3; . \vdash \text{match } wts_u \text{ with } | \text{nil} \mapsto E_4 | wt :: wts \mapsto E_5}$$

D2.1:

$$\frac{}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_2; eta : !T_{eta} \vdash eta : !T_{eta}}$$

D2.0:

$$\frac{}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_1; ans : !T_{ans} \vdash ans : !T_{ans}}$$

D2:

$$\frac{D2.1 \quad D3}{D2.0 \quad \frac{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_2; \Gamma_3 \vdash \text{let! } eta_u = eta \text{ in } E_3 : T_6}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_2; \Gamma_3 \vdash E_{0.4} : T_6}}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_1; \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{let! } ans_u = ans \text{ in } E_{0.4} : T_6}$$

D1:

$$\frac{}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_0; advs : !T_{advs} \vdash advs : !T_{advs}}$$

D0:

$$\frac{}{.; \Theta_0; .; .; weights : !T_w \vdash weights : !T_w}$$

Main derivation:

$$\frac{D1 \quad \frac{D2}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_1; \Gamma_2 \vdash E_{0.3} : T_6}}{D0 \quad \frac{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_0; \Gamma_1 \vdash \text{let! } advs_u = advs \text{ in } E_{0.3} : T_6}{.; \Theta_0; .; \Omega_0; \Gamma_1 \vdash E_{0.2} : T_6}}{.; \Theta_0; .; .; \Gamma_0 \vdash \text{let! } wts_u = weights \text{ in } E_{0.2} : T_6}}{.; \Theta_0; .; .; \Gamma_0 \vdash E_{0.1} : T_6}}{.; .; .; .; \vdash E_0 : T_0}$$

4.3 Multi-armed bandit

```

1  bandit : ∀T : ℕ, n : ℕ, γ : ℝ+, reward : ℕ → ℕ → ℝ+.
2      !N(T)
3      -o !N(n)
4      -o !R(γ)
5      -o ∀w : ℕ → ℝ+. !Li<n (w i ≥ e $\frac{T\gamma}{n}$  & R(w i))
6      -o [  $\frac{1}{\frac{\gamma}{n}(1-\frac{\gamma}{n})^{1-\gamma}}$  log (∑i<n w i) + T( $\frac{\gamma(1-\gamma)}{(n-\gamma)}$  + 1)] 1
7      -o PC(a←δ0) 0 (Li<TN)
8  fix bandit.
9  Λ.Λ.Λ.Λ.λ round arms g.Λ.λ wts p.
10  let! roundu = round in
11  let! armsu = arms in
12  let! gu = g in
13  let! wtsu = wts in
14  matchN! !roundu
15  , Z ↦ return nil
16  , S rnd ↦
17  letEx phi = sum !wtsu in
18  let! phiu = phi in
19  let! probu = map !(λx.let y = x in (1 - gu)/phiu * y + gu/armsu) !wtsu in
20  release - = p in
21  bind cArm =
22  bind chArm = toDist !probu in
23  let! chArmu = chArm in
24  bind _ = ↑L ca in return (Ex !chArmu)
25  in
26  letEx cArm' = cArm in
27  let! cArmu = cArm' in
28  let! chReward = getReward {} {} {} !roundu !cArmu in
29  letEx lvs = prepareLossVector {} {} {} {} ![1..armsu] !cArmu !(1 - chReward) in
30  letEx nw' = changeWeights {} {} {} {} {} !wtsu lvs !armsu !gu in
31  bind later = store () in
32  bind rec = bandit {} {} {} {} !rnd !armsu !gu {} nw later in
33  return (Ex cArmu :: rec)

```

where,

[1...n] is a notation for *createListofN* {} !n

```

1  getReward :  $\forall r : \mathbb{N}, ca : \mathbb{N}, reward : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ . \mathbf{N}(r) \multimap \mathbf{N}(ca) \multimap !\mathbf{R}(reward\ r\ ca)$ 

1  prepareLossVector :  $\forall n, ca : \mathbb{N}, cl : \mathbb{R}^+, pr : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ .$ 
2     $!L_{i < n} \mathbf{N}(i) \multimap !\mathbf{N}(ca) \multimap !\mathbf{R}(cl) \multimap \exists lv : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ . !L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(lv\ i)$ 
3  prepareLossVector  $\triangleq$ 
4   $\Lambda . \Lambda . \Lambda . \lambda\ arms\ cArm\ cLoss .$ 
5    let!  $ca_u = cArm$  in
6    let!  $cr_u = cLoss$  in
7    match  $!arms$  with
8    | nil  $\mapsto$  Ex nil
9    |  $a :: as \mapsto$ 
10     letEx  $rec = prepareLossVector\ \{\}\ \{\}\ \{\}$  as  $!ca_u\ !cr_u$  in
11     if  $a == ca_u$ 
12       then Ex  $(cl_u :: rec)$ 
13       else Ex  $(0 :: rec)$ 

1  createListofN :  $\forall n . !\mathbf{N}(n) \multimap !L_{i < n} \mathbf{N}$ 
2  createListofN  $\triangleq$ 
3   $\Lambda . \lambda\ no .$ 
4    matchN!  $no$ 
5    ,  $Z \mapsto ! (0 :: nil)$ 
6    ,  $(S\ x) \mapsto ! let\ rec = createListofN\ \{\}\ x\ in\ !(Sx :: rec)$ 

1  changeWeights :  $\forall n, r, \gamma, w : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, loss : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ .$ 
2   $!L_{i < n} (w\ i \geq e^{\frac{r\gamma}{n}} \ \&\ \mathbf{R}(w\ i)) \multimap !L_{i < n} lvs(loss\ i) \multimap !\mathbf{N}(n) \multimap !\mathbf{R}(\gamma) \multimap$ 
3   $\exists w' . !L_{i < n} (w'\ i \geq e^{\frac{(r-1)\gamma}{n}} \ \&\ \mathbf{R}(w'\ i))$ 
4  changeWeights  $\triangleq$ 
5   $\Lambda . \Lambda . \Lambda . \Lambda . \lambda\ weights\ lvs\ arms\ g .$ 
6    let!  $wts_u = weights$  in
7    let!  $lvs_u = lvs$  in
8    let!  $g_u = g$  in
9    let!  $a_u = arms$  in
10   match  $!wts_u$  with
11   | nil  $\mapsto$  Ex  $\Lambda . nil$ 
12   |  $wt :: wts \mapsto$ 
13     let  $wt' = wt$  in
14     match  $!lvs_u$  with
15     | nil  $\mapsto$  fix  $x . x$ 
16     |  $l :: lss \mapsto$ 
17       letEx  $r = changeWeights\ \{\}\ \{\}\ \{\}\ \{\}\ \{\}$   $!wts\ !lss\ !a_u\ !g_u$  in
18       Ex  $(\Lambda . wt' * e^{(-\frac{g_u}{a_u} * l)} :: r)$ 

```

Let $\phi(t) = \sum_{j < n} w_j(t)$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}[\text{loss}_t] &= \sum_{i < n} \mathbb{P}[\text{selecting } i] \cdot \text{loss}_i(t) \\
&= \sum_{i < n} \left((1 - \gamma) \frac{w_i(t)}{\phi(t)} + \frac{\gamma}{n} \right) \cdot \text{loss}_i(t) \\
&= \frac{(1-\gamma)}{\phi(t)} \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot (1 - \text{reward}_i(t)) + \frac{\gamma}{n} \sum_{i < n} (1 - \text{reward}_i(t)) \\
&= (1 - \gamma) - \frac{(1-\gamma)}{\phi(t)} \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot \text{reward}_i(t) + \gamma - \frac{\gamma}{n} \sum_{i < n} \text{reward}_i(t) \\
&= 1 - \frac{(1-\gamma)}{\phi(t)} \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot \text{reward}_i(t) - \frac{\gamma}{n} \sum_{i < n} \text{reward}_i(t)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\phi(t+1) &= \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot \exp(-\frac{\gamma}{n}(1 - \text{reward}_i(t))) \\
&\leq \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n} \cdot (1 - \text{reward}_i(t)) + \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} \cdot (1 - \text{reward}_i(t))^2) \\
&\leq \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) - \frac{\gamma}{n} \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot (1 - \text{reward}_i(t)) + \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot (1 - \text{reward}_i(t))^2 \\
&\leq \phi(t) - \frac{\gamma}{n} \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma}{n} \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot \text{reward}_i(t) + \\
&\quad \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot \text{reward}_i(t)^2 - 2 \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot \text{reward}_i(t) \\
&\leq \phi(t) - \frac{\gamma}{n} \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma}{n} \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot \text{reward}_i(t) - \\
&\quad 2 \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot \text{reward}_i(t) + \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot \text{reward}_i(t)^2 \\
&\leq \phi(t) - \frac{\gamma}{n} \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma}{n} \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot \text{reward}_i(t) (1 - 2 \frac{\gamma}{n}) + \\
&\quad \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot \text{reward}_i(t)^2 \\
&\leq \phi(t) - \frac{\gamma}{n} \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma}{n} \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot \text{reward}_i(t) (1 - 2 \frac{\gamma}{n}) + \\
&\quad \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot \text{reward}_i(t) \\
&\leq \phi(t) - \frac{\gamma}{n} \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma}{n} \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot \text{reward}_i(t) (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \\
&\leq \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \sum_{i < n} w_i(t) \cdot \text{reward}_i(t) \\
&\leq \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n} \sum_{i < n} \text{reward}_i(t) - \mathbb{E}[\text{loss}_t]) \frac{\phi(t)}{1-\gamma} \\
&\leq \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{\phi(t)}{1-\gamma} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n} \sum_{i < n} \text{reward}_i(t) - \mathbb{E}[\text{loss}_t]) \\
&\leq \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{\phi(t)}{1-\gamma} - \frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{\phi(t)}{1-\gamma} \frac{\gamma}{n} \sum_{i < n} \text{reward}_i(t) - \frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{\phi(t)}{1-\gamma} \mathbb{E}[\text{loss}_t] \\
&\leq \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} \phi(t) + \frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{\phi(t)}{1-\gamma} - \frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{\phi(t)}{1-\gamma} \mathbb{E}[\text{loss}_t] \\
&\leq \phi(t) (1 + \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} + \frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{1}{1-\gamma} - \frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \mathbb{E}[\text{loss}_t]) \\
&\leq \phi(t) (1 - (\frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \mathbb{E}[\text{loss}_t] - \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} - \frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{1}{1-\gamma})) \\
&\leq \phi(t) e^{-(\frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \mathbb{E}[\text{loss}_t] - \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} - \frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{1}{1-\gamma})} \\
\log \phi(t+1) &\leq \log \phi(t) - (\frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \mathbb{E}[\text{loss}_t] - \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} - \frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{1}{1-\gamma}) \\
\log \phi(t+1) &\leq \log \phi(t) - \frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \mathbb{E}[\text{loss}_t] + \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} + \frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \\
\mathbb{E}[\text{loss}_t] &\leq \frac{1}{\frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{1}{1-\gamma}} \log \phi(t) - \frac{1}{\frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{1}{1-\gamma}} \log \phi(t+1) + \frac{1}{\frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{1}{1-\gamma}} \frac{\gamma^2}{n^2} + 1 \\
\mathbb{E}[\text{loss}_t] &\leq \frac{1}{\frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{1}{1-\gamma}} \log \phi(t) - \frac{1}{\frac{\gamma}{n} (1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}) \frac{1}{1-\gamma}} \log \phi(t+1) + \frac{\gamma(1-\gamma)}{(n-\gamma)} + 1
\end{aligned}$$

Theorem 58 (Expected loss of bandit).

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \text{loss}(t) \right] \leq \frac{(1-\gamma)}{\gamma} \cdot \frac{n^2 \log(n)}{(n-\gamma)} + \left(\frac{(n+\gamma)(1-\gamma)}{(n-\gamma)} + 1 \right) \cdot T$$

Proof. From the typing derivation we know that

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \text{loss}(t) \right] \leq \frac{1}{\frac{\gamma}{n} \left(1 - \frac{\gamma}{n}\right)^{\frac{1}{1-\gamma}}} \log \phi(0) + T \cdot \left(\frac{\gamma(1-\gamma)}{(n-\gamma)} + 1 \right)$$

Since the starting weight of each arm $\geq e^{T\frac{\gamma}{n}}$. Therefore we get,

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \text{loss}(t) \right] \leq \frac{(1-\gamma)}{\gamma} \cdot \frac{n^2 \log(n)}{(n-\gamma)} + \left(\frac{(n+\gamma)(1-\gamma)}{(n-\gamma)} + 1 \right) \cdot T$$

□

$E_0 \triangleq \Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\lambda \text{ round arms } g.\Lambda.\lambda p \text{ wts}.E_{0.0}$
 $E_{0.0} \triangleq \text{let! } \text{round}_u = \text{round} \text{ in } E_1$
 $E_1 \triangleq \text{let! } \text{arms}_u = \text{arms} \text{ in } E_2$
 $E_2 \triangleq \text{let! } g_u = g \text{ in } E_3$
 $E_3 \triangleq \text{let! } \text{wts}_u = \text{wts} \text{ in } E_4$
 $E_4 \triangleq \text{matchN! } !\text{round}_u, Z \mapsto E_5, (S \text{ rnd}) \mapsto E_6$
 $E_5 \triangleq \text{return nil}$
 $E_6 \triangleq \text{letEx } \text{phi} = \text{sum } !\text{wts}_u \text{ in } E_{6.1}$
 $E_{6.1} \triangleq \text{let! } \text{phi}_u = \text{phi} \text{ in } E_{6.2}$
 $E_{6.2} \triangleq \text{let! } \text{prob}_u = \text{map } !(\lambda x.\text{let } y = x \text{ in } (1 - g_u)/\text{phi}_u * y + g_u/\text{arms}_u) !\text{wts}_u \text{ in } E_{6.3}$
 $E_{6.3} \triangleq \text{release } - = p \text{ in } E_{6.4}$
 $E_{6.4} \triangleq \text{bind } \text{cArm} = E_{6.5} \text{ in } E_{7.0}$
 $E_{6.5} \triangleq \text{bind } \text{chArm} = \text{toDist } !\text{prob}_u \text{ in } E_{6.51}$
 $E_{6.51} \triangleq \text{let! } \text{chArm}_u = \text{chArm} \text{ in } E_{6.6}$
 $E_{6.6} \triangleq \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^{-(\hat{L} \text{ ca})} \text{ in return } (E_x !\text{chArm}_u)$
 $E_{7.0} \triangleq \text{letEx } \text{cArm}' = \text{cArm} \text{ in } E_{7.01}$
 $E_{7.01} \triangleq \text{let! } \text{cArm}_u = \text{cArm}' \text{ in } E_{7.1}$
 $E_{7.1} \triangleq \text{let! } \text{chReward} = \text{getReward } \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} !\text{round}_u !\text{cArm}_u \text{ in } E_{7.2}$
 $E_{7.2} \triangleq \text{letEx } \text{lvs} = \text{prepareLossVector } \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} !\text{arms}_u !\text{prob}_u !\text{cArm}_u !\text{chReward} \text{ in } E_{7.3}$
 $E_{7.3} \triangleq \text{letEx } \text{nw} = \text{changeWeights } \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} !\text{wts}_u \text{ lvs } !\text{arms}_u !g_u \text{ in } E_{7.30}$
 $E_{7.30} \triangleq \text{bind } \text{later} = \text{store } () \text{ in } E_{7.4}$
 $E_{7.4} \triangleq \text{bind } \text{rec} = \text{bandit } \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} !\text{rnd} !\text{arms}_u !g_u \{ \} \text{nw } \text{later} \text{ in } E_{7.5}$
 $E_{7.5} \triangleq \text{return } (E_x \text{cArm}_u :: \text{rec})$

Θ	\triangleq	$r, n, \gamma, reward, w$
Θ_1	\triangleq	$r, n, \gamma, reward, w, i$
$\Theta_{1.0}$	\triangleq	$r, n, \gamma, reward, w, i, sw$
Θ'_1	\triangleq	$r, n, \gamma, reward, w, i, sw, ca$
Θ_2	\triangleq	$r, n, \gamma, reward, w, i, sw, carm$
Θ'_2	\triangleq	$r, n, \gamma, reward, w, i, sw, carm, c$
Θ_3	\triangleq	$r, n, \gamma, reward, w, i, sw, carm, lv$
Θ_4	\triangleq	$r, n, \gamma, reward, w, i, sw, carm, lv, w'$
Γ	\triangleq	$round : T_r, arms : T_n, g : T_g, p : T_p, wts : T_w$
Γ_1	\triangleq	$arms : T_n, g : T_g, p : T_p, wts : T_w$
Γ_2	\triangleq	$p : T_p$
Γ_3	\triangleq	$lvs : T_{lv}$
Γ_4	\triangleq	$nw : T_{cw}$
Γ_5	\triangleq	$nw : T_{cw}, later : T_{lp}$
Γ_6	\triangleq	$later : T_{lp}$
Ω_1	\triangleq	$round_u : T_{ru}$
Ω_2	\triangleq	$round_u : T_{ru}, arms_u : T_{nu}, g_u : T_{gu}, wts_u : T_{wu}$
Ω_3	\triangleq	$round_u : T_{ru}, arms_u : T_{nu}, g_u : T_{gu}, wts_u : T_{wu}, rnd :$
Ω_4	\triangleq	$round_u : T_{ru}, arms_u : T_{nu}, g_u : T_{gu}, wts_u : T_{wu}, rnd :, phi_u : \mathbf{R}(sw)$
Ω_5	\triangleq	$round_u : T_{ru}, arms_u : T_{nu}, g_u : T_{gu}, wts_u : T_{wu}, rnd :, phi_u : \mathbf{R}(sw), prob_u : T_{prs}$
Ω_6	\triangleq	$round_u : T_{ru}, arms_u : T_{nu}, g_u : T_{gu}, wts_u : T_{wu}, rnd :, phi_u : \mathbf{R}(sw), prob_u : T_{prs}, cArm_u : \mathbf{N}(carm)$
Ω_7	\triangleq	$round_u : T_{ru}, arms_u : T_{nu}, g_u : T_{gu}, wts_u : T_{wu}, rnd :, phi_u : \mathbf{R}(sw), prob_u : T_{prs}, cArm_u : \mathbf{N}(carm), chReward : T_{gl}$

$$\begin{aligned}
T_0 &\triangleq \forall r : \mathbb{N}, n : \mathbb{N}, \gamma : \mathbb{R}^+, \text{reward} : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+. T_1 \\
T_1 &\triangleq T_r \multimap T_n \multimap T_g \multimap T_2 \\
T_r &\triangleq !\mathbf{N}(r) \\
T_n &\triangleq !\mathbf{N}(n) \\
T_g &\triangleq !\mathbf{R}(\gamma) \\
T_2 &\triangleq \forall w : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+. T_w \multimap T_3 \\
T_3 &\triangleq T_p \multimap T_5 \\
T_5 &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (L_{i < r} \mathbf{N}) \\
T_{5.1} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \text{pt} (L_{i < r} \mathbf{N}) \\
T_6 &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} EC (\exists \text{carm}. !\mathbf{N}(\text{carm})) \\
T_{6.1} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} EC \mathbf{1} \\
T_{6.2} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\exists \text{carm}. !\mathbf{N}(\text{carm})) \\
T_7 &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} \text{later} (L_{i < r} \mathbf{N}) \\
T_{rec} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (L_{i < r-1} \mathbf{N}) \\
T_{recl} &\triangleq L_{i < r-1} \mathbf{N} \\
T_{dist} &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(ca \leftarrow \mu)} 0 (!\mathbf{N}(ca)) \\
T_{gl} &\triangleq \mathbf{R}(\text{reward } r \text{ } ca) \\
T_{lv} &\triangleq L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(lv \ i) \\
T_{ecw} &\triangleq \exists w'. T_{cw} \\
T_{cw} &\triangleq !L_{i < n} (w' \ i \geq e^{\frac{(r-1)\gamma}{n}} \ \& \ \mathbf{R}(w' \ i)) \\
T_p &\triangleq [\text{pt}] \mathbf{1} \\
T_w &\triangleq !L_{i < n} (w \geq e^{\frac{r\gamma}{n}} \ \& \ \mathbf{R}(w \ i)) \\
T_l &\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0)} \text{later} ([\text{later}] \mathbf{1}) \\
T_{prs} &\triangleq L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(pr \ i) \\
\text{pt} &\triangleq \frac{1}{\frac{\gamma}{n}(1-\frac{\gamma}{n})\frac{1}{1-\gamma}} \log \phi + r \left(\frac{\gamma(1-\gamma)}{(n-\gamma)} + 1 \right) \\
\text{later} &\triangleq \frac{1}{\frac{\gamma}{n}(1-\frac{\gamma}{n})\frac{1}{1-\gamma}} \log \phi' + (r-1) \left(\frac{\gamma(1-\gamma)}{(n-\gamma)} + 1 \right) \\
\phi &\triangleq \sum_{i < n} (w \ i) \\
\phi' &\triangleq \sum_{i < n} (w' \ i) \\
cl &\triangleq (\text{reward } r \text{ } ca) \\
pr &\triangleq \lambda i. (1-\gamma) \cdot (w \ i) / \phi + \gamma/n \\
\mu &\triangleq (C, M) \\
&\quad C = \{i \mid i < n\} \\
&\quad M = \{i \mapsto pr \ i \mid i < n\} \\
\hat{L} &\triangleq \lambda i. (1 - \text{reward } r \ i) / (pr \ i) \\
EC &\triangleq \sum_{j < n} (pr \ j) \cdot (\hat{L} \ j)
\end{aligned}$$

D7.52:

$$\frac{}{.; \Theta_4; i + 1 = r; \Omega_7; rec : T_{recl} \vdash rec : T_{recl}}$$

D7.51:

$$\frac{\frac{.; \Theta_4; i + 1 = r; \Omega_7; . \vdash cArm_u : \mathbf{N}(b)[carm/b] \quad .; \Theta_4; i + 1 = r \vdash carm}{.; \Theta_4; i + 1 = r; \Omega_7; . \vdash Ex cArm_u : \exists b. \mathbf{N}(b)}}{.; \Theta_4; i + 1 = r; \Omega_7; . \vdash Ex cArm_u : \mathbf{N}}$$

D7.5:

$$\frac{\frac{D7.51 \quad D7.52}{.; \Theta_4; i + 1 = r; \Omega_7; rec : T_{recl} \vdash (Ex cArm_u :: rec) : L_{i < r} \mathbf{N}}{.; \Theta_4; i + 1 = r; \Omega_7; rec : T_{recl} \vdash \mathbf{return} (Ex cArm_u :: rec) : T_5}}{.; \Theta_4; i + 1 = r; \Omega_7; rec : T_{recl} \vdash E_{7.5} : T_5}$$

D7.41:

$$\frac{}{.; \Theta_4; i + 1 = r; \Omega_7; \Gamma_5 \vdash bandit \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} !rnd !arms_u !g_u \{ \} nw later : T_{rec}}$$

D7.4:

$$\frac{D7.41 \quad D7.5}{.; \Theta_4; i + 1 = r; \Omega_7; \Gamma_5 \vdash \mathbf{bind} rec = bandit \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} !rnd !arms_u !g_u \{ \} later nw \mathbf{in} E_{7.5} : T_5}}{.; \Theta_4; i + 1 = r; \Omega_7; \Gamma_5 \vdash E_{7.4} : T_5}$$

D7.32:

$$\frac{\frac{.; \Theta_4; i + 1 = r; \Omega_6, cArmReward ;; . \vdash \mathbf{store} () : T_1}{.; \Theta_4; i + 1 = r; \Omega_6; \Gamma_4 \vdash \mathbf{bind} later = \mathbf{store} () \mathbf{in} E_{7.1} : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes \dots \delta_0)} later (L_{i < r} \mathbf{N})}}{D7.4}{.; \Theta_4; i + 1 = r; \Omega_6; \Gamma_4 \vdash E_{7.30} : T_7}$$

D7.31:

$$\frac{}{.; \Theta_3; i + 1 = r; \Omega_7; lvs : T_{lv} \vdash changeWeights \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} !wts_u lvs !arms_u !g_u : T_{ecw}}$$

D7.3:

$$\frac{D7.31 \quad D7.32}{.; \Theta_3; i + 1 = r; \Omega_7; \Gamma_3 \vdash \mathbf{letEx} nw = changeWeights \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} !wts_u lvs !arms_u !g_u \mathbf{in} E_{7.4} : T_5}}{.; \Theta_3; i + 1 = r; \Omega_7; \Gamma_3 \vdash E_{7.3} : T_5}$$

D7.2:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{.; \Theta_2; i + 1 = r; \Omega_7; . \vdash} \\
\frac{\text{prepareLossVector } \{\} \{\} \{\} \{\} !arms_u !prob_u !cArm_u !chReward : \exists lv. T_{lv}}{.; \Theta_2; i + 1 = r; \Omega_7; . \vdash} \\
\frac{\text{letEx } lvs = \text{prepareLossVector } \{\} \{\} \{\} \{\} !arms_u !prob_u !cArm_u !chReward \text{ in } E_{7.3} : T_5}{.; \Theta_2; i + 1 = r; \Omega_7; . \vdash E_{7.2} : T_5}
\end{array}$$

D7.3

D7.1:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{.; \Theta_2; i + 1 = r; \Omega_6; . \vdash \text{getReward } \{\} \{\} \{\} !round_u !cArm_u !T_{gl}} \\
\frac{.; \Theta_2; i + 1 = r; \Omega_6; . \vdash \text{let! } chReward = \text{getReward } \{\} \{\} \{\} !round_u !cArm_u \text{ in } E_{7.2} : T_5}{.; \Theta_2; i + 1 = r; \Omega_6; . \vdash E_{7.1} : T_5}
\end{array}$$

D7.2

D7.01:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{.; \Theta_2; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5; cArm' !\mathbf{N}(carm) \vdash cArm' !\mathbf{N}(carm)} \\
\frac{.; \Theta_2; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5; cArm' !\mathbf{N}(carm) \vdash \text{let! } cArm_u = cArm' \text{ in } E_{7.1} :}{.; \Theta_2; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5; cArm' !\mathbf{N}(carm) \vdash E_{7.01} : T_5}
\end{array}$$

D7.1

D7.0:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{.; \Theta'_1; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5; cArm : \exists carm. !\mathbf{N}(carm) \vdash cArm : \exists carm. !\mathbf{N}(carm)} \\
\frac{.; \Theta'_1; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5; cArm : \exists carm. !\mathbf{N}(carm) \vdash \text{letEx } cArm' = cArm \text{ in } E_{7.01} : T_5}{.; \Theta'_1; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5; cArm : \exists carm. !\mathbf{N}(carm) \vdash E_{7.0} : T_5}
\end{array}$$

D7.01

D6.13:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{.; \Theta'_1; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5, chArm_u : \mathbf{N}(ca); . \vdash !chArm_u : !\mathbf{N}(carm)[ca/carm]} \\
\frac{}{.; \Theta'_1; i + 1 = r \vdash ca} \\
\frac{.; \Theta'_1; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5, chArm_u : \mathbf{N}(ca); . \vdash \text{Ex } !chArm_u : \exists carm. !\mathbf{N}(carm)}{.; \Theta'_1; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5, chArm_u : \mathbf{N}(ca); . \vdash \text{return } (\text{Ex } !chArm_u) : T_{6.2}}
\end{array}$$

D6.12:

$$\frac{}{.; \Theta'_1; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5; . \vdash \uparrow^{\hat{L} ca} : T_{6.1}}$$

D6.1:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{.; \Theta'_1; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5, chArm_u : \mathbf{N}(ca); . \vdash} \\
\frac{\text{bind } _ = \uparrow^{\hat{L} ca} \text{ in return } !chArm_u : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(-\leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes -\delta_0)} EC (\exists carm. !\mathbf{N}(carm))}{.; \Theta'_1; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5, chArm_u : \mathbf{N}(ca); . \vdash E_{6.6} : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(-\leftarrow \delta_0)} EC (\exists carm. !\mathbf{N}(carm))}
\end{array}$$

D6.12 D6.13

D6:

$$\frac{\frac{\cdot; \Theta_{1.0}; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5; \cdot \vdash \text{toDist! } !prob_u : T_{dist}}{D6.1}}{\cdot; \Theta_{1.0}; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5; \cdot \vdash \text{bind } chArm_u = \text{toDist! } !prob_u \text{ in } E_{6.6} : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(\leftarrow \mu \otimes \dots \delta_0)} EC (\exists carm. !\mathbf{N}(carm))} \frac{}{\cdot; \Theta_{1.0}; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5; \cdot \vdash E_{6.5} : T_6}$$

D5:

$$\frac{\frac{D6 \quad D7.0}{\cdot; \Theta_{1.0}; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5; \cdot \vdash \text{bind } cArm_u = E_{6.5} \text{ in } E_{7.0} : T_{5.1}}{\cdot; \Theta_{1.0}; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5; \cdot \vdash E_{6.4} : T_{5.1}}}$$

D4:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\cdot; \Theta_{1.0}; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5; \Gamma_2 \vdash p : T_p}{D5}}{\cdot; \Theta_{1.0}; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5; \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{release } - = p \text{ in } E_{6.4} : T_5}}{\cdot; \Theta_{1.0}; i + 1 = r; \Omega_5; \Gamma_2 \vdash E_{6.3} : T_5}$$

D3:

$$\frac{\frac{\cdot; \Theta_{1.0}; i + 1 = r; \Omega_4; \cdot \vdash \text{map } !(\lambda x. \text{let } y = x \text{ in } (1 - g_u)/phi_u * y + g_u/arms_u) !wts_u : !T_{prs}}{D4}}{\cdot; \Theta_{1.0}; i + 1 = r; \Omega_4; \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{let! } prob_u = \text{map } !(\lambda x. \text{let } y = x \text{ in } (1 - g_u)/phi_u * y + g_u/arms_u) !wts_u \text{ in } E_{6.3} : T_5} \frac{}{\cdot; \Theta_{1.0}; i + 1 = r; \Omega_4; \Gamma_2 \vdash E_{6.2} : T_5}$$

D2:

$$\frac{\frac{D3}{\vdots}}{\cdot; \Theta_1; i + 1 = r; \Omega_3; \Gamma_2 \vdash E_6 : T_5}$$

D1:

$$\frac{\frac{\cdot; \Theta; \cdot; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{return nil} : T_5}}{\cdot; \Theta; \cdot; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash E_5 : T_5}}$$

D0:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\cdot; \Theta; \cdot; \Omega_2; \cdot \vdash !round_u : T_{ru}}{D1 \quad D2}}{\cdot; \Theta; \cdot; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{matchN! } !round_u, Z \mapsto E_5, (S \text{ rnd}) \mapsto E_6 : T_5}}{\cdot; \Theta; \cdot; \Omega_2; \Gamma_2 \vdash E_4 : T_5}}$$

Main derivation:

$$\begin{array}{c}
 D0 \\
 \vdots \\
 \frac{\frac{\frac{.; \Theta; .; .; \text{round} : T_r \vdash \text{round} : T_r}{. ; \Theta; .; .; \Gamma_1 \vdash E_1 : T_5}}{.; \Theta; .; .; \Gamma \vdash \text{let! } \text{round}_u = \text{round in } E_1 : T_5}}{.; \Theta; .; .; \Gamma \vdash E_{0.0} : T_5}}{.; .; .; .; \vdash \Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\lambda \text{ round arms } g.\Lambda.\lambda p \text{ wts. } E_{0.0} : T_0} \\
 \frac{.; .; .; .; \vdash \Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\lambda \text{ round arms } g.\Lambda.\lambda p \text{ wts. } E_{0.0} : T_0}{.; .; .; .; \vdash E_0 : T_0}
 \end{array}$$

4.4 Stochastic gradient descent

```

1  sgd : ∀ r : ℕ, n : ℕ, m : ℕ, η : ℝ+, f' : (ℝ+)n → (ℝ+)n → ℝ+, θ* : (ℝ+)n, D : ((ℝ+)n)m.
2      !ℕ(r)
3      → !Li<n(Lj<nℝ+(Di,j))
4      → !ℝ(η)
5      → ∀θ : (ℝ+)n.
6      [((||θ - θ*||n)2/2η + T * η * G2/2)/m] 1
7      → !(∀D' : (ℝ+)n.Lj<n(ℝ+(D'j)) → Lk<n(ℝ+(θk)) → ℝ+(f' D' θ))
8      → !Li<nℝ+(θi)
9      → ℙC(a←δ0) 0 (∃θ'' : (ℝ+)n.Li<n ℝ+(θ''i))
10  fix sgd.Λ.Λ.Λ.Λ.λ T data eta.Λ.λ p f pr.
11    let! Tu = T in
12    let! datau = data in
13    let! etau = eta in
14    let! fu = f in
15    let! pru = pr in
16    let! lenu = length !datau in
17    let prob = 1/lenu in
18    matchN! !Tu
19      , Z ↦ return (Ex pru)
20      , S rnd ↦
21        let ⟨here, later⟩ = split p in
22        release _ = here in
23        bind d = toDist (replicate lenu prob) in
24        bind _ = ↑(f' Dd θ - f' Dd θ*) in
25        letEx pr' = (zipWithSub {} {} pru (etau · (∇ (fu {} d) pru))) in
26        sgd {} {} {} {} !rnd !datau !etau {} later !fu pr'

```

Let $p(t) = ((\|\theta_t - \theta^*\|_n)^2/2\eta + (T - t) * \eta * G^2/2)/m$

$$\mathbb{E}[f' D_i \theta_t - f' D_i \theta^*] + p(t+1) - p(t) \leq 0$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{0 \leq i < m} \mathbb{U}[\text{selecting } i] \cdot (f' D_i \theta_t - f' D_i \theta^*) + \\ & + ((\|\theta_{t+1} - \theta^*\|_n)^2/2\eta + (T - t - 1) * \eta * G^2/2)/m \\ & - ((\|\theta_t - \theta^*\|_n)^2/2\eta + (T - t) * \eta * G^2/2)/m \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{0 \leq i < m} \mathbb{U}[\text{selecting } i] \cdot (f' D_i \theta_t - f' D_i \theta^*) \\ & + ((\|\theta_{t+1} - \theta^*\|_n)^2/2\eta + (T - t - 1) * \eta * G^2/2 \\ & - (\|\theta_t - \theta^*\|_n)^2/2\eta + (T - t) * \eta * G^2/2)/m \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{0 \leq i < m} \mathbb{U}[\text{selecting } i] \cdot (f' D_i \theta_t - f' D_i \theta^*) \\ & + ((\|\theta_{t+1} - \theta^*\|_n)^2/2\eta - (\|\theta_t - \theta^*\|_n)^2/2\eta \\ & - \eta * G^2/2)/m \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{0 \leq i < m} \mathbb{U}[\text{selecting } i] \cdot (f' D_i \theta_t - f' D_i \theta^*) \\ & + (((\|\theta_{t+1} - \theta^*\|_n)^2 - (\|\theta_t - \theta^*\|_n)^2)/2\eta \\ & - \eta * G^2/2)/m \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{0 \leq i < m} \mathbb{U}[\text{selecting } i] \cdot (f' D_i \theta_t - f' D_i \theta^*) \\ & + ((2\langle \theta_t - \theta^*, \theta_{t+1} - \theta_t \rangle + (\|\theta_{t+1} - \theta_t\|_n)^2)/2\eta \\ & - \eta * G^2/2)/m \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{0 \leq i < m} \mathbb{U}[\text{selecting } i] \cdot (f' D_i \theta_t - f' D_i \theta^* + \\ & + \langle \theta_t - \theta^*, -\eta \cdot \nabla f' D_i \theta_t \rangle / \eta + \eta/2 \cdot \|\nabla f' D_i \theta_t\|_n^2) \\ & - \eta * G^2/2/m \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{0 \leq i < m} \mathbb{U}[\text{selecting } i] \cdot (f' D_i \theta_t - f' D_i \theta^* + \\ & + \langle \theta^* - \theta_t, \nabla f' D_i \theta_t \rangle + \eta/2 \cdot \|\nabla f' D_i \theta_t\|_n^2) \\ & - \eta * G^2/2/m \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{0 \leq i < m} \mathbb{U}[\text{selecting } i] \cdot (0 + \eta/2 \cdot \|\nabla f' D_i \theta_t\|_n^2) \\ & - \eta * G^2/2/m \leq 0 \quad (\text{Using convexity}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\eta * G^2/2/m - \eta * G^2/2/m \leq 0$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0 &\triangleq \Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\lambda T \text{ data } eta.\Lambda.\lambda p f pr.E_{0.1} \\
E_{0.1} &\triangleq \text{let! } T_u = T \text{ in } E_{0.2} \\
E_{0.2} &\triangleq \text{let! } data_u = data \text{ in } E_{0.3} \\
E_{0.3} &\triangleq \text{let! } eta_u = eta \text{ in } E_{0.4} \\
E_{0.4} &\triangleq \text{let! } f_u = f \text{ in } E_{0.5} \\
E_{0.5} &\triangleq \text{let! } pr_u = pr \text{ in } E_1 \\
E_1 &\triangleq \text{let! } len = length !data_u \text{ in } E_2 \\
E_2 &\triangleq \text{let } prob = 1/len \text{ in } E_3 \\
E_3 &\triangleq \text{matchN } T, Z \mapsto E_4, (S \text{ rnd}) \mapsto E_5 \\
E_4 &\triangleq \text{return (Ex } pr_u) \\
E_5 &\triangleq \text{let } \langle here, later \rangle = \text{split } p \text{ in } E_{5.1} \\
E_{5.1} &\triangleq \text{release } _ = here \text{ in } E_{5.2} \\
E_{5.2} &\triangleq \text{bind } d = \text{toDist (replicate } len \text{ prob) in } E_{5.3} \\
E_{5.3} &\triangleq \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^{(f' D_{d'} \theta - f' D_{d'} \theta^*)} \text{ in } E_{5.4} \\
E_{5.4} &\triangleq \text{letEx } pr' = (\text{zipWithSub } \{\}\{\}\{\} pr_u (eta \cdot (\nabla (f \{\} d)) pr_u)) \text{ in } E_{5.5} \\
E_{5.5} &\triangleq \text{sgd } \{\}\{\}\{\}\{\} rnd data eta \{\} later f pr'
\end{aligned}$$

T_0	$\triangleq \forall r : \mathbb{N}, n : \mathbb{N}, m : \mathbb{N}, \eta : \mathbb{R}^+, f' : (\mathbb{R}^+)^n \rightarrow (\mathbb{R}^+)^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+, \theta^* : (\mathbb{R}^+)^n, D : ((\mathbb{R}^+)^n)^m. T_b$
T_b	$\triangleq T_t \multimap T_d \multimap T_e \multimap T_{c'} \multimap T_p \multimap T_f \multimap T_c \multimap T_r$
T_t	$\triangleq !\mathbf{N}(r)$
T_d	$\triangleq !L_{i < m}(L_{j < n} \mathbf{R}^+(D_{i,j}))$
T_e	$\triangleq !\mathbf{R}(\eta)$
T_p	$\triangleq [((\ \theta - \theta^*\ _n)^2 / 2\eta + T * \eta * G^2 / 2) / m] \mathbf{1}$
T_f	$\triangleq !(\forall D' : (\mathbb{R}^+)^n. L_{j < n}(\mathbf{R}^+(D'_j)) \multimap L_{k < n}(\mathbf{R}^+(\theta_k)) \multimap \mathbf{R}^+(f' D' \theta))$
T_{pr}	$\triangleq !L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}^+(\theta_i)$
T_r	$\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} 0 (\exists \theta'' : (\mathbb{R}^+)^n. L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}^+(\theta''_i))$
$T_{r1.0}$	$\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \cup n \otimes \dots \delta_0)} (\sum_{0 \leq d' < m} (f' D_{d'} \theta - f' D_{d'} \theta^*) / m) (\exists \theta'' : (\mathbb{R}^+)^n. L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}^+(\theta''_i))$
T_{r1}	$\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} (\sum_{0 \leq d' < m} (f' D_{d'} \theta - f' D_{d'} \theta^*) / m) (\exists \theta'' : (\mathbb{R}^+)^n. L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}^+(\theta''_i))$
T_{sr}	$\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} (f' D_{d'} \theta - f' D_{d'} \theta^*) \mathbf{1}$
$T_{sr1.0}$	$\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0 \otimes \dots \delta_0)} (f' D_{d'} \theta - f' D_{d'} \theta^*) (\exists \theta'' : (\mathbb{R}^+)^n. L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}^+(\theta''_i))$
T_{sr1}	$\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \delta_0)} (f' D_{d'} \theta - f' D_{d'} \theta^*) (\exists \theta'' : (\mathbb{R}^+)^n. L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}^+(\theta''_i))$
$T_{pr'}$	$\triangleq L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}^+(\theta'_i)$
T_{theta}	\triangleq
T_{tu}	$\triangleq !\mathbf{N}(r)$
T_{du}	$\triangleq !L_{i < m}(L_{j < n} \mathbf{R}^+(D_{i,j}))$
T_{eu}	$\triangleq !\mathbf{R}(\eta)$
$T_{pr'u}$	$\triangleq \forall \theta : (\mathbb{R}^+)^n.$
T_p	$\triangleq [((\ \theta - \theta^*\ _n)^2 / 2\eta + T * \eta * G^2 / 2) / m] \mathbf{1}$
T_{hr}	$\triangleq [\sum_{0 \leq d' < m} (f' D_{d'} \theta - f' D_{d'} \theta^*) / m] \mathbf{1}$
T_{tr}	$\triangleq [((\ \theta - \theta^*\ _n)^2 / 2\eta + (T - 1) * \eta * G^2 / 2) / m] \mathbf{1}$
T_u	$\triangleq \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(d' \leftarrow \cup n)} 0 \mathbf{N}(d')$
T_{fu}	$\triangleq !(\forall D' : (\mathbb{R}^+)^n. L_{j < n}(\mathbf{R}^+(D'_j)) \multimap L_{k < n}(\mathbf{R}^+(\theta_k)) \multimap \mathbf{R}^+(f' D' \theta))$
T_{pru}	$\triangleq L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}^+(\theta_i)$
Γ	$\triangleq T : T_t, data : T_d, eta : T_e, p : T_p, f : T_f, pr : T_{pr}$
Γ_1	$\triangleq data : T_d, eta : T_e, p : T_p, f : T_f, pr : T_{pr}$
Γ_2	$\triangleq eta : T_e, p : T_p, f : T_f, pr : T_{pr}$
Γ_3	$\triangleq p : T_p, f : T_f, pr : T_{pr}$
Γ_4	$\triangleq p : T_p, pr : T_{pr}$
Γ_5	$\triangleq p : T_p$
Γ'_5	$\triangleq p : T_p, prob : \mathbf{R}(1/m)$
Ω	$\triangleq sgd : T_0, T_u : T_{tu}, data_u : T_{du}, eta_u : T_{eu}, f_u : T_{fu}, pr_u : T_{pru}$
Ω'	$\triangleq sgd : T_0, T_u : T_{tu}, data_u : T_{du}, eta_u : T_{eu}, f_u : T_{fu}, pr_u : T_{pru}, len_u : \mathbf{N}(m)$
Θ	$\triangleq r, n, m, \eta, f', \theta^*, D, \theta$

D4.5:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \cdot; \Theta, i, d', \theta'; i + 1 = r; \Omega', rnd : \mathbf{N}(i); later : T_{tr}, pr' : T_{pr'} \vdash \\ \quad sgd \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} \{ \} !rnd !data_u !eta_u \{ \} later !f_u pr' : T_r \end{array}}{\cdot; \Theta, i, d', \theta'; i + 1 = r; \Omega', rnd : \mathbf{N}(i); later : T_{tr}, pr' : T_{pr'} \vdash E_{5.5} : T_r}$$

D4.4:

$$\frac{\frac{.; \Theta, i, d'; i + 1 = r; \Omega', rnd : \mathbf{N}(i); d : \mathbf{N}(d') \vdash (zipWithSub \{\}\{\} pr_u (eta_u \cdot (\nabla (f_u \{\} d) pr_u)))}{D5.5}}{.; \Theta, i, d'; i + 1 = r; \Omega', rnd : \mathbf{N}(i); later : T_{tr}, d : \mathbf{N}(d') \vdash \text{letEx } pr' = (zipWithSub \{\}\{\} pr_u (eta_u \cdot (\nabla (f_u \{\} d) pr))) \text{ in } E_{5.5} : T_r}}{.; \Theta, i, d'; i + 1 = r; \Omega', rnd : \mathbf{N}(i); later : T_{tr}, d : \mathbf{N}(d') \vdash E_{5.4} : T_r}$$

D4.3:

$$\frac{\frac{.; \Theta, i, d'; i + 1 = r; \Omega', rnd : \mathbf{N}(i); . \vdash \uparrow^{(f' D_{d'} \theta - f' D_{d'} \theta^*)} : T_{sr}}{D4.4}}{.; \Theta, i, d'; i + 1 = r; \Omega', rnd : \mathbf{N}(i); later : T_{tr}, d : \mathbf{N}(d') \vdash \text{bind } _ = \uparrow^{(f' D_{d'} \theta - f' D_{d'} \theta^*)} \text{ in } E_{5.4} : T_{sr1.0}}{\text{coupling}} \frac{.; \Theta, i, d'; i + 1 = r; \Omega', rnd : \mathbf{N}(i); later : T_{tr}, d : \mathbf{N}(d') \vdash E_{5.3} : T_{sr1}}$$

D4.2:

$$\frac{.; \Theta, i; i + 1 = r; \Omega', rnd : \mathbf{N}(i); prob : \mathbf{R}(1/m) \vdash \text{toDist } (replicate len_u prob) : T_u}{D4.3}}{.; \Theta, i; i + 1 = r; \Omega', rnd : \mathbf{N}(i); prob : \mathbf{R}(1/m), later : T_{tr} \vdash \text{bind } d = \text{toDist } (replicate len_u prob) \text{ in } E_{5.3} : T_{r1.0}}{.; \Theta, i; i + 1 = r; \Omega', rnd : \mathbf{N}(i); prob : \mathbf{R}(1/m), later : T_{tr} \vdash E_{5.2} : T_{r1}}$$

D4.1:

$$\frac{\frac{.; \Theta, i; i + 1 = r; \Omega', rnd : \mathbf{N}(i); here : T_{hr} \vdash here : T_{hr}}{D4.2}}{.; \Theta, i; i + 1 = r; \Omega', rnd : \mathbf{N}(i); prob : \mathbf{R}(1/m), here : T_{hr}, later : T_{tr} \vdash \text{release } _ = here \text{ in } E_{5.2} : T_r}}{.; \Theta, i; i + 1 = r; \Omega', rnd : \mathbf{N}(i); prob : \mathbf{R}(1/m), here : T_{hr}, later : T_{tr} \vdash E_{5.1} : T_r}$$

D4:

$$\frac{\frac{.; \Theta, i; i + 1 = r; \Omega', rnd : \mathbf{N}(i); p : T_p \vdash \text{split } p : T_{hr} \times T_{tr}}{D4.1}}{.; \Theta, i; i + 1 = r; \Omega', rnd : \mathbf{N}(i); \Gamma'_5 \vdash \text{let } \langle here, later \rangle = \text{split } p \text{ in } E_{5.1} : T_r}}{.; \Theta, i; i + 1 = r; \Omega', rnd : \mathbf{N}(i); \Gamma'_5 \vdash E_5 : T_r}$$

D3:

$$\frac{\frac{.; \Theta; r = 0; \Omega'; \Gamma'_5 \vdash pr_u : (L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}^+(\theta''_i))[\theta/\theta''] \quad \Theta; r = 0 \vdash \theta}{.; \Theta; r = 0; \Omega'; \Gamma'_5 \vdash \text{Ex } pr_u : \exists \theta'' : (\mathbb{R}^+)^n. L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}^+(\theta''_i)}}{.; \Theta; r = 0; \Omega'; \Gamma'_5 \vdash \text{return } (\text{Ex } pr_u) : T_r}}{.; \Theta; r = 0; \Omega'; \Gamma'_5 \vdash E_4 : T_r}$$

D2:

$$\frac{}{.; \Theta; .; \Omega'; . \vdash !T_u : T_{tu}}$$

D1:

$$\frac{\frac{D2 \quad D3 \quad D4}{.; \Theta; .; \Omega'; \Gamma'_5 \vdash \text{matchN! } !T_u, Z \mapsto E_4, (S \text{ rnd}) \mapsto E_5 : T_r}}{.; \Theta; .; \Omega'; \Gamma'_5 \vdash E_3 : T_r}$$

D0:

$$\frac{\frac{.; \Theta; .; \Omega', len_u : \mathbf{N}(m); . \vdash 1/len_u : \mathbf{R}(1/m) \quad D1}{.; \Theta; .; \Omega', len_u : \mathbf{N}(m); \Gamma_5 \vdash \text{let } prob = 1/len \text{ in } E_3 : T_r}}{.; \Theta; .; \Omega', len_u : \mathbf{N}(m); \Gamma_5 \vdash E_2 : T_r}$$

D0.5:

$$\frac{\frac{.; \Theta; .; \Omega'; \Gamma \vdash \text{length } !data_u : \mathbf{N}(m) \quad D0}{.; \Theta; .; \Omega'; \Gamma_5 \vdash \text{let! } len = \text{length } !data_u \text{ in } E_2 : T_r}}{.; \Theta; .; \Omega'; \Gamma_5 \vdash E_1 : T_r}$$

D0.4:

$$\frac{.; \Theta; .; \text{sgd} : T_0, T_u : T_{tu}, data_u : T_{du}, eta_u : T_{eu}, f_u : T_{fu}; pr : T_{pr} \vdash pr : T_{pr} \quad D0.5}{.; \Theta; .; \text{sgd} : T_0, T_u : T_{tu}, data_u : T_{du}, eta_u : T_{eu}, f_u : T_{fu}; \Gamma_4 \vdash \text{let! } pr_u = pr \text{ in } E_1 : T_r}$$

D0.3:

$$\frac{.; \Theta; .; \text{sgd} : T_0, T_u : T_{tu}, data_u : T_{du}, eta_u : T_{eu}; f : T_f \vdash f : T_f \quad D0.4}{.; \Theta; .; \text{sgd} : T_0, T_u : T_{tu}, data_u : T_{du}, eta_u : T_{eu}; \Gamma_3 \vdash \text{let! } f_u = f \text{ in } E_{0.5} : T_r}$$

D0.2:

$$\frac{.; \Theta; .; \text{sgd} : T_0, T_u : T_{tu}, data_u : T_{du}; eta : T_e \vdash eta : T_e \quad D0.3}{.; \Theta; .; \text{sgd} : T_0, T_u : T_{tu}, data_u : T_{du}; \Gamma_2 \vdash \text{let! } eta_u = eta \text{ in } E_{0.4} : T_r}$$

D0.1:

$$\frac{.; \Theta; .; \text{sgd} : T_0, T_u : T_{tu}; data : T_d \vdash data : T_d \quad D0.2}{.; \Theta; .; \text{sgd} : T_0, T_u : T_{tu}; \Gamma_1 \vdash \text{let! } data_u = data \text{ in } E_{0.3} : T_r}$$

D0.0:

$$\frac{.; \Theta; .; \text{sgd} : T_0; T : T_t \vdash T : T_t \quad D0.1}{.; \Theta; .; \text{sgd} : T_0; \Gamma \vdash \text{let! } T_u = T \text{ in } E_{0.2} : T_r}$$

Main derivation:

$$\begin{array}{c}
D0.0 \\
\hline
.; \Theta; .; sgd : T_0; \Gamma \vdash E_1 : T_b \\
\hline
.; .; .; sgd : T_0; . \vdash \Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\Lambda.\lambda T \text{ data eta}.\Lambda.\lambda p f pr.E_1 : T_0 \\
\hline
.; .; .; sgd : T_0; . \vdash E_0 : T_0 \\
\hline
.; .; .; .; . \vdash \text{fix } sgd.E_0 : T_0
\end{array}$$

$zipWithSub : \forall R1R2 : L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(R1 \ i) \multimap L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(R2 \ i) \multimap \exists R.L_{i < n} \mathbf{R}(R \ i)$

5 Isomorphism

$$c_1 : \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau \multimap [\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau$$

$$c_1 \triangleq \lambda e. \lambda p. \text{release } y = p \text{ in } e$$

$$c_2 : ([\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau) \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau$$

$$c_2 \triangleq \lambda f. \text{bind } x = \text{store}() \text{ in } f x$$

Lemma 59. $\forall p, T, \tau, \kappa, \mu.$

$$(p, T, c_1 \cdot c_2) \in \mathcal{E}[[([\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau) \multimap ([\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau)]]$$

$$\iff$$

$$(p, T, \lambda f. f) \in \mathcal{E}[[([\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau) \multimap ([\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau)]]$$

Proof. Direction \Rightarrow

Directly from Definition 8 and Lemma 12

Direction \Leftarrow

$$\text{Given: } (p, T, \lambda f. f) \in \mathcal{E}[[([\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau) \multimap ([\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau)]] \quad (\text{E1})$$

$$\text{To prove: } (p, T, c_1 \cdot c_2) \in \mathcal{E}[[([\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau) \multimap ([\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau)]]$$

This means from Definition 8 it suffices to prove that

$$(p, T, c_1 \cdot c_2) \in \mathcal{V}[[([\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau) \multimap ([\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau)]]$$

From Definition 8 it further suffices to prove that

$$\forall p', f', T' < T. (p', T', f') \in \mathcal{E}[[([\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau)]] \implies$$

$$(p + p', T', c[f'/f]) \in \mathcal{E}[[([\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau)]]$$

where,

$$c_1 \cdot c_2 = \lambda f. c \text{ and } c = (\lambda e. \lambda p. \text{release } y = p \text{ in } e) \text{ (bind } x = \text{store}() \text{ in } f x)$$

This means given some $p', f', T' < T$. s.t $(p', T', f') \in \mathcal{E}[[([\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau)]]$

It suffices to prove that

$$(p + p', T', c[f'/f]) \in \mathcal{E}[[([\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau)]]$$

From Definition 8, this further means that

$$\forall t < T', v. c[f'/f] \downarrow_t v \implies (p + p', T' - t, v) \in \mathcal{E}[[([\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau)]]$$

From the reduction rules we know that $\exists t$ s.t. $c[f'/f] \downarrow_t v$

where $v = (\lambda p. \text{release } y = p \text{ in } (\text{bind } x = \text{store}() \text{ in } f' x))$

This means it suffices to prove that

$$(p + p', T' - t, v) \in \mathcal{V}[[([\kappa] \mathbf{1} \multimap \mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau)]]$$

Again from Definition 8, we know that given some p'', t' s.t. $(p'', t', ()) \in \mathcal{E}[[([\kappa] \mathbf{1}]]$

It suffices to prove that

$$(p + p' + p'', T' - t - t', v') \in \mathcal{V}[[\mathbb{P}\mathbb{C}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} 0 \tau]]$$

where

$$v' = (\text{release } y = () \text{ in } (\text{bind } x = \text{store}() \text{ in } f' x))$$

We get the desired using (E1) using f' and Definition 8

□

Lemma 60. $\forall p, T, \tau, \kappa, \mu.$

$$\begin{aligned} (p, T, c_2 \cdot c_1) &\in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau \multimap \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau] \\ &\iff \\ (p, T, \lambda f.f) &\in \mathcal{E}[\mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau \multimap \mathbb{PC}_{(a \leftarrow \mu)} \kappa \tau] \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Similar proof as Lemma 59

□